

ACUTE - Accessibility and Connectivity Knowledge Hub for Urban Transformation in Europe

WP1 – ENUAC Cross Research Community

D1.4.2 Annex: Compilation of European projects on urban transport with a focus on accessibility and connectivity.

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Project Partners

Organisation	Country
University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna BOKU	AUSTRIA
Université Gustav Eiffel UEiffel	FRANCE
Centre d'études et d'expertise sur les risques, l'environnement, la mobilité et l'aménagement Cerema	FRANCE
Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies LBTU	LATVIA
University of Latvia LU	LATVIA
Research Institutes of Sweden RISE	SWEDEN
University of Westminster UoW	UNITED KINGDOM
Malmö University MAU	SWEDEN
Grazer Energieagentur GmbH, Graz Energy Agency GEA	AUSTRIA
VTI/Sweden's national centre for research and education on public transport K2	SWEDEN
Power Circle PC	SWEDEN
University of Innsbruck UIBK	AUSTRIA

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Project Overview

Acronym	Project Title	Programme	Duration	
CASUAL	Co-creating attractive and sustainable urban areas and lifestyle – exploring new forms of inclusive urban governance	JPI Urban Europe	2013	2016
CONCOORD	Consolidation and coordination in urban areas	JPI Urban Europe	2013	2016
GUST	Governance of urban sustainability transitions: advancing the role of living labs	JPI Urban Europe	2014	2017
E4-Share	Models for ecological, economical, efficient, electric car-sharing	JPI Urban Europe	2014	2017
Play!UC	Playing with urban complexity: using co-located serious games to reduce the urban carbon footprint among young adults	JPI Urban Europe	2014	2017
BREATHE	Building Resilient Economic Agglomerations addressing Transportation and Health Effects: Urban form, location choice and transport solutions for low-carbon cities	JPI Urban Europe	2016	2019
CIVIC	Construction in vicinities: innovative co-creation	JPI Urban Europe	2016	2018
DESENT	Smart decision support system for urban energy and transportation	JPI Urban Europe	2016	2019
IP-SUNTAN	Innovative policies for sustainable urban transportation	JPI Urban Europe	2016	2019
me ²	Integrated smart city mobility and energy platform	JPI Urban Europe	2016	2018
Smart Commuting	Smart and Mobile Work in Growth Regions	JPI Urban Europe	2016	2018
SmarterLabs	Improving Anticipation and Social Inclusion in Living Labs for Smart City Governance	JPI Urban Europe	2016	2019
SmartGov	Advanced decision support for smart governance	JPI Urban Europe	2016	2019
SPACERGY	Space-Energy patterns for smart energy infrastructures, community reciprocities & related governance	JPI Urban Europe	2016	2019
TRANS-FORM	smart transfers through unravelling urban form and travel flow dynamics	JPI Urban Europe	2016	2019
c3places	Using ICT for Co-Creation of Inclusive Public Places	JPI Urban Europe	2017	2019
LOOPER	Learning loops in the public realm	JPI Urban Europe	2017	2020
SMART PEDESTRIAN NET (SPN)	Smart cities are walkable: SPN - a model to plan a pedestrian network and a pedestrian navigation system	JPI Urban Europe	2017	2020
MIMIC	Minimizing impact of construction material flows in cities: Innovative Co-Creation	JPI Urban Europe	2018	2021
OptiMaaS	Optimized Mobility as a Service	JPI Urban Europe	2018	2021
SimpliCITY	Marketplace for user-centered sustainability services platform	JPI Urban Europe	2018	2021
SMUrTS	Sustainable mixed urban transit system with electric and conventional buses	JPI Urban Europe	2019	2022
MAAT	Multi-faceted valuation and administration of access to housing and transportation	JPI Urban Europe	2019	2022
SIMETRI	Sustainable Mobility and Equality in mega-ciTy Regions	JPI Urban Europe	2019	2022
U-PASS	Urban Public Administration and Services innovation for Innovative Urban Mobility Management and Policy	JPI Urban Europe	2019	2023
CATAPULT	PoliCies for inclusive, demand-oriented and target group-specific automated mobility solutions for cities	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2023
ITEM	Inclusive Transition towards Electric Mobility	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2024
ASAP	Awaken Sleeping Assets Project	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2024
EASIER	Seamless sustainable everyday urban mobility	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2024
EX-TRA	EXperimenting with city streets to TRAnsform urban mobility	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2024
GeoSense	Geofencing strategies for implementation in urban traffic management and planning	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2024
DyMoN	Dynamic Mobility Nudge: Shaping sustainable urban mobility behaviour with real-time, user-generated and public open data	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2024
MyFairShare	Individual Mobility Budgets as a Foundation for Social and Ethical Carbon Reduction	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2024
TAPforuncertainfuture	Using Triple Access Planning to Enhance Urban Accessibility and Connectivity in the Face of Deep Uncertainty	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2024
TuneOurBlock	Transforming urban quarters to human scale environments: applying superblock concepts for different urban structures	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2024
SMARTHubs	Smart Mobility Hubs as Game Changers in Transport	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2024

JUSTICE	Joining Urban morphology, Spatio-Temporal and socio-cognitive accessibility for an Inclusive City Environment	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2024
SortedMobility	Self-Organized Rail Traffic for the Evolution of Decentralized MOBILITY	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2024
WALKUrban	Walkable Urban Neighbourhoods – Freeing up Potential for Sustainable and Active Travel by Improving Walking and its Connections with Public Transport	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2024
COCOMO	COmpeting and COmplementary MObility solutions in urban contexts	JPI Urban Europe	2021	2024
ACUTE	Accessibility and Connectivity knowledge hub for Urban Transformation in Europe	JPI Urban Europe	2022	2024
E-Laas	Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service	JPI Urban Europe	2023	2026
e-MATS	Electric Multimodal Transport Systems for Enhancing Urban Accessibility and Connectivity	JPI Urban Europe	2023	2025
IMTECC	Integrated systems and analysis of urban Mobility for climate-neutral and susTainable Cities in Europe and China	JPI Urban Europe	2023	2026
IMUMCN	Improved urban mobility toward climate neutrality under new working habits and transport modes	JPI Urban Europe	2023	2026
NEW NORMAL	Sustainable mobility and logistics for post-pandemic second-tier cities	JPI Urban Europe	2023	2026
SINERGI	Sustainable Innovative digitalized NETwork of uRban loGistics	JPI Urban Europe	2023	2026
SOUL	Sustainable Operations in Urban Logistics	JPI Urban Europe	2023	2026
TOD2	Transit-Oriented Development 2 – Public spaces, mobility hubs and climate neutrality toolbox	JPI Urban Europe	2023	2026
TAAM	Toolbox for Agile urban Accessibility Management	JPI Urban Europe	2023	2025
TollsThatWork	City tolls that work	JPI Urban Europe	2023	2025
StreetForum	Transforming streets into accessible urban oases through consensus building with digital and analogue tools	JPI Urban Europe	2023	2025
ACCTRA	Evidence and acceptance - from experiments to transformation	JPI Urban Europe	2023	2025
City&Co	Older Adults Co-Creating a Sustainable Age-friendly City	JPI Urban Europe	2022	2025
EmbedderLabs	Better Embedded Labs for More Synergistic Sustainable Urban Transformation Planning	JPI Urban Europe	2022	2025
Carin-PT	Capacities for Resilient and Inclusive Urban Public Transport Infrastructure and Built Environment	JPI Urban Europe	2023	2025
VIVALDI	Visionary and Vibrant Actions through Local Transport Demonstration Initiatives	FP5	2002	2006
TRENDSETTER	TRENDSETTER setting trends for sustainable urban mobility	FP5	2002	2006
MIRACLES	Multi-Initiative for Rationalised Accessibility and Clean Liveable Environments	FP5	2002	2006
TELLUS	Transport and Environment Alliance for Urban Sustainability	FP5	2002	2006
MOBILIS	Mobility initiatives for local integration and sustainability	FP6	2005	2009
SUCCESS	Smaller Urban Communities in CIVITAS for Environmentally Sustainable Solutions	FP6	2005	2009
CARAVEL	Travelling towards a new mobility	FP6	2005	2009
SMILE	Towards Sustainable Mobility for people in urban areas	FP6	2005	2009
NICHES+	New and Innovative Concepts for Helping European Transport Sustainability - Towards Implementation	FP7	2008	2011
RENAISSANCE	Testing Innovative Strategies for Clean Urban Transport for historic European cities	FP7	2008	2012
ELAN	Mobilising citizens for vital cities	FP7	2008	2012
ARCHIMEDES	Achieving Real CHange with Innovative transport MEasures Demonstrating Energy Savings	FP7	2008	2012
MODERN	MObility, Development and Energy use ReductioN	FP7	2008	2013
MIMOSA	Making Innovation in MObility and Sustainable Actions	FP7	2008	2013
DYN@MO	DYNamic citizens @ctive for sustainable Mobility	FP7	2012	2016
2MOVE2	New forms of sustainable urban transport and mobility	FP7	2012	2016
PASTA	PHYSICAL ACTIVITY THROUGH SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT APPROACHES	FP7	2013	2017
CIPTEC	Collective Innovation for Public Transport in European Cities	H2020	2015	2018
CityLab	City Logistics in Living Laboratories	H2020	2015	2018
EMPOWER	EMPOWERING a reduction in use of conventionally fueled vehicles using Positive Policy Measures.	H2020	2015	2018

FLOW	Furthering Less Congestion by creating Opportunities for more Walking and cycling	H2020	2015	2018
SUCCESS	Sustainable Urban Consolidation Centres for construction	H2020	2015	2018
CREATE	Congestion Reduction in Europe : Advancing Transport Efficiency	H2020	2015	2018
ELIPTIC	Electrification of public transport in cities	H2020	2015	2018
NOVELOG	New cooperative business models and guidance for sustainable city logistics	H2020	2015	2018
TRACE	Opening the cycling and walking tracking potential	H2020	2015	2018
U-TURN	Rethinking Urban Transportation through advanced tools and supply chain collaboration	H2020	2015	2018
DESTINATIONS		H2020	2016	2021
ECCENTRIC	Innovative solutions for sustainable mobility of people in suburban city districts and emission free freight logistics in urban centres.	H2020	2016	2020
PORTIS	PORT-Cities: Integrating Sustainability	H2020	2016	2020
PROSPERITY	Prosperity through innovation and promotion of Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans	H2020	2016	2020
SUMPS-Up	European Programme for Accelerating the Take up of Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans	H2020	2016	2020
SUITS	Sustainable Urban Integrated Transport Systems: Transferable Tools for Small-Medium local authorities	H2020	2016	2021
SUNRISE	Sustainable Urban Neighbourhoods – Research and Implementation Support in Europe	H2020	2017	2021
Cities-4-People	New approaches for community-driven sustainable mobility innovations at neighbourhood and urban district level	H2020	2017	2020
Metamorphosis	Transformation of neighbourhoods in a child-friendly way to increase the quality of life for all citizens.	H2020	2017	2020
MUV	Mobility Urban Values	H2020	2017	2020
INCLUSION	Towards more accessible and inclusive mobility solutions for European prioritised areas	H2020	2017	2020
CCCB	City Changer Cargo Bike	H2020	2018	2022
GreenCharge	GreenCharge	H2020	2018	2022
Handshake	Enabling the transferability of cycling innovations and assessment of its implications	H2020	2018	2022
MORE	Multi-modal Optimisation for Road-space in Europe	H2020	2018	2022
MEISTER	Mobility Environmentally-friendly, Integrated and economically Sustainable Through innovative Electromobility Recharging infrastructure and new business models	H2020	2018	2022
Park4SUMP		H2020	2018	2022
Levitate	Societal Level Impacts of Connected and Automated Vehicles	H2020	2018	2022
MOMENTUM	Modelling Emerging Transport Solutions for Urban Mobility	H2020	2019	2022
HARMONY	Holistic Approach for Providing Spatial & Transport Planning Tools and Evidence to Metropolitan and Regional Authorities to Lead a Sustainable Transition to a New Mobility Era	H2020	2019	2023
ReVeAL	Regulating Vehicle Access for Improved Liveability	H2020	2019	2022
Sprout	Sustainable Policy Response to Urban mobility Transition	H2020	2019	2023
SUMP-PLUS	Sustainable Urban Mobility Planning: Pathways and Links to Urban Systems	H2020	2019	2023
WeCount	Citizens Observing Urban Transport	H2020	2019	2021
INDIMO	Inclusive digital mobility solutions	H2020	2020	2022
eCharge4Drivers	Electric Vehicle Charging Infrastructure for improved User Experience	H2020	2020	2024
LEAD	Low-Emission Adaptive last mile logistics supporting 'on Demand economy' through digital twins	H2020	2020	2024
Senator	Smart Network Operator Platform enabling Shared, Integrated and more Sustainable Urban Freight Logistics	H2020	2020	2024
ULaaDS	Urban Logistics as an on Demand Service	H2020	2020	2024
WE-TRANSFORM	Workforce Europe – Transformation Agenda for Transport Automation	H2020	2020	2024
ASSURED-UAM	Acceptance, Safety and Sustainability Recommendations for Efficient Deployment of Urban Air Mobility	H2020	2021	2023

FastTrack	Fostering the Acceleration of Sustainable Transport To Regions and Authorities through Capacity and Knowledge	H2020	2021	2023
MobiDataLab	Labs for prototyping future Mobility Data sharing cloud solutions	H2020	2021	2024
RECIPROCITY	Replication of innovative concepts for peri-urban, rural or inner-city mobility	H2020	2021	2023
MOVE 21	Multimodal and interconnected hubs for freight and passenger transport contributing to a zero emission 21st century	H2020	2021	2025
SCALE-UP	Scale up user-Centric & dAta driven solutions for ConnEcted Urban Poles	H2020	2021	2025
DIT4TraM	Distributed Intelligence and Technology for Traffic and Mobility Management	H2020	2021	2024
TANGENT	Enhanced Data Processing Techniques for Dynamic Management of Multimodal Traffic	H2020	2021	2024
SCALE	Smart Charging ALignment for Europe	Horizon Europe	2022	2025
NextETRUCK	Efficient and affordable Zero Emission logistics through the NEXTgeneration of Electric TRUCKs	Horizon Europe	2022	2025
DECARBOMILE	Five pillars to DECARBONize the last MILE logistics	Horizon Europe	2022	2026
LENS	L-vehicles Emissions and Noise mitigation Solutions	Horizon Europe	2022	2025
URBANE	Upscaling Innovative Green Urban Logistics Solutions Through Multi-Actor Collaboration and PI-Inspired Last Mile Deliveries.	Horizon Europe	2022	2026
PHOEBE	Predictive ApproacHes fOR SafEr UrBan Environments	Horizon Europe	2022	2026
eBRT2030	European Bus Rapid Transit of 2030: electrified, automated, connected	Horizon Europe	2023	2026
GREEN-LOG	Cooperative and Interconnected Green delivery solutions towards an era of optimized zero emission last-mile Logistics	Horizon Europe	2023	2026
SPINE	Smart Public transport Initiatives for climate-Neutral cities in Europe	Horizon Europe	2023	2026
UPPER	Unleashing the potential of Public Transport in Europe	Horizon Europe	2023	2026
STREnGth_M	Stimulating road Transport Research in Europe and around the Globe for sustainable Mobility	Horizon Europe	2023	2026
CIVITAS MUSE	Mobility for Urban Sustainability and the Environment CIVITAS 2030 Coordination and Support Action: Sustainable and Smart Mobility for All	Horizon Europe	2023	2027
DISCO	Data-driven, Integrated, Syncromodal, Collaborative and Optimised urban freight meta model for a new generation of urban logistics and planning with data sharing at European Living Labs	Horizon Europe	2023	2026
REALLOCATE	Rethinking the dEsign of streets And pubLic spaces to Leverage the mOdal shift to Climate-friendly Active Transport Everywhere	Horizon Europe	2023	2027
SYNCHROMODE	Advanced traffic management solutions for synchronized and resilient multimodal transport services	Horizon Europe	2023	2026
UNCHAIN	Urban logistics and plaNning: AntiCipating urban freigHt generAtion and demand including dIgitalisation of urbaN freight	Horizon Europe	2023	2026
Acumen	Ai-aided deCision tool for seamless mUltiModal nEtwork and traffic management	Horizon Europe	2023	2026
AMIGOS	Active Mobility Innovations for Green and safe city sOLutionS	Horizon Europe	2023	2027
ELABORATOR	The European living lab on designing sustainable urban mobility towards climate neutral cities	Horizon Europe	2023	2026
GEMINI	Greening European Mobility through cascading innovation INItiatives	Horizon Europe	2023	2026
SUM	Seamless Shared Urban Mobility	Horizon Europe	2023	2026
GIANTS	Green Intelligent Affordable New Transport Solutions	Horizon Europe	2024	2027
JULIA	Joint developments for Urban resILlence connecting users to public transport through spAcE technology	Horizon Europe	2024	2026
JUST STREETS	Mobility justice for all: framing safer, healthier and happier streets	Horizon Europe	2024	2027
metaCCAZE	Flexibly adapted MetaInnovations, use cases, collaborative business and governance models to accelerate deployment of smart and shared Zero Emission mobility for passengers and freight	Horizon Europe	2024	2027
MOBILITIES FOR EU	New MOBility solutions for cLimate neutraLity in EU cITIES	Horizon Europe	2024	2028
CodeZERO	CO-DESIGN OF E-COMMERCE LAST-MILE DELIVERY AND RETURN OPTIONS WITH ZERO EMISSIONS	Horizon Europe	2024	2027
GreenTurn	Enabling stakeholder-centric zero emission e-commerce delivery and return practices through transparent and collaborative supply chains	Horizon Europe	2024	2027

REFORM	Integrated REgional Action Plan For Innovative, Sustainable and LOW CaRbon Mobility	Interreg	2017	2020
eHUBS	Smart Shared Green Mobility Hubs	Interreg	2019	2023
e-smartec	enhanced sustainable mobility with marketing techniques	Interreg	2019	2023
PAV	Planning for Autonomous Vehicles	Interreg	2019	2023
Dynaxibility4CE	Capacities for dynamic and flexible planning for low-carbon mobility trends and policies in Central Europe	Interreg	2020	2022
MOBI-MIX	Improved implementation of shared mobility and MaaS to increase up-take of low-carbon transport in cities	Interreg	2020	2022
ShareDiMobiHub	Shared & Digital Mobility Hubs	Interreg	2022	2025
SMALL	Shared Multimodal Mobility For ALL	Interreg	2022	2026
SMAPE	Shared Mobility Action Programmes Exchange	Interreg	2023	2027
UrbFRail	Revitalisation of Inner-Urban Freight Rail Hubs	Interreg	2023	2025
MoLo Hubs	People-Centric Mobility & Logistics Hubs	Interreg	2023	2026
REFOCUS	Regional and Local Mobility Planning Focusing on Inclusive Decision Support Tools	Interreg	2024	2028
FlexCurb	Implementation of dynamic curbside management solutions to improve sustainable city logistics operations	EIT Urban Mobility	2022	2022
ISA-FIT	Boost Safety and cut Costs with Intelligent Speed Assistance	EIT Urban Mobility	2022	2022
LivingLAPT	Future Apt Living Lab for Autonomous Public Transport	EIT Urban Mobility	2023	2023
AI4LIFE		EIT Urban Mobility	2024	2024
EVOSS		EIT Urban Mobility	2024	2024
GreenMob	Multimodal journey planner for sustainable travel	EIT Urban Mobility	2024	2024
IMPULSE	Integrated e-bus power management for optimised transport operations	EIT Urban Mobility	2024	2024
UMF	Public transit analytics for a new mobility flows platform	EIT Urban Mobility	2024	2024
CES4Kids	Children and youth empowerment through DECIDIUM digital platform	EIT Urban Mobility	2021	
DVECE	Dynamic visualizations to enhance citizens engagement	EIT Urban Mobility	2022	
Inclusify	Women empowerment for inclusive mobility	EIT Urban Mobility	2022	
UMCASE	Citizens' Inclusive and Accessible Urban Mobility Solutions	EIT Urban Mobility	2022	
WSCE	WeSolve the Citizen Engagement	EIT Urban Mobility	2022	
Bicycle Heroes	Bicycle Heroes: European Youth Voices for Active Mobility	EIT Urban Mobility	2022	
emc2	The Evolutive Meshed Compact City: A Pragmatic Transition Pathway to the 15-minute City for European Metropolitan Peripheries	DUT Partnership	2023	2026
ERGODIC	Combined Passenger and Goods Transportation in Suburb Traffic	DUT Partnership	2023	2026
SUMODO	Sustainable Urban MObility Development in Outskirts	DUT Partnership	2023	2026
Car-goNE-City	Cargo Bikes and Neighbourhood Engagement in the 15-Minute City: Resident-Based Participatory Approaches to Implementing Effective Shared Bike Mobility for Increasing Accessibility and Reducing Car Use	DUT Partnership	2023	2026
CITWIN	A Generic Digital Twin Framework to Foster Sustainable Mobility in the 15mC	DUT Partnership	2023	2026
JIM	Social and Environmental Justice in 15 Minutes – Toolkit Development for Transition to Urban Sustainable Neighbourhoods	DUT Partnership	2023	2026
ENACT 15mC	Envisioning Neighbourhoods and Co-Creating Thriving Communities in the 15mC	DUT Partnership	2023	2026
15minESTATES	Co-creating Spatial Strategies for Just and Sustainable Mobility in Large-Scale Housing Estates	DUT Partnership	2024	2026
AccessCity4All	Adapting the 15-Minute City Concept to Support Active Mobility in Neighbourhoods with Different Levels of Accessibility	DUT Partnership	2024	2026
COMMON_ACCESS	COMMONing ACCESSibility in Urban Outskirts and Beyond	DUT Partnership	2024	2026
CONFLICTEDSTREETS	Navigating Conflicts Over Streets and Urban Space in the Transition to the 15mC	DUT Partnership	2023/ 2024	2026
DREAMS	Driving Equitable and Accessible 15 Minute Neighbourhood Transformations	DUT Partnership	2024	2026
ENHANCE	Enhancing Sustainable Travel in Small Cities and Outer Metropolitan Areas	DUT Partnership	2024	2026
Fair Mobility	Fair Mobility and Access to Public Life	DUT Partnership	2024	2026
FORTHCOMING	FOsteRing THE City Of proximity through Maas INteGration	DUT Partnership	2024	2026
FRESH	The Freight-Shopping Nexus in Urban Outskirts and Beyond	DUT Partnership	2024	2026

InclusiveCity	Critical Placemaking for Inclusive Cities	DUT Partnership	2024	2026
InPUT	Engaging Places and Communities for Inclusive Peri-Urban Transitions	DUT Partnership	2024	2026
LISTEN	Collective Listening to Communities and Spaces as a Core Capability in Planning Towards 15-minute Suburban Cities	DUT Partnership	2024	2026
MBD15	Mobility Benefit Districts: Travel and Liveability Impacts, Acceptability, and Governance of New Tools for Accelerating Transitions in the 15-minute City	DUT Partnership	2024	2026
MULTIGINATION	Multiplicative Imagination of Citizens and Stakeholders towards the 15-minutes City	DUT Partnership	2024	2026
SuCoLo	Fostering Sustainable Consumer Behaviour with Inclusive Bicycle Logistics Infrastructure in Urban Outskirts	DUT Partnership	2024	2026
SPECIFIC	Specifying Practices Enabled by Cycling in Fifteen-minute Cities	DUT Partnership	2024	2026
SUMI	Technical support related to sustainable urban mobility indicators (SUMI)	Service contract	2017	2020
APOLLO-EU	Alliance Platform for Liveable and Low-Carbon Communities in Europe	Service contract	2019	2023
UVAR Box	User-friendly Information Tool on Urban and Regional Access Regulations Schemes	Preparatory Action	2020	2022
Ride2Autonomy		Pilot Project/ Preparatory Action	2021	2022
deployEMDS		EU Digital Europe Programme	2023	2026

Joint Programming Initiative (JPI) Urban Europe

Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/programme/joint-programming-initiatives-urban-europe
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The Joint Programming Initiative (JPI) Urban Europe was established in 2010 as an “European research and innovation hub” to deal with present urban challenges. It wants to improve urban life by intra- and interdisciplinary transnational research (JPI Urban Europe, n.d.-c). The initiative involves 15 countries as members and five as observers (JPI Urban Europe, n.d.-b).

Joint Programming is a strategic and voluntary process which aims at collaboration of member states to tackle major societal challenges by funding research and innovation. Each of the ten existing JPIs deals with a different topic and develops its own common vision and Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). JPIs are led by the member states, supported by the European Commission and primarily funded by national funds (ERA-LEARN, n.d.).

In JPI Urban Europe’s SRIA for 2015 to 2020, “Accessibility and Connectivity” is one of five thematic research priorities for a transition to sustainable, resilient and liveable cities (JPI Urban Europe, n.d.-d).

From 2012 to 2023, JPI Urban Europe launched 16 calls. Future calls will run under the DUT Partnership. Some calls include top-up funding by the European Commission. These ERA-NET Cofunds allow a connection of JPI Urban Europe with societal challenges of H2020 programme and EU policies and activities (JPI Urban Europe, n.d.-a). The ERA-NET Cofund calls are listed as projects in the CORDIS repository.

While all projects from the ERA-NET Cofund Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (ENUAC) call series can be found in this compilation, other calls are only represented by a few of their projects and some JPI Urban Europe calls were not found to relate to urban transport and accessibility.

The first and second JPI Urban Europe pilot call

Website (pilot call I)	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/calls/jpi-ue-call-1/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/making-cities-work
Website (pilot call II)	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/calls/jpi-ue-call-2/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/jpi-urban-europe-second-pilot-call

CASUAL

Project Full Title	Co-creating attractive and sustainable urban areas and lifestyle – exploring new forms of inclusive urban governance		
Website	https://nordregio.org/publications/casual-co-creating-attractive-and-sustainable-urban-areas-and-lifestyles-synthesis-report/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/casual/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/jpi-urban-europe-first-pilot-call/co-creating-attractive-and-sustainable-urban-areas-and-lifestyle-exploring-new-forms-of-inclusive-urban-governance https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/co-creating-attractive-and-sustainable-urban-areas-and-lifestyle-exploring-new-forms		
Call	JPI Urban Europe pilot call I		
Project Coordinator	Nordregio, Nordic Centre for Spatial Development		
Project Partners	3 partners Austrian Institute for Regional Studies and Spatial Planning / Österreichisches Institut für Raumplanung (ÖIR) Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) Nordregio, Nordic Centre for Spatial Development		
Start date	2013	End date	2016
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options KA2 People-centred urban spaces and planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban governance for mobility transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Citizen and consumer behaviour, sustainable living and consumption patterns, inclusive urban governance, sustainable urban mobility planning, transit-oriented-development, public transport, travel behaviour, urban living labs		
Case Studies	Urban Living Labs: Vienna (In der Wiesen Ost), Stockholm (Årsta, Östberga) Transit-oriented development: The Netherlands		
<p>Urban policies and projects that are expected to promote sustainability are often focused on the built environment and the technical infrastructure. Less attention is given to changing lifestyles and everyday practices, even though citizen and consumer behaviour have a tremendous impact on resource consumption in our cities. In the CASUAL project we have investigated sustainable living and consumption patterns by including citizen and consumer perspectives in the governance of urban areas. We have explored new forms of inclusive urban governance by looking at collectively organised initiatives outside formal planning procedures (so-called urban living labs). In addition, planning for sustainable mobility has been investigated through a focus on transit-oriented developments.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/casual/, retrieved 9 September 2024)</p>			

CONCOORD

Project Full Title	Consolidation and coordination in urban areas		
Website	https://citylogisticsgame.com/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/conCOORD/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/jpi-urban-europe-first-pilot-call/consolidation-and-coordination-in-urban-areas https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/consolidation-and-coordination		
Call	JPI Urban Europe pilot call I		
Project Coordinator	Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) – Operations, Planning, Accounting & Control (OPAC) group Prof. Dr. Tom Van Woensel, t.v.woensel@tue.nl		
Project Partners	5 partners Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) – Operations, Planning, Accounting & Control (OPAC) group Middle East Technical University (METU) / Orta Doğu Teknik Üniversitesi (ODTÜ) Technical University of Denmark / Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU) – Department of Technology, Management and Economics University of Twente / Universiteit Twente (UT) – Industrial Engineering and Business Information Systems (IEBIS) Vienna University of Economics and Business / Wirtschaftsuniversität Wien (WU) – Research Institute for Supply Chain Management		
Start date	2013	End date	2016
Key Area(s)	KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition		
Keywords	City logistics Game, urban freight distribution flows, environmental footprint, performance measurement, sustainable logistics, business models, communication between the stakeholders		
Case Studies	<p>An efficient transportation system is vital for economic growth, European cohesion and the wellbeing of the citizens. CONCOORD focuses on urban related freight transportation flows that are currently fragmented.</p> <p>The CONCOORD project has led to a number of results. Important new models for the coordination and consolidation have been researched and presented in various papers and publications. Secondly, business models have been clearly described and discussed with all relevant stakeholders. Finally, the CONCOORD City Logistics game has been setup and is available (https://citylogisticsgame.com). This city logistics game was designed to demonstrate these difficulties. It is meant as a tool to come to an understanding of the objectives and behavior of the different stakeholders in city logistics. It is also designed to experience the importance of communication between the stakeholders, to experience decision tradeoffs in transport operations and to learn how to interfere when things go wrong.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/conCOORD/, retrieved 9 September 2024)</p>		

GUST

Project Full Title	Governance of urban sustainability transitions: advancing the role of living labs		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/gust/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/jpi-urban-europe-second-pilot-call/governance-of-urban-sustainability-transitions-advancing-the-role-of-living-labs		
Call	JPI Urban Europe pilot call II		
Project Coordinator	Lund University – International Institute for Industrial Environmental Economics (IIIEE) Kes McCormick, kes.mccormick@iiiee.lu.se		
Project Partners	4 partners Durham University – Department of Geography Erasmus University Rotterdam JOANNEUM RESEARCH Forschungsgesellschaft mbH Lund University – International Institute for Industrial Environmental Economics (IIIEE)		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.06.2014	End date	31.05.2017
Key Area(s)	KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Sustainability transitions, urban living labs, open innovation and co-creation, urban policy makers, urban planning, development projects		
Case Studies	<p>European cities face a pressing challenge to provide economic prosperity and social cohesion while achieving environmental sustainability.</p> <p>GUST was active between 2014-2017, as a part of the JPI Urban Europe Pilot Call II. The aim of the GUST project was to examine, inform and advance the governance of sustainability transitions through urban living labs, which are proliferating across Europe as a means for testing innovations in buildings, transport and energy systems.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/gust/, retrieved 9 September 2024)</p>		

E4-Share

Project Full Title	Models for ecological, economical, efficient, electric car-sharing		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/e4-share/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/jpi-urban-europe-second-pilot-call/models-for-ecological-economical-efficient-electric-car-sharing https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/models-ecological-economical-efficient-electric-car-sharing		
Call	JPI Urban Europe pilot call II		
Project Coordinator	University of Vienna – Institut für Statistik und Operations Research Markus Leitner, markus.leitner@univie.ac.at		
Project Partners	6 partners AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH iC consulenten Ziviltechniker GesmbH tbw research GesmbH Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB) – Département d'informatique University of Bologna – Department of Electric, Electronic and Information Engineering University of Vienna – Institut für Statistik und Operations Research		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.09.2014	End date	31.08.2017
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 4. Support sustainable lifestyles		
Keywords	flexible electric carsharing systems, economic viability, potential of shared mobility services, customer and operator needs, efficient planning and operating, optimization problems		
Case Studies	Project examples: Bologna, Brussels, Vienna Comparison of cities: NYC, Vienna, Singapore		
<p>Due to growing awareness and concerns regarding pollution, sustainability and life quality, cities are confronted with severe challenges and need to manage a transformation process that shall lead to less pollution and less energy consumption, while increasing the quality of public space available to citizens. These challenges can be met by flexible carsharing systems based on electric cars which also allow citizens to efficiently use and shift between different modes of transport.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/e4-share/, retrieved 9 September 2024)</p>			

Play!UC

Project Full Title	Playing with urban complexity: using co-located serious games to reduce the urban carbon footprint among young adults		
Website	https://play-uc.net/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/playuc/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/jpi-urban-europe-second-pilot-call/playing-with-urban-complexity-using-co-located-serious-games-to-reduce-the-urban-carbon-footprint-among-young-adults		
Call	JPI Urban Europe pilot call II		
Project Coordinator	University of Groningen / Rijksuniversiteit Groningen – Department of Planning Katharina Gugerell, k.gugerell@rug.nl		
Project Partners	4 partners FH OÖ Research Center Hagenberg HGB – gLab Green City Lab Vienna – Österreichisches Institut für nachhaltige Lebensräume Hasselt University – Researchgroup Arck University of Groningen / Rijksuniversiteit Groningen – Department of Planning		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.09.2014	End date	31.08.2017
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Serious game, urban mobility projects, urban planning, urban development projects, urban carbon footprint, young adults, participatory processes		
<p>Play!UC aims to foster the understanding of complex urban problems by combining participatory processes with serious games in a co-located setting.</p> <p>Play!UC was a part of the JPI Urban Europe Pilot Call II, and ran between 2014–2017. The project focused on engaging young adults and to foster the understanding of complex urban problems by combining participatory processes with serious games.</p> <p>In “Mobility Safari” during a period of five years (= 5 rounds) players try to realize as many innovative urban mobility projects as possible in the categories „innovative & educational“, „fair & safe“, active & healthy“ and „flexible & connected“. The spatial basis therefor is the Vienna city map which forms the game board and contains barriers like the Danube river, the underground railway network as well as some of the important urban development areas. The content of the projects derives from the Viennese Mobility Concept 2025. (https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/playuc/, retrieved 9 September 2024)</p>			

ERA-NET Cofund Smart Cities and Communities (ENSCC)

Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/calls/enscc/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/646453 https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enscc
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BREATHE

Project Full Title	Building Resilient Economic Agglomerations addressing Transportation and Health Effects: Urban form, location choice and transport solutions for low-carbon cities		
Website	https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/faculties/school-of-business-and-economics/more-about/breathe https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/breathe/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enscc/era-net-cofund-smart-cities-and-communities-enscc/urban-form-location-choice-and-transport-solutions-for-low-carbon-cities		
Call	ENSCC		
Project Coordinator	VU University Amsterdam / Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam – Department of Spatial Economics Dr. Steven Poelhekke, steven.poelhekke@vu.nl		
Project Partners	6 partners City of Gothenburg / Goteborgs Kommun / Göteborgs Stad Cylstat Asesoramiento Estadístico S.L. Sabanci University / Sabancı Üniversitesi Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) – Institute of Environmental Science and Technology (ICTA-UAB) University of Gothenburg / Göteborgs universitet VU University Amsterdam / Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam – Department of Spatial Economics		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2016	End date	2019
Key Area(s)	Focus: Spatial-economic equilibrium model for policy simulations KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Urban form, energy use, policy design, air quality, low-carbon cities, socially inclusive cities, preferences and behaviour of firms and households, spatial general equilibrium model, integrated local urban energy and transport systems, economic welfare, policy simulations, linking policy issues		
Case Studies	Amsterdam, Istanbul, Gothenburg, Barcelona		
<p>We study (i) the interactions between urban form, energy use and emissions by households and firms, and (ii) how the design of policies can contribute to social welfare and compliance with local air quality standards, while speeding up the transition towards prosperous low-carbon cities. A central theme throughout this project is the role of spatial structure in defining sustainable and socially inclusive cities. In European economies increasing city size and urban density tend to reduce households' average energy consumption. But increasing population density also tends to reduce local air quality. We analyse and contribute the management of this trade-off, by developing (i) surveys to study (environmental) preferences and (location) behaviour of firms and households in four different European cities –</p>			

Amsterdam, Istanbul, Gothenburg, Barcelona; (ii) a spatial general equilibrium model for policy simulations in cities across Europe. In doing so, we take into account that firms and households sort themselves across space, also in response to environmental and transport policies. Our approach is bottom-up and demand driven by involving city governance structures from the outset. We aim to support policy makers in their design of integrated local urban energy and transport systems, assessing the combined effect on economic welfare.

(<https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enscc/era-net-cofund-smart-cities-and-communities-enscc/urban-form-location-choice-and-transport-solutions-for-low-carbon-cities>, retrieved 9 September 2024)

CIVIC

Project Full Title	Construction in vicinities: innovative co-creation		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/civic/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enscc/era-net-cofund-smart-cities-and-communities-enscc/construction-in-vicinities-innovative-co-creation		
Call	ENSCC		
Project Coordinator	Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences – Urban Technology MSc Susanne Balm, s.h.balm@hva.nl		
Project Partners	10 partners AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences – Urban Technology BERNARD Ingenieure ZT GmbH Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB – Technology Management and economics communiThings ZT GmbH Deudekom and Cargohopper / A.J. van Deudekom B.V. Lindholmen Science Park AB Linköping University / Linköpings Universitet – Institute of Technology and Science Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Business technology and Operations Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electromobility research centre (MOBI)		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2016	End date	2018
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 1. Support striving neighbourhood economies 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Participation of stakeholders, energy efficiency, sustainable and safe construction, Smart Construction Logistics, MAMCA (multi-actor, multi-criteria analysis), decision-making platform, smart governance concepts		
Case Studies	Demonstration cities: Amsterdam, Vienna, Brussels, Stockholm		
<p>Construction is required to create more attractive, sustainable and economically viable cities. This includes the expansion of infrastructure, development of new residential areas and renovation of buildings. However, construction related transport causes negative impacts for people that live, work and/or travel in the vicinity of construction sites. It will increase understanding among stakeholders on improved transport and will generate smart governance strategies to support implementation of the CIVIC approach.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/civic/, retrieved 9 September 2024)</p>			

DESENT

Project Full Title	Smart decision support system for urban energy and transportation		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/desent/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enscc/era-net-cofund-smart-cities-and-communities-enscc/smart-decision-support-system-for-urban-energy-and-transportation		
Call	ENSCC		
Project Coordinator	Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) – Department of the Built Environment Univ. Prof. Dr. Harry Timmermans, h.j.p.timmermans@tue.nl		
Project Partners	8 partners 4ward Energy Research GmbH City of Steinkjer Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) – Department of the Built Environment Municipality of Helmond / Gemeente Helmond Municipality of Weiz / Stadtgemeinde Weiz Reiterer & Scherling GmbH SINTEF AS / SINTEF Technology and Society – SINTEF Energy Research Weizer Energie-Innovations-Zentrum GmbH		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2016	End date	2019
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Smart city, integrated solutions, smart decision support tool, urban energy and transport, co-creation, ICT technology, electric mobility, energy use, activity-travel demand model, energy generation schemes		
Case Studies	Demo cities		
<p>The success of smart city development needs integrated solutions on energy, transport, service and governance with the full involvement of multiple stakeholders, governments, enterprises, citizens, etc. DESENT is such a project focusing on providing a smart decision support tool for urban energy and transport by developing innovative approaches and utilising cutting-edge technologies using co-creation. The consortium which integrates top universities, research institutes, enterprises and private companies, will tackle the various challenges by developing/ implementing the innovative solutions in demo cities. DESENT will support smart decision making for policy makers and personalised services for citizens.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/desent/, retrieved 9 September 2024)</p>			

IP-SUNTAN

Project Full Title	Innovative policies for sustainable urban transportation		
Website	https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/faculties/school-of-business-and-economics/more-about/ip-sun-tan https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/ip-suntan/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enscc/era-net-cofund-smart-cities-and-communities-enscc/innovative-policies-for-sustainable-urban-transportation https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/innovative-policies-sustainable-urban-transportation		
Call	ENSCC		
Project Coordinator	VU University Amsterdam – Department of Spatial Economics Prof. Dr. Erik Verhoef, e.t.verhoef@vu.nl		
Project Partners	9 partners Amsterdam Zuidas City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad – Transportation Administration City of Vienna / Stadt Wien – Department for Urban Planning and Development (MA18) KTH Royal Institute of Technology / Kungliga Tekniska högskolan Stockholm Public Transport Agency / AB Storstockholms Lokaltrafik (SL) Swedish Transport Administration / Trafikverket – Stockholm Regional Office Verkeersonderneming Rotterdam Vienna University of Economics and Business / Wirtschaftsuniversität Wien (WU) – Multilevel Governance & Development VU University Amsterdam / Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam – Department of Spatial Economics		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2016	End date	2019
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Sustainable and efficient urban transport, innovative technologies, ICT based solutions, GPS based solutions, behavioural change, cycling and walking, public transport, electronic fare cards, real-time information, automated tracking, pricing and rewarding, big data, policy measures and strategies		
Case Studies	Case studies: Amsterdam, Rotterdam, Stockholm, Gothenburg, Vienna		
This project develops and investigates smart solutions for urban transport problems.			

Smart means that innovative technologies will be used (for example ICT and GPS based), and that smart ways to stimulate people to change behavior or adopt technologies will be developed and evaluated. The project considers road transport, cycling and walking, and public transport. It looks at a broad range of tools, including electronic fare cards, real-time public transport information, automated tracking of vehicles, and data from innovative pricing and rewarding experiments. The project brings together research groups, local authorities and case studies from Amsterdam, Rotterdam, Stockholm, Gothenburg and Vienna.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/ip-suntan/>, retrieved 9 September 2024)

me²

Project Full Title	Integrated smart city mobility and energy platform		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/me2/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enscc/era-net-cofund-smart-cities-and-communities-enscc/integrated-smart-city-mobility-and-energy-platform-me2 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/integrated-smart-city-mobility-and-energy-platform		
Call	ENSCC		
Project Coordinator	Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences – Energy and Innovation Dr. Robert van den Hoed, r.van.den.hoed@hva.nl		
Project Partners	6 partners Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences – Energy and Innovation Lisboa E-NOVA – Agência Municipal De Energia-Ambiente De Lisboa MediaPrimer MOOSMOAR Energies Universidade Católica Portuguesa Lisbon (UCP) – School of Business & Economics Virtual Power Solutions		
Start date	2016	End date	2018
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Electric mobility, platform for citizens, local community, awareness, energy consumption, user behaviour, efficient and reliable electric grid, smart meter, integration mobility with electricity, business model, B2B market place, energy costs		
Case Studies	Pilots: Amsterdam, Lisbon		
<p>me² (mobility + electricity = synergy) is a platform that connects citizens of local communities, helping them to be more aware of their energy consumption, incentivising changes in their individual and collective behaviour and helping them to save electricity costs while being engaged with a local community. The me² platform, which will be piloted and demonstrated in Lisbon and Amsterdam, can be employed by various actors, such as utilities, EV fleet operators or municipalities, enabling them to control user behaviour in order to make the electric grid more efficient and reliable. Results/Aims: Integration of e-mobility and electricity behaviour in a community setting. A policy recommendation set for local and national agencies.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/me2/, retrieved 9 September 2024)</p>			

Smart Commuting

Project Full Title	Smart and Mobile Work in Growth Regions		
Website	https://smartcommuting.eu/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/smart-commuting/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enscc/era-net-cofund-smart-cities-and-communities-enscc/smart-and-mobile-work-in-growth-regions https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/smart-commuting-smart-and-mobile-work-growth-regions		
Call	ENSCC		
Project Coordinator	Aalto University / Aalto-korkeakoulusäätiö sr – Department of Industrial Engineering and Management Prof. Dr. Matti Vartiainen, matti.vartiainen@aalto.fi		
Project Partners	10 partners Aalto University / Aalto-korkeakoulusäätiö sr – Department of Industrial Engineering and Management AC2SG Software Oy AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH Growth Corridor Finland ISTmobil GmbH Office for Mobility of the Canton of Basel-Stadt tbw research GesmbH Tuup Oy Virta Ltd. / Liikennevirta Oy Zürcher Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften / Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW) – Institute of Sustainable Development (INE)		
Start date	2016	End date	2018
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 3. Provide sustainable solutions for longer trips 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition		
Keywords	MaaS, intelligent transport system services, CO2-free commuting, mobility of the workforce, needs of mobile workers, decision support, urban planning and governance		
Case Studies	Study regions: Korneuburg, Growth Corridor Finland (GCF), Basel		
<p>The Smart Commuting project explored new ways of combining work and life with new intelligent transport system services and developed new concepts to support sustainable CO2-free commuting and mobile, multi-locational work. The mobility of the workforce is increasing due to technology development, commuting and the nature of work, which has many consequences as long commuting may decrease the productivity of work and leave less time for relaxation, resulting in lowered wellbeing. Cities also have to</p>			

address commuting when planning technical solutions, developing services and calculating their finance schemes. Therefore, the first objective of this project was to identify the changing needs of mobile workers for transport. The second objective was to support the implementation of sustainable and intelligent transport services that meet these needs.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/smart-commuting/>, retrieved 9 September 2024)

SmarterLabs

Project Full Title	Improving Anticipation and Social Inclusion in Living Labs for Smart City Governance		
Website	https://smarterlabs.uni-graz.at/en/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/smarter-labs/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enscc/era-net-cofund-smart-cities-and-communities-enscc/smarterlabs-improving-anticipation-and-social-inclusion-in-living-labs-for-smart-city-governance https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/smarterlabs-improving-anticipation-and-social-inclusion-living-labs-smart-city-governance		
Call	ENSCC		
Project Coordinator	Maastricht University – Maastricht Sustainability Institute (MSI) Marc Dijk, m.dijk@maastrichtuniversity.nl		
Project Partners	13 partners BRAL vzw Citizen Action Brussels / Brusselse Raad voor het Leefmilieu City of Bellinzona City of Graz / Stadt Graz City of Maastricht / Gemeente Maastricht Maastricht Bereikbaar Maastricht University – Maastricht Sustainability Institute (MSI) Pro Velo Ticino Sweco Architects / Grontmij University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland / Scuola Universitaria Professionale della Svizzera Italiana University of Graz – RCE Graz-Styria Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Brussels Centre for Urban Studies Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Cosmopolis Centre for Urban Research Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Geography		
Start date	2016	End date	2019
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Smart City Living Lab, smart ICT based solutions, upscaling, large-scale adoption, social inclusion, low-carbon transport, co-design, implementation guidelines		

Case Studies	<p>Living labs: Bellinzona, Brussels, Graz, Maastricht</p> <p>Testing workshops: Helsinki, Santander, Istanbul</p>
<p>The ‘Smart City Living Lab’ is an emerging approach in European cities. It brings together citizens, policymakers, businesses, and researchers to test smart, ICT-based solutions to urban problems in real-life contexts. However, for urban mobility problems, solutions that ‘work’ in the particular reality of a Living Lab may not be adopted at a large scale. Urban infrastructure is interwoven with the daily lives of citizens and therefore difficult to change, and large groups may not even have access to ICT-based solutions. The SmarterLabs project develops a novel approach that anticipates such problems in upscaling, and tests the approach through smart mobility Living Lab experiments in four cities: Bellinzona, Brussels, Graz and Maastricht.</p> <p>https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/smarter-labs/, retrieved 9 September 2024)</p>	

SmartGov

Project Full Title	Advanced decision support for smart governance		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/smartgov/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enscc/era-net-cofund-smart-cities-and-communities-enscc/advanced-decision-support-for-smart-governance https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/advanced-decision-support-smart-governance		
Call	ENSCC		
Project Coordinator	University for Continuing Education Krems / Donau-Universität Krems – Center for E-Governance Mag. Dr. Gregor Eibl, gregor.eibl@donau-uni.ac.at		
Project Partners	8 partners ACTIVE Solution Ingenieurbüro AG City of Quart de Poblet / Ayuntamiento de Quart de Poblet Cyprus University of Technology (CUT) – Department of Electrical Engineering, Computer Engineering and Informatics Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – OTB Research for the Built Environment Interfusion Services Ltd Kenus Informática Limassol Municipality / Dimos Lemesos University for Continuing Education Krems / Donau-Universität Krems – Center for E-Governance		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.04.2016	End date	31.03.2019
Key Area(s)	Focus: Support tools for policy decisions suitable to reduce car usage and increase citizen engagement KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Smart city governance, two-way communication between citizens and urban policymakers, social media, open data, fuzzy cognitive maps (FCMs), user-friendly modelling and visualization tools, policy scenarios, sustainable mobility, social inclusion, decision-making, route suitability		
Case Studies	Quart de Poblet, Limassol, Vienna, Amsterdam		
ABOUT 'Smart Cities' provide new ways of designing and managing public services, infrastructure, sustainable mobility, economic development and social inclusion. However, two-way communication between citizens and urban policymakers is lacking. This is partly the result of underutilisation of citizens' social media feeds and useful open data sets. The SmartGov project creates new support tools that effectively incorporate linked open data and social media into Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (FCMs). FCMs are			

useful modelling and visualization tools for discussing policy scenarios. The developed tools are tested and implemented in four European cities.

ADDED VALUE The benefits for cities can be seen in two ways. The first is improved environmental sustainability through reduction of car usage. Additionally, it illustrates how smart city governance can be executed and how to increase citizen engagement and two-way communication.

RESULTS By combining data from open sources and social media channels, information that previously has been used separately, SmartGov has established a new framework. Through combination of these data and usage of Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (FCM), stakeholders can visualise and analyse the future impact of policy decisions. Two pilots have been conducted, one Quart de Poblet in Spain and one in Limassol in Cyprus. The two pilots were focused on mobility with the aim to engage citizens and incorporate their perspectives. In Quart de Poblet, the municipality recognized a problem with traffic around schools causing safety and environmental issues. The municipality used SmartGov’s framework to minimize the number of cars around schools. Limassol used the framework on the issue of garbage collection and route suitability. By identifying factors influencing the collection process, such as parked vehicles and manoeuvrability, and interacting within a FCM, the city could determine optimal routes for garbage collection vehicles. SmartGov’s framework is comprised of two pieces of software that communicate with each other – a social media tool that collects, filters and categorizes social media posts and a FCM tool which works as a decision making engine. FCMs are a sustainable tool improving efficiency and allowing custom support to each stakeholder’s specific needs. Further, they strengthen the two-way communication between a city and its residents by including citizens opinions in the data on which decisions are based. By identifying relevant experts that provide their knowledge, each FCM becomes an internal, mental model of the problem a certain stakeholder wishes to solve. As expert inputs increase, FCMs become increasingly better tailored to each actors’ specific needs, making them useful for all types of stakeholders wanting to streamline their decision-making processes.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/ENSCC-Results-Catalogue-2019-1.pdf>, retrieved 9 September 2024)

SPACERGY

Project Full Title	Space-Energy patterns for smart energy infrastructures, community reciprocities & related governance		
Website	https://spacergy.wordpress.com/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/spacergy/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enscc/era-net-cofund-smart-cities-and-communities-enscc/space-energy-patterns-for-smart-energy-infrastructures-community-reciprocities-related-governance		
Call	ENSCC		
Project Coordinator	Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – Architecture and the Built Environment Prof.dr.ir. Arjan van Timmeren, a.vantimmeren@tudelft.nl		
Project Partners	10 partners Almere City City Council of Bergen / Bergen Kommune Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – Architecture and the Built Environment Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich (ETH Zurich) – Institute for Transport Planning and Systems Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich (ETH Zurich) – Institute of Technology in Architecture Municipality of Brescia / Comune di Brescia Municipality of Zurich Norwegian Public Roads Administration / Statens vegvesen Stichting Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions (AMS) Western Norway University of Applied Sciences / Høgskulen på Vestlandet (HVL) (Bergen University College) – Department of Civil Engineering		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2016	End date	2019
Key Area(s)	Topic: Assessment framework for district energy demand of mobility KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Energy Sensitive Cities, spatial aspects of urban developments, energy and mobility infrastructures, in-depth modelling, action research, guidelines for informed decision making, local community involvement, energy demand of mobility, liveable and sustainable urban environment, District Energy Integration Model		

Case Studies	Living labs: Zurich, Bergen, Almere
<p>ABOUT SPACERGY studies ‘Energy Sensitive Cities’, to achieve inclusive, shared visions, collaboration and informed acting by planners and decision makers, in joint coalitions with users and other stakeholders. The project builds knowledge regarding reciprocities and beneficial interactions of spatial aspects of urban developments, energy and mobility infrastructure in four cities. Based on in depth modelling and action research produced together with stakeholders, the project provided guidelines to support informed decision making throughout Europe.</p> <p>ADDED VALUE The project helps planners, designers and decision makers facilitate the transitions to a more efficient, liveable and thus sustainable urban environment.</p> <p>RESULTS SPACERGY employed a living lab approach for three urban districts in Zurich in Switzerland, Bergen in Norway and Almere in the Netherlands. These labs were places for experimenting and the three districts had the common aspect of being under (re)development and subjects to a complex process of urban re-densification which provided a chance to actually implement the guidelines. One of the main issues was to understand what energy transitions mean for each spatial and cultural context and with these insights create instruments to help communities with efficient use and exchange of energy. Through workshops and the creation of scenarios, an assessment framework was developed. The framework DEIM (District Energy Integration Model) assesses district energy demand and production by looking at characteristics of the urban morphologies, uses and energy systems, for the evaluation of the building and mobility related energy performance. For example, from a mobility point of view, DEIM was used to analyse the relations between walkability and energy demand for mobility. The DEIM’s consider local and cultural aspects in each district and provide tools that can incorporate expertise from local partners.</p> <p>https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/ENSCC-Results-Catalogue-2019-1.pdf, retrieved 9 September 2024)</p>	

TRANS-FORM

Project Full Title	smart transfers through unravelling urban form and travel flow dynamics		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/trans-form/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enscc/era-net-cofund-smart-cities-and-communities-enscc/smart-transfers-through-unravelling-urban-form-and-travel-flow-dynamics https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/smart-transfers-through-unravelling-urban-form-and-travel-flow-dynamics https://github.com/NicholasMolyneaux/trans-form-integration		
Call	ENSCC		
Project Coordinator	Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – Department of Transport and Planning Dr. Oded Cats, o.cats@tudelft.nl		
Project Partners	6 partners Blekinge Institute of Technology – Department of Computer Science and Engineering Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – Department of Transport and Planning École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) ETRA Investigacion y Desarrollo SA IBM Research GmbH Linköping University / Linköpings Universitet – Department of Science and Technology		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2016	End date	2019
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 3. Provide sustainable solutions for longer trips 4. Integrate new technologies in transport		
Keywords	Smart cities, multimodal public transport network, smart data, simulation of passenger flows, integration tool, demand prediction		
Case Studies	Case study: Netherlands, Den Haag, Sweden, Switzerland		
<p>The TRANS-FORM project was a part of the ENSCC call and active between 2016-2019. Smart cities and communities rely on efficient, reliable and robust transport systems. This project will contribute to a better understanding of how people move in different levels of the public transport network and to offer new techniques to adjust public transport services to respond to actual demand levels. Three case studies in the Netherlands, Sweden and Switzerland will measure how travellers transfer within terminals and urban and regional networks, in order to develop methods for predicting passenger flows, quantify the reliability of passenger experience and evaluate strategies for improved coordination between travel modes, especially in case of disturbances.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/trans-form/, retrieved 9 September 2024)</p>			

ERA-NET Cofund Smart Urban Futures (ENSUF)

Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/calls/ensuf-call/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/693443 https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/ensuf
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c3places

Project Full Title	Using ICT for Co-Creation of Inclusive Public Places		
Website	https://myc3place.di.unimi.it/ https://c3places.eu/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/c3places/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/ensuf/era-net-cofund-smart-urban-futures/using-ict-for-co-creation-of-inclusive-public-places		
Call	ENSUF		
Project Coordinator	Cooperativa de Formação e Animação Cultural CRL / Universidade Lusófona de Humanidades e Tecnologias (UL/CeiED) – Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Education and Development Prof. Dr. Carlos Smaniotto Costa, smaniotto.costa@ulusofona.pt		
Project Partners	7 partners Cooperacy Association Cooperativa de Formação e Animação Cultural CRL / Universidade Lusófona de Humanidades e Tecnologias (UL/CeiED) – Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Education and Development Ghent University / Universiteit Gent – Information Technology Mykolas Romeris University – The LAB of Social Technologies National Laboratory for Civil Engineering / Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (LNEC) – Department of Materials Università degli Studi di Milano – Department of Computer Science Urban Planning Institute of the Republic of Slovenia / Urbanistični inštitut Republike Slovenije (UIRS)		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2017	End date	2019
Key Area(s)	KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Public open spaces, ICT technology, user needs, cultural identity, co-creation, integrated and inclusive development policy, behavioural change, active life styles, creative industries		
Case Studies	Ghent, Lisbon, Milano, Vilnius		
<p>C3Places aims at increasing the quality of public open spaces (squares, parks, green spaces) as a community's service, reflecting through ICT the needs of different social groups.</p> <p>[...]</p> <p>Public spaces are critical for cultural identity, as they offer the place for interactions among generations and ethnicities. Even in the digital era, people still need contact with nature and other people to develop different life skills, values and attitudes, to be healthy, satisfied and environmentally responsible. Using ICT</p>			

and co-creating with users, C3Places will also expand our knowledge on meeting emerging citizens' needs with regard to the future public space

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/c3places/>, retrieved 9 September 2024)

LOOPER

Project Full Title	Learning loops in the public realm		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/looper/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/ensuf/era-net-cofund-smart-urban-futures/learning-loops-in-the-public-realm https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/learning-loops-public-realm https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/looper		
Call	ENSUF		
Project Coordinator	Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electromobility research centre (MOBI) Dr. Imre Keseru, imre.keseru@vub.be		
Project Partners	10 partners BRAL vzw Citizen Action Brussels / Brusselse Raad voor het Leefmilieu City of Verona / Comune di Verona Clicks and Links Ltd. Legambiente Verona S4B Manchester The University of Manchester – Planning, Property and Environmental Management University Iuav of Venice – Departement of Design and Planning in Complex Environment Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Business technology and Operations Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Cosmopolis Centre for Urban Research Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electromobility research centre (MOBI)		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2017	End date	2020
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Participatory co-creation methodology, learning loops, traffic safety, traffic calming, pedestrianization, school streets, air pollution, empowerment of citizens, decision-making, urban challenges, co-implementation and monitoring, Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis (MAMCA), citizen science		
Case Studies	Living Labs: Brussels, Manchester, Verona		
<p>Problems such as traffic congestion, safety and pollution are difficult to tackle as the mitigation involves multiple urban stakeholders. The Urban Living Lab project LOOPER set out to help by creating a participatory co-creation methodology and platform that demonstrates ‘learning loops’: the ways of decision-making that bring together citizens, stakeholders and policy-makers to iteratively learn to handle such urban challenges. The method has three steps: 1) Problem identification, 2) Co-designing solutions, 3) Co-implementing and monitoring. In the problem identification step, you systematically categorise the</p>			

desires of residents and other stakeholders. In the second step, participants (such as citizens and policy makers) co-design solutions and collectively generate and evaluate ideas (for example limited speed zones). In the final step you co-implement and monitor the solutions proposed.

When failures and conflicts are identified within a loop, these are recognised and modified in the next loop. The project's first loop took place around a street in Brussels where residents had had enough of road incidents and unsafe road environments. Through workshops, over 40 ideas were generated so the team adopted the Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis (MAMCA), a software program that identified the potential synergies and conflicts amongst the ideas. The process showed that raising traffic safety awareness was the option that generated the least conflict and carried the most consensus. After testing and evaluation, it was concluded that more drastic measures were needed in the second loop, whereby LOOPER worked with citizen science (for instance, residents were given air quality monitors and speed monitors) and tested the concept of school streets and road signs indicating to motorists that they are bypassing someone's home.

(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/FINAL_ENSUF-Projects-Results-Catalogue-2020-20200928.pdf, retrieved 9 September 2024)

SMART PEDESTRIAN NET (SPN)

Project Full Title	Smart cities are walkable: SPN - a model to plan a pedestrian network and a pedestrian navigation system		
Website	https://ctac.uminho.pt/spn/ https://livelyspaces.info/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/smart-pedestrian-net/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/ensuf/era-net-cofund-smart-urban-futures/smart-cities-are-walkable-spn-a-model-to-plan-a-pedestrian-network-and-a-pedestrian-navigation-system https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/smart-pedestrian-net		
Call	ENSUF		
Project Coordinator	University of Minho – Centre for Territory, Environment and Construction (CTAC) Prof. Rui Ramos, rui.ramos@civil.uminho.pt		
Project Partners	6 partners Association for Sustainable Innovative Development in Economics, Environment and Society (ASIDEES) European University Cyprus (EUC) Research Centre Municipality of Bologna / Comune di Bologna Porto Municipality University of Bologna – Department of Architecture University of Minho / Universidade do Minho – Centre for Territory, Environment and Construction (CTAC)		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2017	End date	2020
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Walkability, smart sustainable and inclusive cities, pedestrian navigation system, GIS, participatory approach, planning policies, street connectivity		
Case Studies	Involved Cities: Porto, Bologna		
<p>Cities are facing growing mobility challenges due to the strong dependence on cars. Motorised traffic is recognisably a major source of air and noise pollution in cities. In EU, urban mobility accounts for 40% of CO2 emissions and up to 70% of other pollutants. The sustainable mobility concept is focused in shifting this pattern towards non-motorised or more sustainable forms of mobility. Walking is a soft and active mode strictly related with sustainable mobility as it reduces traffic congestion and pollution and has positive impacts on health. SPN is a project focused on improving walkability in cities. SPN intends to</p>			

provide a model to help European cities to improve walkability as one of the important dimensions of smart, sustainable and inclusive development.

Aim/objective:

- Assess the urban conditions provided to pedestrians considering a wide range of criteria
- Define planning policies to improve walkability and street connectivity by involving stakeholders
- Develop a pedestrian navigation system for defining routes

(<https://ctac.uminho.pt/spn/>, retrieved 9 September 2024)

Making Cities Work

Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/making-cities-work/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/making-cities-work
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MIMIC

Project Full Title	Minimizing impact of construction material flows in cities: Innovative Co-Creation		
Website	https://closer.lindholmen.se/projekt/mimic-aiming-sustainable-construction-logistics https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/mimic/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/making-cities-work/minimizing-impact-of-construction-material-flows-in-cities-innovative-co-creation		
Call	Making Cities Work		
Project Coordinator	Lindholmen Science Park AB Lina Moritz, lina.moritz@lindholmen.se Lovisa Westblom, lovisa.westblom@lindholmen.se		
Project Partners	10 partners AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH BERNARD Ingenieure ZT GmbH Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB – Architecture and Civil Engineering Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB – Technology Management and economics Lindholmen Science Park AB Linköping University / Linköpings Universitet – Institute of Technology and Science Service public régional de Bruxelles – Brussels Mobility / Bruxelles Mobilité (Administration de l'Équipement et des Déplacements) SINTEF AS / SINTEF Technology and Society Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Business technology and Operations Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electromobility research centre (MOBI)		
Duration (months)	38		
Start date	21.08.2018	End date	01.11.2021
Key Area(s)	KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	smart governance concepts, sustainable construction logistics, construction logistics game, city planning process, urban development decision processes		
Case Studies			
MIMIC wants to demonstrate how smart governance concepts can be used as an aid in the construction and city planning processes to facilitate and support logistics to, from and on urban construction sites. The aim is to improve mobility and reduce congestion within cities and thereby reduce the negative impacts of			

construction sites on the surrounding communities. The project will result in increased understanding among authorities of how different types of construction logistics affect the environment, urban traffic flows and mobility. Further, the implementation of smart governance concepts will enable a supportive platform for urban development decision processes, including analyses and optimization of construction traffic, and a sustainability impact assessment framework.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/mimic/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

OptiMaaS

Project Full Title	Optimized Mobility as a Service		
Website	http://optimaas.tbwrknowledge.org/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/optimaas/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/making-cities-work/optimized-mobility-as-a-service		
Call	Making Cities Work		
Project Coordinator	tbw research GesmbH Angela Muth, a.muth@tbwresearch.org		
Project Partners	9 partners AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH Institute of Transport Economics / Transportøkonomisk Institutt (TOI) MO.Point Mobilitätsservices GmbH Ruter AS Service public régional de Bruxelles – Brussels Mobility / Bruxelles Mobilité (Administration de l'Équipement et des Déplacements) tbw research GesmbH UIV Urban Innovation Vienna GmbH Upstream – next level mobility GmbH WIENER LINIEN GmbH & Co KG		
Duration (months)	30		
Start date	01.09.2018	End date	28.02.2021
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Mobility as a Service (MaaS), multimodal environmentally friendly mobility services, social acceptance, urban periphery, citizens' needs, combined mobility services (CMS), business models, data-driven, urban planning and policy making, IT-solutions, dynamic incentives and pricing		
Case Studies	Mobility Labs (physical and/or virtual): Vienna, Salzburg, Oslo, Brussels		
OptiMaaS develops new methods and processes addressing the needs of public and private mobility actors to provide optimized Mobility as a Service (MaaS) offers. The first objective is to identify changing requirements and novel solution paths for planning better MaaS offers in the urban periphery. The second objective is to generate Mobility Labs focusing diverse social patterns within the urban periphery. Thirdly OptiMaaS will develop new simulation techniques for evaluating the impact of dynamic incentives and pricing as well as personalized MaaS-routing policies on the mobility system as a whole. Mobility-Labs			

(physical and/or virtual) in Vienna, Salzburg, Oslo and Brussels will evaluate the impact of different strategies on city planning policies, new business models, cooperation of public and private mobility actors and user acceptance of individualized MaaS offers.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/optimaas/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

SimpliCITY

Project Full Title	Marketplace for user-centered sustainability services plattform		
Website	https://www.simplicity-project.eu/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/simplicity/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/making-cities-work/simplicity-marketplace-for-user-centered-sustainability-services-plattform		
Call	Making Cities Work		
Project Coordinator	Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH Dr. Veronika Hornung-Prähauser, veronika.hornung-praehauser@salzburgresearch.at		
Project Partners	6 partners City of Salzburg / Stadt Salzburg – 6/00 Energie und Smart City Koordination City of Uppsala Polycular Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH SIR – Salzburger Institut für Raumordnung und Wohnen Uppsala University – Department of Information Technology		
Duration (months)	30		
Start date	01.10.2018	End date	31.03.2021
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 1. Support striving neighbourhood economies KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Regional sustainability services (RSUS), sustainable city lifestyle, nudging, Smart City Initiatives, participation, incentivisation, co-design tool-kit, digital marketplace, behavioural change, bike mobility, local consumption, digital inclusion		
Case Studies	Salzburg, Uppsala, 3 follower-cities		
<p>SimpliCITY aims to boost the digital competences of the urban communities in Salzburg, Uppsala and three follower-cities in living a sustainable lifestyle. The objectives are: to scale up and increase the visibility of regional sustainability services, to raise awareness and create a community through nudging by developing methods and tools for nudging a community for regional sustainability services, and, to initiate and foster international collaboration and knowledge transfer of smart city initiatives. The project will provide the</p>			

proof-of concept for a replicable online marketplace using behavioural nudges and gamified features. It will focus on bike mobility services, local production and consumption and digital inclusion services.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/simplicity/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

Sustainable and Liveable Cities and Urban Areas

Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/calls/sustainable-urbanisation-china-europe/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/europe-china-first-joint-call-for-sustainable-and-liveable-cities-and-urban-areas
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SMUrTS

Project Full Title	Sustainable mixed urban transit system with electric and conventional buses		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/smurts/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/europe-china-first-joint-call-for-sustainable-and-liveable-cities-and-urban-areas/sustainable-mixed-urban-transit-system-with-electric-and-conventional-buses https://prosjektbanken.forskingsradet.no/en/project/FORISS/299078		
Call	Sustainable and Liveable Cities and Urban Areas		
Project Coordinator	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) – Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering Chaoru Lu, Trude Torset, chaoru.lu@ntnu.no		
Project Partners	6 partners Beihang University – School of Transportation Science and Engineering Beijing Jiaotong University (BJTU) – School of Traffic and Transportation Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB – Architecture and Civil Engineering Lund University Norwegian University of Science and Technology / Norges teknisk-naturvitenskapelige universitet (NTNU) – Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering SINTEF AS / SINTEF Technology and Society		
Duration (months)	36 months		
Start date	15.01.2019	End date	14.01.2022
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition		
Keywords	Battery electric buses, limitations, transition process, charging infrastructure, sustainable urban transit system, service quality, circular economy, feasibility analysis		
Case Studies			
<p>Battery electric buses are seen as a well-suited technology for sustainable urban transit system because it has high energy efficiency and generates zero tailpipe emissions. Therefore, conventional buses are likely to be continuously replaced by electric buses. However, the limitations of electric buses, such as range limitations, battery capacity loss and required charging times of battery, are critical issues for the service quality of the urban transit system. Therefore, it is more realistic to develop a sustainable urban transit system mixed with conventional and electric buses in a transitional period until the limitations of electric buses are overcome.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/smurts/, retrieved 16 September 2024)</p>			

MAAT

Project Full Title	Multi-faceted valuation and administration of access to housing and transportation		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/maat/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/europe-china-first-joint-call-for-sustainable-and-liveable-cities-and-urban-areas/multi-faceted-valuation-and-administration-of-access-to-housing-and-transportation		
Call	Sustainable and Liveable Cities and Urban Areas		
Project Coordinator	Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) – Urban Planning Group Dr. Feixiong Liao, f.liao@tue.nl		
Project Partners	6 partners Beihang University – School of Economics and Management École Normale Supérieure Paris-Saclay Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) – Urban Planning Group Huazhong University of Science and Technology – School of Architecture and Urban Planning Huazhong University of Science and Technology – School of Management Université Cergy Pontoise – THEMA		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.03.2019	End date	28.02.2022
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Housing and transportation, behaviour, accessibility, equity, integrated decision support tools, data solutions, liveable city concepts		
Case Studies			
<p>To address policy initiatives promoting sustainable urban areas, this interdisciplinary project aims to better understand the complex process of urban dynamics and how they create spatial and social disparities by developing integrated decision support tools for multi-faceted valuation and administration of access to housing and transportation (H+T). These tools involve analyses of (i) individual and household choice behavior concerning travel, housing, and employment, incorporating budget constraints and heterogeneities; (ii) organizational decision-making process incorporating fiscal competitions and services innovation; and (iii) H+T interactions and coordinated policy outcomes on affordable accessibility, equity, and other H+T externalities. The suggested model systems combine the advantages of aggregate and disaggregate methodologies and will be founded on uniform data solutions, with which data will be collected and analyzed across cities of different countries.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/maat/, retrieved 16 September 2024)</p>			

SIMETRI

Project Full Title	Sustainable Mobility and Equality in mega-ciTy Regions		
Website	https://simetri.uk/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/simetri/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/europe-china-first-joint-call-for-sustainable-and-liveable-cities-and-urban-areas/sustainable-mobility-and-equality-in-mega-city-regions		
Call	Sustainable and Liveable Cities and Urban Areas		
Project Coordinator	University College London (UCL) – Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis (CASA) Prof. Dr. Michael Batty, m.batty@ucl.ac.uk		
Project Partners	7 partners Birkbeck, University of London – Geography Department King’s College London – Geography Shenzhen University – School of Architecture and Urban Planning Sun Yat-sen University – School of Geography and Planning The University of Hong Kong – Shenzhen Institute of Research and Innovation University College London (UCL) – Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis (CASA) VU University Amsterdam / Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam – School of Business and Economics		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.03.2019	End date	28.02.2022
Key Area(s)	KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	mega-city regions, spatial data analytics, urban modelling, urban data and simulation platform, inequality indicators, equity, connectivity, Land Use Transportation Interaction (LUTI), participatory governance		
Case Studies	Pearl River Delta ‘Greater Bay Area’ mega-city region		
<p>We propose to develop a platform for prediction and urban governance using the Pearl River Delta ‘Greater Bay Area’ mega-city region as a demonstrator, bringing sustainability indicators and simulation models from the Greater London and urban Holland (the Randstad) regions to inform the development of an urban data and simulation platform relevant to designing and testing scenarios for new modes of transport and the alleviation of socio-economic inequalities in the Bay Area. These problems, we believe, will be key mega-city regions during the rest of this century. The project will: (1) integrate already developed Land Use Transportation Interaction (LUTI) models for London and the Randstad with ongoing cellular development and transport models for the Greater Bay Area, (2) develop new indicators for measuring spatial efficiency and equity, (3) develop analytics to inform innovative policy analysis and governance, and (4) demonstrate these tools in association with planning agencies and government across the region.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/simetri/, retrieved 16 September 2024)</p>			

U-PASS

Project Full Title	Urban Public Administration and Services innovation for Innovative Urban Mobility Management and Policy		
Website	https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/faculties/school-of-business-and-economics/more-about/u-pass https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/u-pass/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe/europe-china-first-joint-call-for-sustainable-and-liveable-cities-and-urban-areas/urban-public-administration-and-services-innovation-for-innovative-urban-mobility-management-and-policy		
Call	Sustainable and Liveable Cities and Urban Areas		
Project Coordinator	VU University Amsterdam / Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam – Department of Spatial Economics Prof. Dr. Erik Verhoef, e.t.verhoef@vu.nl		
Project Partners	5 partners Beijing Jiaotong University (BJTU) Beijing Transport Institute (BTI) University of Leeds – Institute for Transport Studies VU University Amsterdam / Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam – Department of Spatial Economics Zhejiang University (ZJU)		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.04.2019	End date	31.03.2023
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Efficient reliable safe accessible and environmentally sustainable urban transport, innovative urban mobility management, inclusion, bike and car mobility, electric driving, automated vehicles, tradable credits scheme (TCS), behavioural impacts, modelling approaches, shared parking, policy integration, stakeholder coordination, public administration mechanisms, data management, land use, urban network models		
Case Studies	Applications in China and Europe		
<p>This project aims to deal with these challenges for achieving innovative and sustainable urban mobility in the process of urbanization. The project encompasses modelling approaches and experiments to be developed for and carried out in China and Europe, notably projects involving the use of innovative instruments i.e. automatic/electric Driving (Shared Electrified Autonomous Vehicles, SEAVs), Tradable Credits Scheme (TCS), shared parking, bike/car sharing, and policy integration and stakeholders coordination mechanisms. It also involve the public administration mechanisms of these innovational</p>			

services with the approaches of mobility policy, administration, and data management, sharing and standardization.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/u-pass/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

ERA-NET Cofund Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (ENUAC)

Website (1st ENUAC call)	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/calls/enuac/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/875022 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/urban-accessibility-and-connectivity
Website (Knowledge Hub call)	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/calls/enuac-knowledge-hub/
Website (2nd/Sino-European call)	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/calls/era-net-cofund-urban-accessibility-and-connectivity-sino-european-call/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/2nd-en-auc-joint-cofund-call
Website (3rd/Innovation Action call)	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/calls/enuac-innovation-action/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/3rd-en-auc-joint-call-innovations-for-managing-sustainable-urban-accessibility-enuac

CATAPULT

Project Full Title	Policies for inclusive, demand-oriented and target group-specific automated mobility solutions for cities		
Website	https://catapultproject.eu/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/catapult/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/policies-for-inclusive-demand-oriented-and-target-group-specific-automated-mobility-solutions-for-cities		
Call	ENUAC		
Project Coordinator	AustriaTech – Gesellschaft des Bundes für technologiepoltische Maßnahmen GmbH Nora Spiegel, Nora.Spiegel@austriatech.at		
Project Partners	4 partners AustriaTech – Gesellschaft des Bundes für technologiepoltische Maßnahmen GmbH FACTUM Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (KULeuven) – Institute for Mobility RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB		
Duration (months)	24		
Start date	01.03.2021	End date	28.02.2023
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	user needs and requirements, inclusive mobility services, sustainable automated mobility, inclusive urban policies demand-oriented mobility solutions, underrepresented user groups, children, elderly persons, persons with sensory or physical impairments, co-creative process, serious game, development process		
Case Studies	<p>How can automated mobility be designed and used in a more inclusive way?</p> <p>The needs of user groups that have often been underrepresented in the process of developing new mobility services are of specific interest in this research project. Informed by field tests and consultations in several cities in AT, BE & SE, we aim to support the development of innovative mobility systems and services by providing policy recommendations and frameworks for a co-creation approach. Politicians, urban planners and mobility providers shall be enabled to develop services that are more inclusive and sustainable.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/catapult/, retrieved 16 September 2024)</p>		

ITEM

Project Full Title	Inclusive Transition towards Electric Mobility		
Website	https://www.itemresearch.org/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/item/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/inclusive-transition-towards-electric-mobility		
Call	ENUAC		
Project Coordinator	Institute of Transport Economics / Transportøkonomisk Institutt (TOI) Dr. Tanu Priya Uteng, Tanu.Priyauteng@toi.no Dr. Lars Böcker, Lars.Bocker@toi.no		
Project Partners	5 partners Adam Mickiewicz University Poznań / Uniwersytet im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu (UAM) – Wydział Antropologii i Kulturoznawstwa Heksagon Research Institute of Transport Economics / Transportøkonomisk Institutt (TOI) Oxford University – Transport Studies Unit Utrecht University (UU) – Department of Human Geography and Spatial Planning		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	31.03.2021	End date	28.02.2024
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	E-mobility, Justice, Accessibility dual perspective on households and urban policy, inclusive electric mobility transition process, decision-making and governance, distribution of social and spatial benefits and use, recognition, procedure, scenario planning		
Case Studies	Oslo, Utrecht, Bristol, Poznań		
<p>It remains unclear if European cities' attempts to accelerate electric mobility (EM) transitions are inclusive. Questions like who benefits, whose needs are considered, who decides and how needs further probing. ITEM will advance inclusive EM transitions through a dual perspective on households and urban policy. It will examine inequalities in EM-related needs, capabilities, decision-making, accessibility and everyday mobility. It will co-produce understandings to strengthen urban/transport planning through inclusive EM transition processes. Along with policymakers and mobility service providers, the project will compare transition processes in Oslo, Utrecht, Bristol and Poznań.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/item/, retrieved 16 September 2024)</p>			

ASAP

Project Full Title	Awaken Sleeping Assets Project		
Website	http://www.smarturbanlogistics.eu/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/asap/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/awaken-sleeping-assets-project		
Call	ENUAC		
Project Coordinator	University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna / Universität für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU) – Institute of Production and Logistics Dr. Susanne Wrighton, susanne.wrighton@boku.ac.at		
Project Partners	9 partners ARMINES City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad Fludis Fraunhofer Institut für Materialfluss und Logistik Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg / Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg – Behörde für Wirtschaft und Innovation h2 projekt.beratung KG Orange SA Stockholm Vatten och Avfall (SVOA) University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna / Universität für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU) – Institute of Production and Logistics		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.04.2021	End date	31.03.2024
Key Area(s)	KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Urban Logistics Testbeds on Underused Resources, SULP Information and Interaction platform, Financial sustainability and network integration sustainable urban logistics, sleeping assets, evaluation and standardization, transferability		
Case Studies	Test beds in Düsseldorf, Paris, Versailles, Hamburg, Stockholm, Vienna		
The Awaken Sleeping Assets Project (ASAP) has 3 goals: (1) to activate underused or inactive infrastructure or resources for sustainable urban logistics, (2) to provide testbeds for innovative urban logistics systems			

and (3) to combine these activities to build a new Sustainable Urban Logistics Planning Platform (SULP-Platform).

Cities, industry and research partners from Austria, France, Germany, and Sweden are gathering and processing information to build up an open-access knowledge base from European cities and regions. Based on in-depth evaluation of 14 existing and 11 further testbeds ASAP aims to activate “sleeping” assets in the partner cities and to build a network of “follower” cities.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/asap/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

EASIER

Project Full Title	Seamless sustainable everyday urban mobility		
Website	https://easier.dtu.dk/en/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/easier/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/seamless-sustainable-everyday-urban-mobility		
Call	ENUAC		
Project Coordinator	Technical University of Denmark / Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU) – Department of Technology, Management and Economics Otto Anker Nielsen, oani@dtu.dk		
Project Partners	8 partners German Aerospace Center / Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DLR) Lund University – Department of Technology and Society – Transport and Roads Norwegian University of Science and Technology / Norges teknisk-naturvitenskapelige universitet (NTNU) – Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering Norwegian University of Science and Technology / Norges teknisk-naturvitenskapelige universitet (NTNU) – Department of Architecture and Planning Technical University of Denmark / Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU) – Department of Technology, Management and Economics Technische Universität Kaiserslautern / Rheinland-Pfälzische Technische Universität Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU) – Department of Mathematics The Capital Region of Denmark The Copenhagen Metro		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.04.2021	End date	31.03.2024
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Personal Urban Mobility, User Preferences, Physical, Operational and Organisational Design sustainable mobility, integration between active and public modes of transport, shared mobility services, multimodal journeys, travellers' perspective, tariff systems, regulatory framework, network design, attractive transfers		
Case Studies			
The objective behind EASIER is to make sustainable transport of persons more attractive by combining walking, cycling, public transport, and sharing schemes into seamless transport systems.			

Based on the traveller's perspective, EASIER will focus on:

1. creating new knowledge about user behaviour and preferences in the new transport landscape
2. uncomplicated integration between active and public modes of transport
3. efficient tariff systems that promote the use of sustainable transport
4. improving the urban environment so that pedestrians and cyclists have better experiences in traffic
5. making the physical environment in railway stations and bus terminals more attractive to improve access to public transport
6. more efficient regulation of public transport that supports improved mobility.

(<https://easier.dtu.dk/en/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

EX-TRA

Project Full Title	EXperimenting with city streets to TRAnsform urban mobility		
Website	https://www.ex-tra-project.eu/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/ex-tra/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/experimenting-with-city-streets-to-transform-urban-mobility		
Call	ENUAC		
Project Coordinator	Universiteit van Amsterdam (UvA) – Faculty of Social and Behavioural Sciences Luca Bertolini, l.bertolini@uva.nl		
Project Partners	7 partners City Experience GmbH Ghent University / Universiteit Gent – Department of Geography Politecnico di Milano (POLIMI) Technical University of Munich / Technische Universität München (TUM) – Chair of Urban Structure and Transport Planning The University of Westminster LBG – Transport and Mobilities Research Group Transport for London Universiteit van Amsterdam (UvA) – Faculty of Social and Behavioural Sciences		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.04.2021	End date	31.03.2024
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility and 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Convivial public spaces, Accessibility by proximity, Alternative mobility options, City street experiments diversity and inclusivity in city streets, transport and land use conditions, walking and cycling, shared and micro-mobility, freight delivery, post-car city		
Case Studies	Living labs: Amsterdam, Bologna, Milan, Ghent, Munich, London		
<p>Across Europe, cities are trying to radically reduce their reliance on car-based mobility in order to address sustainability challenges. Two things are lacking in these efforts towards a ‘post-car’ city: a proactive vision of cities that are both sustainable and accessible without cars, and effective strategies to deal with systematic resistance to change. The aim of EX-TRA is to address these shortcomings.</p>			

Central to EX-TRA's approach are transition experiments in city streets, or intentional, temporary changes in street use, regulation and/or form, aimed at exploring systemic change towards a 'post-car' city. By way of urban living labs in Amsterdam, Bologna, Milan, Ghent, Munich and London, the project will generate insights into:

1. Possible combinations of physical design and regulation that increase the types of usage and inclusivity amongst users of city streets
2. Transport and land use conditions for the purpose of enabling and improving walking and cycling accessibility in city districts
3. Shared mobility platforms and micro-mobility and freight delivery options which complement attractive streets and accessible districts
4. Strategies of change that can accelerate the transition towards a 'post-car' city.

(<https://ex-tra-project.eu/about/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

GeoSense

Project Full Title	Geofencing strategies for implementation in urban traffic management and planning		
Website	https://closer.lindholmen.se/en/project/geosence https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/geosence/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/geofencing-strategies-for-implementation-in-urban-traffic-management-and-planning		
Call	ENUAC		
Project Coordinator	Lindholmen Science Park AB Rodrigue Al Fahel, rodrigue.alfahel@lindholmen.se		
Project Partners	<p>10 partners</p> <p>Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB – Technology Management and economics</p> <p>City of Gothenburg / Goteborgs Kommun / Göteborgs Stad</p> <p>City of Munich / Landeshauptstadt München</p> <p>City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad</p> <p>Lindholmen Science Park AB</p> <p>Norwegian Public Roads Administration / Statens vegvesen</p> <p>RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB</p> <p>SINTEF AS / SINTEF Technology and Society – SINTEF Community avd Trondheim</p> <p>Technische Universität Dresden (TU Dresden) – Chair of Traffic and Transportation Psychology</p> <p>The University of Westminster LBG – Transport and Mobilities Research Group</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.04.2021	End date	31.03.2024
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <p>4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p> <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <p>1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity</p> <p>3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p>		
Keywords	Geofencing, Urban traffic management and planning, Implementation strategies user acceptances, impact assessment, use cases, legal and governance framework, speed limits, shared micro-mobility		
Case Studies	Pilots: Gothenburg, Stockholm, Munich		
<p>GeoSense elaborates on geofencing solutions aiming at improving traffic flow, safety and air quality.</p> <p>The overall objective of the project is to design, trial and evaluate geofencing concepts and solutions for specific cases in cities, within the project and from other previous/ongoing geofencing initiatives, and to propose new ways of successfully deploying geofencing technologies. Tools for implementation, as well as approaches to scale-up and spread the innovation further in Europe will be proposed including e.g. ways</p>			

of integrating geofencing functionalities in the decision making, built environment and traffic management in cities.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/geosence/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

DyMoN

Project Full Title	Dynamic Mobility Nudge: Shaping sustainable urban mobility behaviour with real-time, user-generated and public open data		
Website	https://dymon.eu/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/dymon/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/dynamic-mobility-nudge-shaping-sustainable-urban-mobility-behaviour-with-real-time-user-generated-and-public-open-data https://www.salzburgresearch.at/publikation/handbook-digital-nudging-for-sustainable-mobility/		
Call	ENUAC		
Project Coordinator	Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH Dr. Claudia Luger-Bazinger, claudia.luger-bazinger@salzburgresearch.at		
Project Partners	7 partners City of Salzburg / Stadt Salzburg Ecollective Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH Sustainability InnoCenter Trafficon GmbH University of Salzburg / Paris-Lodron-Universität Salzburg (PLUS) – Fachbereich Geoinformatik Z_GIS Uppsala University – Division of Civil Engineering and Built Environment		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.05.2021	End date	30.04.2024
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Sustainable urban mobility, Data-based strategies for urban mobility, Nudging methods, Change of mobility behaviour digital nudging methods, co-creation, toolbox, soft measures, data dashboard		
Case Studies	Salzburg, Uppsala		
DyMoN (Dynamic Mobility Nudge) will provide a solid conceptual and empirical understanding of the potential of combining real-time, user generated and publicly available environmental and transport data with nudging methods for promoting behavior change in sustainable urban mobility.			

The project will investigate and test how to design effective, data-driven, digital nudging methods in cities for encouraging use of sustainable mobility modes. The DyMoN framework will be co-created with city stakeholders, citizens and researchers and demonstrated in two cities (Salzburg and Uppsala) to advance scientific knowledge and to provide guidance for other cities through a toolbox, virtual workshops and policy briefings.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/dymon/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

MyFairShare

Project Full Title	Individual Mobility Budgets as a Foundation for Social and Ethical Carbon Reduction		
Website	https://www.myfairshare.eu/ https://mytrips.ait.ac.at/myfairshare/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/myfairshare/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/individual-mobility-budgets-as-a-foundation-for-social-and-ethical-carbon-reduction		
Call	ENUAC		
Project Coordinator	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH Alexandra Millonig, alexandra.millonig@ait.ac.at		
Project Partners	8 partners AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH German Aerospace Center / Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DLR) Institute of Transport Economics / Transportøkonomisk Institutt (TOI) Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies (LBTU) – Faculty of Information Technologies London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE) – LSE Cities Lorenz Consult University of Latvia (LU) – Faculty of Business, Management and Economics University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna / Universität für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU) – Institute of Social Ecology		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.05.2021	End date	30.04.2024
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 3. Provide sustainable solutions for longer trips 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Mobility budget, Transport equity, Behaviour change policies social and ethical carbon reduction, transport emissions, sustainable mobility, sufficiency, activity space, Travel Time Budget		
Case Studies	Living labs: Vienna, Berlin, Jelgava, London, Sarpsborg		
MyFairShare is a pan-European research project that builds on the sufficiency principles to change mobility habits through individual mobility budgets.			

MyFairShare combines and expands relevant knowledge, data and models to construct a scheme for fair distribution of individual mobility budgets and identifies effective policy strategies. The concept is tested in six different Living Labs varying by scale (community – municipal – (trans-)national) and scope (citizen level– transport management level – strategic development level). The resulting policy toolkits and guidelines support the introduction of socially acceptable mobility budgets on different governance levels, improving urban accessibility and transport equity.

(<https://www.myfairshare.eu/about/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

TAPforuncertainfuture

Project Full Title	Using Triple Access Planning to Enhance Urban Accessibility and Connectivity in the Face of Deep Uncertainty		
Website	https://www.tapforuncertainty.eu/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/tap-for-uncertain-futures/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/using-triple-access-planning-to-enhance-urban-accessibility-and-connectivity-in-the-face-of-deep-uncertainty		
Call	ENUAC		
Project Coordinator	University of the West of England (UWE Bristol) – Centre for Transport and Society (CTS) Glenn Lyons, Glenn.Lyons@uwe.ac.uk		
Project Partners	16 partners Aberdeen City Council Bristol City Council Cagliari Metropolitan Council City Municipality of Nova Gorica City of Utrecht / Gemeente Utrecht KTH Royal Institute of Technology / Kungliga Tekniska högskolan – Division of Urban and Regional Studies Mott MacDonald MuConsult Nijmegen City Council Norrköping Municipality Radboud University Swedish Transport Administration / Trafikverket Transport Scotland University of Cagliari / Università degli Studi di Cagliari (UniCa) – Dipartimento di Ingegneria civile, ambientale e architettura (DICAAR) University of the West of England (UWE Bristol) – Centre for Transport and Society (CTS) Urban Planning Institute of the Republic of Slovenia / Urbanistični inštitut Republike Slovenije (UIRS)		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.05.2021	End date	30.04.2024
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		

Keywords	Urban planning, Triple Access System, Deep uncertainty, SUMPs Movement of people and goods, sustainable urban accessibility, resilience, physical mobility, spatial proximity, digital connectivity, accommodating uncertainty, serious card game, SWOT analysis
Case Studies	Case study cities: Bristol, Aberdeen, Nijmegen, Utrecht, Nova Gorica, Norrköping, Cagliari
<p>The research project Triple Access Planning for Uncertain Futures aims to improve Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP), addressing both the movement of people and goods, through two significant new considerations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Triple Access Planning (TAP) – future sustainable urban accessibility can be achieved through the transport system (physical mobility), the land-use system (spatial proximity) and the telecommunications system (digital connectivity); together constituting a Triple Access System (TAS). • Accommodating uncertainty – unpredictable change dynamics such as demographics, economic developments, locational choices, regulatory context, technological breakthroughs, travel demand, and stakeholder behaviour can be explicitly taken into account in the plan, in terms of development and implementation. <p>(https://www.tapforuncertainty.eu/, retrieved 16 September 2024)</p>	

TuneOurBlock

Project Full Title	Transforming urban quarters to human scale environments: applying superblock concepts for different urban structures		
Website	https://www.tuneourblock.eu/about/ https://www.smarterthancar.com/project/tuneourblock https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/tuneourblock/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/transforming-urban-quarters-to-human-scale-environments-applying-superblock-concepts-for-different-urban-structures		
Call	ENUAC		
Project Coordinator	Technische Universität Wien (TU Wien) – Research Unit of Transport Planning and Traffic Engineering Ulrich Leth, ulrich.leth@tuwien.ac.at Helmut Lemmerer, helmut.lemmerer@tuwien.ac.at		
Project Partners	9 partners AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH Changing Cities e.V. City of Vienna / Stadt Wien – Department for Urban Planning and Development (MA18) Deutsches Institut für Urbanistik gGmbH Institute for Advanced Sustainability Studies (IASS Potsdam) Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts Smarter Than Car studio LAUT – Landscape Architecture and Urban Transformation Technische Universität Wien (TU Wien) – Research Unit of Transport Planning and Traffic Engineering		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.05.2021	End date	30.04.2024
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Superblock, Urban transformation, Co-creative urbanism Re-allocation of street space, policy and planning strategy, implementation processes		
Case Studies	Urban Living Labs: Vienna, Berlin		
TuneOurBlock validates, internationalizes and expands the Superblock concept as policy and planning strategy for transformational urban adaptation. Municipal planners, practitioners, researchers, and NGOs,			

co-create effective and transferrable guidelines, policy options and tools for implementing Superblocks in varied urban contexts.

TuneOurBlock examines strategies to respectfully involve diverse stakeholders and explores practical steps for implementation processes. These strategies are tested in Urban Living Labs (Vienna & Berlin), validated by partners in Slovenia and Romania and with Europe-wide peer-groups of municipal and civic stakeholders.

TuneOurBlock provides recommendations for empowering Superblock implementations in European cities and general knowledge for how to effectively approach transformational urban interventions. A strong dissemination package transfers the results to policymakers, municipal administrations, academia, the private sector and civil society.

(<https://www.smarterthancar.com/project/tuneourblock>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

SMARTHubs

Project Full Title	Smart Mobility Hubs as Game Changers in Transport
Website	https://www.smartmobilityhubs.eu/ https://data.smartmobilityhubs.eu/wiki/Main_Page https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/smarthubs/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/smart-mobility-hubs-as-game-changers-in-transport
Call	ENUAC
Project Coordinator	University of Twente / Universiteit Twente (UT) – Transport Engineering and Management (TEM) research group Prof. dr. Karst T Geurs, k.t.geurs@utwente.nl
Project Partners	34 partners Anderlecht Municipality City of Munich / Landeshauptstadt München CROW Federal Government of Lower Austria HTM Personenvervoer Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality Lojika Field Labs (Lojika Bilgi Teknolojileri Ve Servisleri Ticaret AS) Metropolitan Region Rotterdam – The Hague / Metropoolregio Rotterdam Den Haag MO.Point Mobilitätsservices GmbH Mobility Lab Graz Mpact vzw / Mpact asbl Municipality of Rotterdam / Gemeente Rotterdam Municipality of The Hague / Gemeente Den Haag MVV Munich Public Transport Association / Münchner Verkehrs- und Tarifverbund GmbH NS Stations Rotterdamse Elektrische Tram NV (RET) Service public régional de Bruxelles – Brussels Mobility / Bruxelles Mobilité (Administration de l'Équipement et des Déplacements) Stadt-Umland-Management Wien-Niederösterreich Technical University of Munich / Technische Universität München (TUM) – Chair of Urban Structure and Transport Planning Technische Universität Wien (TU Wien) – Artifact-Based Computing and User Research Unit (ACUR) Technische Universität Wien (TU Wien) – Aspern Mobil Lab Technische Universität Wien (TU Wien) – Research Unit Multidisciplinary Design and User Research Technische Universität Wien (TU Wien) – Research Unit of Transportation System Planning University of Bologna / Università di Bologna – Department of Economics University of Münster (WWU) – Institute for Political Science University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna / Universität für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU) – Institute for Transport Studies University of Twente / Universiteit Twente (UT) – Transport Engineering and Management (TEM) research group UPS Germany

	Verkehrsverbund Ost-Region (VOR) GmbH / ITS Vienna Region Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Brussels Centre for Urban Studies Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Business technology and Operations Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electromobility research centre (MOBI) Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Mobilise Wien 3420 Aspern Development AG		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	03.05.2021	End date	02.05.2024
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options</p> <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity</p> <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 1. Support striving neighbourhood economies</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>		
Keywords	<p>Mobility hubs, Shared mobility, User-centric and co-design tools</p> <p>inclusive sustainable urban mobility and accessibility, participatory and impact assessment tools, open data platform, policy development and integration, platform for associate partners, accessibility network analysis and resilience tool, multi-actor multi-criteria analysis method, gamification, vulnerable to exclusion population segments</p>		
Case Studies	Living labs: Brussels, Rotterdam-the Hague metropolitan region, Munich, Vienna, Istanbul		
<p>What? The SmartHubs project examines mobility hubs, dedicated on-street locations where citizens can choose from different shared and sustainable mobility options.</p> <p>Where? SmartHubs will examine, develop and apply research methods and tools in Living Labs in Brussels, Istanbul, Munich, Rotterdam-The Hague metropolitan region, and Vienna .</p> <p>How? The main objective is to assess if a co-designed, user-centric development can enable mobility hubs to act as a game changer towards inclusive sustainable urban mobility and accessibility.</p> <p>Why?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open data platform and open tools available to organizations and institutions having different needs and functioning at various spatial, cultural, policy, and technological frameworks. • Policy making for mobility hubs through the international cooperation of its associate partners that have experience and are willing to exchange knowledge on policy development. • New policies on mobility hubs and improve existing ones, allowing government authorities and public transport operators to adopt new guidelines tailored to their needs. • Platform for associate partners from all over Europe to join forces which will further contribute to efforts aiming to explore the potential of SmartHubs. <p>(https://www.smartmobilityhubs.eu/info, retrieved 16 September 2024)</p>			

JUSTICE

Project Full Title	Joining Urban morphology, Spatio-Temporal and socio-cognitive accessibility for an Inclusive City Environment		
Website	https://justice-project.eu/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/justice/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/joining-urban-morphology-spatio-temporal-and-socio-cognitive-accessibility-for-an-inclusive-city-environment		
Call	ENUAC		
Project Coordinator	University of Strasbourg / Université de Strasbourg - Laboratoire Image, Ville, Environnement (LIVE) Alexis Conesa, conesa@unistra.fr		
Project Partners	<p>8 partners</p> <p>Collectif Accessibilité Wallonie Bruxelles Konya Metropolitan Municipality Necmettin Erbakan Üniversitesi – Ahmet Keleşoğlu Eğitim Fakültesi STIB-MIB Société des Transports Intercommunaux de Bruxelles / Maatschappij voor het Intercommunale Vervoer te Brussel Université Catholique de Louvain – Centre de recherches et d'études pour l'action territoriale (CREAT) Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB) – Institut de Gestion de l'Environnement et d'Aménagement du Territoire (IGEAT) University of Strasbourg / Université de Strasbourg - Laboratoire Image, Ville, Environnement (LIVE) University of Strasbourg / Université de Strasbourg – Unité de Recherche Sport et Sciences Sociales</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.06.2021	End date	31.05.2024
Key Area(s)	<p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society</p>		
Keywords	Inclusive city, Spatial justice, Participative approach accessibility inequalities, quantitative accessibility modeling and qualitative approaches, specific audiences		
Case Studies	Case studies: Konya, Brussels, Strasbourg		
<p>The JUSTICE project aims to revisit issues of intra-urban accessibility by linking two research fields that have mostly ignored each other. Social and spatial sciences (including sociology, anthropology, land use planning, and urban studies) have first widely discussed that concrete mobilities (and thus access to the city) can be limited by social, physical, and socio-cognitive inequalities in a context where public spaces, public transportation systems, and buildings are not designed to be fully inclusive. On the other hand, quantitative research in geography has measured and modeled models of accessibility that ignore the aforementioned inequalities, implicitly assuming that accessibility is inclusive.</p>			

The JUSTICE project will develop on the very idea that accessibility is not the same for everyone, by intersecting and combining qualitative and quantitative approaches. Modelling exercises will thus be multiplied and refined for four specific groups of people who are subject to mobility and urban planning constraints: physically impaired people, blind and visually impaired people, the elderly and socially underprivileged ones. The way in which social inequalities and disabilities affect accessibility will be addressed by involving the specific audiences at the heart of the research design, as well as policy makers.

The spatio-temporal modelling methods used to measure the accessibility of public transport are in the framework of the project complemented by quantitative and qualitative approaches to highlight physical, financial and socio-cognitive barriers. The aim is to achieve both the construction of a methodological framework that is co-constructed with stakeholders, and recommendations including policy guidelines to help cities to include spatial justice in their inclusiveness strategies.

(<https://justice-project.eu/project/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

SortedMobility

Project Full Title	Self-Organized Rail Traffic for the Evolution of Decentralized MOBILITY		
Website	https://www.sortedmobility.eu/about https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/sortedmobility/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/self-organized-rail-traffic-for-the-evolution-of-decentralized-mobility		
Call	ENUAC		
Project Coordinator	Université Gustave Eiffel – Laboratoire ESTAS Évaluation des Systèmes de Transport Automatisés et de leur Sécurité Paola Pellegrini, paola.pellegrini@unif-eiffel.fr		
Project Partners	7 partners BaneDanmark Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – Digital Rail Traffic Lab (DRT Lab) Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie della Cognizione Rete Ferroviaria Italiana Société nationale SNCF Technical University of Denmark / Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU) – Department of Technology, Management and Economics Université Gustave Eiffel – Laboratoire ESTAS Évaluation des Systèmes de Transport Automatisés et de leur Sécurité		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.06.2021	End date	31.05.2024
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 3. Provide sustainable solutions for longer trips 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies 4. Support sustainable lifestyles		
Keywords	Sustainable urban mobility growth, Self-organizing system, Railway traffic management public transport, intelligent trains, multi-modal integration, market competitiveness, simulation assessment, passenger demand prediction, rail traffic modelling, train platooning, KPIs		
Case Studies	Case studies: Denmark, Italy, France		
SORTEDMOBILITY proposes a holistic approach for self-organizing management of public transport in urban and interurban areas, focusing on rail as mobility backbone. Simulations will assess the self-organization approach in case studies in Denmark, Italy and France. They will integrate advanced methods for passenger demand prediction and rail traffic modelling. In a close			

collaboration between academic and key rail stakeholders, SORTEDMOBILITY will showcase the future of railways while producing guidelines and recommendations to support future public transport systems.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/sortedmobility/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

WALKUrban

Project Full Title	Walkable Urban Neighbourhoods – Freeing up Potential for Sustainable and Active Travel by Improving Walking and its Connections with Public Transport		
Website	https://walkurban.eu/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/walkurban/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/walkable-urban-neighbourhoods-2013-freeing-up-potential-for-sustainable-and-active-travel-by-improving-walking-and-its-connections-with-public-transport		
Call	ENUAC		
Project Coordinator	ILS Research gGmbH Dr. Noriko Otsuka, noriko.otsuka@ils-forschung.de		
Project Partners	4 partners City of Genoa / Comune di Genova ILS Research gGmbH University College London (UCL) University of Gävle – Faculty of Health and Occupational Studies		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.06.2021	End date	31.05.2024
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Walkability, Objective, Subjective and Perceived Accessibility, Public Transport zero-emission active transport mode, walking route assessments, walk-along interviews		
Case Studies	Case studies: Genoa, Dortmund, Gothenburg		
<p>WalkUrban aims to better understand local accessibility and urban walkability in order to free up the potential for walking. By exploring the links between objective, subjective and perceived walking accessibility the project identified key enabling and hindering factors for walking in various urban neighbourhoods. This was done in close collaboration with local stakeholders and citizens in the three chosen European cities: Genoa, Dortmund and Gothenburg. The ultimate aim was to provide local solutions to support walking as a zero-emission, sustainable and active transport mode in urban areas.</p> <p>(https://walkurban.eu/?page_id=68, retrieved 16 September 2024)</p>			

COCOMO

Project Full Title	COmpeting and COmplementary MObility solutions in urban contexts		
Website	https://cocomo.sites.uu.nl/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/cocomo/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/competing-and-complementary-mobility-solutions-in-urban-contexts		
Call	ENUAC		
Project Coordinator	Utrecht University (UU) – Department of Human Geography and Spatial Planning Dick Ettema, d.f.ettema@uu.nl		
Project Partners	3 partners Lund University – Department of Technology and Society – Transport and Roads University of Leeds – Institute for Transport Studies Utrecht University (UU) – Department of Human Geography and Spatial Planning		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	21.06.2021	End date	20.06.2024
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	disruptive mobility, sustainability, equity, public space, multimodality shared micro-mobility, accessibility, co-creation, combination with existing transport systems		
Case Studies	Study Areas: Malmö, Greater Manchester, Utrecht		
<p>There is an emerging need for European cities to develop a strategic view on the deployment of shared micro-mobility (SMM) options. COCOMO aims to provide insights into how SMM are combined with existing travel modes and what this implies for sustainability; how SMM interact with existing forms of travel in public space and how this affects accessibility; how travel implications of, and access to SMM differ between geographical contexts and socio-economic groups, and what this implies for equity and inclusion. COCOMO engages in co-creation with users and stakeholders to develop design and planning guidelines for sustainable and inclusive implementation of SMM.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/cocomo/, retrieved 16 September 2024)</p>			

ACUTE

Project Full Title	Accessibility and Connectivity knowledge hub for Urban Transformation in Europe		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/acute-accessibility-and-connectivity-knowledge-hub-for-urban-transformation-in-europe/		
Call	Knowledge Hub (ENUAC)		
Project Coordinator	University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna / Universität für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU) – Institute of Production and Logistics Dr. Susanne Wrighton, susanne.wrighton@boku.ac.at		
Project Partners	<p>13 partners</p> <p>CEREMA Centre d'études et d'expertise sur les risques, l'environnement, la mobilité et l'aménagement / Centre for Studies on Risks, the Environment, Mobility and Urban Planning</p> <p>Grazer Energieagentur</p> <p>h2 projekt.beratung KG</p> <p>K2 The Swedish knowledge centre for public transport</p> <p>Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies (LBTU) – Faculty of Information Technologies</p> <p>Malmö University / Malmö Universitet</p> <p>Power Circle AB</p> <p>RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB</p> <p>The University of Westminster LBG – Transport and Mobilities Research Group</p> <p>Université Gustave Eiffel – LVMT Laboratoire Ville Mobilité Transport</p> <p>University of Innsbruck</p> <p>University of Latvia (LU) – Faculty of Business, Management and Economics</p> <p>University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna / Universität für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU) – Institute of Production and Logistics</p>		
Duration (months)	24		
Start date	01.11.2022	End date	31.10.2024
Key Area(s)	<p>Focus: Accessibility and Connectivity knowledge hub</p> <p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <p>KA3 Smart urban logistics, production and service sites</p> <p>KA4 Urban governance for mobility transition</p>		
Keywords	Knowledge Hub, sustainable urban passenger mobility, freight transport, connectivity, cross-project cooperation, stakeholder exchange		
Case Studies			
<p>ACUTE will address the challenges of sustainable urban passenger mobility, freight transport and connectivity as an integral and essential part of sustainable urban development. The project wants to enable cross-project cooperation, extract and consolidate knowledge of all existing ENU-UAC projects, initiate efforts to support practitioners and bring together experts from different sectors.</p> <p>The Knowledge Hub ACUTE will support the program EN-UAC and its projects by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Helping to overcome the fragmentation of findings and experiences • Create a space for stakeholder exchange 			

- Enable cross-project cooperation; consolidate and synthesise knowledge
- Support practitioners, policy-makers and funders with the mainstreaming of research results; and
- Provide strategic support for the Program DUT.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/acute-accessibility-and-connectivity-knowledge-hub-for-urban-transformation-in-europe/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

E-Laas

Project Full Title	Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service		
Website	https://www.wt.pw.edu.pl/Badania-i-nauka/Konferencje/Rok-2024/Warsztaty-E-Laas-E-Laas-Workshops/E-Laas-Workshops#5 https://research.chalmers.se/en/project/11138 https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/e-laas/		
Call	Sino-European call (ENUAC)		
Project Coordinator	Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Techniska Hogskola AB - Electrical Engineering Professor Balazs Kulcsar, kulcsar@chalmers.se Shanghai University Professor ZHEN Lu, lzhen@shu.edu.cn		
Project Partners	10 partners Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Techniska Hogskola AB – Electrical Engineering Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Techniska Hogskola AB – Technology Management and economics City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad Metropolis GZM / Upper Silesian-Zaglebie Metropolis / Górnośląsko-Zagłębiowska Metropolia ParkUnload Shanghai University Shanghai Urban-Rural Construction and Transportation Department Tsinghua University Volvo Group Trucks Technology and Operations Warsaw University of Technology (WUT) – Faculty of Transport		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2023	End date	2026
Key Area(s)	KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery		
Keywords	Logistics as a Service (LaaS), multimodal urban logistics systems, energy-based and quantitative approach, modal shift, micro platforms, interlaced energy foot printing, social responsibility, power grid infrastructure, consolidation centres, energy-efficient distributions systems		
Case Studies			
<p>The E-LaaS project aims to create an innovative platform that minimises energy consumption in the distribution process from consolidation centres to customer doors. This platform facilitates energy savings at every distribution stage.</p> <p>What we are going to do:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop energy-efficient urban logistics solutions with quantitative energy consumption characteristics, allowing precise resource management and minimisation of losses. 			

- Develop intelligent, multimodal, and energy-efficient micro-delivery systems, utilising various modes of transport and optimised delivery routes, contributing to reduced energy consumption.
- Analyse disturbances in urban logistics tasks and propose reconfigurable solutions to regain energy efficiency. This key project element allows adaptation to changing conditions and constraints in urban freight transport.
- Develop concepts for co-organising distribution services and unloading zones through charging station infrastructure and the energy network, considering intelligent charging rules and the impact of energy prices on delivery costs. This is an innovative approach to energy management in urban logistics.
- Quantify urban freight transport demand and analyse customer behaviour. These analyses enable more precise delivery planning and energy consumption minimisation.
- Analyse digital and physical components along with the holistic concept of logistics as a service. This approach considers the entire logistics process, allowing comprehensive energy management.
- Develop concepts for scalable, multimodal, and energy-efficient distribution systems, enabling efficient adaptation of urban logistics to various conditions, areas, and requirements.
- Develop new ways to increase social responsibility through E-Laas. This project aims not only to save energy but also to create more sustainable and environmentally friendly logistics solutions.

(<https://www.wt.pw.edu.pl/Badania-i-nauka/Konferencje/Rok-2024/Warsztaty-E-Laas-E-Laas-Workshops/E-Laas-Workshops#5>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

e-MATS

Project Full Title	Electric Multimodal Transport Systems for Enhancing Urban Accessibility and Connectivity		
Website	https://research.chalmers.se/en/project/11003 https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/e-mats/		
Call	Sino-European call (ENUAC)		
Project Coordinator	Politehnica University Timișoara – Calculatoare și Tehnologia Informației (CTI) (http://www.research.upt.ro/page11.html#header02-8w4) Professor Radu-Emil Precup, radu.precup@upt.ro Zhejiang University Professor JIN Sheng, jinsheng@zju.edu.cn		
Project Partners	10 partners Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB – Architecture and Civil Engineering Chongqing University Enjoyor Ltd Co. FellowBot AB Hangzhou Comprehensive Transportation Center Politehnica University Timișoara – Calculatoare și Tehnologia Informației (CTI) Swedish National Road and Transport Research Institute / Statens väg- och transportforskningsinstitut (VTI) The Hong Kong Polytechnic University – Shenzhen Research Institute WSP Sverige AB Zhejiang University (ZJU)		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2023	End date	2025
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Multimodal transport systems, electric public transit, accessibility, connectivity, shared micro-mobility, resilience, co-creation, users’ needs and behavioural responses, infrastructure planning, network design, vehicles/platoon control		
Case Studies	Real-life applications		
The e-MATS project aims to advance the next-generation multimodal transport systems via electrification, connectivity and sharing. The project will facilitate the development of multimodal transport systems that			

connect electric public transit and shared micro-mobility for sustainable, more efficient, and equitable mobility services that enhance urban accessibility and resilience.

The project will tackle critical and unsettled aspects in the current practice and engage key stakeholders at multiple levels in co-creation with considerations of diverse users' needs and behavioral responses. Areas of innovation include infrastructure planning at the strategical level, system optimisation, network design and management at the tactical level, and vehicle / platoon control and battery management at the operational level, with considerations of diverse users' needs and behavioral responses.

Solutions will be demonstrated in real-life applications through public authorities and industry partners. These contribute to promoting urban accessibility and connectivity, climate action in the transport sector, and the citizens' subjective well-being in the long term.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/e-mats/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

IMTECC

Project Full Title	Integrated systems and analysis of urban Mobility for climate-neutral and susTainable Cities in Europe and China		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/imtecc/		
Call	Sino-European call (ENUAC)		
Project Coordinator	Københavns Universitet / University of Copenhagen - Physics of Ice, Climate and Earth Professor Jens Hesselbjerg Christensen, hesselbjerg@nbi.ku.dk Zhejiang University Professor YU Shaocai, shaocaiyu@zju.edu.cn		
Project Partners	6 partners Aarhus University / Aarhus Universitet Copenhagen Municipality / Københavns Kommune Hebei Agricultural University Københavns Universitet / University of Copenhagen – Physics of Ice, Climate and Earth University Paris Est Creteil and University Paris Cité (CNRS) – Laboratoire Interuniversitaire des Systèmes Atmosphériques (LISA) Zhejiang University (ZJU)		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2023	End date	2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition		
Keywords	Multimodal traffic management, sustainable urban mobility, climate-neutral and smart cities, digital twins, big data approaches, smart traffic management technologies, interdisciplinary methods, Integrated Urban System (IUS), key performance indicators (KPIs), urban planning, energy consumption, traffic emissions, air quality, environmental justice		
Case Studies			
<p>Focusing on Chinese and European cities, this project aims to provide tools and case studies for optimizing multimodal traffic management, improving urban mobility, reducing traffic emissions, and finding new solutions towards greener mobility practices, climate-neutral and smart cities.</p> <p>Based on digital twins and big data approaches, smart traffic management technologies and integrated interdisciplinary methods, this project will build an Integrated Urban System (IUS) and key performance indicators (KPIs) for each city. Taking into account the evolving urban planning, energy consumption, transport supply and demand, and group behaviors in each city, the system will improve our</p>			

understanding of the interrelations among urban multimodal mobility, traffic emissions, air quality and climate change in cities.

The results will allow to quantify the leverage effects observed, and to highlight issues of environmental justice. The results will establish a model for building climate- and environment-smart cities, promoting Sino-European exchanges and cooperation, and jointly exploring climate neutrality pathways under future urbanization processes.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/imtecc/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

IMUMCN

Project Full Title	Improved urban mobility toward climate neutrality under new working habits and transport modes		
Website	https://imumcn.com/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/imumcn/		
Call	Sino-European call (ENUAC)		
Project Coordinator	University of Groningen / Rijksuniversiteit Groningen Professor Klaus Hubacek, k.hubacek@rug.nl Beijing Jiatong University (BJTU) Professor BAO Yue, baoyue@bjtu.edu.cn		
Project Partners	7 partners Adam Mickiewicz University Poznań / Uniwersytet im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu (UAM) – Wydział Antropologii i Kulturoznawstwa Beijing Jiaotong University (BJTU) Beijing Transport Institute (BTI) HET: coöperatie Hilversumse Energie Transitie Poznan City Hall / Miasto Poznań Tsinghua University University of Groningen / Rijksuniversiteit Groningen		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2023	End date	2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Climate-neutral multi-mode urban transport system, uncertainty, innovative solutions, transport modelling, behavioural change, integrated Mobility as a Service (MaaS), carbon permit trading, accessible climate-neutral cities, work time and location choices, efficiency and equity of new transport services, emissions accounting framework for resident transport		
Case Studies	Real-life experiments, urban transport modelling		
<p>Most modern cities struggle with severe traffic congestion and emissions. Thus, achieving an efficient and climate-neutral urban transport system is one of the key urban challenges. The widespread availability of technology (e.g., the internet and smart phones) and changes in societal trends, particularly work habits (e.g., telework and overtime work) adds another layer of complexity, increase uncertainty and provide new challenges to urban mobility. Understanding the impacts of these new developments on citizens' location</p>			

choices and associated travel patterns and providing new innovative solutions to the urban traffic system is critical to achieve an efficient, low-emission and sustainable urban environment.

With real-life experiments and advanced urban transport modelling approaches, we will investigate short-term behavioral impacts and long-term implications of these challenges on urban mobility and city structure. We will further explore the potential for integrated Mobility as a Service (MaaS) solutions and market-based personal carbon permit trading in providing an efficient, equitable and zero-emission urban traffic system. This project thus aims to contribute to achieving accessible, climate-neutral and sustainable cities in China and the EU and provide citizens with sustainable and efficient solutions integrating multiple types of transport modes.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/imumcn/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

NEW NORMAL

Project Full Title	Sustainable mobility and logistics for post-pandemic second-tier cities		
Website	https://www.newnormal-jpi-nsfc.eu/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/new-normal/		
Call	Sino-European call (ENUAC)		
Project Coordinator	Wageningen University – Department of Environmental Sciences Dr Bardia Mashhoodi, bardia.mashhoodi@wur.nl Chang’an University – College of Transportation Engineering Professor GE Ying-en, yege@chd.edu.cn		
Project Partners	8 partners Beijing Jiaotong University (BJTU) Chang’an University – College of Transportation Engineering Energiforsk Geo-Col GIS and Collaborative Planning KTH Royal Institute of Technology / Kungliga Tekniska högskolan Municipality of Nijmegen Wageningen University – Department of Environmental Sciences Xi’an Transportation Development Research Center		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2023	End date	2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Sustainable mobility and logistics, second-tier cities, inter- and trans-disciplinary approach, emission-free, energy-independent, space-efficient, car sharing, drone-based logistics, MaaS-Lane, electric vehicles, on-surface solar panels, EV charging, hydrogen generation and storage, GIS database, online platform for citizens, knowledge hubs, more connected cities		
Case Studies	MaaS-Lanes: Xi’an, Nijmegen		
<p>The project puts forward a novel inter- and trans-disciplinary approach for developing an emission-free, energy-independent and space-efficient mobility system based on car sharing and drone-based logistics to meet the influx of newcomers in second-tier cities without the construction of new heavy mobility infrastructure such as metro and tram lines, tunnels, bridges, and widening streets.</p>			

MaaS-Lane is designed based on the potentials of edge technologies tested in the pilot tests on EVs (electric vehicles), drones, on-surface solar panels, wireless EV charging, and hydrogen generation and storage, which are combined into a large-scale approach for mobility and logistics.

Including four universities with expertise in (1) geography and spatial planning, (2) traffic engineering, (3) logistics, and (4) electronic engineering, the project aims at developing and assessing the potential of its novel approach in 169 second-tier, and new first-tier, EU and Chinese cities and, together with partner municipality, to adapt detailed MaaS-Lanes for cities of Xi'an (China) and Nijmegen (the Netherlands). The project seeks broader impact by developing knowledge hubs, an interactive GIS database on the 169 cities for scientists and decision-makers, and an online platform for citizens.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/new-normal/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

SINERGI

Project Full Title	Sustainable Innovative digitalized NETwork of uRban loGistics		
Website	https://sinergi-project.com/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/sinergi/		
Call	Sino-European call (ENUAC)		
Project Coordinator	Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – Sustainable Urban Multimodal mobility (SUM) Lab Dr Shadi Sharif Azadeh, s.sharifazadeh@tudelft.nl Tongji University Professor AN Kun, kunan@tongji.edu.cn		
Project Partners	13 partners Beijing Sankuai Online Technology Ltd (Meituan) City of Amsterdam / Gemeente Amsterdam Copenhagen Business School (CBS) – Department of Economics Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – Sustainable Urban Multimodal mobility (SUM) Lab Hyke Juste Eat Takeaway.com Milkrun Singapore Management University (SMU) Statistics Denmark Stichting Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions (AMS) Tongji University Tsinghua University Vervoerregio Amsterdam – Transport Authority for the Amsterdam Region		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2023	End date	2026
Key Area(s)	KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery		
Keywords	Sustainable urban logistics, digitisation, real-time management, strategic planning, cost-efficient and rider-friendly delivery services, microdelivery, bicycle, scenario development models, smart parking, mini-hubs, urban space utilization, rider behaviour, road safety		
Case Studies	Pilots: Amsterdam, Shanghai, Singapore, and Copenhagen		
<p>The demand for fast home delivery is growing rapidly, especially in cities. However, this is leading to increasing inconvenience from vans and trucks. That can and must change – and hopes are pinned on green solutions such as micro-delivery by bicycle. But how do you design and manage such sustainable urban logistics? That is, basically, the question we are addressing in the SINERGI project.</p>			

SINERGI is a four-year project that will run from 2023 to 2026. It involves thirteen research institutions, governments, and companies collaborating on a comprehensive framework to improve sustainable city logistics. The project aims to enable real-time management and strategic planning of efficient and user-friendly delivery services. By combining real-time and historical data with scenario development models, SINERGI addresses several scientific challenges. These challenges include optimizing the allocation of smart parking and mini-hubs to maximize urban space utilization, analyzing rider behavior to enhance performance, and designing tailored services that consider urban constraints and incorporate real-time data on factors such as space availability, rider behavior, fleet planning, matching, and dispatching.

(<https://sinergi-project.com/about/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

SOUL

Project Full Title	Sustainable Operations in Urban Logistics		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/soul/		
Call	Sino-European call (ENUAC)		
Project Coordinator	Tilburg University – Department of Management Professor Prof Jan Fransoo, jan.fransoo@tilburguniversity.edu Tsinghua University Professor ZHAO Lei, lzhao@tsinghua.edu.cn		
Project Partners	7 partners Bordeaux Metropole China Federation of Logistics and Purchasing (CFLP) Kedge Business School Sichuan University Tianjin University Tilburg University – Department of Management Tsinghua University		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2023	End date	2026
Key Area(s)	KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics		
Keywords	Innovations in sustainable urban logistics, time-sensitive and fragmented delivery, multi-tier urban delivery networks, micro-storage, urban space, customer expectations, couriers' welfare, sustainability		
Case Studies			
<p>Urbanization and rapid growth in e-commerce and on-demand services demand time-sensitive and fragmented delivery, motivating innovations in sustainable urban logistics. Multi-tier urban delivery networks involve micro-storage and sorting of delivery goods, implying increased use of urban space.</p> <p>We develop innovative strategies leveraging advanced analytics to cope with the inherent dynamics of urban logistics systems and limited urban space while meeting increasing customer expectations. We explicitly consider couriers' welfare, recognizing their stress and cognitive strength.</p> <p>Our approach recognizes the triple bottom line of sustainability: ecological, economic, and social sustainability.</p> <p>(https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/soul/, retrieved 16 September 2024)</p>			

TOD2

Project Full Title	Transit-Oriented Development 2 – Public spaces, mobility hubs and climate neutrality toolbox		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/tod2/		
Call	Sino-European call (ENUAC)		
Project Coordinator	KTH Royal Institute of Technology / Kungliga Tekniska högskolan Dr Todor Stojanovski, todor@kth.se Nanjing University Professor DING Wowo, dww@nju.edu.cn		
Project Partners	8 partners Foreningen Bloxhub KTH Royal Institute of Technology / Kungliga Tekniska högskolan Municipality of Frederiksberg Nanjing University NIRAS A/S Stockholm University Tongji University URBANDIGITAL APS		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2023	End date	2026
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space 4. Support sustainable lifestyles <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 		
Keywords	Transit-Oriented Development, public space, mobility hubs, climate-neutrality, toolboxes, urban design policy, redesign car-oriented neighbourhoods, modal shift, shared mobility		
Case Studies	Investigation of station areas in Sweden, Denmark, China		
<p>Automobile travel consumes scarce resources of fossil oil, accelerates climate change globally and creates air pollution locally. Transit-Oriented Development is an urban design policy that seeks to redesign car-oriented neighbourhoods, integrate transit infrastructure in neighborhoods and inspire modal shift from private car to walking and public transport.</p> <p>This project will investigate station areas in Sweden, Denmark and China to develop a TOD2 framework with perspectives on public spaces, shared mobility and innovative mobility hubs, and carbon-neutrality toolboxes. It aims to contribute in achieving decarbonisation and decreased oil dependence in European and Chinese cities.</p>			

<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/tod2/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

TAAM

Project Full Title	Toolbox for Agile urban Accessibility Management		
Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/taam/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/3rd-en-auc-joint-call-innovations-for-managing-sustainable-urban-accessibility-enuac/toolbox-for-agile-urban-accessibility-management		
Call	Innovations for Managing Sustainable Urban Accessibility (ENUAC)		
Project Coordinator	PRISMA solutions EDV-Dienstleistungen GmbH Elisabeth Jarusel, elisabeth.jarusel@prisma-solutions.com		
Project Partners	4 partners Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies (LBTU) – Faculty of Information Technologies PRISMA solutions EDV-Dienstleistungen GmbH Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH WeAreDots SIA		
Duration (months)	30		
Start date	01.01.2023	End date	30.06.2025
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Smart cities, traffic management strategies and regulations, changing conditions, digital lifecycle, web-based tools, agile sustainable mobility strategies		
Case Studies	4 pilot cities in Austria and Latvia		
<p>Smart cities are more and more implementing traffic management strategies and regulations to reach their long-term sustainable mobility goals. While there are already different strategies and regulations in place, a more agile way of adapting these strategies and regulations to dynamically changing conditions is missing. This missing digital lifecycle leads to media discontinuities, reduced awareness and adherence and, in the end, reduced and delayed effects on people’s actual behaviour.</p> <p>TAAM aims at a full digital lifecycle being supported by an integrated toolbox of existing web-based tools of consortium members which enables smart cities and regions to create, manage and publish their traffic management strategies or regulations for more sustainable mobility as well as analysing their impact.</p> <p>The web-based tools will be integrated, adapted and evaluated for selected use cases in four pilot cities in Austria and Latvia.</p> <p>The main goals of TAAM are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enabling the planning of strategies and regulations in a fully digital and thus agile way • Publishing strategies and regulations faster and in a machine-readable way 			

- Analysing the impact of strategies and regulations in real-time
TAAM closes a missing link for smart cities on the way to manage their agile sustainable mobility strategies.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/taam/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

TollsThatWork

Project Full Title	City tolls that work		
Website	https://www.wu.ac.at/en/spatialeconomics/citytollsthatwork/overview/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/tollsthatwork/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/3rd-en-auc-joint-call-innovations-for-managing-sustainable-urban-accessibility-enuac/city-tolls-that-work		
Call	Innovations for Managing Sustainable Urban Accessibility (ENUAC)		
Project Coordinator	Vienna University of Economics and Business / Wirtschaftsuniversität Wien (WU) – Multilevel Governance & Development Stefanie Peer, speer@wu.ac.at		
Project Partners	4 partners Baltic International Centre for Economic Policy Studies (BICEPS) Dolphin Technologies GmbH Swedish National Road and Transport Research Institute / Statens väg- och transportforskningsinstitut (VTI) Vienna University of Economics and Business / Wirtschaftsuniversität Wien (WU) – Multilevel Governance & Development		
Duration (months)	30		
Start date	01.01.2023	End date	30.06.2025
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	City tolls, urban accessibility, public acceptability, distributional effects, pricing mechanism, congestion charging system, professional traffic, mobility behaviour, app		
Case Studies	Real-world data from Sweden, Surveys in Vienna and Riga, Field experiment		
<p>City tolls are widely recognised as an effective policy measure to fight congestion and decrease the negative environmental impacts of car traffic in cities. However, they suffer from low public acceptability, with one reason being expected adverse distributional impacts. Such public resistance makes the idea of city tolls de facto non-operational, with noticeable exceptions being Singapore, London, Stockholm and Gothenburg. This motivates our search for road tolling schemes that can really work in cities, i.e., that make cities more accessible and sustainable, while also being perceived as fair and having broad public support.</p> <p>To succeed, one first needs to gain a solid understanding of what population groups actually benefit and lose under existing city tolls and why. We use unique real-world congestion pricing and registry data of the full Swedish population to acquire new insights on long-term distributional effects of city tolls. These will inform our project further, as we propose and gauge public support for an innovative road-pricing scheme with a cash-back component, in which collected tolls are returned directly back to drivers in the form of</p>			

public transport tokens. We will then design a field experiment that measures behavioral reactions to such novel pricing instruments.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/tollsthatwork/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

StreetForum

Project Full Title	Transforming streets into accessible urban oases through consensus building with digital and analogue tools		
Website	https://streetforum.eu/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/streetforum/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/3rd-en-auc-joint-call-innovations-for-managing-sustainable-urban-accessibility-enuac/transforming-streets-into-accessible-urban-oases-through-consensus-building-with-digital-and-analogue-tools		
Call	Innovations for Managing Sustainable Urban Accessibility (ENUAC)		
Project Coordinator	Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Mobilise Imre Keseru, imre.keseru@vub.be streetforum@vub.be		
Project Partners	11 partners		
Duration (months)	30		
Start date	01.03.2023	End date	31.08.2025
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		
Keywords	Accessibility in urban neighbourhoods, consensus building, street transformation projects, digital and analogue tools, guidelines, consensus making design game, Street Value Model, Multi-actor multi-criteria analysis (MAMCA), Stakeholder-based Impact Scoring (SIS)		
Case Studies	Living labs: Brussels, Vienna, Stockholm, Istanbul		
<p>What is the best for our communities? How can we support change? How do we negotiate with residents, road users and the authorities to find a consensus to reduce traffic and improve liveability in our neighbourhood? The StreetForum Toolkit will help to answer these questions by developing a set of analogue and digital tools available free-of-charge to local communities to support their efforts of neighbourhood street transformation, reduce car traffic and improve liveability. The tools will be demonstrated in Istanbul, Brussels, Vienna and Stockholm working with local communities to transform car-dominated streets into streets for people.</p> <p>(https://streetforum.eu/, retrieved 16 September 2024)</p>			

ACCTRA

Project Full Title	Evidence and acceptance - from experiments to transformation		
Website	https://acctra.eu/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/acctra/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/3rd-en-auc-joint-call-innovations-for-managing-sustainable-urban-accessibility-enuac/evidence-and-acceptance-from-experiments-to-transformation		
Call	Innovations for Managing Sustainable Urban Accessibility (ENUAC)		
Project Coordinator	Technische Universität Wien (TU Wien) – Research Unit of Transportation System Planning Martin kp Berger, martin.kp.berger@tuwien.ac.at Gunnar Grandel, gunnar.grandel@tuwien.ac.at		
Project Partners	8 partners Bogazici University – Department of Civil Engineering Cultureghem vzw Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality space and place – kulturelle raumgestaltung Spacescape AB Technische Universität Wien (TU Wien) – Artifact-Based Computing and User Research Unit (ACUR) Technische Universität Wien (TU Wien) – Institute of Visual Computing & Human Centred Technology Tisserand Alain, Claude Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Brussels Centre for Urban Studies Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Business technology and Operations Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Mobilise		
Duration (months)	30		
Start date	01.05.2023	End date	31.10.2025
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	safe and attractive active mobility, public transport, street design, multimodality, street transformations, acceptance, guidelines, planning process, accessible and sustainable transport		
Case Studies	Experiments: Istanbul, Klagenfurt		
The ACCTRA project aims to make the city more sustainable, liveable and accessible for everyone through adjustments to the transport system. To do so, we will create a better understanding of how street			

experiments can be used to empower alternatives to car traffic such as walking, biking, public transports or scooters.

The project will be conducted with local administrations in Istanbul, Turkey, and Klagenfurt, Austria. As an outcome, we will create guidelines for creating more accessible and sustainable transport using street experiments. The project results will further be embedded in municipal projects in street transformations.

(<https://acetra.eu/>, retrieved 16 September 2024)

ERA-NET Cofund Urban Transformation Capacities (ENUTC)

Website	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/calls/enutc/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enutc https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101003758
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City&Co

Project Full Title	Older Adults Co-Creating a Sustainable Age-friendly City		
Website	https://cityco.snsa.ro https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/cityco/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enutc/1st-enutc-call-2021/older-adults-co-creating-a-sustainable-age-friendly-city		
Call	ENUTC		
Project Coordinator	The Hague University of Applied Sciences (THUAS) / De Haagse Hogeschool (HHS) / Stichting Hoger Beroepsonderwijs Haaglanden – Centre of Expertise Governance of Urban Transitions Liesbeth de Wit, l.s.dewit@hhs.nl Joost van Hoof, j.vanhoof@hhs.nl		
Project Partners	10 partners AFEdeMy Academy on age-friendly environments in Europe B.V. GEAC Asociația Grupul de Educație și Acțiune pentru Cetățenie Jagiellonian University / Uniwersytet Jagiellonski Krakow Municipality / Gmina Miejska Krakow – Miasto Na Prawach Powiatu Municipality of The Hague / Gemeente Den Haag Municipality of Wrocław / Gmina Miejska Wrocław National University of Political Studies and Public Administration / Scoala Nationala de Studii Politice si Administrative The Hague University of Applied Sciences (THUAS) / De Haagse Hogeschool (HHS) / Stichting Hoger Beroepsonderwijs Haaglanden – Centre of Expertise Governance of Urban Transitions VNG Vereniging van Nederlandse Gemeenten / Association of Netherlands Municipalities Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences / Uniwersytet Przyrodniczy we Wrocławiu		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2022	End date	2025
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Older adults, sustainable age-friendly city, co-creative approach, measuring tools, data collection, adequate and evidence-based government, qualitative and quantitative community-based assessment, housing, social participation, healthcare facilities, financial situation, mobile website, age-friendly strategies		
Case Studies	The Hague, Wrocław, Kraków, Bucharest		

How age-friendly are our cities? The international City&Co project is developing measuring tools and a co-creative approach for this. The project awarded a substantial grant in the international ERA-NET Urban Transformation Capacities (ENUTC) competition, within the framework of the European Commission's Joint Programming Initiative Urban Europe. Together, research partners in the Netherlands Poland and Romania will investigate the age-friendliness of The Hague, Wrocław, Kraków and Bucharest.

Over 1,100 cities worldwide have joined the World Health Organization's Global Network for Age-Friendly Cities and Communities. The consortium works on a reliable measuring tool for age-friendliness, in which we fully involve older people. This will provide a basis for many other cities to build on. The project's ultimate goal is a local ecosystem of the over 65s, researchers and municipal employees who together make the city more age-friendly. This forms an internationally useful basis for collecting relevant data on age-friendliness, which will allow municipalities to govern more adequately and based on evidence.

(<https://cityco.snspa.ro/about-the-project/>, retrieved 18 September 2024)

EmbedterLabs

Project Full Title	Better Embedded Labs for More Synergistic Sustainable Urban Transformation Planning		
Website	http://www.embedterlabs.com.pl/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/embedterlabs/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enutc/1st-enutc-call-2021/better-embedded-labs-for-more-synergistic-sustainable-urban-transformation-planning		
Call	ENUTC		
Project Coordinator	Maastricht University – Maastricht Sustainability Institute (MSI) Marc Dijk, m.dijk@maastrichtuniversity.nl		
Project Partners	<p>13 partners</p> <p>City of Gdansk / Gdańsk / Gmina Miasta Gdanska City of Maastricht / Gemeente Maastricht City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad Gdansk Community Foundation / Wspólnota Gdańska Gdansk University of Technology / Politechnika Gdańska – Faculty of Architecture KTH Royal Institute of Technology / Kungliga Tekniska högskolan – Division of Urban and Regional Studies Lund University – Department of Architecture and Built Environment Maastricht Bereikbaar Maastricht University – Department of Science, Technology and Society Studies (MUSTS) Maastricht University – Maastricht Sustainability Institute (MSI) Olivia Business Centre Sweco Architects / Grontmij Uppsala University</p>		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2022	End date	2025
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <p>1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options</p> <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <p>1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity</p> <p>2. Focus on people-centred public space</p> <p>4. Support sustainable lifestyles</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p> <p>3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>		
Keywords	Embedded Labs, synergistic urban planning, sustainable and resilient urban areas, Urban Living Labs (ULLs), mobility infrastructure, public space, transformative capacity for urban policy makers, participatory approach		
Case Studies	Experiments: Gdansk, Stockholm, Maastricht		

The EmbedterLabs project will develop capacity for more synergistic urban planning for transformations towards sustainable and resilient urban areas. It deals with a key deficiency of current urban planning: the rather context-specific lessons of Urban Living Labs (ULLs) are poorly translated into citywide, integrated, transformative policy implications, leaving them having limited impact. To do so, it answers two questions: 1) how to orient labs and experiments to inform broader learning processes, and 2) how to align laboratory insights with established policy mixes to enable transformation? To achieve this, a novel approach will be developed, tested and refined through retrospective analysis of experiments in Gdansk, Stockholm and Maastricht followed by action research through ULL experiments in each city. The experiments will focus on mobility infrastructure and public space, one key dimension of urban sustainability. These activities will improve the learning processes of experiments and accordingly support the creation of transformative capacity for urban policy makers.

The consortium is well-positioned by including universities with complementary knowledge, cities committed to experiment and learn to transform, companies developing innovations, and organizations representing stakeholder interests. All research and city partners have experience with multi-actor Living Lab and participatory approaches, and concrete experiments are already identified.

(<https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/embedterlabs/>, retrieved 18 September 2024)

Carin-PT

Project Full Title	Capacities for Resilient and Inclusive Urban Public Transport Infrastructure and Built Environment		
Website	https://carinpt.eu/ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/carin-pt/ https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enutc/1st-enutc-call-2021/capacities-for-resilient-and-inclusive-urban-public-transport-infrastructure-and-built-environment		
Call	ENUTC		
Project Coordinator	Tallinn University / Tallinna Ülikooli (TLU) – School of Humanities Prof. Tauri Tuvikene, tauri.tuvikene@tlu.ee		
Project Partners	<p>21 partners</p> <p>Bolt Services NO AS</p> <p>Flemish association of cities and municipalities vzw / de Vereniging van Vlaamse Steden en Gemeenten VVSG</p> <p>Huddinge Municipality</p> <p>Institute of Transport Economics / Transportøkonomisk Institutt (TOI)</p> <p>K2 The Swedish knowledge centre for public transport</p> <p>Lime Norway AS</p> <p>Lund University – Department of Technology and Society – Transport and Roads</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>Region Stockholm</p> <p>Resenårsforum</p> <p>Saue municipality</p> <p>Swedish national cycling advocacy organisation (Cykelfrämjandet)</p> <p>Swedish National Road and Transport Research Institute / Statens väg- och transportforskningsinstitut (VTI)</p> <p>Tallinn University / Tallinna Ülikooli (TLU) – School of Humanities</p> <p>The City of Tallinn / Tallinna Linn / Tallinn linnavalitsus</p> <p>The Flemish Department of Mobility and Public Works (MOW)</p> <p>TIER Mobility Sweden AB</p> <p>Tyréns AB</p> <p>Vlaamse Vervoersmaatschappij (VVM) De Lijn</p> <p>Voi Technology Norway AS</p> <p>Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Geography</p>		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2023	End date	2025
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <p>1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options</p> <p>4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p> <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <p>1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity</p>		

	<p>2. Focus on people-centred public space</p> <p>4. Support sustainable lifestyles</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p>
Keywords	Social justice, dual perspective, resilient and inclusive public transport, needs, capabilities, decision-making, accessibility, built environment, inclusive urban planning, micromobility, fare structures, on-demand public transport, transit-oriented development, dual perspective, resilience
Case Studies	Tallinn, Flanders, Stockholm, Oslo
<p>The European research Project CARIN-PT explores the relation between social inequalities and public transport. Public transport (PT) is an essential urban infrastructure. Improving PT quality and increasing its ridership is generally expected to generate environmental benefits and sustaining economic growth. However, the social justice dimension of PT development remains largely under-researched. This includes the understanding of who decides about PT development and how (participation), whose needs are considered in this process (recognition), and who benefits from its outcome (distribution). The close relationship between socio-economic dynamics, accessibility and the use of PT is poorly understood. Therefore, the research will examine social and spatial inequalities related to PT in terms of needs, capabilities, decision-making, accessibility and the built environment, both in a quantitative and a qualitative manner. It will co-produce understandings on how urban planning oriented towards resilience can be strengthened through inclusive processes. In close collaboration with policy-makers and service providers, the project will consider micromobility, fare structures, flexible on-demand PT and transit-oriented development (TOD) in the urban regions of Tallinn (Estonia), Flanders (Belgium), Stockholm (Sweden) and Oslo (Norway). The project aims to bring about a shift in how mobility policies and services are developed, as to become more integrated and inclusive.</p> <p>https://carinpt.eu/, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>	

EU Framework Programmes for Research and Innovation

The framework programmes (FPs) are the key funding programmes for research and innovation in the EU. The first framework programme (FP1) started in 1984 with a budget of € 3,75 billion and a runtime of four years. Since then, budgets, scope, instruments, aims and complexity increased, and the focus shifted towards engaging in societal challenges and contributing to the SDGs. Currently the ninth FP named Horizon Europe is running with a budget of € 94,1 billion for seven years (European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation et al., 2023).

71 of the 93 collected projects funded by the FPs are part of the CIVITAS Initiative.

CIVITAS stands for City-VITALity-Sustainability and support cities in the implementation of sustainable urban transport measures since 2002 (European Commission, n.d.-b). Ten thematic areas covering different aspects of urban mobility and planning guide the efforts of CIVITAS and its projects:

- Active mobility
- Behavioural change and mobility management
- Clean and energy-efficient vehicles
- Collective passenger transport and shared mobility
- Demand and urban space management
- Integrated and inclusive planning
- Public participation and co-creation
- Road safety and security
- Smart and connected mobility
- Urban logistics (CIVITAS ELEVATE, 2021).

CIVITAS also offers the CIVITAS Urban Mobility Tool Inventory (<https://civitas.eu/tool-inventory>), an online database with over 200 tools and methods for urban mobility planning, and a Learning Centre with capacity building opportunities (<https://civitas.eu/learning-centre>).

With CIVITAS starting under FP5, this was the first FP included. However, the most projects by the FPs featured in the compilation are funded by Horizon 2020, particularly under the societal challenge “Smart, Green And Integrated Transport”, and Horizon Europe, in the cluster “Climate, Energy and Mobility”.

Fifth framework programme of the European Community for research, technological development and demonstration activities (FP5)

Website	https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/FP5
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VIVALDI

Project Full Title	Visionary and Vibrant Actions through Local Transport Demonstration Initiatives		
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/vivaldi https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/11958 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/visionary-and-vibrant-actions-through-local-transport-demonstration-initiatives		
Call	FP5-GROWTH		
Project Coordinator	Bristol City Council transport_initiatives@bristol-city.gov.uk		
Project Partners	22 partners Aalborg Municipality / Aalborg Kommune Agence d'urbanisme de la région nantaise (AURAN) Bremer Energie-Konsens GmbH Bremer Straßenbahn AG / Bremen Straßenbahn AG Bristol City Council Bristol Dial-a-Ride Cambio Mobilitätsservice GmbH & Co KG First City Line Ltd. Free Hanseatic City of Bremen / Freie Hansestadt Bremen – Senator für Bau und Umwelt GVZ-City-Logistik Bremen GmbH Kaunas City Municipality Nantes Métropole / Communauté urbaine de Nantes North Jutland's Transport Company / Nordjyllands Trafikselskab Société d'économie mixte des transports en commun de l'agglomération nantaise Stadtauto Bremen Carsharing GmbH Sustrans Ltd. SWB Enordia GmbH Transport, Infrastructure & Telematics Universität Bremen – Zentrale wissenschaftliche Einrichtung Arbeit und Region University of the West of England (UWE Bristol) – Centre for Transport and Society (CTS) Verkehrsverbund Bremen / Niedersachsen GmbH Zweckverband Verkehrsverbund Bremen / Niedersachsen		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	03.08.2002	End date	31.01.2006
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 1. Support striving neighbourhood economies 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics		

	KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments
Keywords	Innovative transport strategies and measures, urban vitality, economic success, social inclusion, health and well-being, sustainability, travel demand reduction, demand management, real-time passenger information system, car sharing, freight consolidation centre, digital tools, modification of public transport, alternative fuels
Case Studies	Aalborg, Bremen, Bristol, Kaunas, Nantes
<p>The VIVALDI project sought to implement an integrated package of innovative transport strategies and measures in five EU cities, and to assess their contribution to improving four key urban policy goals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • urban vitality and economic success; • social inclusion; • health and well-being; and • sustainability. <p>Through a reduction in motorised traffic and a measurable shift to environmentally friendly modes of transport, VIVALDI led to a substantial reduction in emissions of air pollutants and noise.</p> <p>Since a reduction in demand for travel was considered as the most effective way to cut emissions, the project comprised a range of measures in the field of demand management, including car sharing. There were also attempts to further reduce emissions by introducing clean vehicles.</p> <p>(https://civitas.eu/projects/vivaldi, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>	

TRENDSETTER

Project Full Title	TRENDSETTER setting trends for sustainable urban mobility		
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/trendsetter https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/11689 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/setting-trends-sustainable-urban-mobility		
Call	FP5-EESD		
Project Coordinator	City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad – Environment and Health Administration Gustaf Landahl, Gustaf.Landahl@miljo.stockholm.se		
Project Partners	20 partners 878 Cityfunk GmbH AGA Gas AB Austrian Mobility Research / Forschungsgesellschaft Mobilität (FGM) – AMOR Gemeinnützige GmbH City of Graz / Stadt Graz City of Prague / Hlavní Město Praha City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad – Environment and Health Administration City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad – Transportation Administration Dipl-Ing Peter Erlach – Erlach Consulting and Engineering Energie Graz GmbH & Co KG / Grazer Stadtwerke AG home2you AB Lille Métropole communauté urbaine Municipality of the City of Pécs / Pécs Megyei Jogú Város Önkormányzata Pécsi Városüzemelési és Vagyonkezelő rt. Provincial Government of Styria / Land Steiermark Spedition- und Internationale Transport GmbH Statoil Detaljhandel AB Steirische Verkehrsverbund Gesellschaft GmbH Stockholm Public Transport Agency / AB Storstockholms Lokaltrafik (SL) Swedish Transport Administration / Trafikverket Syndicat mixte des transports		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	10.08.2002	End date	31.01.2006
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		

Keywords	Sustainable mobility solutions, advance mobility management schemes, clean cost-effective and energy-efficient vehicles, shift to public transportation, efficiency of urban freight distribution, public acceptance, bio-fuels, short- and long-term strategy, heavy vehicles, private cars, pricing strategies, information technologies, intermodal interchanges, demand systems, policy changes, environmental zones, access restriction zones for heavy vehicles, pedestrian zones, parking and traffic management, accessibility, environmental and socioeconomic effects
Case Studies	Graz, Lille, Pecs, Prague, Stockholm
<p>TRENDESETTER's objectives are to ameliorate urban air quality and noise levels, and congestion while supporting exceptional mobility and urban quality of life. It will help other cities see how they can curb unsustainable traffic growth by using advanced mobility management schemes combined with clean vehicle fleets.</p> <p>TRENDESETTER aims to promote the use of public transport and other alternatives to private cars but also show new ways to improve goods logistics and efficiency. The project will increase the acceptance for bio-fuels among citizens and encourage operators, politicians and social groups to use innovative, low-noise and low emission technology by practical day-to-day operation. TRENDESETTER will prove that cities can achieve Kyoto and EU goals, e.g. by reducing fossil CO₂ by 5% through a combination of measures. The results are intended as inputs to European policy making and to set trends for a sustainable transport future in Europe.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/11689, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>	

MIRACLES

Project Full Title	Multi-Initiative for Rationalised Accessibility and Clean Liveable Environments		
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/miracles https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/11953 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/multi-initiatives-rationalised-accessibility-and-clean-liveable-environments		
Call	FP5-GROWTH		
Project Coordinator	City of Rome / Roma Capitale / Comune di Roma		
Project Partners	<p>18 partners</p> <p>Agenzia per i Trasporti Autoferrotramviari del Comune di Roma (ATAC S.p.A.) Autoritat del Transport Metropolità (ATM) Barcelona Municipality / Ajuntament de Barcelona Barcelona Tecnologia S.A. City of Rome / Roma Capitale / Comune di Roma Cork City Council Disseny de sistemes i desenvolupament S.A. Ente per le Nuove Tecnologie, l'Energia e l'Ambiente Gruppo Interclub s.r.l. Hampshire County Council – Highways and Transport Policy Interclub Service SAS Peopleservice s.r.l. STA Società Trasporti Automobilistici S.p.A. Transports de Barcelona SA / Transports Metropolitans de Barcelona (TMB) Università degli studi di Roma La Sapienza – Dipartimento di idraulica, trasporti e strade Università degli studi di Roma La Sapienza – Dipartimento di psicologia University College Cork, National University of Ireland University of Southampton – Transportation Research Group (TRG)</p>		
Duration (months)	43		
Start date	05.09.2002	End date	31.03.2006
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <p>1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p> <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <p>3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies 4. Support sustainable lifestyles</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p>		
Keywords	Sustainable and efficient urban transport systems, modal shift to cleaner fuels and vehicles, accessibility, economic efficiency, policy strategies, city-centre clean zones, parking and pricing policies, low-emission bus fleets, new public transport lines,		

	park and ride, bicycle parking infrastructure, car-sharing, information technology, freight delivery, public awareness, public and political acceptance
Case Studies	Rome, Barcelona, Winchester, Cork
<p>The aim was to improve the sustainability and efficiency of urban transport systems by reducing congestion, lowering emissions, and achieving a shift in the modal split towards cleaner fuels and vehicles. The four participating cities strove to achieve four strategic goals with the support of the MIRACLES project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A reduction in transport-related environmental impacts at the local level. • Increased urban accessibility. • Enhanced economic efficiency through better transport management. • An overall improvement in citizens' quality of life. <p>To achieve these objectives, the MIRACLES cities designed common policy strategies based on the CIVITAS measures. These measures were implemented in a coordinated manner, making it easier to identify and evaluate the impacts of the individual measures, measure clusters and horizontal integrated packages. The consortium comprised municipalities and county councils; transport authorities; transport operators (both public and private); universities and research organisations; public relations and press organisations (for dissemination); as well as technology specialists.</p> <p>(https://civitas.eu/projects/miracles, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>	

TELLUS

Project Full Title	Transport and Environment Alliance for Urban Sustainability
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/tellus https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/11991 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/transport-environment-alliance-urban-sustainability
Call	FP5-GROWTH
Project Coordinator	Municipality of Rotterdam / Gemeente Rotterdam Arjan Oranje
Project Partners	<p>30 partners</p> <p>ANT</p> <p>Arnhold, Huhn und Sandock Partnerschaft, Diplom-Pädagogin, Diplom-Kauffrau, Diplom-Psychologe Berlin – Senate Department for Urban Development, Building und Housing / Senatsverwaltung für Stadtentwicklung</p> <p>Berliner Verkehrsbetriebe (BVG)</p> <p>City of Gdynia / Gdynia-Miasto na prawach powiatu</p> <p>City of Gothenburg / Goteborgs Kommun / Göteborgs Stad – Traffic and Public Transport Authority / Trafikkontoret</p> <p>Collect Car B.V.</p> <p>Danzas ASG Eurocargo AB</p> <p>Deutsche Bahn Rent GmbH</p> <p>eloqu-metabasis GmbH</p> <p>FordonsGas Veast</p> <p>Forschungs- und Anwendungsverbund Verkehrssystemtechnik Berlin (FAV Berlin)</p> <p>GASAG – Berliner Gaswerke AG</p> <p>Goteborg Gatu AB / Göteborgs Gatuaktiebolag</p> <p>Green Cargo</p> <p>Institutet foer transportforskning</p> <p>IVU Traffic Technologies AG</p> <p>Mobi Power Ltd</p> <p>Mobile Parkin GmbH</p> <p>Municipality of Rotterdam / Gemeente Rotterdam</p> <p>Norra Älvstranden Utveckling AB</p> <p>Port of Rotterdam / Havenbedrijf Rotterdam</p> <p>Renova AB</p> <p>Societatea de Transport București (STB) / Regia Autonomă de Transport București (RATB)</p> <p>Stichting Bereikbaarheid Rijnmond</p> <p>Taxi-Ruf GmbH "City-Funk"</p> <p>Technische Universität Berlin (TU Berlin) – Center Technology and Society (ZTG)</p> <p>Universiteit van Amsterdam (UvA) – IVAM UvA B.V.</p> <p>VIA Collect B.V.</p> <p>Vipre B.V.</p>
Duration (months)	38

Start date	19.12.2002	End date	31.01.2006
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		
Keywords	<p>Modal shift, sustainable urban transport, public transport, cycling, political and public awareness, public-private cooperation, innovative measures, implementation and concept development, commercial transport, accessibility, planning aspects, user participation, soft measures, evaluation</p>		
Case Studies	<p>Rotterdam, Berlin, Gothenburg, Gdynia, Bucharest</p>		
<p>The key concept behind the TELLUS project was variety. The project comprised a variety of very different cities applying a variety of transport strategies and innovative transport measures in order to make urban transport more sustainable.</p> <p>A variety of approaches were used to implement those measures and a variety of methods and instruments were applied to conceptualise, monitor, analyse and assess the measures in order to present results and impacts as well as to explain processes, drivers and constraints. The main aims of the project included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • shifting the modal share in favour of public transport; • increasing the use of bicycles; • lowering congestion; • reducing traffic-related air and noise pollution below national and EC standards; • decreasing city-centre car usage; • improving intra-organisational cooperation at city level; • increasing political and public awareness; • reducing road casualties; and • improving public-private cooperation <p>In general, the focus of the TELLUS project was on translating urban transport policy into the practical implementation of innovative, city-specific measures. However, not all measures were concerned with implementation: some aimed at preparing the ground while others supported strategies and measures by developing a concept to be implemented later. Out of the 48 TELLUS measures, 28 aimed at direct implementation, 17 at concept development and implementation, and three at concept development only.</p> <p>https://civitas.eu/projects/tellus, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>			

Sixth framework programme of the European Community for research, technological development and demonstration activities, contributing to the creation of the European Research Area and to innovation (FP6)

Website	https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/FP6
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MOBILIS

Project Full Title	Mobility initiatives for local integration and sustainability
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/mobilis https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/513562 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/mobility-initiatives-local-integration-and-sustainability
Call	FP6-2003-TREN-2
Project Coordinator	Syndicat mixte des transports en commun de l'agglomération toulousaine
Project Partners	<p>33 partners</p> <p>Agence d'urbanisme et d'aménagement Toulouse aire métropolitaine (AUAT) AGIRE – Agenzia Veneziana per l'Energia Agricultural Institute of Slovenia / Kmetijski inštitut Slovenije Azienda del Consorzio Transporti Veneziano Azienda Servizi Mobilità S.p.A. Cecile Centre d'études techniques de l'Équipement du sud-ouest City of Debrecen / Debrecen Megyei Jogú Város Önkormányzata City of Ljubljana / Mestna občina Ljubljana City of Toulouse / Ville de Toulouse City of Venice / Comune di Venezia Commissario del Governo Delegato al Traffico Acqueo nella Laguna di Venezia Communauté d'agglomération de Grand Toulouse Communauté d'agglomération de Toulouse sud-est (Sicoval) Connex Toulouse DKV Debreceni Közlekedési Részvénytársaság Forma Urbis di Fabio Carrera e C. S.a.s. Gaz de France Hajdú Volán Közlekedési Részvénytársaság Javno podjetje Ljubljanski potniški promet d.o.o. (LPP) Magyar Közút Kht. Hajdú-Bihar Megyei Területi Igazgatósága Mobiel 21 vzw Municipality of Blagnac / Commune de Blagnac Pinus tovarna kemičnih izdelkov D.D. Regional Environmental Center for Central and Eastern Europe (REC) Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH Sava / Savatech d.o.o. Syndicat mixte des transports en commun de l'agglomération toulousaine Teol-Kemicna Industrija D.D. The City of Odense – Environmental and Technical Department University of Debrecen University of Maribor – Faculty of Mechanical Engineering – Institute of Power, Process and Environmental Engineering VESTA S.p.A. – Venezia Servizi Territoriali Ambientali</p>

Duration (months)	48		
Start date	14.01.2005	End date	13.01.2009
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies 4. Support sustainable lifestyles <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		
Keywords	Clean urban mobility, sustainable and economic development, stakeholder and public participation, integrated packages of policies and measures, exchange of experiences, social inclusion and equity, alternative fuels, agglomeration level, behavioural change, new technologies in transport, transition process, energy-efficient vehicles, modal shift, public space, transport-minimising urban structures, safety, efficient planning and implementation processes, awareness raising, Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), accessibility, freight distribution centre, clean urban logistics, public transport quality, targeted mobility services, car pooling and sharing, marketing, training, car access restriction, parking management, capacities of mobility stakeholders		
Case Studies	Toulouse, Debrecen, Ljubljana, Venice, Odense		
<p>The cities of Toulouse (France), Debrecen (Hungary) and Ljubljana (Slovenia), their public transport operators, the private sector and research institutions are committed to establish a European partnership for 'Sustainable Mobility Measures and Innovations in Transport' (SUMMIT).</p> <p>Aiming for radical strategies for clean urban transport, the political leaders of the three cities joined forces to create a new culture for clean mobility in European cities in the wider frame of sustainable development, broad participation of all relevant actors and particular care of social inclusion. The cities have developed a solidly packaged work programme which addresses all eight CIVITAS Policy Fields in an integrative approach.</p> <p>The highlights of policy areas are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • broadening the use of alternative fuels and clean vehicles through large-scale operation of clean vehicles for public transport (CNG, bio fuels); • emphasising on determining the optimum mix of alternative fuels, following EU objectives to migrate in long-term from bio-fuel <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/513562, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>			

SUCCESS

Project Full Title	Smaller Urban Communities in CIVITAS for Environmentally Sustainable Solutions		
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/success https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/513785 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/smaller-urban-communities-civitas-environmentally-sustainable-solutions		
Call	FP6-2003-TREN-2		
Project Coordinator	Communauté d'agglomération de La Rochelle Jean Marie Grellier, Jean-marie.grellier@agglo-larochelle.fr		
Project Partners	<p>12 partners</p> <p>City of La Rochelle / Commune de la Rochelle Communauté d'agglomération de La Rochelle École d'Ingénieurs en Génie des Systèmes Industriels Lancashire County Council Ploiești City Hall Preston Bus Ltd Preston City Council Regia Autonoma de Transport Public Ploiesti (RATPP) / S.C. „Transport Călători Express” S.A Ploiești (TCE Ploiești) South Ribble Borough Council Syndicats mixtes de la Communauté Tarifaire en Charente-Maritime Transport & Travel Research Ltd Universitatea Petrol si Gaze din Ploiești</p>		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.02.2005	End date	31.01.2009
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 		
Keywords	Medium-sized cities, road safety, sustainable urban mobility, alternative fuels, traffic management, energy policy, improvement of public transport, research and assessment activities, all-inclusive training and communication initiatives, access control schemes, integrated pricing systems, car-sharing fleets, transport information systems, city logistics, energy-efficient vehicles, infrastructure development for cycling and walking, business and school travel plans, IT and GPS solutions, freight quality partnership		

Case Studies / Living Labs	La Rochelle, Preston, Ploiesti
<p>The main aim of CIVITAS SUCCESS was to address mobility-related challenges typical for medium-sized cities. La Rochelle, Preston and Ploiesti faced specific transport issues that were typical of medium-sized European cities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a small surface area, implying a greater interconnection among activities; • a lack of funding, which can be a barrier to the implementation of sophisticated technologies; • the need to adopt political solutions quickly; • unfamiliarity with the complexity of European projects; and • seasonal changes in transport uses. <p>The SUCCESS cities decided to use the latest clean-vehicle technologies in combination with other measures in order to create locations where citizens are able to enjoy a high-quality environment and travel easily and safely; to build local partnerships for tackling sustainable mobility issues; to develop efficient management systems; and to adopt new approaches to urban transport. The general objectives of SUCCESS were to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • demonstrate that alternative fuels can be an efficient choice for urban transport, with a target for all vehicle fleets to achieve a decrease of 20 percent in the use of fossil fuels, and to cut energy consumption and emissions of carbon dioxide, particulates and nitrogen oxide and nitrogen dioxide by 10 percent; • demonstrate that, with an ambitious package of mobility and traffic management measures, significant results can be provided regarding sustainable transport and energy policy; • demonstrate that cities in candidate countries can avoid the mistakes made in Western Europe and contribute to the development of their collective transport systems; and • support related research and assessment activities, including new, all-inclusive training and communication initiatives to disseminate results and encourage transferability. <p>https://civitas.eu/projects/success, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>	

CARAVEL

Project Full Title	Travelling towards a new mobility		
Website	https://www.rupprecht-consult.eu/project/civitas-caravel https://civitas.eu/projects/caravel https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/513553 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/travelling-towards-new-mobility		
Call	FP6-2003-TREN-2		
Project Coordinator	City of Genoa / Comune di Genova Antonio Rossa, arossa@comune.genova.it		
Project Partners	<p>22 partners</p> <p>Agencja Rozwoju Miasta S.A. Agenzia regionale per la protezione dell'ambiente Ligure Agenzia regionale per l'energia della Liguria s.p.a. Azienda Mobilità e Trasporti Genova S.p.A. (AMT Genova) Burgos City Hall City of Genoa / Comune di Genova Cracow University of Technology / Politechnika Krakowska D'Appolonia S.p.A. Forms Group Instituto Tecnológico de Castilla y León Istituto Internazionale delle Comunicazioni (IIC Genova) Krakow Municipality / Gmina Miejska Krakow – Miasto Na Prawach Powiatu Miejskie Przedsiębiorstwo Komunikacyjne w Krakowie (MPK Kraków) Plan Estratégico de la Cultura de la ciudad de Burgos QN Financial Service S.p.A. Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH Softeco Sismat S.p.A. SSP Consult Beratende Ingenieure GmbH State capital Stuttgart / Landeshauptstadt Stuttgart Università di Genova – Facoltà di Economia – Dipartimento di Economia e Metodi quantitativi University of Stuttgart Verband Region Stuttgart</p>		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.02.2005	End date	31.01.2009
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies 		

	<p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p> <p>3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>
Keywords	<p>Clean urban mobility, sustainable development, safe and equitable access, citizens well being, medium-sized cities, integrated transport policy, renewable energy resources, transport behaviour, bicycles, car sharing and pooling, efficient public transport, vulnerable and disadvantaged citizens, awareness raising, round-table-discussions with stakeholders, high mobility corridors, mobility marketing, alternative transport modes, know-how transfer, economic competitiveness, public-private partnerships, evaluation, access restriction zones, road and parking pricing, freight distribution schemes</p>
Case Studies	<p>Genova, Burgos, Krakow, Stuttgart</p>
<p>The cities of Krakow and Genoa, their public transport operators, industrial partners, and research institutions have defined a common project proposal entitled ACTIV21 - "Agenda for Clean Transport In Vital cities of the 21st century". Their political leaders agree to establish a new culture for clean mobility in European cities in support of sustainable development, citizens well being and safe access for all.</p> <p>A substantial work programme, with both cities addressing all eight CIVITAS policy fields, has been defined by this ambitious pair of cities. A bold package of measures will be introduced:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • large-scale demonstrators with a substantial impact will be implemented (e.g. road and parking pricing, extension of access-restricted zones coupled with enforcement; High Clean Mobility Corridors; freight distribution schemes and others) • the use of CNG vehicles for freight, high volume PT and flexible services are demonstrated in linked sites. <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/513553, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>	

SMILE

Project Full Title	Towards Sustainable Mobility for people in urban areas
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/smile https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/513518 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/sustainable-urban-transport-europe-tomorrow
Call	FP6-2003-TREN-2
Project Coordinator	City of Malmö / Malmö Stad – Environment Department Dagmar Gormsen City of Malmö / Malmö Stad – Streets and Parks Department Magnus Fahl
Project Partners	29 partners 215 215 Transporter AB Agenzia Ricerca E Produzione Avanzata (ARPA) Anglian Bus Ltd AS MRP Linna Liinid City of Malmö / Malmö Stad – Environment Department City of Malmö / Malmö Stad – Streets and Parks Department CTP EON / Sydkraft AB First Eastern Counties Buses Ltd Lund University Malmö Lastbilcentral AB Malmö University / Malmö Universitet – School of Technology and Society Mobility Energy Environment And New Technologies s.r.l. Norfolk County Council Potenza Province Regione Basilicata Scania Regional Transport Authority Skånemejerier Smart Moves Ltd T/A City Car Club Suceava Municipality Tallinn University of Technology / Tallinna Tehnikaülikool (TalTech) Tallinna Linnatranspordi AS (Tallinna Autobussikoondise AS / Tallinn Bus Company, Tallinna Trammi- ja Trollibussikoondis / Tallinn Tram and Trolleybus Company) The City Council of Norwich The City of Tallinn / Tallinna Linn / Tallinn linnavalitsus Transport & Travel Ltd UMAS University Hospital, Malmö General Hospital University of East Anglia – Estates & Buildings Division University of the West of England (UWE Bristol) Volvo On Demand / Sunfleet Car-sharing
Duration (months)	48

Start date	01.02.2005	End date	31.01.2009
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 3. Provide sustainable solutions for longer trips 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), intelligent sustainable and inter-modal urban transport systems, bio-fuels, clean vehicles, intelligent door-to-door travel choices, road safety, efficient and clean distribution of goods, medium-sized cities, public transport, cycling, car sharing, regional perspective, low-emission zones, SUMPs, innovative measures, long-term planning, freight consolidation centre		
Case Studies	Leading cities: Malmo, Norwich Follower sites: Tallinn, Suceava, Potenza		
<p>The CIVITAS SMILE project, “Towards Sustainable Mobility for People in Urban Areas”, was structured around two leading cities, Malmo (Sweden) and Norwich (UK), with three follower sites, Tallinn (Estonia), Suceava (Romania) and Potenza (Italy).</p> <p>Within the project, a set of measures was implemented with the aim of developing intelligent, sustainable and inter-modal urban transport systems allowing citizens to live an active life without using a car. The project aimed to improve urban air quality, quality of life, health, safety and security through the promotion of bio-fuels, clean vehicles and intelligent door-to-door travel choices. The objective was to halt the current trend towards increased car use, promote sustainable alternatives and stimulate the efficient and clean distribution of goods in the cities.</p> <p>The CIVITAS SMILE cities illustrated some of the typical problems facing historic medium-sized cities in the European Union and accession countries, indicating a high level of transferability of the project results. CIVITAS SMILE involved 27 partners, who implemented 51 demonstration measures all aimed at lowering hazardous emissions from city traffic. With impacts stretching well after the project’s conclusion, the project fostered a modal shift towards public transport, cycling and car sharing.</p> <p>CIVITAS focused primarily on urban transport. However, it is often very difficult to consider urban transportation in isolation from the wider regional perspective. This was reflected both in the formation of the SMILE partnership, which included a range of regional authorities and one regional transport authority; and also in the measures, many of which had a regional rather than purely urban perspective.</p> <p>(https://civitas.eu/projects/smile, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>			

Seventh framework programme of the European Community for research and technological development and demonstration activities (FP7)

Website	https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/FP7
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NICHES+

Project Full Title	New and Innovative Concepts for Helping European Transport Sustainability - Towards Implementation		
Website	https://www.rupprecht-consult.eu/project/niches-1 https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/218504 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/niches/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/new-and-innovative-concepts-helping-european-ttransport-sustainability-towards		
Call	FP7-SST-2007-RTD-1		
Project Coordinator	POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale		
Project Partners	6 partners Eurocities ASBL POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH TRANSMAN Consulting for Transport System Management Ltd University of Newcastle upon Tyne University of Southampton – Transportation Research Group (TRG)		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.05.2008	End date	30.04.2011
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Innovative urban transport concepts, accessibility to mobility options, efficiency of infrastructure, urban traffic management, automated & space efficient transport, networking, implementation scenarios, research recommendations, user needs, travel training for public transport, neighbourhood accessibility planning, users with reduced mobility, intermodal interchanges, Personal Rapid Transit		
Case Studies	Champion cities: Artois-Gohelle, Burgos, Worcestershire, Trondheim, Cork, Daventry		
NICHES+ (New and Innovative Concepts for Helping European Transport Sustainability - Towards Implementation) built further on the NICHES project. Its mission was to promote innovative measures for making urban transport more efficient and sustainable and to move them from their current 'niche' position into a mainstream urban transport application.			

To help local and regional authorities to develop implementation scenarios for introducing innovative concepts to existing policies of urban transport, project researchers focused on four topical themes and corresponding innovative concepts: increased accessibility to urban mobility options, increased use and efficiency of infrastructure and interchanges, exploiting functionalities of urban traffic management centers, and automated and space-efficient transport.

A working group of experts was set up in each thematic area to share expertise and facilitate networking activities. Seven champion cities and innovative concepts were chosen for work on implementation scenarios, which were pegged to address issues related to the actual roll-out of transport measures. The needs and expectations of potential users and implementers were studied, and the transferability of innovative concepts was reviewed. Guidelines for implementers, and research and policy recommendations were also developed.

(<https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/niches/>, 26 September 2024)

RENAISSANCE

Project Full Title	Testing Innovative Strategies for Clean Urban Transport for historic European cities		
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/renaissance https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/219120 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/testing-innovative-clean-urban-transport-strategies-historic-european-cities		
Call	FP7-SST-2007-TREN-1_		
Project Coordinator	Municipality of Perugia		
Project Partners	<p>30 partners</p> <p>Advanced Communications & Electronic Systems Ltd (ACES) Advanced Transport System Ltd / Ultra Global PRT APM Esercizi S.p.A. Bath & North East Somerset Council City of Skopje City of Szczecinek / Miasto Szczecinek Comunicare s.r.l. First West of England Ltd / First Somerset & Avon Ltd FIT Consulting s.r.l. Gorna Oryahovitsa Airport PLC Gorna Oryahovitsa Sector for Passenger Railway Transport, Bulgarian State Railways Institute of Transport and Communications Ltd Komunikacja Miejska Sp. z o.o. w Szczecinku Landi Renzo S.p.A. Mizar Automazione S.p.A. MRC Mclean Hazel Ltd. Municipality of Gorna Oryahovitsa Municipality of Perugia NEA Transport Research and Training Politechnika Koszalińska Powabyke Ltd Public Transport Company Of Skopje / Javno Soobrakajno Pretpriятие Skopje Samorządowa Agencja Promocji i Kultury Smart Moves Ltd T/A City Car Club Szczecinecka Lokalna Organizacja Turystyczna Università degli Studi di Perugia – Centro Interuniversitario di Ricerca sull'Inquinamento da Agenti Fisici (CIRIAF) University "St. Kliment Ohridski" Bitola – Faculty for Technical Sciences University of the West of England (UWE Bristol) – Centre for Transport and Society (CTS) Veliko Tarnovo / Weliko Tarnowo – Regional Office of the National Road Infrastructure Fund Yantra Transport JSC</p>		
Duration (months)	50		
Start date	15.09.2008	End date	14.11.2012

Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Support striving neighbourhood economies <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society
Keywords	<p>innovative and sustainable clean urban transport solutions, historic cities, seasonal tourism, economic vitality and employment, public awareness, social aspects, attractive public transport, traffic management, access and mobility measures</p>
Case Studies	<p>Perugia, Bath, Gorna Oryhavitsa, Szczecinek, Skopje</p>
<p>RENAISSANCE aims to develop a valid, reliable and integrated package of access and mobility measures for historic cities. These will make possible the rediscovery, preservation and enhancement of historic cities in Europe, together with the sustainable development of the local economy, to the benefit of visitors, residents and local business alike. RENAISSANCE brings together a group of historic/tourism cities across Europe that are in the vanguard of sustainable development.</p> <p>The RENAISSANCE cities have a strong reliance on heritage and tourism, which must marry environmental concerns, and sustainable access and mobility, with economic development. The partners face common problems: they are all historic cities with common layouts, and very valuable heritage to be preserved and enhanced. The partners also face unique local and regional challenges, including those brought about by social and economic integration within the EU. There is great added value in RENAISSANCE because the best practices that will be demonstrated will have resonance and relevance throughout the range of European Historic Cities.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/219120, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>	

ELAN

Project Full Title	Mobilising citizens for vital cities
Website	https://www.rupprecht-consult.eu/project/civitas-elan https://civitas.eu/projects/elan https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/218954 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/mobilising-citizens-vital-cities-ljubljana-gent-zagreb-brno-porto
Call	FP7-SST-2007-TREN-1_28June
Project Coordinator	City of Ljubljana / Mestna občina Ljubljana Zdenka Šimonovic, zdenka.simonovic@ljubljana.si
Project Partners	<p>39 partners</p> <p>Agricultural Institute of Slovenia / Kmetijski inštitut Slovenije</p> <p>Associação Nacional Rodoviária de Transportadores Pesados de Passageiros</p> <p>Austrian Mobility Research / Forschungsgesellschaft Mobilität (FGM) – AMOR Gemeinnützige GmbH</p> <p>biciklistickog kluba bicikl</p> <p>City of Ghent / Stad Gent</p> <p>City of Ljubljana / Mestna občina Ljubljana</p> <p>City of Zagreb / Grad Zagreb</p> <p>Digipolis</p> <p>Dopravní podnik města Brna AS (DPMB)</p> <p>Etrek svetovanje in druge storitve d.o.o.</p> <p>Flanders / Vlaanderen / Vlaamse Gewest / Vlaams Gewest</p> <p>Fundação Ensino e Cultura Fernando Pessoa Pcup</p> <p>Ghent University / Universiteit Gent – Department of Biochemical and microbial technology</p> <p>Ghent University / Universiteit Gent – Department of Geography</p> <p>HŽ Infrastruktura d.o.o.</p> <p>Institut Jožef Stefan (IJS, JSI)</p> <p>Javno podjetje Ljubljanski potniški promet d.o.o. (LPP)</p> <p>Max Mobiel vzw</p> <p>Metro do Porto SA</p> <p>ODRAZ-Održivi razvoj zajednice</p> <p>Optimização e Planeamento de Transportes SA</p> <p>Optimobil Vlaanderen</p> <p>Porto Municipality</p> <p>Prometni institut Ljubljana d.o.o.</p> <p>Regional Environmental Center for Central and Eastern Europe (REC)</p> <p>Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH</p> <p>Slovenske železnice d.o.o.</p> <p>Sociedade de Transportes Colectivos do Porto SA</p> <p>Statutory city Brno / Statutární město Brno</p> <p>Studentenmobilität vzw</p> <p>Technum – Tractebel Engineering nv</p> <p>Telargo d.o.o. informacijske rešitve v prometu in transportu</p>

	University of Ljubljana / Univerza v Ljubljani University of Porto / Universidade do Porto – Faculdade de Ciências (FCUP) University of Porto / Universidade do Porto – Faculdade de Engenharia University of Zagreb – Faculty of Transport and Traffic Sciences / Sveučilište u Zagrebu – Fakultet prometnih znanosti Urban Planning Institute of the Republic of Slovenia / Urbanistični inštitut Republike Slovenije (UIRS) Vlaamse Vervoersmaatschappij (VVM) De Lijn Zagrebački holding d.o.o.		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	15.09.2008	End date	14.09.2012
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Citizen participation, needs and expectations of citizens, health and access for all, alternative fuels, clean energy efficient vehicles, collective transport services, intermodal integration, demand management, congestion charging scheme, management of public space, travel behaviour, mobility marketing approach, safe and secure mobility, vulnerable road users, innovative mobility services, car sharing, freight distribution, transport telematics, process-oriented approach, risk management, inclusive governance, walking and cycling		
Case Studies	Ljubljana, Ghent, Zagreb, Brno, Porto		
<p>CIVITAS-ELAN is a large and ambitious project of great strategic importance to its project partners and funding institutions. The mayors of the cities of Ljubljana, Gent, Zagreb, Brno and Porto have agreed to a common mission statement “To ‘mobilise’ our citizens by developing with their support clean mobility solutions for vital cities, ensuring health and access for all. The five cities intend to cooperate on the basis of a clear set of common objectives, based on the principle of “putting the citizen first”. For each of the CIVITAS policy fields a common set of objectives and project goals has been agreed, and the cities have developed a programme of in total sixty-nine measures, which are described in detail, including concrete targets. The focus on citizen participation has been deeply built into the workplan, also several NGOs are part of the project consortium. The ELAN cities are representative of a growing number of dynamic, mainly medium-sized national or regional centres with strong cultural background. The planning of the project is mature with detailed timetable, resources and organisational structures. The project consortium is very experienced, some partners were involved in CIVITAS 1 and 2 from various perspectives. As requested in the call, a city from New Member States (NMS) (Ljubljana) is the project coordinator and a learning city (Brno) is also from a NMS. A further leading city (Zagreb) is from a candidate country thus bringing the CIVITAS initiative in the enlargement prospect. The workplan addresses topics of specific interest to cities</p>			

in the NMS. Through CIVITAS-ELAN three new countries, Portugal, Croatia and Belgium will be put on the CIVITAS map as ELAN cities are committed to become ambassadors in their countries. As a policy-driven project, CIVITAS-ELAN will make significant contributions to major global, EU and national policy processes. (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/218954>, retrieved 18 September 2024)

ARCHIMEDES

Project Full Title	Achieving Real CHange with Innovative transport MEasures Demonstrating Energy Savings		
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/archimedes https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/218940 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/achieving-real-change-innovative-transport-measures-demonstrating-energy-savings		
Call	FP7-SST-2007-TREN-1_28June		
Project Coordinator	Aalborg Municipality / Aalborg Kommune		
Project Partners	<p>16 partners</p> <p>Aalborg Municipality / Aalborg Kommune Brighton & Hove Bus and Coach Company Ltd Brighton & Hove City Council City Council of Donostia San Sebastián / Ayuntamiento de Donostia – San Sebastián Compañía del Tranvía de San Sebastián SA (CTSS) Grupo de estudios y alternativas GEA 21 Iasi Municipality / Municipiul Iași Instituto Vasco de Logística y Movilidad Sostenible / Logistikako Euskal Erakundea (IVL-LEE) Municipality of Monza / Comune di Monza North Jutland's Transport Company / Nordjyllands Trafikselskab Project Automation S.p.A. Regia Autonomă de Transport Public (RATP) Iași / Compania de Transport Public (CTP) Iași Statutory City of Usti nad Labem / Statutární město Ústí nad Labem T.P.M. Trasporti Pubblici Monzesi Universitatea Tehnică „Gheorghe Asachi” din Iași (TUIASI) University of the Basque Country / Universidad del País Vasco / Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea</p>		
Duration (months)	45		
Start date	15.09.2008	End date	14.12.2012
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <p>1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options</p> <p>4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p> <p>KA2 People-centred urban spaces and planning</p> <p>4. Support sustainable lifestyles</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p> <p>2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society</p>		
Keywords	Sustainable and energy-efficient urban transport, safe and convenient travel services, medium-sized urban areas, policy tools, innovative integrated and ambitious strategies, clean engine technology and fuels, education of students citizens and practitioners, awareness and acceptance of new services, knowledge exchange, evaluation, behaviour change		

Case Studies	Aalborg, San Sebastian, Iasi, Monza, Usti-nad-Laben, Brighon & Hove
<p>ARCHIMEDES is an integrating project, bringing together 6 European cities to address problems and opportunities for creating environmentally sustainable, safe and energy efficient transport systems in medium sized urban areas. The objective of ARCHIMEDES is to introduce innovative, integrated and ambitious strategies for clean, energy-efficient, sustainable urban transport to achieve significant impacts in the policy fields of energy, transport, and environmental sustainability. An ambitious blend of policy tools and measures will increase energy-efficiency in transport, provide safer and more convenient travel for all, using a higher share of clean engine technology and fuels, resulting in an enhanced urban environment (including reduced noise and air pollution). Visible and measurable impacts will result from significantly sized measures in specific innovation areas. Demonstrations of innovative transport technologies, policy measures and partnership working, combined with targeted research, will verify the best frameworks, processes and packaging required to successfully transfer the strategies to other cities. Two learning cities will participate fully in the decision making and organisational structure. New member state representation is assured with one Lead City and one Learning City. A strong educational objective will be realised with training and learning actions within the consortium, and via promotion, training events and educational exchanges between students, citizens and stakeholders in the project innovation areas. Dissemination of results and the focus on exploitation activities will impact well beyond the innovation area itself, providing lessons for citizens, practitioners and policy makers. The result will be a greater acceptance for new tools, services and technologies and the objectives that lie behind them.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/218940, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>	

MODERN

Project Full Title	MObility, Development and Energy use Reduction		
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/modern https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/219041 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/modern-mobility-development-and-energy-use-reduction		
Call	FP7-SST-2007-TREN-1_28June		
Project Coordinator	Local Council of Craiova Municipality / Consiliul Local al Municipiului Craiova Gabriel Vladut, office@ipacv.ro		
Project Partners	<p>22 partners</p> <p>Brescia Mobilità S.p.A. – Società Metropolitana di Mobilità Brescia Transporti S.p.A. Centro de Estudios Ambientales (CEA) Coimbra Municipality / Câmara Municipal de Coimbra CORE s.r.l. Critical Software SA Ente Vasco de la Energía (EVE) IPA SA Istituto di Studi per l’Integrazione dei Sistemi (I.S.I.S) – Società cooperativa Local Council of Craiova Municipality / Consiliul Local al Municipiului Craiova Methodos S.p.A. MO.VE Mobility Venice AISBL Municipality of Brescia / Comune di Brescia Perform Energia Prodeso – Ensino Profissional, E.M., Lda Real Automóvil Club Vasco Navarro Asociacion (RACVN) Regia Autonomă de Transport Craiova r.a. (RAT Craiova) Serviços Municipalizados de Transportes Urbanos de Coimbra (SMTUC) Transportes urbanos de Vitoria-Gasteiz SA Universidade de Coimbra – Energy for Sustainability Initiative (EFS UC) University of Brescia / Università degli Studi di Brescia Vitoria-Gasteiz City Hall / Ayuntamiento de Vitoria-Gasteiz</p>		
Duration (months)	52		
Start date	15.10.2008	End date	14.02.2013
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies 4. Support sustainable lifestyles 		

	<p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders
Keywords	Stakeholder engagement, performance-led approach, regional capitals, efficiency and accessibility of public transport, innovative sustainable mobility measures, clean vehicles, traffic management, info-mobility, promotional campaigns, project management skills, urban planning, superblock, e-ticketing, innovative energy sources, cities' collaboration, knowledge sharing
Case Studies	Craiova, Brescia, Coimbra, Vitoria-Gasteiz
<p>The project outlines a bold package of integrated measures in all the cities of the consortium, and covers all the areas required by the CIVITAS PLUS programme. The project shows ambitious goals which will have a substantial impact on the state of the mobility in the cities and a good visibility at the European level, mixing measures with large scale application actions based in existing and commercially available technologies, and measures with more advanced trials and methodologies.</p> <p>The project has common main targets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To increase the quality and the effectiveness of the public transport system (from the environmental and from the service point of view), increasing the number of users; • To limit the waste of energy and to support the diffusion of the use of clean fuels among the citizens; • To support the effort of improvement of public transport through a series of measure capable of limiting the circulation of private cars; • To give value at alternative “sweet” mobility modes improving safety and liveability for their users; • To lower the number of accidents on the roads; • To increase the technological endowment of the cities as a support to more and more intelligent mobility management policies and as a service to citizens; • To diffuse as much as possible the culture of an environmental sustainable mobility among citizens and to increase the social awareness of the vital importance of these themes. <p>The project has 49 different measures within 5 middle-size cities: Craiova (Romania - Project Coordinator), Brescia (Italy), Vitoria Gasteiz (Spain), Coimbra (Portugal), and Ostrava (Czech Republic) and 25 partners with all the Municipalities and all the local PT companies.</p> <p>Another crucial target is to assess a wide communication and debate among the cities at the level of political decision makers and important stakeholders, and a strong cooperation among scientists and technicians of the European team to circulate experiences and best practice.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/219041, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>	

MIMOSA

Project Full Title	Making Innovation in MObility and Sustainable Actions		
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/mimosa https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/218953 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/civitas-making-innovation-mobility-sustainable-actions		
Call	FP7-SST-2007-TREN-1_28June		
Project Coordinator	Municipality of Bologna / Comune di Bologna Manuela Marsano, Manuela.marsano@comunce.bologna.it		
Project Partners	<p>18 partners</p> <p>ATC S.p.A.</p> <p>City of Gdansk / Gdańsk / Gmina Miasta Gdanska</p> <p>City of Utrecht / Gemeente Utrecht</p> <p>Funchal Town Hall / Câmara Municipal do Funchal</p> <p>Horários do Funchal – Transportes Públicos SA</p> <p>Interactions Ltd</p> <p>Istituto di Studi per l’Integrazione dei Sistemi (I.S.I.S) – Società cooperativa</p> <p>Kamer van Koophandel Utrech (KVK)</p> <p>MASTERPLAN B.V.</p> <p>Municipality of Bologna / Comune di Bologna</p> <p>Polo Científico e Tecnológico da Madeira, Madeira Tecnopolo AS</p> <p>Regione Emilia Romagna</p> <p>SRM Reti e Mobilità S.p.A.</p> <p>SRM Reti e Mobilità s.r.l.</p> <p>Tallinna Linnatranspordi AS (Tallinna Autobussikoondise AS / Tallinn Bus Company, Tallinna Trammi- ja Trollibussikoondis / Tallinn Tram and Trolleybus Company)</p> <p>Technische Universität Berlin (TU Berlin) – Integrated Transport Planning</p> <p>The City of Tallinn / Tallinna Linn / Tallinn linnavalitsus</p> <p>Trasporto Passeggeri Emilia-Romagna (TPER S.p.A.)</p>		
Duration (months)	52		
Start date	15.10.2008	End date	14.02.2013
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		

Keywords	Sustainable urban mobility, quality of life, sharing of experiences, integrated innovative solutions, cleaner vehicles and fuels, public transport, pricing strategies for access control, road and parking management, car sharing, sustainable car usage, security and safety, walking and cycling, telematics systems, passenger and goods traffic management, marketing, citizen and stakeholder involvement, knowledge transfer, integration, impact evaluation, awareness raising, communication campaigns, policy assessment, cycling cities, ITS systems
Case Studies	Bologna, Funchal, Gdansk, Tallinn, Utrecht
<p>Since 2002, CIVITAS Initiative has been able to attract a raising interest among local authorities in Europe, becoming a true point of reference, even beyond the boundaries of the European Union. This is because worldwide, massive resources are poured into research and development of new solutions for a better urban environment. However, funds often target individual initiatives, which doubtlessly procure knowledge advancements in the fields of application. What sets CIVITAS apart is the integrative nature of the approach it advocates, based on comprehensive and innovative handling of energy and transport policy. The objectives of competitive, secure, safe, and environmentally friendly mobility must be conjugated and complemented with the involvement of national, regional and local governments, and that of citizens and industry. The partners of CIVITAS MIMOSA see in CIVITAS the ideal instrument to better understand the frameworks, processes and technicalities required to successfully introduce and test innovative, courageous and integrated strategies for a clean, energy-efficient and sustainable urban transport. The possibility to do so with a group of peers makes it all the more stimulating and meaningful, as it supplies local authorities with policies that are both validated by widespread experimentation and legitimised by the concurrent adoption in other cities. The CIVITAS MIMOSA approach is based on a clear set of measures that have been developed by: -Monitoring traffic flows and analysis of mobility demand and supply; -Identifying problems and opportunities; -Planning initiatives that public administrations and citizens can implement to tackle the problems; -Identify the most suitable demonstration actions for CIVITAS (i.e. a mix of tested good practices and bold, innovative actions), pushing citizens towards the desired behavioural shift; -Implement the actions and showcase them for replication or inspiration in other urban contexts.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/218953, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>	

DYN@MO

Project Full Title	DYNamic citizens @ctive for sustainable Mobility		
Website	https://www.rupprecht-consult.eu/project/civitas-dynmo https://civitas.eu/projects/dynmo https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/296057 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/civitas-dynmo		
Call	FP7-SST-CIVITAS-2011-MOVE		
Project Coordinator	City of Aachen / Stadt Aachen Georg Werdermann, georg.werdermann@mail.aachen.de		
Project Partners	<p>27 partners</p> <p>Aachener Straßenbahn und Energieversorgungs AG Aachener Verkehrsverbund GmbH Čazmatrans Koprivnica društvo s ograničenom odgovornošću za prijevoze i usluge City of Aachen / Stadt Aachen City of Gdynia / Gdynia-Miasto na prawach powiatu City of Koprivnica / Grad Koprivnica City of Turku / Turun kaupunki Consortio Eurolocal-Mallorca Fachhochschule Aachen (FH Aachen) – European Center for Sustainable Mobility (ECSM) Gdansk University of Technology / Politechnika Gdańska – Faculty of Civil and Environmental Engineering gewoge AG Gradsko Komunalno poduzeće Komunalac društvo s ograničenom odgovornošću (Komunalac d.o.o.) HŽ Infrastruktura d.o.o. KAMPUS d.o.o. Lund University – MAX IV Laboratory Przedsiębiorstwo Komunikacji Trolejbusowej Sp z o.o. Razvojna agencija Sjever – DAN Društvo za usluge privlačenja investicija, stvaranje radnih mjesta, izradu projekata za privlačenje sredstava fondova EU i obrazovanje d.o.o. (DAN d.o.o.) Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH RWTH Aachen University / Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen / RWTH Aachen Campus GmbH RWTH Aachen University / Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen / RWTH Aachen Campus GmbH – Chair and Institute of Urban and Transport Planning Societat municipal d'aparcaments i projectes SA (SMAP) Städtereion Aachen Stadtteilauto Car Sharing GmbH Stadtwerke Aachen Aktiengesellschaft Town Council of Palma de Mallorca / Ayuntamiento de Palma de Mallorca University of Gdansk / Uniwersytet Gdański – Department of Transportation Market University of the Balearic Islands / Universitat de les Illes Balears (UIB)</p>		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.12.2012	End date	30.11.2016

Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders
Keywords	<p>Sustainable interactive mobility planning, collaboration, new media, innovative transport services, Mobility 2.0, web 2.0 technologies, city and citizen-friendly electric mobility, electric and hybrid vehicles, citizen dialogue, citizen and stakeholder participation, ICT and ITS systems, new mobility services, exchange and training for decision makers, SUMP, clean public transport, alternative fuels</p>
Case Studies	<p>Leading cities: Aachen, Gdynia</p> <p>Learning cities: Palma de Mallorca, Koprivnica</p>
<p>CIVITAS-DYN@MO is an ambitious project with strategic importance to sustainable mobility planning in four dynamic European cities. Aachen (DE), Gdynia (PL), Koprivnica (HR) and Palma (ES) will jointly develop "Mobility 2.0" systems and services, implement city and citizen-friendly, electric mobility solutions and vehicles, and engage in a dynamic citizen dialogue for mobility planning and service improvement.</p> <p>CIVITAS-DYN@MO is targeting "dynamic citizens", and especially the "digital natives" in response to an emerging new mobility paradigm. A considerable part of the younger population in the DYN@MO university cities will be challenged to use web 2.0 apps to find appropriate means of travelling within the city and to communicate with PT operators.</p> <p>A sound basis for mobility planning is a citizen-centred Sustainable Urban Transport Plan. The two leading cities Aachen and Gdynia will advance their planning culture, while Koprivnica and Palma will develop ambitious sustainable urban transport plans – all involving extensively citizens and stakeholders via web2.0 applications.</p> <p>Clean public transport remains the backbone of urban transport systems, and the cities have strong commitment to enhance the environmental performance and energy efficiency of their fleets. Alternative fuels, such as CNG and hybrid buses, and the increased use of electromobility in public transport and car sharing schemes will help to accelerate the introduction of clean vehicles in the European market. Venturing in new technology and mobility options as well as promoting new life styles will increase the people’s acceptance for mobility without a private car.</p> <p>The cities propose complementing packages with a high degree of transferability across Europe. Profound evaluation and research with strong dissemination and mutual learning through SUTP Competence Centres will strengthen the strategic impact of the project.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/296057, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>	

2MOVE2

Project Full Title	New forms of sustainable urban transport and mobility		
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/2move2 https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/296036 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/new-forms-sustainable-urban-transport-and-mobility		
Call	FP7-SST-CIVITAS-2011-MOVE		
Project Coordinator	State capital Stuttgart / Landeshauptstadt Stuttgart Wolfgang Forderer, wolfgang.forderer@stuttgart.de		
Project Partners	8 partners Dopravní podnik města Brna AS (DPMB) Málaga City Council / Ayuntamiento de Málaga SSP Consult Beratende Ingenieure GmbH State capital Stuttgart / Landeshauptstadt Stuttgart Statutory city Brno / Statutární město Brno Technion – Israel Institute of Technology Tel Aviv Yafo Municipality University of Stuttgart		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.12.2012	End date	30.11.2016
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Leading and learning cities, knowledge exchange, sustainable energy-efficient urban transport systems, ICT and ITS-based traffic management, SUMPs, integration of personal collective and freight transport, accident avoidance, road pricing, smart payment systems, land-use, cycling and walking, public transport, e-mobility, mobility information services		
Case Studies	Stuttgart, Brno, Málaga, Tel Aviv-Yafo		
Mobility for each citizen as well as the transport of goods must be ensured in combination with a free choice of transport modes. However, actions of mobility management should be strengthened to raise people's awareness towards sustainable mobility.			

Due to changing conditions (e. g demographic development, rising energy costs, new ecological standards) new quality standards for an attractive pedestrian, bicycle, and public transport infrastructure are on the urban agenda in many cities.

The four cities Stuttgart, Brno, Malaga and Tel Aviv-Yafo decided to create more sustainable, clean and energy-efficient urban transport systems in their cities to establish new forms of mobility in a common approach for the benefit of all citizens, society and climate policy, respecting the environment and natural resources.

The development and implementation of similar projects and initiatives in the four cities will allow evaluating and comparing the results and impacts in the different contexts in the leading and learning cities. In addition, the measures in the four cities have been selected in a way that allows transfer and applicability to small- and medium-sized towns.

Specific emphasis has been given to the measures of e-mobility, freight and ITS-based traffic management. Also the continuous reflection of the proposed projects with the SUMP as well as with urban development plans is stressed.

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/296036>, retrieved 18 September 2024)

PASTA

Project Full Title	PHYSICAL ACTIVITY THROUGH SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT APPROACHES		
Website	https://www.pastaproject.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/602624 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/pasta/		
Call	FP7-HEALTH-2013-INNOVATION-1		
Project Coordinator	University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna / Universität für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU) – Institute for Transport Studies		
Project Partners	<p>15 partners</p> <p>Fundació Centre de Recerca en Epidemiologia Ambiental (CREAL)</p> <p>German Sports University of Cologne – Institute of Health Promotion and Clinical Movement Science</p> <p>Gesundheit Österreich Forschungs- und Planungs GmbH (GÖG)</p> <p>ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH / ICLEI Europasekretariat GmbH</p> <p>Imperial College London – Centre for Environmental Policy (CEP)</p> <p>Instituto de Salud Global de Barcelona (ISGlobal)</p> <p>London Borough of Newham</p> <p>Oxford University – Transport Studies Unit</p> <p>Roma Servizi per la Mobilità s.r.l. / Roma Mobilità</p> <p>Technische Universität Dresden (TU Dresden) – Chair of Mobility System Planning</p> <p>Trivector Traffic AB</p> <p>University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna / Universität für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU) – Institute for Transport Studies</p> <p>University of Zürich (UZH) – Epidemiology, Biostatistics, and Prevention Institute (EBPI)</p> <p>Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek (VITO NV)</p> <p>World Health Organisation (WHO) – Regional Office for Europe</p>		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.11.2013	End date	31.10.2017
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies 4. Support sustainable lifestyles <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 		
Keywords	Physical activity, transport and health, active mobility, walking, cycling, public transport, good practice, indicator set, traffic safety interventions, health impact assessment, cycling network		
Case Studies	Antwerp, Barcelona, London, Örebo, Rome, Vienna, Zurich		
This project focuses on the systematic promotion and facilitation of active mobility (AM) (i.e. walking and cycling including the combination with public transport use) as an innovative approach to integrate			

physical activity (PA) into individuals' everyday lives. In contrast to sports or exercise, AM requires less time and motivation, since AM provides both convenience as a mode of transport, and a healthy lifestyle. As such it has potential to reach parts of the population which have not been receptive to the appeals and benefits of sports and exercise.

The objectives of the project are the following:

- The project will review the literature on AM and identify innovative measures and systematic initiatives to promote AM as well as traffic safety interventions.
- A longitudinal study will be conducted to evaluate the ongoing AM initiatives combined with traffic safety interventions to better understand correlates of AM and their effects on overall PA, injury risk and exposure to air pollution.
- An improved user-friendly tool for more comprehensive health impact assessment (HIA) of AM will be developed.
- The tool will be applied to AM behavior observed in the case study cities and allow the assessment of health and economic impacts of measures.
- The project will also produce a compendium of good practices of AM promotion aimed at decision makers, implementing authorities, businesses, civil society organizations and end users.
- Findings and progress reports will be communicated to diverse target audiences, including policy makers, practitioners, researchers and end-users, through a number of media, i.e. reports, journals, brochures, web-content, workshops and presentations.

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/602624>, retrieved 26 September 2024)

Horizon 2020 Framework Programme (H2020)

<p>Website</p>	<p>https://wayback.archive-it.org/12090/20220124075100/https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/</p> <p>https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-2020_en</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020-EC</p> <p>https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/programme/horizon2020-eu-framework-programme-research-and-innovation</p> <p>https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/programme/horizon-2020-smart-green-and-integrated-transport</p>
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CIPTEC

Project Full Title	Collective Innovation for Public Transport in European Cities		
Website	http://cipotec.eu/ http://toolbox.cipotec.eu/ http://crowdsourcing.cipotec.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/cipotec https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/636412 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/collective-innovation-public-transport-european-cities		
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015		
Project Coordinator	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki / Panepistimio Thessalias / Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis (AUTH) – Transport Systems Research Group (TSRG) Prof. Dr. Aristotelis Naniopoulos, naniopou@civil.auth.gr wg@cipotec.eu		
Project Partners	12 partners Aristotle University of Thessaloniki / Panepistimio Thessalias / Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis (AUTH) – Transport Systems Research Group (TSRG) EMTA European Metropolitan Transport Authorities European Passengers' Federation IVZW (EPF) Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (KULeuven) – Reseach Centre for Marketing and Consumer Science Local Public Transport Authority of the City of Frankfurt am Main / traffiQ Lokale Nahverkehrsgesellschaft Frankfurt am Main mbH MemEx s.r.l. Metropolitan Region Rotterdam – The Hague / Metropoolregio Rotterdam Den Haag Mobycon B.V. Ortelio Ltd POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Tero Monoprosopi IKE / Tero Ltd TIEMME S.p.A. White Research s.r.l.		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.05.2015	End date	30.04.2018
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		

Keywords	Public transport innovation, service concepts, business models, user-centred marketing approach, consumer behaviour, collective intelligence, co-creation, user needs, crowdsourcing platform, evaluation
Case Studies	Workshops held in Frankfurt, Rotterdam, Southern Tuscany, Thessaloniki
<p>CIPTEC introduces an integrated approach which draws on the best ideas deriving from marketing (i.e. customer orientation, marketing research, consumer intelligence), consumer behaviour (i.e. advanced motivational research, behavioural experimentation), innovation (i.e. crowd sourcing, collective intelligence, co-creation and co-design of new ideas, fusion of business concepts with social innovation), evaluation (i.e. socioeconomic, technological and ethical) and co-exploitation within a wider than usual stakeholder platform attacking the challenges that hinder the public transport “environment” transition and re-orientation towards increasing PT market shares, thus substantially contributing to urban road congestion reduction in a sustainable manner.</p> <p>In the frame of CIPTEC, we study the demand side and how its needs are affected by the continuous storm of change but we take a close look to the supply in an attempt to demystify the needs and understand the distinct challenges PT providers face in tackling the same changes.. We dig out and map promising existing innovation from PT and adjacent fields but we also put forth a collective intelligence subprogram to crowd-source and co-produce novel approaches to tackle underserved needs. We survey public transport users to appreciate the finer differences in preferences for the promising innovations but we dig deeper looking for motivation triggers able to achieve natural behaviour change – not only in the lab but in real life. We provide a translation-in-a-box of our results but we don’t wait for stakeholders to use them; we work with them to motivate and apply these insights into concrete street-action. We invite the broader community to cooperate along the value chain but we bring along an unexpected ally – social entrepreneurs - to build and apply disruptive models of sustainable and replicable value.</p> <p>Our team is set to provide evidence and innovative tools for achieving growth in European public transport.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/636412, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>	

CityLab

Project Full Title	City Logistics in Living Laboratories
Website	https://www.citylab.soton.ac.uk/ https://civitas.eu/projects/citylab https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/635898 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/citylab/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/city-logistics-living-laboratories-0
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015
Project Coordinator	Institute of Transport Economics / Transportøkonomisk Institutt (TOI) Sidsel Ahlmann Jensen, saj@toi.no
Project Partners	<p>28 partners</p> <p>CEREMA Centre d'études et d'expertise sur les risques, l'environnement, la mobilité et l'aménagement / Centre for Studies on Risks, the Environment, Mobility and Urban Planning</p> <p>City of Oslo / Oslo Kommune</p> <p>City of Paris / Ville de Paris</p> <p>City of Rome / Roma Capitale / Comune di Roma</p> <p>German Aerospace Center / Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DLR)</p> <p>Gnewt Cargo Ltd</p> <p>Institute of Transport Economics / Transportøkonomisk Institutt (TOI)</p> <p>Koninklijke PostNL B.V.</p> <p>Meachers Global Logistics Ltd</p> <p>Meware s.r.l.</p> <p>Municipality of Rotterdam / Gemeente Rotterdam</p> <p>Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research / Nederlandse Organisatie voor toegepast-natuurwetenschappelijk onderzoek (TNO)</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>Poste Italiene S.p.A.</p> <p>Procter & Gamble Services Company NV</p> <p>Roma Servizi per la Mobilità s.r.l. / Roma Mobilità</p> <p>Service public régional de Bruxelles – Brussels Mobility / Bruxelles Mobilité (Administration de l'Équipement et des Déplacements)</p> <p>Southampton City Council</p> <p>Steen OG Strom Norge / Steen & Strøm</p> <p>The University of Westminster LBG – Transport and Mobilities Research Group</p> <p>TNT UK Ltd</p> <p>Transport for London</p> <p>Università degli Studi Roma Tre – Dipartimento di Scienze Politiche</p> <p>Université Gustave Eiffel – Laboratoire SPLOTT Systèmes Productifs, Logistique, Organisation des Transports et Travail</p> <p>University of Gothenburg / Göteborgs universitet</p> <p>University of Southampton – Transportation Research Group (TRG)</p> <p>Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Business technology and Operations</p> <p>Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electromobility research centre (MOBI)</p>

Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.05.2015	End date	30.04.2018
Key Area(s)	KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 1. Support thriving neighbourhood economies 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Emission-free city logistics, living laboratories, last-mile deliveries, urban waste, return trips, recycling, innovative solutions, business profitability, cost-effective policies, increased load factors, public and private measures, micro-hubs, cycle freight deliveries, electric vehicles, logistics hotels, consolidation		
Case Studies	Living Labs: Rotterdam, Amsterdam, Brussels, London, Oslo, Paris, Rome, Southampton Transfer Cities and Regions: Budapest, Delft, Flanders Region, Madrid, Manchester, Pisa, Prague, Rogaland Region, Turin Follower Cities and Regions: Antwerp, Gdynia, Gothenburg, Graz, L'Hospitalet, Mechelen, Milan, Skedsmo, West Midlands		
<p>Goods, waste and service trips in urban areas impose negative traffic and environmental impacts, and there is a need for cost-effective and sustainable solutions. The CITYLAB objective is to develop knowledge and solutions that result in up-scaling and roll-out of strategies, measures and tools for emission-free city logistics in urban centres by 2030. The project focuses on four axes for intervention:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly fragmented last-mile deliveries in city centres • Large freight attractors and public administrations • Urban waste, return trips and recycling • Logistics facilities and warehouses <p>CITYLAB aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve basic knowledge and understanding on areas of freight distribution and service trips in urban areas that have received too little attention to date • Test and implement seven innovative solutions that are promising in terms of impact on traffic, externalities and business profitability and have a high potential for future growth • Provide a platform for replication and spreading supported solutions <p>The core of CITYLAB is a set of living laboratories, where cities work as contexts for innovation and implementation processes for public and private measures contributing to increased efficiency and sustainable urban logistics. Linkages will be established between the different living labs for exchange of experiences and to develop methodologies for transfer of implementations between cities and between companies. The outputs from the living labs will include best practice guidance on innovative approaches and how to replicate them. CITYLAB will lay the groundwork for roll-out, up-scaling and transfer of cost-effective policies and implementations that lead to increased load factors and reduced vehicle movements of freight and service trips in urban areas.</p> <p>(https://www.citylab.soton.ac.uk/objectives.php, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>			

EMPOWER

Project Full Title	EMPOWERING a reduction in use of conventionally fueled vehicles using Positive Policy Measures.		
Website	https://environment.leeds.ac.uk/transport-research/dir-record/research-projects/749/empower-rewarding-change https://civitas.eu/projects/empower https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/636249 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/empowering-reduction-use-conventionally-fueled-vehicles-using-positive-policy-measures		
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015		
Project Coordinator	University of Leeds – Institute for Transport Studies Professor Susan Grant-Muller, S.M.Grant-Muller@its.leeds.ac.uk		
Project Partners	<p>13 partners</p> <p>Forum Virium Helsinki OY Mobidot B.V. Municipality Enschede / Gemeente Enschede Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research / Nederlandse Organisatie voor toegepast-natuurwetenschappelijk onderzoek (TNO) Pocketweb GmbH RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB – RISE Viktoria AB Sürdürülebilir Ulaşım ve Şehirler Derneği SWARCO Mobility Nedeland B.V. United Nations Human Settlements Programme University of Leeds – Institute for Data Analytics University of Leeds – Institute for Transport Studies University of Twente / Universiteit Twente (UT) – Department of Civil Engineering & Management (CEM) Wuppertal Institut für Klima, Umwelt, Energie gGmbH</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.05.2015	End date	30.04.2018
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <p>1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p> <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <p>4. Support sustainable lifestyles</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society</p>		
Keywords	conventionally fueled vehicles (CFV), influencing mobility behaviour, positive evidence-based and cost-effective policy interventions, innovative mobility services,		

	sustainable urban mobility, shared mobility, demand reduction, social network sharing schemes, positive incentives
Case Studies	4 living lab experiments, 7 City pilots
<p>The main objective of EMPOWER is to substantially reduce the use of conventionally fueled vehicles (CFV) in cities by influencing the mobility behaviour of CFV drivers and users towards fundamental change. To achieve this objective EMPOWER will create a set of tools for industry, policy makers and employers. These will empower them beyond the lifespan of this project to understand, help choose and successfully implement 'positive' evidence-based and cost-effective policy interventions, based on new and innovative mobility services, and in the context of already existing infrastructure, policy and measures. EMPOWER will reduce the use of CFV by: shifting trips to other modes/other vehicle types, promoting sharing and self-organisation and reducing demand overall e.g. through remote access to services. Undesirable impacts from CFV use will be reduced by: shifting CFV use to outside peak times and diversions to avoid particular areas/routes. The research will be multidisciplinary and involve: social science research with the public, 4 living lab experiments and 7 City demonstrators which will be chosen through an open 'bidding' process. The EMPOWER concept will be used in practice by: City stakeholders being able (through a software tool) to choose positive policy options based on their expected impacts and deliver incentives and social network sharing schemes to individuals using software. The innovation outputs of EMPOWER include an EMPOWER Toolkit to support industry, policy makers and employers to understand, choose and implement positive policy interventions. The Toolkit includes: new mobility services to provide innovative positive policy measures, new evidence on behavioural responses and impacts from positive incentives, improved organisational models for successful implementation of positive policy measures and innovation in the evaluation methodology for new mobility services. We expect at least 1 million persons to be impacted by EMPOWER.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/636249 18.09.2024)</p>	

FLOW

Project Full Title	Furthering Less Congestion by creating Opportunities for more Walking and cycling		
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/flow https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/635998 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/flow/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/furthering-less-congestion-creating-opportunities-more-walking-and-cycling		
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015		
Project Coordinator	Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH Bonnie Fenton, b.fenton@rupprecht-consult.eu Kristin Tovaa, k.tovaa@rupprecht-consult.eu		
Project Partners	<p>19 partners</p> <p>Access Associates Ltd</p> <p>BKK Centre for Budapest Transport / Budapesti Közlekedési Központ Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság</p> <p>Budapest University of Technology and Economics / Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem (BME)</p> <p>Bundesanstalt für Straßenwesen</p> <p>City of Gdynia / Gdynia-Miasto na prawach powiatu</p> <p>City of Munich / Landeshauptstadt München</p> <p>Dublin City Council</p> <p>European Cyclists Federation ASBL</p> <p>FEHRL Forum of European National Highway Research Laboratories / Forum des laboratoires européens de recherche routière AISBL</p> <p>Gdansk University of Technology / Politechnika Gdańska – Department of Transportation Engineering</p> <p>Lisbon City Council / Câmara Municipal de Lisboa</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>PTV Planung Transport Verkehr GmbH</p> <p>Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH</p> <p>Sistema – Soluzioni Per L Ingegneria Dei Sistema Di Trasporto E L Infomobilita s.r.l.</p> <p>Sofia Urban Mobility Centre EAD / Tsentar za Gradska Mobilnost EAD (SUMC)</p> <p>Traject NV</p> <p>TRL Transport Research Laboratory Ltd</p> <p>Wuppertal Institut für Klima, Umwelt, Energie gGmbH</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.05.2015	End date	30.04.2018
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred urban spaces and planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies 		

	KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments
Keywords	Active mobility, congestion reduction, effective walking and cycling measures, transport planning, traffic modelling, user-friendly methodology, methodology and congestion assessment tools, cycle-to-work campaigns
Case Studies	Budapest, Dublin, Gdynia, Lisbon, Munich, Sofia
<p>FLOW sees a need for a paradigm shift wherein non-motorised transport (often seen from a transport policy perspective simply as a nice “extra”) is placed on an equal footing with motorised modes with regard to urban congestion. To do this, FLOW will create a link between (currently poorly-connected) walking and cycling and congestion by developing a user-friendly methodology for evaluating the ability of walking and cycling measures to reduce congestion.</p> <p>FLOW will develop assessment tools to allow cities to evaluate effects of walking and cycling measures on congestion. Our aim is for the tools to become the standard for assessing the impact of walking and cycling measures on congestion. The tools include a congestion impact assessment (including socio-economic impact, an assessment of soft measures, congestion evaluation based on KPIs and a cost benefit analysis) and traffic modelling. Current modelling software will be calibrated and customised in FLOW partner cities to analyse the relationship of cyclist and pedestrian movements to congestion.</p> <p>The modelling and impact assessment will identify the congestion reducing effect of walking and cycling measures. FLOW partner cities will develop implementation scenarios and action plans for adding or up-scaling measures that are shown to reduce congestion. FLOW will target three distinct audiences, with appropriate materials and messaging for each. Cities will learn about the value and use of new transport modelling tools, businesses will be made aware of the potential market in congestion busting products and services and decision makers will be provided with facts to argue for walking and cycling to be put on equal footing with other modes of transport. FLOW will meet the challenge of “significantly reducing urban road congestion and improving the financial and environmental sustainability of urban transport” by improving the understanding of walking and cycling measures that have potential to reduce urban congestion.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/635998, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>	

SUCCESS

Project Full Title	Sustainable Urban Consolidation Centres for construction		
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/success-0 https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/633338 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/sustainable-urban-consolidation-centres-construction		
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015		
Project Coordinator	Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST) Francesco Ferrero, francesco.ferrero@list.lu		
Project Partners	<p>11 partners</p> <p>Association pour le développement de la formation professionnelle dans le transport (AFT) C.M.B. Società cooperativa Muratori e Braccianti di Carpi (CMB) Federación Valenciana de Empresarios de la Construcción (FEVEC) Fundación de la Comunidad Valenciana para la Investigación, Promoción y Estudios Comerciales de Valenciaport Fundación de la Comunidad Valenciana para la Promoción Estratégica, el Desarrollo y la Innovación Urbana Institute for Transport and Logistics Foundation / Fondazione Istituto sui trasporti e la logistica (ITL) Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST) Regione Emilia Romagna Tralux Société Générale de Travaux – Luxembourg SARL Università degli studi di Modena e Reggio Emilia (Unimore) Vinci Construction France</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.05.2015	End date	30.04.2018
Key Area(s)	<p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		
Keywords	Sustainable urban logistics, urban construction logistics, construction consolidation centre (CCC), clean vehicles, supply chain management, increased load factor, cost/benefit analysis tool		
Case Studies	Luxembourg, Paris, Valencia, Verona		
<p>Currently freight transport represents 40% of the total transport emission and 32% in urban area. Many initiatives are under development to reduce costs and negative impact of freight and service trip in urban area. Some of them concern supply chain improvements and more specifically consolidation centre projects. Few study cases are dedicated to construction industry.</p>			

However, urban population tends to grow, increasing the need to develop and reconstruct urban centres. Construction material logistic impact in urban area will intensify in terms of costs and negative impacts in urban area. Yet, only few experiences of Construction Consolidation Centres can be found.

Among these initiatives, four are construction site specific (Stockholm, Utrecht, Berlin, London Heathrow) and only one is dedicated to several construction projects (London CC). These pilots studies have demonstrated reduced transportation impacts, positive effects on transportation efficiency and construction site productivity.

Several limitations to the transferability of this concept are identified: one on hand the demonstrators were implemented in specific contexts (regulatory incentives, cities investment contribution, and specific transport and logistics infrastructure issues) which are not the same in France, Spain, Italy and Luxembourg. On the other hand, economic viability has not been demonstrated.

The project addresses the different requirements for transferability of supply chain optimization concepts as well as CCCs and new ways of working between supply chain stakeholders. The approach is to identify an integrated collaborative approach and business model among construction supply chain actors. Three main steps will be performed: analyse the current issues along the construction supply chain, propose several optimization scenarios regarding these issues, simulate and analyse costs optimization and environmental impacts to propose new partnership opportunities based on savings distribution.

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/633338>, retrieved 18 September 2024)

CREATE

Project Full Title	Congestion Reduction in Europe : Advancing Transport Efficiency		
Website	http://create-mobility.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/create https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/636573 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/congestion-reduction-europe-advancing-transport-efficiency		
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015		
Project Coordinator	University College London (UCL) – Department of Civil, Environment & Geomatic Engineering Peter Jones, peter.jones@ucl.ac.uk (Adams et al., 2019)		
Project Partners	18 partners Adana Metropolitan Municipality Berlin – Senate Department for Urban Development, Building und Housing / Senatsverwaltung für Stadtentwicklung City of Skopje Copenhagen Municipality / Københavns Kommune COWI AS Eurocities ASBL European Integrated Project Fondation Nationale des Sciences Politiques (Sciences Po) Greater Amman Municipality INRIX UK Ltd l'Institut d'aménagement et d'urbanisme de la région d'Île-de-France / L'Institut Paris Region Municipality of Bucharest / Municipiul București Technische Universität Dresden (TU Dresden) – Chair of Mobility System Planning The City of Tallinn / Tallinna Linn / Tallinn linnavalitsus Transport for London University College London (UCL) – Department of Civil, Environment & Geomatic Engineering University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna / Universität für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU) – Institute for Transport Studies Vectos (South) Ltd		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.06.2015	End date	31.05.2018
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		

Keywords	Congestion, transport efficiency, place-based cities, household travel patterns, policy responses, reduction of car use, public spaces, capacity building, SUMP, sustainable mobility, MaaS, smart city
Case Studies	Berlin, Copenhagen, London, Paris, Vienna, Adana, Amman, Bucharest, Skopje, Tallinn
<p>CREATE addresses the task Tackling Urban Road Congestion, taking a long-term view of how this can be achieved, especially in cities experiencing rapid growth in car ownership and use. It deals with most of the issues set out in the recent Urban Mobility Package.</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rigorously and systematically develop practical definitions of urban road congestion and of network performance, and identify factors influencing conditions in different cities. • Work with Western European (WE) cities that have succeeded in decoupling traffic growth from economic growth, to analyse quantitatively the objective factors which have contributed to this, and the qualitative factors which have enabled a policy evolution from ‘supporting traffic growth’ to ‘encouraging sustainable mobility’. • Develop concrete guidance and provide capacity building for cities in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE), and the EuroMed region, enabling them to move rapidly to develop a feasible, effective and deliverable Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (SUMP). • Anticipating future pressures on city transport systems (congestion and overcrowding), to investigate how new transport technologies might increase transport efficiency, and how non-transport technologies and changes in business and social practices could reduce pressures on transport systems. <p>These objectives will be achieved by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysing congestion and network performance data provided by INRIX and WE cities. • Using detailed household travel data from repeat surveys in WE cities since the 1970s/1980s and complementary data on network, economic and demographic conditions; and documents setting out historical policy development. • Preparing detailed guidance and training for our CEE cities, which will then be delivered to a much larger set of cities. • Working with leading technology providers, businesses and futurists, to explore what options there might be to provide high quality mobility in cities facing increasing population and employment. <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/636573, retrieved 18 September 2024)</p>	

ELIPTIC

Project Full Title	Electrification of public transport in cities
Website	https://www.rupprecht-consult.eu/project/eliptic https://civitas.eu/projects/eliptic https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/636012 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/eliptic/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/electrification-public-transport-cities
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015
Project Coordinator	Free Hanseatic City of Bremen / Freie Hansestadt Bremen Michael Glotz-Richter, eliptic@UMWELT.Bremen.de (Adams et al., 2019)
Project Partners	<p>34 partners</p> <p>ASSTRA – Associazione Trasporti Barcelona de Serveis Municipals SA (B:SM) Barnimer Busgesellschaft mbH Bremer Straßenbahn AG / Bremen Straßenbahn AG Centre Internacional de Mètodes Numèrics en Enginyeria Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V. Free Hanseatic City of Bremen / Freie Hansestadt Bremen International Association of Public Transport / Union Internationale des Transports Publics (UITP) Irizar S Coop Kiepe Electric GmbH Leipziger Verkehrsbetriebe (LVB) GmbH Low Carbon Vehicle Partnership (LowCVP) / Zemo Partnership Łukasiewicz Research Network / Sieć Badawcza Łukasiewicz – Automotive Industry Institute / Przemysłowy Instytut Motoryzacji Miejskich Zakładów Autobusowych SP z o.o. (MZA) POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Przedsiębiorstwo Komunikacji Trolejbusowej Sp z o.o. Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH RWTH Aachen University / Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen / RWTH Aachen Campus GmbH – Institute for Power Electronics and Electrical Drives Siemens Aktiengesellschaft Società Unica Abruzzese di Trasporto S.p.A. Unipersonale Solaris Bus & Coach Spółka z ograniczoną odpowiedzialnością STIB-MIB Société des Transports Intercommunaux de Bruxelles / Maatschappij voor het Intercommunale Vervoer te Brussel STOAG Stadtwerke Oberhausen GmbH Szegedi Közlekedési Kft (SZKT) Transport for London Transports de Barcelona SA / Transports Metropolitans de Barcelona (TMB) trolley:motion – Verein zur Förderung moderner Trolleybussysteme Università degli studi di Roma La Sapienza – Ingegneria Civile Edile e Ambientale University of Gdansk / Uniwersytet Gdański – Department of Transportation Market</p>

	University of Szeged / Szegedi Tudományegyetem – Faculty of Engineering Verband Deutscher Verkehrsunternehmen Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electrical Engineering and Power Electronics Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electromobility research centre (MOBI) Ziehl-Abegg SE		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.06.2015	End date	31.05.2018
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Electric mobility, electric public transport, sustainable mobility, SUMP, transport electrification, cost-efficiency, business cases, energy storage systems, multi-purpose use of infrastructure, integration of electricity grids, guidelines, decision-making support tools, stakeholder and user forum		
Case Studies	Warsaw, Szeged, London, Brussels, Bremen, Gdynia, Barcelona		
<p>The overall aim of ELIPTIC is to develop new use concepts and business cases to optimise existing electric infrastructure and rolling stock, saving both money and energy. ELIPTIC will advocate electric public transport sector at the political level and help develop political support for the electrification of public transport across Europe. ELIPTIC looks at three thematic pillars:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safe integration of e-buses into existing electric PT infrastructure through (re)charging e-buses “en route”, upgrading trolleybus networks with battery buses or trolleyhybrids and automatic wiring/de-wiring technology • upgrading and/or regenerating electric public transport systems (flywheel, reversible substations) • Multi-purpose use of electric public transport infrastructure: safe (re)charging of non-public transport vehicles (pedelecs, electric cars/ taxis, utility trucks) <p>With a strong focus on end users, ELIPTIC will analyse 23 use cases within the three thematic pillars. The project will support uptake and exploitation of results by developing guidelines and tools for implementation schemes for upgrading and/or regenerating electric public transport systems. Option generator and decision-making support tools, strategies and policy recommendations will be created to foster Europe-wide take up and rollout of various development schemes. Partners and other cities will benefit from ELIPTIC's stakeholder and user forum approach.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/636012, retrieved 19 September 2024)</p>			

NOVELOG

Project Full Title	New cooperative business models and guidance for sustainable city logistics
Website	http://www.novelogtool.imet.gr https://civitas.eu/projects/novelog https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/636626 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/novelog/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/new-cooperative-business-models-and-guidance-sustainable-city-logistics
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015
Project Coordinator	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT) Dr. Georgia Aifandopoulo, elpixenou@certh.gr Elpida Xenou, gea@certh.gr novelogoffice@certh.gr
Project Partners	29 partners ADDMA S.A Athens Development and Destination Management Agency / Etairia Anaptyxis Kai Touristikis Provolis Athinon – Anaptyxiaki Anonymos Etaireia Organismou Topikis Aftodiokisis Aristotle University of Thessaloniki / Panepistimio Thessalias / Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis (AUTH) B.I.M. Beratung und Informationsverarbeitung im Mobilitätsbereich – Frantz, König und Schallaböck OG Barcelona Municipality / Ajuntament de Barcelona Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT) Centre International de Mètodes Numèrics en Enginyeria City of Gothenburg / Goteborgs Kommun / Göteborgs Stad City of Graz / Stadt Graz City of Mechelen / Stad Mechelen City of Turin / Comune di Torino Copenhagen Municipality / Københavns Kommune European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation – Intelligent Transport Systems & Services Europe (ERTICO – ITS Europe) Hellenic Train – Anonymi Sidirodromiki Etaireia Institute for Transport and Logistics Foundation / Fondazione Istituto sui trasporti e la logistica (ITL) IRU Projects ASBL / The International Road Transport Union Kühne+Nagel Societe Anonyme for Transports & Logistics London Borough of Barking and Dagenham Maritime University of Szczecin / Politechnika Morska w Szczecinie – Faculty of Economics and Transport Engineering Municipality of Pisa / Comune di Pisa Panteia B.V. POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Regione Emilia Romagna Renault SAS RINA Consulting S.p.A.

	Roma Servizi per la Mobilità s.r.l. / Roma Mobilità Synergy in Supply Chain Anonimi Etairia Systimatou Efodiastiki Alysidas Università degli studi di Roma La Sapienza – Centro di Ricerca CTL University of Newcastle upon Tyne – Freight Logistics and Sustainable Supply Chains (SCM) Venice International University (VIU) – TeDIS		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.06.2015	End date	31.05.2018
Key Area(s)	KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Sustainable city logistics, cooperative business models, urban freight transportation (UFT) measures and policies, Understanding the Cities Tool (UCT), cost-effective and eco-friendly measures, governance and co-operation, sustainable policy-making and mobility planning, SUMP		
Case Studies	Athens, Barcelona, Copenhagen, Emilia-Romagna Region, Gothenburg, Graz, London, Mechelen, Pisa, Rome, Turin, Venice		
<p>Urban areas represent the greatest challenges for freight transport and service trips, both in terms of goods distribution and service allocation performance, and environmental impacts (air emission, traffic congestion, road safety, accidents and noise). The salient scope of the proposal is the enabling of knowledge and understanding of freight distribution and service trips by providing guidance for implementing effective and sustainable policies and measures. This guidance will support the choice of the most optimal and applicable solutions for urban freight and service transport, and will facilitate stakeholder collaboration and the development, field testing and transfer of best governance and business models.</p> <p>This shall be achieved through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the targeted understanding of urban freight and service trips, fostered by data collection on city logistics, • field testing and implementation of representative city logistics measures, • the development and application of a modular, integrated, evaluation framework for the assessment of these measures • the development of a typology between cities and potential city logistics components, and • the provision of guidance to cities, shaping consistent implementation channels for successful solutions, all according to the local needs and constraints. <p>These activities will be accompanied by the production of practical tools that could support the take-up impact of NOVELOG project to wider international city and industrial networks and beyond the project's lifetime. NOVELOG will contribute to the European Commission's research and policy agenda through the generation of sound knowledge that introduces a new approach to guidance strategies that supports a more sustainable urban environment.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/636626, retrieved 19 September 2024)</p>			

TRACE

Project Full Title	Opening the cycling and walking tracking potential		
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/trace https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/635266 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/opening-cycling-and-walking-tracking-potential		
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015		
Project Coordinator	INESC ID Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores – Investigação e Desenvolvimento em Lisboa Paulo Ferreira, paulo.ferreira@inesc-id.pt		
Project Partners	12 partners Energy Agency of Plovdiv Association (EAP) IJsberg Holding B.V. INESC ID Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores – Investigação e Desenvolvimento em Lisboa LuxMobility S.A.R.L. Mobiel 21 vzw Municipality Breda / Gemeente Breda Municipality of Agueda / Município de Águeda POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Southend-on-Sea Borough Council SRM Reti e Mobilitàà s.r.l. TIS PT Consultores em Transportes, Inovação e Sistemas SA University of Belgrad / Univerzitet u Beogradu – Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering / Saobraćajni fakultet		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.06.2015	End date	31.05.2018
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Promote walking and cycling, ICT-based tracking services, flexible open access tools, ICT challenges, citizen and stakeholder involvement		
Case Studies	Agueda, Belgrade, Breda, Esch, Flanders, Plovdiv, Southend-on-Sea		
This project will explore the potential of walking and cycling tracking services to promote walking and cycling mobility. We will focus on established walking and cycling promotion measures and thoroughly assess the potential of ICT based tracking services to overcome barriers to implementation and finding			

new factors driving the effectiveness of those measures. Through specific research, the related ICT challenges like scheme dynamics, privacy, trust, low-cost, interoperability and flexibility will be tackled for each type of measure. The measures to target will be established measures to promote walking and cycling travel to workplace, shopping, school and leisure promotion measures. We will investigate both the ability that tracking tools may have to address traditional challenges of these measures and their potential to bring new features in the fields of awareness raising, financial/tax incentives, infrastructure planning and service concepts. A common, flexible and open access tool will be developed to provide an ICT input and output platform that addresses the related ICT challenges. Over this platform it will be easy for anyone to build products based on tracking services tailored to the requirements of the specific measures. This project will develop and test a representative set of such products in real measures underway. These test cases will at the same time validate and provide additional inputs for the project's research issues and trigger the widespread of tracking services to support walking and cycling measures in Europe. Users, policy makers and walking and cycling practitioners and final users will be deeply involved in all stages of the project.

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/635266>, retrieved 19 September 2024)

U-TURN

Project Full Title	Rethinking Urban Transportation through advanced tools and supply chain collaboration		
Website	https://u-turn-project.eu/about.html https://civitas.eu/projects/u-turn https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/635773 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/rethinking-urban-transportation-through-advanced-tools-and-supply-chain-collaboration		
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015		
Project Coordinator	Netcompany-Intrasoft		
Project Partners	<p>11 partners</p> <p>Athens University of Economics and Business – Research Center Barilla G. e R. Fratelli S.p.A. Barilla Hellas Anonumi Viomichanikiemporiki Etaireia Trofimon Cranfield University – Cranfield School of Management LCP Consulting Ltd Netcompany-Intrasoft Netcompany-Intrasoft SA OPTILOG Advisory Services IKE SimPlan AG Technical University of Dortmund / Technische Universität Dortmund (TUDO) – IT in Production and Logistics TRT Trasporti e Territorio s.r.l.</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.06.2015	End date	31.05.2018
Key Area(s)	<p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Support striving neighbourhood economies 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		
Keywords	Urban logistics, urban food transportation, shared logistics, freight distribution, innovative business models, environmentally and economically efficient operations, collaboration platform		
Case Studies	Pilot initiatives: Athens, Milan, London		
<p>The U-TURN project aims at addressing freight urban distribution, focusing on food logistics. The project will contribute to our understanding of freight distribution in urban areas, especially addressing the special requirements and needs of food transportation, and will suggest innovative collaboration practices and tools towards achieving more efficient operations from both an environmental and cost perspective. The project will analyse existing freight urban flows, identify synergies and winning logistics sharing and collaboration strategies and will assess them in three ways: through comparative analysis based on actual</p>			

market data, through simulation experimentation and via pilot execution in four different countries: Germany, UK, Italy and Greece. U-TURN will further contribute to the adoption of these strategies through managerial assessment, quantifiable benefits and the provision of tools, including a "smart" transport matching tool, a collaboration platform, a simulation tool and economic assessment model.

The project aims to exploit the opportunities that currently exist for consolidation of transportation flows from food manufacturers to the various point-of-sales located in urban areas, as well as from local food producers and online retailers directly to consumers, and the high industrial interest behind this topic.

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/635773>, retrieved 19 September 2024)

DESTINATIONS

Project Full Title	
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/destinations https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/689031 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/civitas-destinations
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015
Project Coordinator	Horários do Funchal – Transportes Públicos SA Claudio Mantero, claudiomantero@horariosdofunchal.pt
Project Partners	<p>32 partners</p> <p>Agência Regional da Energia e Ambiente da Região Autónoma da Madeira (AREAM) ARDITI Agência Regional para o Desenvolvimento da Investigação, Tecnologia e Inovação Authority for Transport in Malta Beijing University of Technology CINESI S.L. City Council of Las palmas de Grancanaria / Ayuntamiento de Las Palmas de Grancanaria City of Rethymnon / Dimos Rethimnis Conférence des régions périphériques maritimes d’Europe (CRPM) Euro Project Consult SARL European Integrated Project Funchal Town Hall / Câmara Municipal do Funchal Guaguas Municipales Sociedad Anonima Horários do Funchal – Transportes Públicos SA Ingenieria Electronica Canaria S.L. Insight Innovation GmbH Istituto di Studi per l’Integrazione dei Sistemi (I.S.I.S) – Società cooperativa Limassol Municipality / Dimos Lemesos Limassol Tourism Development and Promotion Co. Ltd. / Etairia touristikis Anaptixis Kai Provolis Periferias Lemesou Limited MemEx s.r.l. Ministry for Tourism and Consumer Protection (Malta) Municipality of Portoferraio / Comune di Portoferraio Municipality of Rio / Comune di Rio Secretaria Regional de Turismo e Cultura (SRTC) Sociedad Municipal de Aparcamientos de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria SA Stratagem Energy Ltd sustainable Services S.L. Technical University of Crete / Polytechnio Kritis (TUC) – Interactive Technologies Institute University of Malta / Università ta' Malta (UM) – Institute for Climate Change & Sustainable Development (ICCSA) Valletta Local Council Vectos (South) Ltd Vectos GmbH Vice-presidência do Governo Regional da Madeira</p>

Duration (months)	47 months		
Start date	01.09.2016	End date	31.05.2021
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		
Keywords	Sustainable tourism and mobility strategies, island locations, quality of life, SUMP, SULPs, accessible public space, behavioural change, shared mobility and e-mobility, managed mobility demand, re-allocation of urban space, efficient and accessible public transport, COVID-19 pandemic		
Case Studies	Elba, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Limassol, Madeira, Rethymno, Valletta Region		
<p>While European economies in the Mediterranean increasingly rely on tourism, many towns lack the necessary resources and tailored services to effectively deliver sustainable mobility solutions to both residents and tourists. Transportation poses crucial and challenging problems in most tourist destinations. To address this issue, the EU-funded DESTINATIONS project aims to provide green, smart, and flexible transportation proposals, as well as establish effective private-public collaboration schemes and business models. The project will implement integrated innovative mobility solutions in Madeira, Limassol, Rethymno, Valletta, Elba, and Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, targeting the mobility demands of residents and tourists. It will deliver sustainable mobility tools and strategies while also demonstrating and evaluating the effectiveness of each of the six proposed solutions.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/689031, retrieved 19 September 2024)</p>			

ECCENTRIC

Project Full Title	Innovative solutions for sustainable mobility of people in suburban city districts and emission free freight logistics in urban centres.
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/eccentric https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690699 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/innovative-solutions-sustainable-mobility-people-suburban-city-districts-and-emission-free
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015
Project Coordinator	City Council of Madrid / Ayuntamiento de Madrid Francisco José López Carmona, lopezcfjo@madrid.es
Project Partners	<p>32 partners</p> <p>AVIA Ingeniería y Diseño CarShare Ventures B.V. City Council of Madrid / Ayuntamiento de Madrid City of Munich / Landeshauptstadt München City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad City of Turku / Turun kaupunki Club Sustainable Development of Civil Society Association Consortio Regional de Transportes Públicos Regulares de Madrid Cykelkonsulterna Svergie AB Empresa Municipal de Transportes de Madrid (EMT Madrid) FlexiDrive Sverige AB FM Logistic Corporate FM Logistic Ibérica S.L. Gasum Biovakka OY GomagkPark Genossenschaft EG GoMore APS Green City e.V. Green City Experience GmbH Grupo de estudios y alternativas GEA 21 ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH / ICLEI Europasekretariat GmbH Ingeniería y consultoría para el control automático (ICCA) KTH Royal Institute of Technology / Kungliga Tekniska högskolan – Department of Engineering Design Mobility Motors Sweden AB Municipality of Rouse / Obshtina Ruse / Община Русе Regional Council of Southwest Finland / Varsinais-Suomen liitto Stadtwerke München GmbH Technical University of Munich / Technische Universität München (TUM) – Chair of Urban Structure and Transport Planning Turku University of Applied Sciences / Turun ammattikorkeakoulu OY Turun Kaupunkiliikenne OY UbiGo Innovation AB Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) – Centro de Investigación del Transporte (TRANSyT) Western Systems OY</p>

Duration (months)	51		
Start date	01.09.2016	End date	30.11.2020
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space 4. Support sustainable lifestyles <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 		
Keywords	Sustainable mobility in peripheral areas, suburban districts, sustainable urban logistics, active mobility, public transport connectivity, inclusive urban planning, parking policies, neglected groups, planning process, co-creation, MaaS, safe walking and cycling, electric vehicles, new shared mobility solutions, economically viable supply chains, consolidation centres, cargo bikes, SUMP		
Case Studies	Munich, Madrid, Ruse, Stockholm, Turku		
<p>The cities of Madrid, Stockholm, Munich, Turku and Ruse have formed the CIVITAS ECCENTRIC consortium to tackle the challenges of mobility in suburban districts and clean, silent and CO2 free city logistics. In many cities, these two important areas have received less attention in urban mobility policies. [...]</p> <p>ECCENTRIC will demonstrate and test the potential and replicability of integrated and inclusive urban planning approaches, innovative policies and emerging technologies to reach sustainable urban mobility objectives. The solutions will be implemented in 5 living laboratory areas in the outskirts that face high population growth and an increasing pressure on the existing transport networks.</p> <p>As highlighted in the SUMPs of the ECCENTRIC cities, this action on a wider geographical scale than the city centre is needed in order to meet the targets of the Transport White Paper in terms of air quality, energy use and CO2 emissions, road casualties and wide uptake of clean vehicles.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690699, retrieved 19 September 2024)</p>			

PORTIS

Project Full Title	PORT-Cities: Integrating Sustainability
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/portis https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690713 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/port-cities-integrating-sustainability
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015
Project Coordinator	City of Antwerp / Stad Antwerpen Marijke De Roeck, Marijke.DeRoeck@stad.Antwerpen.be Marjolein Salens, Marjolein.Salens@stad.Antwerpen.be
Project Partners	35 partners Aberdeen City Council Aberdeen Harbour Board Aberdeenshire Council AREA Science Park / Area di Ricerca Scientifica e Tecnologica di Trieste Asociația "Cluster" pentru Promovarea Afacerilor Specializate în Ecotehnologii și Surse Alternative de Energie (Regiunea Sud-Est și Regiunea București-Ilfov) (MEDGreen Cluster) Asociația de Dezvoltare Intercomunitară Zona Metropolitană Constanța Austrian Mobility Research / Forschungsgesellschaft Mobilität (FGM) – AMOR Gemeinnützige GmbH Autorità di Sistema Portuale del Mare Adriatico Orientale (AdSP del Mare Adriatico Orientale) Beheersmaatschappij Antwerpen Mobiel (Lantis) Center of Strategies for Youth Development / Asociația Centrul European pentru Dezvoltarea City of Antwerp / Stad Antwerpen City of Trieste / Comune di Trieste Compania Nationala Administrația Porturilor Maritime SA Constanta Constanta Municipal Council / Municipiul reședință de județ Constanța European Integrated Project Istituto di Studi per l'Integrazione dei Sistemi (I.S.I.S) – Società cooperativa Klaipeda City Municipality Administration / Klaipėdos Miesto Savivaldybės Administracija Ningbo University North East Transport Partnership (Nestrans) Ovidius University of Constanta / Universitatea Ovidius din Constanța Port of Antwerp-Bruges / Haven van Antwerpen-Brugge Province of Antwerp / Provincie Antwerpen Robert Gordon University (RGU) – School of Creative & Cultural Business Robert Gordon University (RGU) – Scott Sutherland School of Architecture & Built Environment Smart Continent LT UAB Société nationale des chemins de fer belges (SNCB) Traject NV Transport & Mobility Leuven (TML) NV Trieste Trasporti S.p.A. Università degli studi di Trieste University of Aberdeen Vectos (South) Ltd Vectos GmbH

	Viešoji įstaiga Klaipėdos kelevinis transportas Vlaamse Vervoersmaatschappij (VVM) De Lijn		
Duration (months)	51 months		
Start date	01.09.2016	End date	30.11.2020
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 3. Provide sustainable solutions for longer trips 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies 4. Support sustainable lifestyles <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		
Keywords	Sustainable mobility, port cities, governance, cooperation platforms, participatory decision-making process, SUMP, collective and active transport, shared mobility, hard and soft measures, user needs, Intelligent Transport Systems, IT solutions, efficient road traffic management, parking management, electric vehicles, efficient city-port freight		
Case Studies	Aberdeen, Antwerp, Constanta, Klaipeda, Trieste Follower: Ningbo		
<p>Port cities are unique urban environments that combine the best of both worlds – sea and land – and are thus ideal testing grounds for multidimensional urban mobility solutions. The EU-funded PORTIS project will design, demonstrate and assess integrated sets of sustainable mobility solutions in five major port cities located on the North Sea (Aberdeen and Antwerp), the Mediterranean Sea (Trieste), the Black Sea (Constanța) and the Baltic Sea (Klaipėda), and in a major international follower port city on the East China Sea (Ningbo). The project aims to demonstrate that more efficient and sustainable mobility is instrumental in establishing vital and multimodal hubs for urban, regional, national and international mobility.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690713, retrieved 19 September 2024)</p>			

PROSPERITY

Project Full Title	Prosperity through innovation and promotion of Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans		
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/prosperity https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690636 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/prosperity-through-innovation-and-promotion-sustainable-urban-mobility-plans		
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015		
Project Coordinator	Forschungsgesellschaft Mobilität / Austrian Mobility Research (FGM) – AMOR Gemeinnützige GmbH Robert Pressl, pressl@fgm.at		
Project Partners	26 partners Aplinkosaugos valdymo ir technologijų centras Viešoji įstaiga (ECAT) Asociația Orașe în mișcare Austrian Mobility Research / Forschungsgesellschaft Mobilität (FGM) – AMOR Gemeinnützige GmbH Centrum dopravního výzkumu v.v.i. / Transport Research Centre (CDV) City of Dubrovnik / Grad Dubrovnik City of Fagaras / Municipiul Făgăraș City of Koprivnica / Grad Koprivnica City of Szeged / Szeged Megyei Jogú Város Önkormányzatának Club Sustainable Development of Civil Society Association Deutsches Institut für Urbanistik gGmbH Grupo de estudios y alternativas GEA 21 Instituto da Mobilidade e dos Transportes Terrestres I.P. / Institute for Mobility and Transport (IMT, I.P.) Jonava District Municipality / Jonavos rajono savivaldybės administracija Limassol Municipality / Dimos Lemesos Lisbon City Council / Câmara Municipal de Lisboa Michnej Maciej Mobiel 21 vzw Mobilissimus Korlátolt felelősségű társaság Municipality of Kassel / Magistrat der Stadt Kassel Municipality of Katowice / Katowice – Miasto na prawach powiatu Municipality of Ljutomer / Občina Ljutomer Municipality of Varna / Obshtina Varna Statutory city of Hradec Králové / Statutární město Hradec Králové Stratagem Energy Ltd TRT Trasporti e Territorio s.r.l. Urban Planning Institute of the Republic of Slovenia / Urbanistični inštitut Republike Slovenije (UIRS)		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.09.2016	End date	31.08.2019
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility		

	<p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p> <p>3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>
Keywords	SUMPs, national SUMP Task Forces, mobility planning, capacity building, knowledge transfer, regional and national authorities, National SUMP Support Programmes
Case Studies	<p>“Champion Cities”</p> <p>Partner cities: Hradec Kralove, Limassol, Lisbon, Szeged, Varna, Ljutomer, Sint-Niklaas, Dubrovnik</p>
<p>PROSPERITY will:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Produce a culture shift in terms of environment for SUMPs in member states and in the organisational culture of transport planning in city authorities. 2. Get ministries and national agencies to play a national leading role on SUMPs, as in many member states these are the organisations from which cities take their main direction; where ministries are already playing this role, to support and strengthen their approach. 3. To provide mechanisms and tools for Ministries to take this lead role. 4. Analyse clearly the problems of (lack of) take-up of SUMPs – to understand from cities themselves why they are not taken up and then to help cities to address these barriers. 5. Extend the existing 25-county EU-SUMP-network with at least two more countries 6. Get more cities to take up effective high quality SUMPs – through cities’ involvement in the project and indirectly through more cities hearing about SUMPs in their country. 7. Ensure that these SUMPs contain and will lead to implementation of a broad range of innovative sustainable transport measures. 8. Build cities’ capacity to develop and implement SUMPs that genuinely reflect the spirit of the EU SUMP Guidelines, rather than being mandatory documents to fulfil a requirement linked to major transport infrastructure. 9. Deliver a measurable impact. <p>The core concept of PROSPERITY is bringing ministries into the project, which will significantly enhance the visibility of the project at the national level and therefore increase numbers of cities active on SUMPs. Thus PROSPERITY will ensure that more cities commit to SUMPs that are in line with the EU SUMP Guidelines and that include a broad range of innovative measures. This will generate a high leverage factor, especially in regions and cities where take up is so far low and the impacts from transport are severe – therefore the majority of PROSPERITY activities is in such regions and cities - thus in southern, central-eastern and eastern Europe.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690636, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

SUMPs-Up

Project Full Title	European Programme for Accelerating the Take up of Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans		
Website	https://sumps-up.eu/home/ https://www.sump-assessment.eu/English/start https://civitas.eu/projects/sumps-up https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690669 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/sumps-up/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/european-programme-accelerating-take-sustainable-urban-mobility-plans		
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015		
Project Coordinator	ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH / ICLEI Europasekretariat GmbH contact@sumps-up.eu		
Project Partners	<p>15 partners</p> <p>Birmingham City Council</p> <p>BKK Centre for Budapest Transport / Budapesti Közlekedési Központ Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság</p> <p>CEREMA Centre d'études et d'expertise sur les risques, l'environnement, la mobilité et l'aménagement / Centre for Studies on Risks, the Environment, Mobility and Urban Planning</p> <p>City Council of Donostia San Sebastián / Ayuntamiento de Donostia – San Sebastián</p> <p>City of Malmö / Malmö Stad</p> <p>City of Turku / Turun kaupunki</p> <p>Eurocities ASBL</p> <p>Fondazione Piemonte Innova</p> <p>ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH / ICLEI Europasekretariat GmbH</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH</p> <p>Sofia Urban Mobility Centre EAD / Tsentar za Gradska Mobilnost EAD (SUMC)</p> <p>Transport Authority of Thessaloniki S.A. / Organismos Sygkoinoniakoy Ergou Thessalonikis Anonymi Etairia</p> <p>Trivector Traffic AB</p> <p>Wuppertal Institut für Klima, Umwelt, Energie gGmbH</p>		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.09.2016	End date	29.02.2020
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		

Keywords	Accessibility, SUMP development and implementation, planning authorities, capacity building, guidelines, SUMP Learning Programmes, user needs assessment, Innovation Pilot Pool
Case Studies	Role models: Birmingham, Budapest, Malmö, Donostia-San Sebastian, Sofia, Thessaloniki, Turin
<p>Through SUMP-Up, an experienced consortium of public and private organisations, including four major city networks and seven frontrunner cities, skilled in coordinating major European SUMP projects will accelerate the take-up of SUMP, where this is currently low, ensuring that SUMP is the primary mobility planning concept in Europe. To achieve this, the project will combine comprehensive SUMP research, tailored capacity-building, strong mechanisms for technical support, as well as constant SUMP monitoring and evaluation. As a result, the project will accelerate the development of 100 SUMP, reach out to 600 cities and will therefore engage about 80% of the EU-cities above 50,000 inhabitants. SUMP-Up will review, strengthen and integrate existing SUMP resources, designing a support system to assist cities to develop high quality SUMP. A SUMP Tool Inventory will help mobility planners make better informed decisions about which planning tools to apply in their local context. This will be enriched with experiences from the city partners who will be testing innovative solutions in SUMP preparation and implementation. The SUMP Up Innovation Pilot Pool will create a mechanism that allows identifying and validating the most effective concepts, approaches and methodologies in SUMP practice for different framework conditions and different types of cities, complemented by a peer learning programme, to leverage resources and enable more cities to apply the SUMP concept. At Member State level, SUMP-Up will foster exchange to improve national SUMP frameworks.</p> <p>Close monitoring and evaluation of the project and supported activities will show evidence of the SUMP concept's value and serve as a quality control mechanism for both project activities and the SUMP being developed. SUMP-Up will broadly communicate the positive impacts of SUMP, producing and disseminating insightful reports and research. Ultimately, SUMP-Up will stimulate a European movement of mobility planning authorities experienced in preparing and implementing SUMP in compliance with the European requirements.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690669, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

SUITS

Project Full Title	Sustainable Urban Integrated Transport Systems: Transferable Tools for Small-Medium local authorities		
Website	https://www.suits-project.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/suits https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690650 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/supporting-urban-integrated-transport-systems-transferable-tools-authorities		
Call	H2020-MG-2014-2015		
Project Coordinator	Coventry University – Mobility and Transport Research Centre Andree Woodcock, adx974@coventry.ac.uk		
Project Partners	<p>24 partners</p> <p>5T s.r.l. Arcadis (UK) Ltd City of Turin / Comune di Torino Council of the City of Coventry Coventry University – Mobility and Transport Research Centre Eurokleis s.r.l. F.K. Liotopoulos Kai Sia EE / SBOING Fundación de la Comunidad Valenciana para la Promoción Estratégica, el Desarrollo y la Innovación Urbana Instituto tecnológico del embalaje, transporte y Logística (ITENE) Integral Consulting R&D Interactions Ltd LEVER SA Development Consultants LogDrill Informatikai és Szolgáltató Korlátolt Felelősségű Társaság Makios Logistics SA Municipality of Alba Iulia Municipality of Kalamaria / Dimos Kalamarias Politecnico di Torino (POLITO) – Department of Environment, Land and Infrastructure Engineering (DIATI) Roma Servizi per la Mobilità s.r.l. / Roma Mobilità Signosis Sprl Smart Continent LT UAB Technische Universität Ilmenau (TU Ilmenau) – Media Production Group VTM Consultores em Engenharia e Planeamento LDA West Midlands Combined Authority Wuppertal Institut für Klima, Umwelt, Energie gGmbH</p>		
Duration (months)	51		
Start date	01.12.2016	End date	28.02.2021
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning		

	<p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p> <p>3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>
Keywords	Small and medium sized cities, capacity building of local authorities and transport stakeholders, tools on effective and sustainable transport measures, sustainable inclusive integrated and accessible transport, integrated urban mobility planning for freight and passengers, SUMP
Case Studies	Alba Iulia, Coventry, Stuttgart, Kalamaria, Palanga, Rome, Turin, Valencia
<p>The aim of the SUITS project was to increase the capacity of Small-Medium local authorities to develop and implement sustainable, inclusive, integrated and accessible transport strategies, policies, tools, measures and intelligent transport systems that recognize the end-to-end travel experiences of all users and freight. The SUITS project stands for <i>Sustainable Urban Integrated Transport Systems: Transferable Tools for Small-Medium local authorities</i>.</p> <p>The project outputs provided valuable tools for local authorities and policy makers by making the case for socially and economically sustainable investments in transport. SUITS targeted four key areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity gaps in small-medium local authorities' knowledge and work practices • The need for integrated urban mobility planning for both freight and passengers based on the capture and use of information relating to the diversity of active, private, public, shared and multimodal forms of transport, journey types and travellers/freight • The need to exploit future transport technologies to enhance transport efficiency and quality of life • The need to maximise the effectiveness and sustainability of transport measures through transferable best practice, new funding models and creation of sustainable opportunities for new business entries. <p>https://civitas.eu/projects/suits, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

SUNRISE

Project Full Title	Sustainable Urban Neighbourhoods – Research and Implementation Support in Europe		
Website	https://civitas-sunrise.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/sunrise https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/723365 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/sunrise/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/sustainable-urban-neighbourhoods-research-and-implementation-support-europe		
Call	H2020-MG-2016-2017		
Project Coordinator	Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH Ralf Brand, r.brand@rupprecht-consult.eu Kristin Tovaas, k.tovaas@rupprecht-consult.eu		
Project Partners	17 partners BKK Centre for Budapest Transport / Budapesti Közlekedési Központ Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság City of Malmö / Malmö Stad Edinburgh Napier University – Transport Research Institute (TRI) Free Hanseatic City of Bremen / Freie Hansestadt Bremen Fundación Zaragoza Logistics Center Greater Baka Community Council HQ Architects Ltd Koucky & Partners AB Mobilissimus Korlátolt felelősségű társaság Municipality of Budapest / Budapest Főváros Önkormányzata Municipality of Jerusalem POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH Southend-on-Sea Borough Council Technische Universität Wien (TU Wien) – Research Unit of Sociology Transport Authority of Thessaloniki S.A. / Organismos Sygkoinoniakoy Ergou Thessalonikis Anonymi Etairia Urbanista OHG		
Duration (months)	50		
Start date	01.05.2017	End date	31.07.2021
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity		

	<p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Support striving neighbourhood economies <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society
Keywords	Co-creation process, innovative potentials at neighbourhood level, co-learning, citizen science, urban development, behavioural change, crowd wisdom, Sustainable Neighbourhood Mobility Planning concept (SNMP), SUMP
Case Studies	Action cities: Bremen, Budapest, Jerusalem, Malmö, Southend-on-Sea, Thessaloniki
<p>SUNRISE will develop, implement, assess and facilitate learning about new, collaborative ways to address common mobility challenges at the neighbourhood level. Towards this aim, 6 cities will foster collaborative processes in specific neighbourhoods as “Neighbourhood Mobility Labs” with the explicit mandate to implement innovative solutions for and with their residents, businesses etc.</p> <p>SUNRISE rests on several pillars: A) Utilisation of neighbourhood-specific opportunities. B) Co-creation of solutions, i.e. through strategic civic-public alliances C) Socio-technical nature of solutions as combinations of services, social arrangements, rules, technologies or small infrastructures etc. D) New forms of synergies between bottom-up and top-down.</p> <p>All SUNRISE activities are structured along the following phases of the innovation chain: 1) Co-identification of mobility problems; 2) Co-planning / co-selection of solutions; 3) Co-implementation of solutions; 4) Co-evaluation; 5) Co-learning and uptake.</p> <p>In strategic terms, SUNRISE will lay the foundation for a Sustainable Neighbourhood Mobility Planning concept (SNMP) to complement SUMP.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/723365, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

Cities-4-People

Project Full Title	New approaches for community-driven sustainable mobility innovations at neighbourhood and urban district level		
Website	https://cities4people.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/cities-4-people https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/723194 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/new-approaches-community-driven-sustainable-mobility-innovations-neighbourhood-and-urban		
Call	H2020-MG-2016-2017		
Project Coordinator	Copenhagen Business School (CBS) – Department of Management, Society and Communication Isabel Fróes, ifr.msc@cbs.dk Julie Jo Nygaard, jjn.msc@cbs.dk		
Project Partners	15 partners Anaptyxiaki Etaireia Dimou Trikkaion Anaptyxiaki Anonymi Etaireia OTA / E-Trikala AE BKK Centre for Budapest Transport / Budapesti Közlekedési Központ Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság Copenhagen Business School (CBS) – Department of Management, Society and Communication Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg / Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg HafenCity Universität Hamburg (HCU) – CityScienceLab HafenCity Universität Hamburg (HCU) – Fachbereich Digital City Science Istanbul University / İstanbul Üniversitesi KTI Hungarian Institute for Transport Sciences Non-Profit Ltd / Magyar Közlekedéstudományi és Logisztikai Intézet Nonprofit Korlátolt Felelősségű Társaság Municipality of Budapest / Budapest Főváros Önkormányzata Oxfordshire County Council Q-Plan International Advisors PC Stichting Waag Society University College London (UCL) – Institute of Health Equity Üsküdar Municipality White Research s.r.l.		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.06.2017	End date	30.11.2020
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		

Keywords	People-oriented transport and mobility (POTM), sustainable urban and peri-urban mobility, social innovation and neighbourhood governance, community empowerment, sustainable urban planning, participatory inclusive and transparent innovation processes, Citizen Mobility Communities
Case Studies	Mobility Labs: Hamburg, Oxfordshire, Budapest, Trikala, Istanbul
<p>The people-oriented transport and mobility (POTM) approach is a promising solution for addressing the sustainable mobility challenges that many urban and peri-urban areas face in the EU. However, despite its potential, there is currently a lack of evidence and transformative POTM solutions within the research and innovation framework. The EU-funded Cities-4-People project has formed a multidisciplinary consortium that aims to introduce a community-driven POTM framework relying on participatory, inclusive and transparent innovation processes. The innovative framework will address the real needs of EU citizens and co-create new mobility concepts and solutions while harnessing digital and social innovation. The project will test the best solutions in five EU urban areas with a rich diversity in size, population density and socio-economic context.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/723194, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

Metamorphosis

Project Full Title	Transformation of neighbourhoods in a child-friendly way to increase the quality of life for all citizens.		
Website	https://www.metamorphosis-project.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/metamorphosis https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/723375 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/transformation-neighbourhoods-child-friendly-way-increase-quality-life-all-citizens		
Call	H2020-MG-2016-2017		
Project Coordinator	Stichting Breda University of Applied Sciences – Academy for Built Environment & Logistics Susanne Wrighton, s.wrighton@cyclindingustries.com Karl Reiter, reiter@fgm.at		
Project Partners	12 partners Austrian Mobility Research / Forschungsgesellschaft Mobilität (FGM) – AMOR Gemeinnützige GmbH City of Munich / Landeshauptstadt München Lendwirbel Verein für nachbarschaftliche Stadtentwicklung / Association for neighbourly urban development Municipality of Alba Iulia Municipality of Merano / Comune di Merano / Stadtgemeinde Meran Municipality of Tilburg / Gemeente Tilburg Ökoinstitut Südtirol / Alto Adige istitute per uno sviluppo ecologicoe sociale cooperative Southampton City Council Stichting Breda University of Applied Sciences – Academy for Built Environment & Logistics Synergo Mobilität-Politik-Raum-GmbH Technische Universität Dresden (TU Dresden) – Chair of Transport Ecology University of Southampton – Transportation Research Group (TRG)		
Duration (months)	41		
Start date	01.06.2017	End date	31.10.2020
Key Area(s)	KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Behavioural change, child-friendly mobility solutions, liveable shared space, innovative neighbourhood transformation, sustainable neighbourhood, street design		
Case Studies	Alba Iulia, Graz, Merano, Munich, Southampton, Tilburg, Zurich		

Metamorphosis is on transforming neighbourhoods with a focus on children.

Metamorphosis starts from the premise that when a neighbourhood has many children on its public spaces, this is a major indicator that it is well designed as a sustainable neighbourhood. The word sustainability itself is already inseparably combined with children as it implicates “designed for the next generations”. Thus Metamorphosis will address the challenges of the topic 4.5. from this perspective and will thus:

1. Transform car-oriented neighbourhoods into children-friendly neighbourhoods achieving behavioural change and increase in the quality of life
2. Build the vision needed for such transformations
3. Answer basic research questions related to neighbourhood transformation
4. Achieve creative breakthrough innovations – in development, in design, in governance and in planning procedures – for public spaces in neighbourhoods and urban districts
5. Through the above described mechanisms, develop and implement children friendly mobility solutions
6. Evaluate take-up, involvement, process and impacts using innovative evaluation methodologies
7. Develop and implement innovative transfer instruments to transfer Metamorphosis-innovations from city to city and country to country, also beyond the duration of the project

Children can help to develop positive emotions for the neighbourhood (and this is a key issue, as behaviour and decisions are mostly determined by emotions, and only to a much lesser degree by rational arguments such as cost-benefit). Thus:

- children can easily find a direct way to their parent’s hearts
- to be against children’s needs and demands isn’t socially well accepted

Metamorphosis will include trial implementation cities with completely different neighbourhoods. Each city will participate with up to four different neighbourhoods, selected to have a wide variety: in size, structure, density and diversity.

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/723375>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

MUV

Project Full Title	Mobility Urban Values		
Website	https://www.wepush.org/sites/muv2020/ https://www.muvgame.com/en/ https://civitas.eu/projects/muv https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/723521 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/mobility-urban-values		
Call	H2020-MG-2016-2017		
Project Coordinator	Palermo Urban Solutions Hub (PUSH) Salvatore Di Dio, s.didio@wepush.org		
Project Partners	<p>16 partners</p> <p>Aalborg University – Department of Architecture, Design and Media Technology Aalborg University – Department of Sustainability and Planning BaG! Consulting LDA City of Amsterdam / Gemeente Amsterdam City of Ghent / Stad Gent City of Palermo / Comune di Palermo Fondazione LINKS – Leading Innovation & knowledge for society Forum Virium Helsinki OY Fundacio Privada i2Cat, Internet i Innovació Digital a Catalunya Institut Municipal d'Informàtica de Barcelona Istituto Superiore Mario Boella (ISMB) LUCA School of Arts Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST) Municipality of Fundão / Município do Fundao Palermo Urban Solutions Hub (PUSH) Stichting Waag Society</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.06.2017	End date	31.05.2020
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Support sustainable lifestyles <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Support striving neighbourhood economies <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 		

Keywords	Behavioural change, sustainable and healthy urban mobility, citizen awareness, Open Data, co-creation, mobile app, planning process, gamification, local businesses, ICT, added-value services, marketing, data visualization, more liveable urban environments
Case Studies	Neighbourhoods in Amsterdam, Barcelona, Fundao, Ghent, Helsinki, Palermo
<p>Urban life faces mounting pressures from increasing mobility challenges that cannot be effectively addressed by conventional policies. It is crucial to adopt innovative approaches that involve active citizen participation. The EU-funded MUV (Mobility Urban Values) project seeks to bring about a revolutionary transformation by engaging six European neighbourhoods. Leveraging extensive data analysis, MUV aims to understand behaviours, needs and values, fostering collaborative efforts to reimagine urban mobility. Technological tools such as a wearable app, an environmental monitoring system, and a cloud-based data platform will strengthen this endeavour. Also, gamification techniques and rewards will inspire community members to embrace sustainable transportation options, thereby promoting positive behavioural change.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/723521, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

INCLUSION

Project Full Title	Towards more accessible and inclusive mobility solutions for European prioritised areas		
Website	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/770115 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/inclusion/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/towards-more-accessible-and-inclusive-mobility-solutions-european-prioritised-areas		
Call	H2020-MG-2016-2017		
Project Coordinator	algoWatt S.p.A.		
Project Partners	15 partners algoWatt S.p.A. ATAF Gestioni s.r.l. BKK Centre for Budapest Transport / Budapesti Közlekedési Központ Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság Busitalia Sita Nord s.r.l. BUSUP Technologies S.L. EMTA European Metropolitan Transport Authorities Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón MemEx s.r.l. Mosaic Factor S.L. Mpact vzw / Mpact asbl POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH The Highlands and Islands Transport Partnership (HITRANS) University of Aberdeen – The University Court of the University of Aberdeen Verkehrsverbund Rhein-Sieg GmbH		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.10.2017	End date	30.09.2020
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport		
Keywords	Accessibility and inclusiveness of public transport, equity of transport, vulnerable users, equitable conditions, innovative and transferable solutions, ICT-enabled Social innovation		
Case Studies	Pilot Labs: Rhein-Sieg, Cairngorms National Park, Florence Metropolitan Area, Flanders region, Barcelona conurbation, Budapest		
<p>INCLUSION was a 3-year project that aims to address several challenges related to the accessibility of public transport in specific urban and rural areas where accessibility, inclusive mobility and equity challenges are greatest.</p> <p>The main objective of INCLUSION was to understand, assess and evaluate the accessibility and inclusiveness of transport solutions in European prioritised areas. The project identified gaps and needs to propose and experiment with a range of innovative and transferable solutions. Accessible and inclusive</p>			

public transport for all and especially for vulnerable categories is key to ensuring equity of transport and social inclusion.

(<https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/inclusion/>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

CCCB

Project Full Title	City Changer Cargo Bike		
Website	http://cyclelogistics.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/city-changer-cargo-bike https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/769086		
Call	H2020-MG-2016-2017		
Project Coordinator	City of Utrecht / Gemeente Utrecht Susanne Wrighton, s.wrighton@cyclingingindustries.com info@cyclelogistics.eu		
Project Partners	<p>23 partners</p> <p>Associazione culturale SUD-EST Austrian Mobility Research / Forschungsgesellschaft Mobilität (FGM) – AMOR Gemeinnützige GmbH Behrensen Arne / cargobike.jetzt GmbH Cambridgeshire County Council Centro de Estudios Ambientales (CEA) City Council of Donostia San Sebastián / Ayuntamiento de Donostia – San Sebastián City of Dubrovnik / Grad Dubrovnik City of Gdynia / Gdynia-Miasto na prawach powiatu City of Mechelen / Stad Mechelen City of Oslo / Oslo Kommune City of Rimini / Comune di Rimini City of Utrecht / Gemeente Utrecht Copenhagense APS Cracow University of Technology / Politechnika Krakowska – Chair of Transportation Systems Eurométropole de Strasbourg European Cycle Logistics Federation European Cyclists Federation ASBL Les Industries du vélo en Europe Lisbon City Council / Câmara Municipal de Lisboa Messenger AS Municipality of Alba Iulia Municipality of Drama / Dimos Drama Municipality of Varna / Obshtina Varna</p>		
Duration (months)	47		
Start date	01.09.2018	End date	31.07.2022
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 		

	<p>2. Focus on people-centred public space 4. Support sustainable lifestyles</p> <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>
Keywords	Cargo bikes, cost-effective and larger scale deployment, awareness, sustainable logistics operations, training, multipliers, media bikes, place maker bikes, funding & financing schemes, tryout and sharing schemes
Case Studies	Lisbon, Varna, Gdynia, Alba Iulia, Dubrovnik, Rimini, CEA Vitoria Gasteiz, Strasbourg, Mechelen, Oslo, San Sebastian, Cambridgeshire County Council, Utrecht
<p>The large scale introduction and application of cargo bikes in urban areas has shown to be a game changer for cities: the image of cycling improves; general levels of cycling increase (both for freight and passengers); urban space is used more efficiently; air quality, safety levels as well as quality of life improve. However, this innovative solution is present in only a few cities and at best in the starting phase in other European cities. Its full potential has not been achieved in any European city.</p> <p>CityChangerCargoBike (CCCB) aims to change this and increase and accelerate take-up. CCCB will take the very best cargo bike implementation examples, contexts and expertise in Europe and profit and learn from them in order to transfer these on a large scale and in the best way possible to new cities and contexts - in CCCB's forerunner cities, in the follower cities and beyond. CCCB has the following objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness among the relevant stakeholders: public, private and commercial sector. • Utilise innovative tools for the take-up and scale-up and transfer between forerunner and follower cities: e.g. peer-to-peer exchange. • Establish favourable framework conditions for cargo bike use. • Achieve wide roll-out and transferability through Forerunner cities, Follower cities (within the consortium) and External follower cities. • Reduce congestion, emissions; increase safety; increase public space and improve public space usage <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/769086, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

GreenCharge

Project Full Title	GreenCharge		
Website	https://www.greencharge2020.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/greencharge https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/769016 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/greencharge		
Call	H2020-MG-2016-2017		
Project Coordinator	SINTEF AS / SINTEF Technology and Society Jacqueline Floch, jacqueline.floch@sintef.no info@greencharge2020.eu		
Project Partners	<p>19 partners</p> <p>atlantis it S.L. City of Oslo / Oslo Kommune Cloudselling B.V. EGEN B.V. eSmart Systems AS Fortum Oyj Free Hanseatic City of Bremen / Freie Hansestadt Bremen Fundacio Eurecat Hsubject GmbH ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH / ICLEI Europasekretariat GmbH Millor Energy S.L. Motit World S.L. PMC Personal Mobility Center NordWest e.G. PNO Consultants B.V. PNO Consultants GmbH SINTEF AS / SINTEF Technology and Society Università degli Studi della Campania Luigi Vanvitelli – Dipartimento di Ingegneria University of Oslo – Department of Informatics zet GmbH</p>		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.09.2018	End date	28.02.2022
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition		
Keywords	Electric vehicles, smart charging system, zero-emission transport system, automatic energy management, shared mobility, business models		
Case Studies	Pilot living labs: Barcelona, Bremen, Oslo		

GreenCharge takes us a few important steps closer to achieving one of the dreams of modern cities: a zero emission transport system based on electric vehicles running on green energy, with traffic jams and parking problems becoming things of the past.

Power to the people! The GreenCharge dream can only be achieved if people feel confident that they can access charging infrastructure as and when they need it. So GreenCharge is developing a smart charging system that lets people book charging in advance, so that they can easily access the power they need.

The delicate balance of power. If lots of people try to charge their vehicles around the same time (e.g. on returning home from work), public electricity suppliers may struggle to cope with the peaks in demand. So we are developing software for automatic energy management in local areas to balance demand with available supplies. This balancing act combines public supplies and locally produced reusable energy, using local storage as a buffer and staggering the times at which vehicles get charged.

Getting the financial incentives right. Electric motors may make the wheels go round, but money makes the world go round. So we are devising and testing business models that encourage use of electric vehicles and sharing of energy resources, allowing all those involved to cooperate in an economically viable way.

Showing how it works in practice. GreenCharge is testing all of these innovations in practical trials in Barcelona, Bremen and Oslo. Together, these trials cover a wide variety of factors: vehicle type (scooters, cars, bicycles), ownership model (private, shared individual use), charging locations (private residences, workplaces, public spaces, transport hubs), energy management (using solar power, load balancing at one charging station or within a neighbourhood, battery swapping), and charging support (booking, priority charging).

(<https://www.greencharge2020.eu/about-project/>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

Handshake

Project Full Title	Enabling the transferability of cycling innovations and assessment of its implications		
Website	https://handshakecycling.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/handshake https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/769177 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/enabling-transferability-cycling-innovations-and-assessment-its-implications		
Call	H2020-MG-2016-2017		
Project Coordinator	Istituto di Studi per l'Integrazione dei Sistemi (I.S.I.S) - Società cooperativa Mario Gualdi, mgualdi@isinnova.org		
Project Partners	<p>19 partners</p> <p>Bordeaux Metropole</p> <p>City of Amsterdam / Gemeente Amsterdam</p> <p>City of Bruges / Stad Brugge</p> <p>City of Helsinki / Helsingin Kaupunki</p> <p>City of Munich / Landeshauptstadt München</p> <p>City of Turin / Comune di Torino</p> <p>Copenhagen Municipality / Københavns Kommune</p> <p>Decisio B.V.</p> <p>Dublin City Council</p> <p>ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH / ICLEI Europasekretariat GmbH</p> <p>Istituto di Studi per l'Integrazione dei Sistemi (I.S.I.S) – Società cooperativa</p> <p>Krakov Municipality / Gmina Miejska Krakow – Miasto Na Prawach Powiatu</p> <p>Mobiél 21 vzw</p> <p>Municipality of Cadiz / Ayuntamiento de Cádiz</p> <p>Riga City Council / Rīgas pilsētas pašvaldība</p> <p>Roma Servizi per la Mobilità s.r.l. / Roma Mobilità</p> <p>Stichting Vélo Mondial</p> <p>Transport for Greater Manchester (TFGM)</p> <p>Universiteit van Amsterdam (UvA) – Faculty of Social and Behavioural Sciences</p>		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.09.2018	End date	31.08.2022
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 4. Support sustainable lifestyles <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 		

Keywords	Active mobility, cycling, cycling infrastructure, intelligent transport systems, bike sharing, mentoring programmes, knowledge transfer, transition management, inclusive transport planning, modelling & assessment, awareness, education, safety, public health, cycling attractiveness and competitiveness
Case Studies	Cycling Capitals: Copenhagen, Amsterdam, Munich Future Cycling Capitals: Bordeaux, Bruges, Cadiz, Dublin, Greater Manchester, Helsinki, Krakow, Riga, Rome, Turin
<p>HANDSHAKE supports the effective take up of the integrated cycling solutions successfully developed by Amsterdam, Copenhagen and Munich, our Cycling Capitals and world-renowned cycling front runners, to our 10 highly committed Future Cycling Capitals, Bordeaux Metropole, Bruges, Cadiz, Dublin, Helsinki, Krakow, Greater Manchester, Riga, Rome and Turin. Our partner cities are combined in a composite working environment in which diverse geographical contexts, socio-economic conditions and planning cultures work toward the same goals, that is, delivering the desired cycling change. The project believes that effective transfer can happen only in the presence of: i) state-of-art body of knowledge on cycling policy and solutions; ii) sustaining transition processes; iii) motivating and supporting forms of mentorship. In HANDSHAKE this is ensured by the presence of 3 cycling planning champions, the employment of highly innovative methods brought together into a supportive and novel transfer cycle (including Bikenomics, Immersive Study Tours and Transition Management), and a mentorship programme that takes by the hand each participating city. The gathered team will cooperate to reach a number of strategic objectives: i) Inspire the creation or refinement of holistic cycling visions and concrete transfer approaches; ii) Foster the adoption of a multidisciplinary planning culture to empower the project process and consolidate future cycling policies and investments; iii) allow cycling to become a key element of urban transport; iv) Improve cycling modal share and safety; v) Leverage the potential of cycling as a critical congestion relief tool; vi) Leverage cycling to improve public health; vii) Foster economic growth. HANDSHAKE expects to improve cycling attractiveness by +52% and competitiveness by 17%, shift ca. 60.000 people to cycling with +34% in frequency of cycling use, 37,5% in accidents, traffic levels lowered by 6,34%, and CO2 savings of -3.706.000 kg CO2/year.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/769177, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

MORE

Project Full Title	Multi-modal Optimisation for Road-space in Europe		
Website	https://morewebsite.wpenginepowered.com/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/769276 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/more/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/multi-modal-optimisation-road-space-europe		
Call	H2020-MG-2016-2017		
Project Coordinator	University College London (UCL) – Department of Civil, Environment & Geomatic Engineering Peter Jones, peter.jones@ucl.ac.uk		
Project Partners	20 partners BKK Centre for Budapest Transport / Budapesti Közlekedési Központ Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság Buchanan Computing Ltd City of Malmö / Malmö Stad Constanta Municipal Council / Municipiul reședință de județ Constanța European Cyclists Federation ASBL European Integrated Project Fondation Nationale des Sciences Politiques (Sciences Po) International Association of Public Transport / Union Internationale des Transports Publics (UITP) International Federation of Pedestrians (IFP) – Research IRU Projects ASBL / The International Road Transport Union Lisbon City Council / Câmara Municipal de Lisboa POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale PTV Planung Transport Verkehr GmbH SLR Consulting Ltd SWARCO Mobility Nedeland B.V. Technische Universität Dresden (TU Dresden) – Chair of Mobility System Planning Transport for London University College London (UCL) – Department of Civil, Environment & Geomatic Engineering Vectos (South) Ltd Vectos GmbH		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.09.2018	End date	28.02.2022
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 3. Provide sustainable solutions for longer trips 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity		

	<p>2. Focus on people-centred public space 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>
Keywords	TEN-T network, urban corridor roads, big data, new technologies, dynamic traffic signing, needs of road users, web or computer-based tools, road-space reallocation, stakeholder engagement, encourage street activity, use of kerb space
Case Studies	Budapest, Constanta, Lisbon, London, Malmö
<p>MORE will develop and implement procedures for the design of urban corridor roads.</p> <p>MORE will test these in five urban nodes of the Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T). It will deliver tools to assist cities in their roadspace design process.</p> <p>Corridor roads are under pressure from increased mobility. Delays and variable travel times result in time losses for road passengers and freight deliveries. This requires a more efficient use of road space, applying multimodal design. At the same time, developing safe and attractive cities demands transport and city planners to encourage street activity and reduce traffic dominance. MORE will develop design concepts that acknowledge such variety in economic and social interests, considering the needs of all road users.</p> <p>https://morewebsite.wpenginepowered.com/what-is-more, retrieved 26 September 2024)</p>	

MEISTER

Project Full Title	Mobility Environmentally-friendly, Integrated and economically Sustainable Through innovative Electromobility Recharging infrastructure and new business models		
Website	https://meisterproject.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/meister https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/769052 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/mobility-environmentally-friendly-integrated-and-economically-sustainable-through		
Call	H2020-MG-2016-2017		
Project Coordinator	ETRA Investigacion y Desarrollo SA Patricia Bellver Muñoz, meister@grupoetra.com María del Carmen Tomás, mtomas.etraid@grupoetra.com		
Project Partners	16 partners Berlin – Senate Department for Mobility, Transport, Climate Protection and the Environment / Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) City of Gothenburg / Goteborgs Kommun / Göteborgs Stad City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad E.ON Solutions GmbH ETRA Investigacion y Desarrollo SA Fundación Centro de Investigaciones Estratégicas y de Desarrollo Económico y Social de Málaga (CIEDES) Gewobag Wohnungsbau-Aktiengesellschaft Berlin. Institut für Klimaschutz, Energie und Mobilität – Recht, Ökonomie und Politik e.V. (IKEM) Málaga City Council / Ayuntamiento de Málaga Novadays S.L. RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB – RISE Viktoria AB RWTH Aachen University / Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen / RWTH Aachen Campus GmbH Sociedad Municipal de Aparcamientos y Servicios S.A (SMASSA) VMZ Berlin Betreibergesellschaft mbH		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.09.2018	End date	28.02.2022
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		

Keywords	Electric vehicles, charging infrastructure, SUMP integration, MaaS, shared mobility, sustainable business models, electromobility market paradigm, barrier-free access, renewable energy, e-mobility interoperability platform, smart grid services
Case Studies	Malaga, Berlin, Gothenburg
<p>MEISTER will deliver a set of tools to foster e-mobility large scale adoption by (1) demonstrating innovative, sustainable business models to lower installation and operation costs of charging infrastructure, (2) optimizing usage of infrastructure by the smart combination of charging and parking services, (3) integrating EV within urban SUMPs, including the establishment of EV sharing and the inclusion of EV within MaaS schemas to reduce CO2 emissions and optimize urban space usage, (4) providing interoperable platforms and services to users for an easy, convenient and barrier-free access to charging, billing and smart grid services, including an increase of the use of RES and self-generation to power EVs.</p> <p>Thus, MEISTER aims at creating the conditions for smart e-mobility market take up in cities, by means of developing integrated approaches, smart solutions and innovative, sustainable business models, which will be tested and validated in three urban areas in Southern, Central and Northern Europe: Malaga (Spain), Berlin (Germany), and Gothenburg (Sweden). These 3 sites are EU leaders in the field of e-mobility, have complementary contexts and share a common vision on EV deployment. The three MEISTER pilots will involve 51,500 users, 1,000 EV and 660 charging points.</p> <p>MEISTER expects to increase by 15% the demand for EVs, as well to reduce by 20% the installation costs of EVSE infrastructure. At the same time, the project expects to help reduce charging prices by 20% and increase by 30% the usage of RES to charge EVs. As a result of these figures, the project will also have a substantial impact in terms of a reduction of emissions and environmental sustainability, as described in section 2.1.4. Business models and public-private partnership frameworks developed and demonstrated by the project will be designed and documented to facilitate trans-European transferability and impact.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/769052, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

Park4SUMP

Project Full Title			
Website	https://park4sump.eu/ https://parkpad.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/park4sump https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/769072 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/park4sump/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/actions-demonstrate-how-park4sump-will-lead-achieve-sustainable-transport-urban-areas		
Call	H2020-MG-2016-2017		
Project Coordinator	Mobiel 21 vzw Patrick Auwerx, patrick.auwerx@mobiel21.be		
Project Partners	23 partners Austrian Mobility Research / Forschungsgesellschaft Mobilität (FGM) – AMOR Gemeinnützige GmbH Centro de Estudios Ambientales (CEA) City of Freiburg / Stadt Freiburg City of Gdansk / Gdańsk / Gmina Miasta Gdanska City of La Rochelle / Commune de la Rochelle City of Shkodër / Bashkia Shkoder / Bashkisë Shkodër City of Sint-Niklaas / Stad Sint-Niklaas City of Zadar / Grad Zadar Deutsches Institut für Urbanistik gGmbH Edinburgh Napier University – School of Computing, Engineering and the Built Environment Istituto di Studi per l’Integrazione dei Sistemi (I.S.I.S) – Società cooperativa Krakow Municipality / Gmina Miejska Krakow – Miasto Na Prawach Powiatu Lisboa E-NOVA – Agência Municipal De Energia-Ambiente De Lisboa Mobiel 21 vzw Municipality of Reggio Emilia / Comune di Reggio Emilia Municipality of Rotterdam / Gemeente Rotterdam POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Slatina municipality / Municipiul Slatina Sofia Urban Mobility Centre EAD / Tsentar za Gradska Mobilnost EAD (SUMC) The City of Tallinn / Tallinna Linn / Tallinn linnavalitsus Trondheim Municipality / Trondheim Kommune Umeå Parkerings AB Urban Planning Institute of the Republic of Slovenia / Urbanistični inštitut Republike Slovenije (UIRS)		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.09.2018	End date	31.08.2022
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space		

	<p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <p>3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies</p> <p>4. Support sustainable lifestyles</p> <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>1. Support striving neighbourhood economies</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p>
Keywords	Effective and holistic parking management, SUMP integration, participatory planning, human-centred neighbourhoods, acceptance, capacity building, active mobility, behaviour change, traffic and travel avoidance, modal shift, PUSH&PULL
Case Studies	<p>Leading Cities: Vitoria Gasteiz, Rotterdam, Freiburg, Krakow, Trondheim</p> <p>Follower cities: Sint-Niklaas, Slatina, Sofia, Tallinn, Zadar, Shkodra, Lisboa, Gdansk, La Rochelle, Reggio Emilia, Umeå</p>
<p>Parking management should be an important part of sustainable urban mobility planning (SUMP) but unfortunately, it is one of the most underdeveloped segments. Most EU member states lack national level policy and guidance on parking. PARK4SUMP aims to change this, because good parking management has proved to be of utmost importance. It frees the public space, supports local businesses, reduces search travel, generates revenue, increases safety, supports urban planning and can make cities more attractive. The general concept is to take the very best parking management examples, contexts and expertise in Europe, learn and profit from these, and transfer them on a large scale and in the best way possible to new cities. This covers raising awareness and gaining acceptance among relevant stakeholders; building capacity, particularly among cities that have difficulty in picking up such policies; stimulating further innovation; and achieving wide roll-out and transferability. Park4SUMP will work on traffic and travel avoidance; it will support less car dependent lifestyles and put into practice innovations in planning and location policy. It will also optimise the use of existing infrastructure. Furthermore the modal shift towards more efficient modes like walking, cycling and public transport will be encouraged. Convincing arguments to incorporate parking management can be given: it has low costs, it pays for itself, it delivers money, it is easy to implement and to modify and it can be done in incremental steps. The main expected impact will be cities with strongly improved parking policies that are creatively used to improve the quality of life and business in cities and develop the cities in a more sustainable way. Park4SUMP aims to establish parking management as an essential part of SUMP of its leading, follower and external follower cities. Park4SUMP will deliver behaviour change whilst generating revenue.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/769072, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

Levitate

Project Full Title	Societal Level Impacts of Connected and Automated Vehicles		
Website	https://levitate-project.eu/ https://www.ccam-impacts.eu/ https://www.lboro.ac.uk/schools/design-creative-arts/research-innovation/projects/levitate/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824361 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/levitate/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/societal-level-impacts-connected-and-automated-vehicles		
Call	H2020-DT-ART-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	Loughborough University – School of Design and Creative Arts Professor Pete Thomas, p.d.thomas@lboro.ac.uk		
Project Partners	13 partners Aimsun SLU AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH City of Vienna / Stadt Wien Institute for Road Safety Research / Stichting Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek Verkeersveiligheid (SWOV) Institute of Transport Economics / Transportøkonomisk Institutt (TOI) Loughborough University – School of Design and Creative Arts National Technical University of Athens / Ethnicon Metsovion Polytechnion (NTUA) – Road Safety Observatory National Technical University of Athens / Ethnicon Metsovion Polytechnion (NTUA) – Traffic Engineering Laboratory POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Queensland University of Technology (QUT) Tongji University Transport for Greater Manchester (TFGM) University of Michigan		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.12.2018	End date	31.05.2022
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Connected and automated vehicle (CAV) technology, evaluation framework, impact on individual mobility and society, decision support tool, safety, Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM)		

Case Studies	
	<p>LEVITATE’s aim is to develop a new impact assessment framework to enable policymakers to manage the introduction of connected and automated transport systems, maximise the benefits and generally harness the technology to achieve societal objectives.</p> <p>LEVITATE is currently building tools to help European cities, regions and national governments prepare for a future with increasing levels of automated vehicles in passenger cars, urban transport services and urban logistics:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establish a method for assessing the short, medium and long-term impacts of automated vehicles on mobility, safety, environment, society and other areas (multi-disciplinary methodology) 2. Apply the method to forecast the impact of driverless vehicles in a variety of city environments 3. Create a back-casting tool to enable authorities to determine which policies and measures to implement to achieve a desired long-term vision 4. Develop a web-based Policy Support Tool that will make the LEVITATE impact assessment framework user friendly for public authorities and transport planners 5. Formulate policy recommendations building on the learnings of the impact assessments 6. Enable structured exchange with stakeholders to have a wider basis for bringing in user requirements and to enable a continuous dialogue on the impact assessment of CATs <p>(https://levitate-project.eu/about/activities-outputs/, retrieved 10 October 2024)</p>

MOMENTUM

Project Full Title	Modelling Emerging Transport Solutions for Urban Mobility		
Website	https://h2020-momentum.eu/ https://momentum.imet.gr/ https://civitas.eu/projects/momentum https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/815069 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/momentum/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/modelling-emerging-transport-solutions-urban-mobility		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	Empresa Municipal de Transportes de Madrid (EMT Madrid) Irene Blázquez, Irene.Blazquez@emtmadrid.es Niklas Schmalholz, NSchmalholz@polisnetwork.eu		
Project Partners	13 partners Aimsun SLU Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) City of Leuven / Stad Leuven City of Regensburg / Stadt Regensburg Empresa Municipal de Transportes de Madrid (EMT Madrid) International Association of Public Transport / Union Internationale des Transports Publics (UITP) Municipality of Thessaloniki / Dimos Thessalonikis Nommon Solutions and Technologies S.L. POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Technical University of Munich / Technische Universität München (TUM) – Chair of Transportation Systems Engineering Transport & Mobility Leuven (TML) NV University of Deusto / Universidad de la Iglesia de Deusto Entidad Religiosa – Deusto Smart Mobility University of Deusto / Universidad de la Iglesia de Deusto Entidad Religiosa – DeustoTech		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.05.2019	End date	30.04.2022
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Mobility as a Service (MaaS), Connected Automated Vehicles (CAVs), shared mobility, demand responsive transport, data analysis, transport models, planning support tools, travel behaviour, new mobility systems, big data, transport planning		
Case Studies	Case Studies: Madrid, Leuven, Regensburg, Thessaloniki		

Disruptive technologies, such as MaaS and CAVs, are bringing radical changes in urban mobility. The goal of MOMENTUM is to develop a set of new data analysis methods, transport models and planning support tools able to capture the impact of new transport options on urban mobility, in order to support cities in the task of designing the right policy mix to exploit the full potential of emerging mobility solutions. The specific objectives of the project are:

1. Identify a set of plausible future scenarios for the next decade to be taken into account for mobility planning in European cities, considering the introduction of disruptive technologies such as CAVs.
2. Characterise emerging activity-travel patterns, by profiting from the increasing availability of high-resolution spatio-temporal data collected from personal mobile devices and digital sensors.
3. Develop data-driven predictive models of the adoption and use of new mobility concepts and transport solutions, in particular MaaS and shared mobility, and their interaction with public transport.
4. Provide transport simulation and planning support tools able to cope with the new challenges faced by transport planning, by enhancing existing state-of-the-art tools with the new data analysis methods and travel demand models developed by the project.
5. Demonstrate the potential of the newly developed methods and tools by testing the impact of a variety of policies and innovative transport services in different European cities with heterogeneous sizes and characteristics, namely Madrid, Thessaloniki, Leuven, and Regensburg, and evaluating the contribution of the proposed measures to the strategic policy goals of each city.
6. Provide guidelines for the practical use of the methods, tools and lessons learnt delivered by the project in the elaboration and implementation of SUMP and other planning instruments.

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/815069>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

HARMONY

Project Full Title	Holistic Approach for Providing Spatial & Transport Planning Tools and Evidence to Metropolitan and Regional Authorities to Lead a Sustainable Transition to a New Mobility Era		
Website	https://harmony-h2020.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/harmony https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/815269 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/title-holistic-approach-providing-spatial-transport-planning-tools-and-evidence		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	University College London (UCL) – Energy Institute Maria Kamargianni, m.kamargianni@ucl.ac.uk		
Project Partners	<p>22 partners</p> <p>Aimsun SLU</p> <p>Airbus Defence and Space GmbH</p> <p>Anaptyxiaki Etaireia Dimou Trikkaion Anaptyxiaki Anonymi Etaireia OTA / E-Trikala AE</p> <p>Arrival Ltd</p> <p>Associazione Urban Lab</p> <p>Athens Urban Transport Organisation / Organismos Astikon Sygkoinonion Athinon AE (OASA S.A.)</p> <p>City of Turin / Comune di Torino</p> <p>Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft)</p> <p>ENIDE Solutions S.L.</p> <p>Griff Aviation AS</p> <p>Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) / Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institutouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston</p> <p>Metropolis GZM / Upper Silesian-Zaglebie Metropolis / Górnośląsko-Zagłębiowska Metropolia</p> <p>MOBY X SOFTWARE Ltd</p> <p>Municipality of Rotterdam / Gemeente Rotterdam</p> <p>Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research / Nederlandse Organisatie voor toegepast-natuurwetenschappelijk onderzoek (TNO)</p> <p>Oxfordshire County Council</p> <p>Significance B.V.</p> <p>TRT Trasporti e Territorio s.r.l.</p> <p>University College London (UCL) – Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis (CASA)</p> <p>University College London (UCL) – Energy Institute</p> <p>University of the Aegean / Panepistimio Aigaiou – Department of Shipping, Trade and Transport</p> <p>University of Wolverhampton – Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) lab</p>		
Duration (months)	45		
Start date	01.06.2019	End date	28.02.2023
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <p>1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options</p> <p>4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p>		

	<p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity</p> <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society</p>
Keywords	Low-carbon new mobility era, new mobility services for people and freight, co-creation labs, urban mobility transition, spatial and multimodal transport planning tools, SUMP, automated vehicles, drones, data integration, model suite (MS), TEN-T corridors
Case Studies	Rotterdam, Oxfordshire, Turin, Athens, Trikala, Upper Silesian-Zaglebie Metropolis
<p>The transport sector has been singularly unsuccessful in becoming low carbon and less resource intensive. The EU-funded HARMONY project aims to develop a new generation of harmonised spatial and multimodal transport planning tools that will enable metropolitan authorities to lead the transition to a low carbon new mobility era in a sustainable manner. The HARMONY model provides an integrated approach necessary for authorities which quantifies the multidimensional impact of various concepts, soft and hard policies on citizens' quality of life, sustainability, economic growth, while identifying the most appropriate solutions and recommending ways to exploit advances in mobility concepts. The model suite is already linked to six EU metropolitan areas assisting research: Rotterdam, Oxfordshire, Turin, Athens, Trikala and Upper Silesian-Zaglebie Metropolis.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/815269, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

ReVeAL

Project Full Title	Regulating Vehicle Access for Improved Liveability		
Website	https://civitas-reveal.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/reveal https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/815008 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/reveal/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/regulating-vehicle-access-improved-livability Reveal Toolkit http://accessregulationsforyourcity.eu/tool/		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	City of Bielefeld / Stadt Bielefeld Olaf Lewald (City of Bielefeld), olaf.lewald@bielefeld.de Bonnie Fenton (Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH), b.fenton@rupprecht-consult.eu		
Project Partners	15 partners Centro de Estudios Ambientales (CEA) City of Bielefeld / Stadt Bielefeld Ghent University / Universiteit Gent – Department of Industrial Systems Engineering and Product Design Municipality of Helmond / Gemeente Helmond Municipality of Jerusalem Municipality of Padua / Comune di Padova POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH Sadler Consultants Europe GmbH The Mayor and Commonalty and Citizens of the City of London Transport for London TRT Trasporti e Territorio s.r.l. Università degli Studi di Padova V-tron B.V. WSP Sverige AB		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.06.2019	End date	30.11.2022
Key Area(s)	KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		

Keywords	Urban Vehicle Access Regulations (UVAR), urban mobility transition, spatial interventions, reallocation of parking and road space, pricing aspects, regulatory measures, Zero Emission Zones, user needs and public acceptance, compliance
Case Studies	Pilot cities: Bielefeld, City of London, Helmond, Jerusalem, Padova, Vitoria-Gasteiz
<p>The goal of ReVeAL is to add Urban Vehicle Access Regulations (UVAR) to the standard range of urban mobility transition approaches of cities across Europe. The EU funded R&I ReVeAL project looks at this hot topic for the first time since the CURACAO project (ending a decade ago).</p> <p>The overarching mission of the project is to enable cities to optimise urban space and transport network usage through new and integrated packages of urban vehicle access policies and technologies. Such policies can lead to fewer emissions, less noise and improved accessibility and quality of life, which especially benefits the people living in these cities. These policies can also encourage more sustainable transport choices, enabling cities to become more liveable, ultimately healthier and more attractive for every member of society.</p> <p>To this end, ReVeAL combines conceptual work and case study research with hands-on UVAR implementation in six pilot cities, as well as systematic stakeholder interaction through professional communication activities.</p> <p>(https://civitas-reveal.eu/about/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

Sprout

Project Full Title	Sustainable Policy RespOnse to Urban mobility Transition
Website	https://sprout-civitas.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/sprout https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/814910 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/sprout/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/sustainable-policy-response-urban-mobility-transition Sprout Toolbox http://sprouttoolbox.nuacampus.org/
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020
Project Coordinator	Fundación Zaragoza Logistics Center Maria Teresa de la Cruz Eiriz, mdelacruz@zlc.edu.es
Project Partners	33 partners Agencia Municipal de Energia de Almada (AGENEAL) Almada City Council / Municipio de Almada BKK Centre for Budapest Transport / Budapesti Közlekedési Központ Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság Budapest Közút Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) City Hall of Valencia / Ayuntamiento de València City of Gothenburg / Goteborgs Kommun / Göteborgs Stad City of Kalisz / Miasto Kalisz City of Mechelen / Stad Mechelen City of Minneapolis Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat Valenciana Fundación de la Comunidad Valenciana para la Investigación, Promoción y Estudios Comerciales de Valenciaport Fundación Zaragoza Logistics Center Fundacja Kaliski Inkubator Przedsiębiorczości Łukasiewicz Research Network / Sieć Badawcza Łukasiewicz – Poznań Institute of Technology / Poznański Instytut Technologiczny Municipality of Arad / Municipiul Arad Municipality of Ioannina Municipality of Padua / Comune di Padova Municipality of 's-Hertogenbosch / Gemeente 's-Hertogenbosch Ningbo Municipal Bureau of Commerce Ningbo Supply Chain Innovation Institut China Ningbo University of Technology POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Région Île-de-France Technion – Israel Institute of Technology Tel Aviv Yafo Municipality

	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) – Centro de Investigación del Transporte (TRANSyT) Venice International University (VIU) – TeDIS Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Business technology and Operations Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electromobility research centre (MOBI) Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Mobilise West Midlands Combined Authority Wuppertal Institut für Klima, Umwelt, Energie gGmbH		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.09.2019	End date	28.02.2023
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Urban mobility transition, innovative data driven policy response, user needs, digitally enabled operating and business models, Open Innovation Community, policy-making capacity		
Case Studies	Pilot cities: Valencia, Padua, Kalisz, Budapest, Tel Aviv, Ningbo Validation cities: Minneapolis, West Midlands, Gothenburg, Almada, Île-de-France, Mechelen, Arad, Ioannina, 's-Hertogenbosch		
<p>SPROUT provides a new city-led innovative and data-driven policy response to address the impacts of emerging mobility patterns, digitally-enabled operating & business models, and transport users' needs. Starting from an understanding of the transition in urban mobility, the project will define the impacts on the sustainability and policy level. It will also harness these through a city-led innovative policy response. The aim is to build cities' data-driven capacity to identify, track and deploy innovative urban mobility solutions. The findings will help navigate future policy. To achieve its goals, SPROUT is creating an Open Innovation Community on Urban Mobility Policy and will employ 6 city pilots and 7 validation cities with real-life policy challenges faced as a result of urban mobility transition in both passenger and freight transport.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/814910, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

SUMP-PLUS

Project Full Title	Sustainable Urban Mobility Planning: Pathways and Links to Urban Systems		
Website	https://sump-plus.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/sump-plus https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/814881 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/sustainable-urban-mobility-planning-pathways-and-links-urban-systems		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	City of Antwerp / Stad Antwerpen Marijke De Roeck, Marijke.DeRoeck@stad.Antwerpen.be		
Project Partners	<p>19 partners</p> <p>Austrian Mobility Research / Forschungsgesellschaft Mobilität (FGM) – AMOR Gemeinnützige GmbH City of Antwerp / Stad Antwerpen City of Lucca / Comune di Lucca European Integrated Project Fondation Nationale des Sciences Politiques (Sciences Po) ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH / ICLEI Europasekretariat GmbH International Association of Public Transport / Union Internationale des Transports Publics (UITP) Klaipeda City Municipality Administration / Klaipėdos Miesto Savivaldybės Administracija MemEx s.r.l. Municipality of Alba Iulia Municipality of Platania / Dimos Platania SLR Consulting Ltd SLR Environmental Consulting (Ireland) Ltd Space Syntax Ltd Technical University of Crete / Polytechnio Kritis (TUC) – Renewable and Sustainable Energy Systems Laboratory (ReSEL-TUC) Transport for Greater Manchester (TFGM) University College London (UCL) – Department of Civil, Environment & Geomatic Engineering Vectos (South) Ltd Vectos GmbH</p>		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.09.2019	End date	28.02.2023
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options</p> <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>		

Keywords	SUMP implantation processes, sustainable urban transformation, co-creation laboratories, cross-sectoral links, implementation gap, mobility solutions for freight and passenger transport, public-private partnerships, business models, capacity building, context-specific implementation pathways, accessibility planning, CityConsult Agency
Case Studies	City Laboratories: Alba Iulia, Antwerp, Greater Manchester, Klaipeda, Lucca, Platania 19 Follow Cities
<p>In recent years, local and regional authorities have become increasingly interested in engaging in strategic mobility plans, encouraging a shift towards more sustainable transport modes. The EU-funded SUMP-PLUS project provides for a three-year research plan designed to address challenges linked to urban mobility. It also aims to exploit new opportunities by developing a strong, rigorous evidence base. SUMP-PLUS will develop and apply transition pathways towards more sustainable cities, taking into account the need to establish stronger links with other urban system components. The project aims to set up a programme of trials and comprehensive evaluation in six co-created City Laboratories.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/814881, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

WeCount

Project Full Title	Citizens Observing Urban Transport		
Website	https://we-count.net/ https://www.tmleuven.be/en/project/wecount https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872743 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/wecount/		
Call	H2020-SwafS-2018-2020		
Project Coordinator	Transport & Mobility Leuven (TML) NV Griet De Ceuster, griet.deceuster@tmleuven.be info@we-count.net		
Project Partners	7 partners Ideas 3493 S.L. / Ideas for Change (IFC) Mobiel 21 vzw POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Transport & Mobility Leuven (TML) NV University College Dublin (UCD), National University of Ireland, Dublin – Spatial Dynamics Lab University of Ljubljana / Univerza v Ljubljani – Faculty of Architecture University of the West of England (UWE Bristol) – Science Communication Unit		
Duration (months)	24		
Start date	01.12.2019	End date	30.11.2021
Key Area(s)	Focus: traffic data through citizens science KA1 Smart Urban Mobility KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Live traffic counting by citizens, transport policy-making and research, sustainable urban mobility, neighbourhoods, production of data evidence and knowledge, participatory citizen science methods, multi-stakeholder engagement mechanisms, cost-effective data, road transport challenges, involvement of disadvantaged groups, air quality, cycling		
Case Studies	Madrid, Barcelona, Leuven, Ljubljana, Dublin, Cardiff		
<p>WeCount aims to empower citizens to take a leading role in the production of data, evidence and knowledge around mobility in their own neighbourhoods, and at street level. The project will follow participatory citizen science methods to co-create and use innovative low cost, automated, road traffic counting sensors (i.e. Telraam) and multi-stakeholder engagement mechanisms in 5 pilots in Madrid, Ljubljana, Dublin, Cardiff and Leuven. Following this approach, we will be able to quantify local road transport (cars, large vehicles, active travel modes and speed), produce scientific knowledge in the field of mobility and environmental pollution, and co-design informed solutions to tackle a variety of road transport challenges. Moreover, the project will provide cost-effective data for local authorities, at a far</p>			

greater temporal and spatial scale than what would be possible in classic traffic counting campaigns, thereby opening up new opportunities for transportation policy making and research.

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872743>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

INDIMO

Project Full Title	Inclusive digital mobility solutions		
Website	https://www.indimoproject.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/875533 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/indimo/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/inclusive-digital-mobility-solutions		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Mobilise Imre Keseru, imre.keseru@indimoproject.eu		
Project Partners	<p>15 partners</p> <p>cambiaMO Sociedad cooperative Madrilena CoopCycle Deep Blue s.r.l. Door2Door GmbH European Passengers' Federation IVZW (EPF) Fundación Zaragoza Logistics Center Institute for Transport and Logistics Foundation / Fondazione Istituto sui trasporti e la logistica (ITL) Interuniversity Microelectronics Centre / Interuniversitair Micro-electronica Centrum (IMEC) Mozgássérültek Budapesti Egyesülete POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Poste Italiene S.p.A. Technion – Israel Institute of Technology VDI/VDE Innovation + Technik GmbH Vivero de Iniciativas Ciudadanas (VIC) Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Mobilise</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2020	End date	31.12.2022
Key Area(s)	<p>Focus: inclusive digital mobility</p> <p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 		
Keywords	digital solutions for the management of mobility and logistics, inclusive and accessible services, physically and digitally security, user-friendly, user-centric by design, co-creation process, vulnerable-to-exclusion group		

Case Studies	Madrid, Antwerp, Berlin, Emilia-Romagna, Galilee
<p>New transport products and services should be fully accessible. However, vulnerable groups such as older people, the disabled, ethnic minorities and the poor do not enjoy unrestricted access to those services due to gaps in the development of digital mobility solutions. The EU-funded INDIMO project will support researchers, operators and policymakers to review and integrate the user perspective in the entire design and deployment process of digital mobility solutions. The project deploys an inclusive digital mobility toolbox, which is a complex service comprising a universal design manual, universal language interface icons, guidelines for cybersecurity and data protection as well as a policy evaluation tool. The project will develop strategies to integrate social aspects into the digital mobility design process.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/875533, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

eCharge4Drivers

Project Full Title	Electric Vehicle Charging Infrastructure for improved User Experience
Website	https://echarge4drivers.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/875131 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/echarge4drivers/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/electric-vehicle-charging-infrastructure-improved-user-experience
Call	H2020-LC-GV-2018-2019-2020
Project Coordinator	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) / Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston Angelos Amditis, a.amditis@iccs.gr
Project Partners	<p>32 partners</p> <p>ABB e-mobility B.V. Avesta Battery & Energy Engineering (ABEE) Barcelona de Serveis Municipals SA (B:SM) Barcelona Regional, Agència Metropolitana de Desenvolupament Urbanístic i d'Infraestructures, S.A. Bayerische Motoren Werke Aktiengesellschaft (BMW) Building Facility Services (BFS) / Parochiypiresion Anonymi Etaireia Centro Ricerche Fiat S.C.p.A. Chargery GmbH Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives (CEA) Consorzio Interuniversitario per l'Ottimizzazione e la Ricerca Operativa (ICOOR) Electromaps S.L. European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation – Intelligent Transport Systems & Services Europe (ERTICO – ITS Europe) Grenoble-Alpes Métropole (GAM) Hsubject GmbH IDIADA Automotive Technology S.A. Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) / Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston Mosaic Factor S.L. Nexxlab SA Open Technology Services AE (OTS) POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Politecnico di Milano (POLIMI) – Dipartimento di Elettronica, Informazione e Bioingegneria (DEIB) Polytechnic University of Bari / Politecnico di Bari (POLIBA) Powerdale Robert Bosch GmbH Route220 s.r.l. / ewway Scutum Logistic S.L. Smatrix GmbH & Co KG Swobbee GmbH The University of Sussex – Thermo-Fluid Mechanics Research Centre</p>

	Università degli studi di Modena e Reggio Emilia (Unimore) – Dipartimento di Scienze e Metodi dell'Ingegneria Università di Pisa – Department of Information Engineering (DII) Verbund AG Volvo Cars / Volvo personvagnar AB Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Business technology and Operations Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electrical Engineering and Power Electronics Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electromobility research centre (MOBI) Zorlu Enerji Elektrik Uretim		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.06.2020	End date	31.05.2024
Key Area(s)	Focus: Charging solutions for e-vehicles KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 3. Provide sustainable solutions for longer trips 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Electric vehicles, charging experience in urban areas, Electric Vehicle Charging Location Planning Tool, guidelines for investors and authorities, sustainability of charging infrastructure and services, user-friendly charging stations, innovative charging solutions, smart services, market models		
Case Studies	Demonstration sites: Barcelona, Grenoble, Berlin, Luxembourg, Zellik, Bari, TEN-T corridors (Austria, Northern Italy, Greece, Istanbul & Western Turkey)		
<p>As the popularity of electric vehicles (EV) grows, users' needs and expectations on charging solutions and services are increasing. The EU-funded eCharge4Drivers project will improve the user experience as regards available charging options and services. Specifically, it will develop and demonstrate user-friendly charging stations, smart services and charging solutions, including mobile charging and battery swapping stations. User-centric services such as route planning, booking, and charging location planning will be developed to further improve users' experience and foster e-mobility growth. The project's user-friendly charging systems and interoperable services will be demonstrated in 10 areas, covering cities, the Trans-European Transport Network and cross-border routes. The project will conclude with recommendations for legislative and regulatory amendments, as well as guidelines for the sustainability of charging infrastructure investments.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/875131, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

LEAD

Project Full Title	Low-Emission Adaptive last mile logistics supporting 'on Demand economy' through digital twins
Website	https://www.leadproject.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/lead https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/861598 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/lead/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/low-emission-adaptive-last-mile-logistics-supporting-demand-economy-through-digital-twins
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020
Project Coordinator	Empresa Municipal de Transportes de Madrid (EMT Madrid) Irene Blázquez, Irene.BlazquezJimenez@emtmadrid.es
Project Partners	31 partners Argusi B.V. BKK Centre for Budapest Transport / Budapesti Közlekedési Központ Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság City of Oslo / Oslo Kommune CITYlogin Iberica S.L. Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) DHL Express Netherlands B.V. Elergone Energia LDA Empresa Municipal de Transportes de Madrid (EMT Madrid) Fundación Zaragoza Logistics Center Inlecom Innovation Astiki Mi Kerdoskopiki Etaireia Institut de recherche technologique SystemX (IRT SystemX) Last Mile Team S.L. Lyon Confluence Lyon Park Auto (LPA) MC Shared Services SA / Sonae MC Modelo Continente Hipermercados SA Molde University College / Høgskolen i Molde Municipality of The Hague / Gemeente Den Haag Next2Company B.V. Nimber AS Nimber Tech Anaptyxi Logismikou Monoprosopi EPE Panasonic Business Support Europe GmbH POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Shenzhen Bus Group Co Ltd Shenzhen Haylion Technologies Co Ltd Shenzhen Pengeheng Electric Taxi Co Ltd Southern University of Science and Technology Texas A&M University System Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) – Centro de Investigación del Transporte (TRANSyT)

	University of Győr / Széchenyi István Egyetem Waberers-Szemerey Logisztika Kft		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.06.2020	End date	31.05.2023
Key Area(s)	KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery		
Keywords	Shared-connected and low-emission logistics operations, innovative business models, agile freight storage and distribution, electric delivery vehicles (EDVs), cargo-bikes, delivery robots, smart data driven logistics solutions, CAD technology, digital twins, TEN-T urban nodes, on-demand logistics operations, PI-inspired framework, integrated planning and management		
Case Studies	Digital Twins: Madrid, The Hague, Budapest, Lyon, Oslo, Porto		
<p>Sprawling cities need smart urban logistics to become more environmentally, socially and economically sustainable. It is important for today's tech-savvy city planners to generate simulations that can help guide their future plans. This is why it is necessary for them to make maximum use of the latest computer-aided design (CAD) technology. The EU-funded LEAD project is designing digital twins of urban logistics to support experimentation and decision making in public-private urban settings. Specifically, the project's long-term goal is to develop an open physical internet-inspired framework for smart city logistics. Headed by a large consortium, the project will test its solutions in six cities: Madrid, The Hague, Budapest, Lyon, Oslo and Porto.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/861598, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

Senator

Project Full Title	Smart Network Operator Platform enabling Shared, Integrated and more Sustainable Urban Freight Logistics		
Website	https://www.senatorproject.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/senator https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/861540 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/smart-network-operator-platform-enabling-shared-integrated-and-more-sustainable-urban		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	Sociedad Estatal Correos Y Telegrafos SA SME Santiago Muñoz, santiago.munoz@correos.com		
Project Partners	<p>15 partners</p> <p>An Post</p> <p>City Council of Zaragoza / Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza</p> <p>Correos Express Paqueteria Urgente SA SME</p> <p>Correos Telecom SA SME MP</p> <p>DOTGIS Corporation S.L.</p> <p>Dublin City Council</p> <p>Fundación Zaragoza Ciudad del Conocimiento (FZC)</p> <p>itCampus Software- und Systemhaus GmbH</p> <p>MDS Transmodal Ltd</p> <p>RINA Consulting S.p.A.</p> <p>Sociedad Estatal Correos Y Telegrafos SA SME</p> <p>Software AG</p> <p>University College Dublin (UCD), National University of Ireland, Dublin – School of architecture, Planning and Environmental Policy (APEP)</p> <p>University of Deusto / Universidad de la Iglesia de Deusto Entidad Religiosa – DeustoTech</p> <p>Zabala Innovation Consulting SA</p>		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.09.2020	End date	31.08.2024
Key Area(s)	<p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <p>1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity</p> <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p> <p>2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society</p> <p>3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>		
Keywords	Urban planning policies, governance schemes, user demand planning, transport planning, freight and logistics planning, city infrastructure, common logistics		

	operation framework, city centred and socially inclusive logistic services, new market opportunities
Case Studies	Living Labs: Zaragoza, Dublin
<p>In order to manage urban planning policies in an optimal way, the EU-funded SENATOR project aims to produce governance schemes on user demand planning, transport planning, freight and logistics planning and city infrastructure. Within this scope, the project will create a multi-collaborative framework that will bring together stakeholders in urban freight logistics. A 'control tower' will help plan the operations and ease the relationships between urban planners and urban freight logistics players. Eventually, the project will create a new urban logistic model focussed on the four urban layers (end-receiver, transport, logistics and infrastructure) and enhance citizen engagement in urban planning policies.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/861540, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

ULaaDS

Project Full Title	Urban Logistics as an on Demand Service		
Website	https://ulaads.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/ulaads https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/861833 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/urban-logistics-demand-service		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	Free Hanseatic City of Bremen / Freie Hansestadt Bremen Karsten Hülsemann, karsten.huelsemann@umwelt.bremen.de		
Project Partners	<p>27 partners</p> <p>Allgemeiner Deutscher Fahrrad-Club Landesverband Bremen e.V. (adfc) Austrian Mobility Research / Forschungsgesellschaft Mobilität (FGM) – AMOR Gemeinnützige GmbH Bax Innovation Consulting S.L. / Bax & Company Bpost City Council of Bergen / Bergen Kommune City of Mechelen / Stad Mechelen Dropper B.V. Eurocities ASBL Flanders Institute for Logistics / Vlaams Instituut voor de Logistiek vzw (VIL) Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V. Free Hanseatic City of Bremen / Freie Hansestadt Bremen Groningen City Club Institute of Transport Economics / Transportøkonomisk Institutt (TOI) Interdisziplinäres Forschungszentrum für Technik, Arbeit und Kultur Iv-Ent Miebach Consulting SA Municipality of Alba Iulia Municipality of Groningen / Gemeente Groningen Openbaar Lichaam OV-Bureau Groningen en Drenthe Roma Servizi per la Mobilità s.r.l. / Roma Mobilità Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH RYTLE GmbH to-be-now-logistics-research-gmbh Transport for Edinburgh Ltd University of Groningen / Rijksuniversiteit Groningen UPS Ltd VIA Technologies Europe B.V.</p>		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.09.2020	End date	29.02.2024
Key Area(s)	KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning		

	<p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Support striving neighbourhood economies 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders
Keywords	Innovative shared zero-emission urban logistics, on-demand economy, integrated passenger and urban freight networks, innovative technology solutions, multi-stakeholder collaboration, sharing economy, SUMPs, SULPs, new business models, decision support tools
Case Studies	<p>Lighthouse cities: Bremen, Mechelen, Groningen</p> <p>Satellite cities: Alba Iulia, Bergen, Edinburgh, Rome</p>
<p>The EU-funded ULaaDS project sets out to offer a new approach to system innovation in urban logistics. Its vision is to develop sustainable and liveable cities through re-localisation of logistics activities and re-configuration of freight flows at different scales. Specifically, ULaaDS will use a combination of innovative technology solutions (vehicles, equipment and infrastructure), new schemes for horizontal collaboration (driven by the sharing economy) and policy measures and interventions as catalysers of a systemic change in urban and peri-urban service infrastructure. This aims to support cities in the path of integrating sustainable and cooperative logistics systems into their sustainable urban mobility plans (SUMP). ULaaDS will deliver a novel framework to support urban logistics planning aligning industry, market and government needs, following an intensive multi-stakeholder collaboration process. This will create favourable conditions for the private sector to adopt sustainable principles for urban logistics, while enhancing cities' adaptive capacity to respond to rapidly changing needs. The project findings will be translated into open decision support tools and guidelines.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/861833, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

WE-TRANSFORM

Project Full Title	Workforce Europe – Transformation Agenda for Transport Automation
Website	https://wetransform-project.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006900 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/we-transform/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/workforce-europe-transformation-agenda-transport-automation
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020
Project Coordinator	<p>Politecnico di Torino (POLITO) – Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning (DIST)</p> <p>Cristina Pronello, cristina.pronello@polito.it</p>
Project Partners	<p>34 partners</p> <p>Advanis Inc Akciju sabiedrība Transporta un sakaru institūts AustriaTech – Gesellschaft des Bundes für technologisch-politische Maßnahmen GmbH Board of Regents of Nevada System of Higher Education Elliniko Metro Single Member S.A. Empresa Municipal de Transportes de Valencia (EMT Valencia) Eugenides Foundation / Idryma Evgenidou European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation – Intelligent Transport Systems & Services Europe (ERTICO – ITS Europe) Fabrique – Avvocati Associati Federazione Italiana Lavoratori Trasporti CGIL (FILT CGIL) Federazione Italiana Trasporti CISL (FIT-CISL) Ferrovie dello Stato Italiane S.p.A. Fundación de la Comunidad Valenciana para la Investigación, Promoción y Estudios Comerciales de Valenciaport Fundacja Rozwoju Logistyki i Zarządzania Hellenic Train – Anonymi Sidirodromiki Etaireia Hitachi Rail STS S.p.A. Institut VEDECOM International union of railways / Union Internationale des Chemins de fer (UIC) Keolis NV Kyungil University Leonardo S.p.A. LGI Sustainable Innovation Mercedes-Benz AG Missions Publiques POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Politecnico di Torino (POLITO) – Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning (DIST) Six Seconds Tampereen kaupunkiseudun elinkeinoja kehitysyhtiö Business Tampere Oy Tokai National Higher Education and Research System, National University Corporation</p>

	Uiltrasporti University of Surrey University of the Aegean / Panepistimio Aigaiou University of West Attica / Panepistimio Dytikis Attikis (UNIWA) Virtech OOD		
Duration (months)	40		
Start date	01.12.2020	End date	31.03.2024
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 1. Support striving neighbourhood economies KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Automation, sustainable affordable and accessible mobility services, labour requirements, mobility stakeholders, cross-national living hub, knowledge and action platform, innovative and evidence-based policymaking, collaboration for innovation, automation impacts, advisory board, stakeholder forum, living hub		
Case Studies			
<p>Automation in transport and digitalisation will affect both transport users and its workforce. Currently, there is a knowledge gap regarding the repercussions across the transport chain. The EU-funded WE-TRANSFORM project will combine expertise across all facets of transport and analytical tools and apply a participatory approach, using collective intelligence, to generate an evidence-based and action-oriented agenda to tackle the challenges connected to the effects of automation on the transport labour force, among other things. To do this, the project will establish a collaborative platform for stakeholders that will produce user-friendly and shareable knowledge on automation impacts on transport labour.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006900, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

ASSURED-UAM

Project Full Title	Acceptance, Safety and Sustainability Recommendations for Efficient Deployment of Urban Air Mobility		
Website	https://assured-uam.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/assured-uam https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006696 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/acceptance-safety-and-sustainability-recommendations-efficient-deployment-uam		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	Łukasiewicz Research Network / Sieć Badawcza Łukasiewicz – Institute of Aviation / Instytut Lotnictwa Dziugieł Bartosz, Bartosz.Dziugiel@ilot.lukasiewicz.gov.pl		
Project Partners	8 partners CEiiA Centro de Engenharia e Desenvolvimento (Associacao) Distretto Tecnologico Aerospaziale scarl (DTA) Istituto di Studi per l'Integrazione dei Sistemi (I.S.I.S) – Società cooperativa Italian Aerospace Research Center / Centro Italiano Ricerche Aerospaziali (CIRA) Italian Institute for Sustainable Society and Innovation / Fondazione Institute for Sustainable Society and Innovation (ISSNOVA) Łukasiewicz Research Network / Sieć Badawcza Łukasiewicz – Institute of Aviation / Instytut Lotnictwa Metropolis GZM / Upper Silesian-Zaglebie Metropolis / Górnośląsko-Zagłębiowska Metropolia Royal Netherlands Aerospace Centre / Stichting Koninklijk Nederlands Lucht – en Ruimtevaartcentrum (NLR)		
Duration (months)	28		
Start date	01.01.2021	End date	30.04.2023
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Urban Air Mobility (UAM), safety, sustainability, acceptability, policy definition support, U-Space Air Traffic Management System, UAM community integration, cooperation		
Case Studies	Górnośląsko-Zagłębiowska Metropolia, Bari, Porto		
Urban Air Mobility (UAM) services will be more and more deployed in the near future. The ASSURED-UAM project aims to guarantee outstanding robustness in terms of safety, sustainability and acceptability of UAM. It will promote aviation best practices, standards, recommendations and organizational solutions to			

the administrative and legislative bodies. Authorities, policy makers and urban industry organizations will receive complete policy definition support in order to implement vertical transport with the horizontal urban space and peri-urban mobility systems. Moreover, the project will carry out the U-Space Air Traffic Management System, so that the introduction of unmanned UAM will be well integrated with organizational and policy framework.

The project will look at scenarios for up to 10 use cases within 5, 10 and 15-years' timeframe, make knowledge base and policy recommendations in 8 languages. It will create standards for products and processes as well as tools for exchange and learning of Urban Air Mobility, project development support and technical assistance. There will be UAM community integration and wide consultations, cooperation, and synergy with other projects, industry and user groups.

(<https://assured-uam.eu/>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

FastTrack

Project Full Title	Fostering the Acceleration of Sustainable Transport To Regions and Authorities through Capacity and Knowledge		
Website	https://fasttrackmobility.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/fasttrack https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006853 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/fostering-acceleration-sustainable-transport-regions-and-authorities-through-capacity-and		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH / ICLEI Europasekretariat GmbH Ana Drăguțescu, ana.dragutescu@iclei.org		
Project Partners	<p>11 partners</p> <p>BKK Centre for Budapest Transport / Budapesti Közlekedési Központ Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság</p> <p>Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT)</p> <p>City of Antwerp / Stad Antwerpen</p> <p>City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad</p> <p>Eurocities ASBL</p> <p>European Integrated Project</p> <p>ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH / ICLEI Europasekretariat GmbH</p> <p>Mobiel 21 vzw</p> <p>Municipality of Bologna / Comune di Bologna</p> <p>Municipality of Budapest / Budapest Főváros Önkormányzata</p> <p>Vectos GmbH</p>		
Duration (months)	30		
Start date	01.02.2021	End date	31.07.2023
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies 4. Support sustainable lifestyles <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		

Keywords	Urban and peri-urban areas, knowledge-sharing, capacity-building, sustainable mobility innovation deployment plans, accelerate transition to sustainable transport, learning programme
Case Studies	24 urban and peri-urban areas Ambassadors: Antwerp, Bologna, Budapest, Stockholm
<p>Urban transport is strategically important for the economic competitiveness, social cohesion and sustainable growth of Europe. The EU is encouraging cities and towns to move towards sustainable and integrated urban transport. To support these efforts, the EU-funded FastTrack project will deliver climate-resilient urban, peri-urban and rural areas through the deployment of sustainable mobility innovations across two dozen local areas, involving local authority project affiliates and several ambassadorial partners. The project will present a suite of interlinking methods that provide local authorities with opportunities to learn from the best, capturing and presenting the experiences of those who have already accelerated transition successfully.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006853, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

MobiDataLab

Project Full Title	Labs for prototyping future Mobility Data sharing cloud solutions		
Website	https://mobidatalab.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006879 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/mobidatalab/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/labs-prototyping-future-mobility-data-sharing-cloud-solutions		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	AKKODIS (AKKA I&S) Thierry Chevallier, thierry.chevallier@akka.eu		
Project Partners	13 partners AETHON Engineering Single Member PC AKKODIS (AKKA I&S) Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – Institute for Information Science and Technologies (CNR-ISTI) Consorzio Interuniversitario per l'Ottimizzazione e la Ricerca Operativa (ICOOR) F6S Network Ireland Ltd F6S Network Ltd HERE Deutschland GmbH & Co KG HERE Global B.V. HOVE Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (KULeuven) – Research Centre for IT & IP Law (CiTiP) POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale The public university of Tarragona / Universitat Rovira i Virgili (URV) – CRISES research group Università degli studi di Modena e Reggio Emilia (Unimore)		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.02.2021	End date	31.01.2024
Key Area(s)	Focus: mobility data share, cloud-based service platform KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	new mobility data sharing solutions, open tools, hackathons, Open Knowledge Base, Transport cloud prototype, living and virtual labs, socio-economic impact		
Case Studies			
<p>There has been an explosion of mobility services and data sharing in recent years. The EU-funded MobiDataLab project will work to foster the sharing of data amongst transport authorities, operators and other mobility stakeholders in Europe. It will develop knowledge as well as a cloud solution aimed at easing the sharing of data. Specifically, the project is based on a continuous co-development of knowledge</p>			

and technical solutions. It will collect and analyse the advice and recommendations of experts and supporting cities, regions, clusters and associations. These actions will be assisted by the incremental construction of a cross-thematic knowledge base and a cloud-based service platform, which will improve access and usage of data sharing resources.

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006879>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

RECIPROCITY

Project Full Title	Replication of innovative concepts for peri-urban, rural or inner-city mobility		
Website	https://reciprocity-project.eu/ https://www.arrival-platform.eu/portal/log-in.html https://civitas.eu/projects/reciprocity https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006576 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/replication-innovative-concepts-peri-urban-rural-or-inner-city-mobility		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	R-Tech GmbH Anne Häner, anne.haener@techbase.de Uwe Pfeil, uwe.pfeil@techbase.de		
Project Partners	12 partners Business Upper Austria / OÖ Wirtschaftsagentur GmbH Dowel Innovation European Regions Research and Innovation Network Greenovate ! Europe Helsinki-Uusimaa Regional Council / Uudenmaan Liitto Instituto Aragonés de Fomento Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón Istanbul Okan University / İstanbul Okan Üniversitesi Mov'eo / NextMove Regionální rozvojová agentura Plzeňského kraje o.p.s. (RRA PK) R-Tech GmbH ZONE Klaszter Nonprofit Korlatolt Felelessegu Tarsasag / Connected and Automated Mobility Cluster of Zala		
Duration (months)	32		
Start date	01.02.2021	End date	30.09.2023
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Accelerating replication for smarter and cleaner mobility, connected multimodal nodes, replication framework, urban and peri-urban areas, knowledge exchange, partnerships, existing innovative mobility solutions, Information and Communication Platform		
Case Studies	Rambouillet, Milan, Würzburg, Perg, Zaanstad, Porvoo, Zalaegerszeg, Tuzla Belediye Baskanligi, Kaposvar, Birmingham, Pendik, Derry, La Rochelle, Regensburg, Rovereto, Lohja, Tomar, Gaziantep, Pardubice, Riihimäki, Ingostadt, Huesca, Clermont		

	Auvergne, Passau, Coventry, Nagykanisza, Pilsen, Département du Val d’Oise, Teruel, Werfenweng, Guldborgsund, Örebro, Jihlava, Koprivnica
<p>The EU-funded RECIPROCITY project will initiate innovative mobility solutions in at least 20 European cities and municipalities to tackle the challenges of urbanisation, climate change and digitalisation - megatrends that make a rethink of mobility inevitable. Areas that differ in size, location, degree of urbanisation and mobility needs will be equipped with tools, knowledge and contacts to accelerate the development process of innovative mobility solutions. Workshops, webinars and matchmaking events will help form new partnerships and local exchange to strengthen networking and knowledge sharing. Successful examples are then to be replicated in other partner regions to make innovative mobility solutions quickly and easily accessible to a larger circle of cities and municipalities.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006576, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

MOVE 21

Project Full Title	Multimodal and interconnected hubs for freight and passenger transport contributing to a zero emission 21st century		
Website	https://move21.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/move21 https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/953939 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/move21/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/multimodal-and-interconnected-hubs-freight-and-passenger-transport-contributing-zero		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	City of Oslo / Oslo Kommune Tiina Ruohonen, tiina.ruohonen@byr.oslo.kommune.no		
Project Partners	<p>25 partners</p> <p>Business Region Göteborg AB (BRG)</p> <p>Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT)</p> <p>City of Gothenburg / Goteborgs Kommun / Göteborgs Stad</p> <p>City of Munich / Landeshauptstadt München</p> <p>City of Oslo / Oslo Kommune</p> <p>DB Station&Service AG</p> <p>Eurocities ASBL</p> <p>Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg / Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg</p> <p>Göteborgs Stads Parkerings AB</p> <p>HafenCity Universität Hamburg (HCU) – CityScienceLab</p> <p>HafenCity Universität Hamburg (HCU) – Fachbereich Digital City Science</p> <p>IKT-Norge</p> <p>Institute of Transport Economics / Transportøkonomisk Institutt (TOI)</p> <p>Metropolitan City of Bologna / Città metropolitana di Bologna</p> <p>MIXMOVE AS</p> <p>Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research / Nederlandse Organisatie voor toegepast-natuurwetenschappelijk onderzoek (TNO)</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>Renova AB</p> <p>RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB</p> <p>Roma Servizi per la Mobilità s.r.l. / Roma Mobilità</p> <p>Ruter AS</p> <p>Università degli Studi Roma Tre – Dipartimento di Scienze Politiche</p> <p>Urban Sharing AS</p> <p>Viken County / Viken fylkeskommune</p> <p>Volvo Technology AB</p>		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.05.2021	End date	30.04.2025

Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments
Keywords	<p>Integration of passenger and freight transport, smart zero emissions nodes for mobility and logistics, mobility hubs, new governance models, combined technological and non-technological innovations, business and collaboration models, policy integration, social cohesion, Scan-Med Observatory, electric and biofuel-based vehicles, shared charging infrastructures</p>
Case Studies	<p>Living Labs: Oslo, Gothenburg, Hamburg</p> <p>Replicator cities: Munich, Bologna, Rome</p> <p>Cascade cities: Bilbao, Murcia, Sofia, Stockholm, Thessaloniki, Toulouse</p>
<p>The rapid transition to zero emissions and climate resilient transport systems requires an integrated approach to passenger and freight transport. The EU-funded MOVE21 project will tackle six urban nodes, from policy definition to planning and implementation in the participating cities. The integrated and holistic approach of MOVE21 ensures that potential negative effects from zero emission solutions in one field are not transferred to other domains, ultimately boosting the resilience of the European transport systems. MOVE21 will work through the Living Labs of Gothenburg, Hamburg and Oslo and the three replicator cities Bologna, Munich and Rome. It will test different mobility hubs and innovations and develop means for clean and smart mobility and logistics.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/953939, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

SCALE-UP

Project Full Title	Scale up user-Centric & dAta driven soLutions for ConnEcted Urban Poles		
Website	https://www.scale-up-project.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/scale-up https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/955332 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/scale-user-centric-and-data-driven-solutions-connected-urban-poles		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	City of Antwerp / Stad Antwerpen Marijke De Roeck, marijke.deroeck@stad.antwerpen.be		
Project Partners	<p>24 partners</p> <p>Avanza Bike S.L. Ayesa Advanced Technologies SA Beheersmaatschappij Antwerpen Mobiel (Lantis) Be-Mobile City Council of Madrid / Ayuntamiento de Madrid City of Antwerp / Stad Antwerpen City of Turku / Turun kaupunki Consortio Regional de Transportes Públicos Regulares de Madrid Ecorys Nederland B.V. Empresa Municipal de Transportes de Madrid (EMT Madrid) ETRA Investigacion y Desarrollo SA Eurocities ASBL Flanders / Vlaanderen / Vlaamse Gewest / Vlaams Gewest Hacon Ingenieurgesellschaft mbH Port of Antwerp-Bruges / Haven van Antwerpen-Brugge Province of Antwerp / Provincie Antwerpen Regional Council of Southwest Finland / Varsinais-Suomen liitto Siemens Rail Automation SA Smart Transportation Alliance (STA) Traject NV Transport & Mobility Leuven (TML) NV Turku University of Applied Sciences / Turun ammattikorkeakoulu OY Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) – Centro de Investigación del Transporte (TRANSyT) Vinka OY</p>		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.06.2021	End date	31.05.2025
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 3. Provide sustainable solutions for longer trips 4. Integrate new technologies in transport		

	<p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity</p> <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p>
Keywords	Urban nodes, innovative mobility measures, vertical and horizontal upscaling, multi-modal transport systems for passengers and freight, multi-level governance models, multi-stakeholder cooperation, data driven strategies, clean safe and inclusive mobility, behavioural change, knowledge exchange
Case Studies	Urban nodes: Antwerp, Madrid, Turku
<p>Transport today represents almost a quarter of Europe's greenhouse gas emissions. To reduce the share of transport and mobility emissions, urban transport systems need to move people and goods using more sustainable modes. Mobility initiatives need to be smart, clean and inclusive. The EU-funded SCALE-UP project will explore such solutions. It will assist three European urban nodes (Madrid in Spain, Antwerp in Belgium, and Turku in Finland) in becoming better connected and climate resilient while developing and operating complex multimodal transport systems, which can easily be scaled up. Specifically, the project will aim to improve the multilevel and multi-stakeholder governance enabling seamless multimodal transport across and beyond the three urban nodes.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/955332, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

DIT4TraM

Project Full Title	Distributed Intelligence and Technology for Traffic and Mobility Management		
Website	https://dit4tram.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/953783 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/dit4tram/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/distributed-intelligence-and-technology-traffic-and-mobility-management		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – Department of Transport and Planning – Mobility Innovation Centre Delft (MICD) Dr. ir. Sascha Hoogendoorn-Lanser, S.Hoogendoorn-Lanser@tudelft.nl Prof. dr. ir. Serge Hoogendoorn, S.P.Hoogendoorn@tudelft.nl		
Project Partners	22 partners Aimsun SLU Arane Adviseurs in Vekeer en Vervoer B.V. Bar-Ilan University Bestmile SA Bordeaux Metropole City of Amsterdam / Gemeente Amsterdam City of Utrecht / Gemeente Utrecht D.E.I.A. Development Engineering Infrastructure Association Ltd Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – Department of Transport and Planning Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – Mobility Innovation Centre Delft (MICD) École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich (ETH Zurich) – Computational Social Science GERTRUDE Saem, Système de Transport Intelligent Glyfada Municipality National Technical University of Athens / Ethnicon Metsovion Polytechnion (NTUA) – Traffic Engineering Laboratory NeoGLS OSeven Single Member Private Company / OSeven Telematics POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Siemens Mobility GmbH Stichting Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions (AMS) Technolution B.V. Université Gustave Eiffel		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.09.2021	End date	31.08.2024
Key Area(s)	Focus: Swarm intelligence concepts and algorithms		

	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies
Keywords	Swarm intelligence approach, Traffic and mobility management, local and bottom-up regulation, connected cars, smart bicycles, intelligent traffic control systems, smooth and safe traffic flow, decentralized solutions, distributed intelligence
Case Studies	Pilot studies: Bordeaux, Glyfada, Athens, Amsterdam, Utrecht, AP-7 freeway (Spain)
<p>The way people and products move has changed dramatically over the past decades and will continue to evolve for many more. The mobility ecosystem is undergoing a remarkable transformational shift on all fronts: technological, social and economic. In this context, the EU funded DIT4TraM project will explore smart ways to manage traffic which is driven more and more by user-centred mobility services and integrated and intelligent transport networks. It will develop and test a holistic approach to decentralisation, distribution and mechanism design for traffic and mobility management. The project's goal is to accelerate the transition to seamless and sustainable connected and autonomous mobility. The findings will lay the foundation for a 180 degree paradigm shift in traffic and mobility management.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/953783, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

TANGENT

Project Full Title	Enhanced Data Processing Techniques for Dynamic Management of Multimodal Traffic		
Website	https://tangent-h2020.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/955273 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/tangent/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/enhanced-data-processing-techniques-dynamic-management-multimodal-traffic		
Call	H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020		
Project Coordinator	University of Deusto / Universidad de la Iglesia de Deusto Entidad Religiosa – DeustoTech Leire Serrano, leire.sezrrano@deusto.es		
Project Partners	16 partners Aimsun SLU Atobe – Mobility Technology SA Cefriel Società consortile a responsabilità limitata Società benefit Companhia Carris de Ferro de Lisboa EM SA Eegle Interuniversity Microelectronics Centre / Interuniversitair Micro-electronica Centrum (IMEC) Keolis NV National Technical University of Athens / Ethnicon Metsovion Polytechnion (NTUA) – Traffic Engineering Laboratory Panteia B.V. Pôle de compétitivité Idforcar / ID4MOBILITY POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Rennes Métropole Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH Transport for Greater Manchester (TFGM) University of Deusto / Universidad de la Iglesia de Deusto Entidad Religiosa – DeustoTech Via Verde Portugal – Gestão de Sistemas Electrónicos de Cobrança SA		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.09.2021	End date	31.08.2024
Key Area(s)	Focus: Data processing for multimodal traffic KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition		
Keywords	Efficient traffic operations, multimodal transport networks, management of mobility flows, innovative mobility solutions, business models, connected and automated		

	mobility, passenger and freight transport, Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques, traffic operation decision making support tool, traffic flow and conditions forecast, travel behaviour modelling, data from intermodal mobility, vehicle to user (V2X) communication, Applied Learning Cycle methodology
Case Studies	Pilot cities: Lisbon, Greater Manchester, Rennes, Athens
<p>Transport is at a crossroad. The sector is paved with disruptive technologies and mobility solutions designed to revolutionise transport networks and traffic management. The EU-funded TANGENT project will develop new tools to improve traffic operations in a coordinated way, considering automated and non-automated vehicles, passengers, and freight transport. TANGENT will research advanced techniques on modelling and simulation, such as simulation models for future demand and supply of transport; optimisation techniques for balancing demand flows; and modelling users' travel behaviour. A set of applications for decision-making support will be delivered to provide traffic management recommendations and to support transport authorities in their design of network-wide optimal strategies. Case studies will be conducted in France, Portugal, the UK and Greece.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/955273, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

Horizon Europe

Website	https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/cluster-5-climate-energy-and-mobility_en https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/programme/horizon-europe
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SCALE

Project Full Title	Smart Charging Alignment for Europe
Website	https://scale-horizon.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101056874 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/scale/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/smart-charging-alignment-europe
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D5-01
Project Coordinator	Stichting ElaadNL Baerte de Brey, baerte.de.brey@elaad.nl
Project Partners	<p>29 partners</p> <p>ABB e-mobility B.V.</p> <p>AVERE, The European Association for Electromobility / L'association européenne de la mobilité électrique</p> <p>Bayern Innovativ, Bayerische Gesellschaft für Innovation und Wissenstransfer mbH</p> <p>Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT)</p> <p>Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB – Electrical Engineering</p> <p>City of Utrecht / Gemeente Utrecht</p> <p>Current Eco AS / Current SmartCharge</p> <p>Emobility Solutions Szolgaltato es Kereskedelmi Kft</p> <p>Enedis</p> <p>Enervalis</p> <p>Equigy B.V.</p> <p>FIER B.V.</p> <p>GoodMoovs B.V.</p> <p>Hyundai Motor Netherlands B.V.</p> <p>LEW Verteilnetz GmbH (LVN)</p> <p>Norsk elbilforening / Norwegian EV Association</p> <p>Polestar Performance AB</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>Renault SAS</p> <p>RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB</p> <p>Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH</p> <p>Serviced Office Belbuda Kft</p> <p>Sono Motors GmbH</p> <p>Stichting ElaadNL</p> <p>Trialog</p> <p>Urban Electric Mobility Initiative (UEMI) gGmbH</p> <p>Utrecht University (UU) – Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development</p> <p>VDL Enabling Transport Solutions B.V. (VDL ETS)</p> <p>We Drive Solar NL B.V.</p>
Duration (months)	36

Start date	01.06.2022	End date	31.05.2025
Key Area(s)	Focus: smart charging infrastructure for mass deployment of e-vehicles KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Smart charging infrastructure, mass deployment of electric vehicles, Vehicle to Everything (V2X) solutions, energy eco-system, interoperability, connectivity, fair market conditions, innovations, user-centric approach, acceptance, grid reinforcement, V2X Alliance		
Case Studies	Use Case Locations: Toulouse, Greater Munich Area, Budapest, Debrecen, Oslo, Gothenburg, Rotterdam, Utrecht, Eindhoven		
<p>SCALE is a three-year project (2022-2025) co-funded by the new Horizon Europe Programme with a budget of around 10 million EUR. It aims to advance smart charging infrastructure and facilitate the mass deployment of electric vehicles. The project will reduce uncertainties around the roll-out of smart charging, interoperable and V2X (Vehicle-to-Everything) solutions, whether these are technical, organizational, economic, social or policy-related, and help shape a new energy eco-system wherein the flexibility of EV batteries' is harnessed. A consortium of 29 partners composed of leading European cities, universities and knowledge partners, charging infrastructure companies, electric vehicle (EV) industry pioneers and more will steer the project.</p> <p>(https://scale-horizon.eu/what-is-scale/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

NextETRUCK

Project Full Title	Efficient and affordable Zero Emission logistics through the NEXTgeneration of Electric TRUCKs		
Website	https://nextetruck.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101056740 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/nextetruck/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/efficient-and-affordable-zero-emission-logistics-through-next-generation-electric-trucks		
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D5-01		
Project Coordinator	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research / Nederlandse Organisatie voor toegepast-natuurwetenschappelijk onderzoek (TNO) Dr. Rene Corbeij, rene.corbeij@tno.nl		
Project Partners	19 partners ABB e-mobility Digital Venture GmbH AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH AVL Deutschland GmbH AVL List GmbH CENEX Centre of excellence for low carbon and fuel cell technologies Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT) Datik Informacion Inteligente S.L. European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation – Intelligent Transport Systems & Services Europe (ERTICO – ITS Europe) Ford Otomotiv Sanayi A.Ş. Fundación Cidetec Fundación TECNALIA Research & Innovation Irizar S Coop JEMA Energy SA Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research / Nederlandse Organisatie voor toegepast-natuurwetenschappelijk onderzoek (TNO) NNG Szoftverfejlesztő és Kereskedelmi KFT POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Stichting Cenex Nederland Tevva Motors Ltd Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electromobility research centre (MOBI)		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.07.2022	End date	31.12.2025
Key Area(s)	Focus: next-generation e-vehicles medium-duty KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics		

	KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition
Keywords	zero-emission electric medium freight haulage, sustainable market replenishment, electric powertrain innovations, Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) reduction, business models, end-user acceptance, digital twin design, fleet management tools, ultra-fast charging concepts, local air quality
Case Studies	Trial sites: Istanbul, Utrecht, Barcelona
<p>The commercial freight sector is expected to grow in the coming years, particularly in the medium to heavy truck categories. However, the EU climate goals present a challenge for the transport sector, as substantial technological advances and business changes are needed to achieve zero emissions over the next 30 years. The EU-funded NextETRUCK project will address the challenges of tomorrow’s urban and suburban logistics for electric medium-duty vehicles. The project will demonstrate innovative and affordable zero-emission e-mobility concepts that are both competitive and synergistic. It will also advance knowledge through innovations in e-powertrain components and architectures, intelligent charging infrastructure and management, improved thermal design of the cabin, and fleet management systems utilising IoT and digital tools.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101056740, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

DECARBOMILE

Project Full Title	Five pillars to DECARBOnize the last MILE logistics
Website	https://decarbomile.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/decarbomile https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069806 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/five-pillars-decarbonize-last-mile-logistics
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01
Project Coordinator	Interface Transport Manon Levrey, mlevrey@interface-transport.com
Project Partners	<p>31 partners</p> <p>Association CARA European Cluster for Mobility Solutions Capillar IT S.L. Copenhagen Business School (CBS) – Department of Economics Deutsche Post AG Euroquality SAS Fleximodal Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg / Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg Genegis GI s.r.l. Getafe City Council / Ayuntamiento de Getafe (ADG) Getafe Iniciativas SA Institut Mines-Télécom (IMT) Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón Intelligent Parking S.L. Interface Transport Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality Les Triporteurs Nantais Logistik-Initiative Hamburg Management GmbH Logrono City Hall / Ayuntamiento de Logroño Migros Ticaret AS Ministarstvo saobraćaja Kantona Sarajevo Nantes Métropole / Communauté urbaine de Nantes New Generation Sensors s.r.l. NMS New Mobility Solutions Hamburg GmbH Opleidingscentrum voor Hout en Bouw vzw (OHB) Pôle de compétitivité Idforcar / ID4MOBILITY Red de Ciudades por la Bicicleta Sivas Cumhuriyet Üniversitesi Technische Universität Hamburg / Hamburg University of Technology (TUHH) – Institute for transport planning and logistics The City of Tallinn / Tallinna Linn / Tallinn linnavalitsus Transmetrics Ad Union of the Baltic Cities / Związek Miast Bałtyckich Stowarzyszenie</p>
Duration (months)	48

Start date	01.09.2022	End date	31.08.2026
Key Area(s)	KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 1. Support striving neighbourhood communities 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Decarbonised last mile logistics, emission reduction, public-private collaboration, local green businesses, noise and air pollution, interoperable electric and multimodal vehicles, cargo-bikes, innovative governance and business models, social innovations, acceptance, qualified workforce, sustainable economics, urban integration and design, collaborative urban consolidation logistics framework, micro urban consolidation centres		
Case Studies	Living Labs: Logrono, Nantes, Hamburg, Istanbul Satellites: Tallinn, Getafe, Ghent, Sarajevo		
<p>DECARBOMILE will develop interoperable and multimodal vehicles for last mile delivery in urban contexts. Multimodal and electric vehicles present a strong potential for greening transportation in cities, especially in terms of optimised delivery service, improved air quality and reduced congestion. Therefore, DECARBOMILE will work on logistics vehicles optimisation, especially regarding cargo-bikes and testing their combinations with transportation modes alternative to the road and conventional trucks (river, rail). These different modes and vehicles will be further tested in the four living labs and four satellites to evaluate and eventually demonstrate their effective optimisation in real conditions and their adaptability to different logistics flows, terrains, external actors, scope of action, etc.</p> <p>(https://decarbomile.eu/about-2/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

LENS

Project Full Title	L-vehicles Emissions and Noise mitigation Solutions		
Website	https://www.lens-horizoneurope.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101056777 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/lens/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/l-vehicles-emissions-and-noise-mitigation-solutions		
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D5-01		
Project Coordinator	EMISIA S.A., anonimi etairia perivallontikon kai energiakon meleton kai anaptixis logismikou Leonidas Ntziachristos, leon@auth.gr		
Project Partners	16 partners Bayerische Motoren Werke Aktiengesellschaft (BMW) Czech University of Life Sciences Prague / Česká zemědělská univerzita v Praze (CZU) – Faculty of engineering Ducati Motor Holding S.p.A. EMISIA S.A., anonimi etairia perivallontikon kai energiakon meleton kai anaptixis logismikou Graz University of Technology / Technische Universität Graz (TU Graz) – Institute of Electrical Measurement and Sensor Systems Graz University of Technology / Technische Universität Graz (TU Graz) – Institute of Thermodynamics and Sustainable Propulsion Systems Horiba Europe GmbH IDIADA Automotive Technology S.A. IFP Energies nouvelles ivl Swedish Environmental Research Institute / Svenska Miljöinstitutet AB Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (KULeuven) – Mecha(tro)nic System Dynamics (LMSD) KTM Forschungs- & Entwicklungs GmbH Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research / Nederlandse Organisatie voor toegepast-natuurwetenschappelijk onderzoek (TNO) Piaggio & C. S.p.A. POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale RWTH Aachen University / Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen / RWTH Aachen Campus GmbH – Institute for Automotive Engineering		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.09.2022	End date	31.08.2025
Key Area(s)	Focus: noise reduction of L-category vehicles KA1 Smart Urban Mobility KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition		
Keywords	L-category vehicles (LVs), noise and air pollution, assessment methods, policy recommendations, mobility app, best practices guidance		
Case Studies	Demonstration sites: Milan, Prague, Flanders, Paris, Rome		

Cities, regulators, and enforcement officials need support in finding ways to reduce noise and air pollution generated by motorcycles and mopeds, i.e. L-category vehicles (LVs). The EU-funded LENS project will apply techniques to monitor LVs' noise and emissions, provide recommendations on how to control the contribution of current and future LVs, examine emissions and noise performance under real driving conditions and deploy methods to identify tampered vehicles. LENS will conduct detailed pollutant and noise characterization to more than 150 vehicles in the lab and on the road and will demonstrate the impacts of LENS recommendations in 3 case studies at different spatial and temporal resolutions. LENS output will be tools and methods for less noise and better air in cities.

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101056777>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

URBANE

Project Full Title	Upscaling Innovative Green Urban Logistics Solutions Through Multi-Actor Collaboration and PI-Inspired Last Mile Deliveries.
Website	https://www.urbane-horizoneurope.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/urbane https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069782 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/urbane/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/upscaling-innovative-green-urban-logistics-solutions-through-multi-actor-collaboration-and
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01
Project Coordinator	Inlecom Innovation Astiki Mi Kerdoskopiki Etaireia Ioanna Fergadiotou, ioanna.fergadiotou@inlecomsystems.com
Project Partners	<p>40 partners</p> <p>ACS Tachidromikes Ipiresies Monoprosopi Anonymi Emporiki Etaireia / ACS Postal Services SMSA Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe (ALICE) Area Metropolitana de Barcelona (AMB) Automotive.Engineering.Network Das Mobilitätscluster e.V. Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT) City Council of Valladolid / Ayuntamiento de Valladolid City of Aarhus / Aarhus Kommune City of Antwerp / Stad Antwerpen City of Helsinki / Helsingin Kaupunki City of Karlsruhe / Stadt Karlsruhe City of Mechelen / Stad Mechelen Communauté d'agglomération de La Rochelle Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) District Prague 6 / Mestská Cast Praha Due Torri S.p.A. EIT KIC Urban Mobility S.L. FIT Consulting s.r.l. Forum Virium Helsinki OY Fundación Cidaut GEL Proximity s.r.l. Inlecom Innovation Astiki Mi Kerdoskopiki Etaireia Institute for Transport and Logistics Foundation / Fondazione Istituto sui trasporti e la logistica (ITL) Interactive Fully Electrical VehicleS s.r.l. (I-FEVS) Konnecta Systems Ike / Konnecta Sytems Ltd Kühne Logistics University gGmbH LMAD Municipality of Bologna / Comune di Bologna Municipality of Ravenna / Comune di Ravenna NORCE Norwegian Research Centre AS</p>

	<p>Open University of Catalonia / La Fundació para la Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC) – Sustainability, Management and Transport Research Group (SUMAT)</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Region of Central Macedonia</p> <p>Schenker OY</p> <p>SEW-Eurodrive GmbH & Co KG</p> <p>SKEMA Business School Association</p> <p>SOBEN S.A.S. / TwinswHeel</p> <p>soluciones Ultima Milla S.L.</p> <p>TRI-VIZOR NV</p> <p>Typ s.r.l.</p> <p>VLTN B.V.</p>		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.09.2022	End date	28.02.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics</p> <p>3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery</p> <p>KA4 Urban governance for mobility transition</p> <p>3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>		
Keywords	<p>Sustainable safe resilient effective last mile delivery solutions, multi-actor collaboration, shared space utilisation models, Innovation Transferability Platform, open models, smart contracts, digital twinning, blockchain technology, automated vehicles, co-creation, data-driven decision-making tools, business plans, commercialisation path</p>		
Case Studies / Living Labs	<p>Lighthouse Living Labs: Helsinki, Bologna, Valladolid, Thessaloniki</p> <p>Twinning Living Labs: Barcelona, Karlsruhe</p> <p>Follower Cities: Aarhus, Antwerp, La Rochelle, Mechelen, Prague, Ravenna</p>		
<p>Advancing the transition path towards safe, efficient and sustainable last mile transport, the last leg of a journey for the movement of goods, is a priority for the EU-funded URBANE project. It will combine green automated vehicles with shared space usage models to uncover last mile delivery solutions. URBANE will focus on four Lighthouse Living Labs in Bologna, Helsinki, Thessaloniki and Valladolid. The project will leverage digital twinning tools, a data-driven impact assessment radar, and Blockchain technology-led smart contracts to get results, which will enable it to verify the ‘physical internet’ (i.e. transport network) for urban deliveries.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069782, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

PHOEBE

Project Full Title	Predictive Approaches fOr SafEr UrBan Environments		
Website	https://phoebe-project.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101076963 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/phoebe/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/predictive-approaches-safer-urban-environments		
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-01		
Project Coordinator	European Road Assessment Programme (EuroRAP) / European Institute of Road Assessment (EIRA) / Evropski inštitut za ocenjevanje cest		
Project Partners	<p>12 partners</p> <p>Aimsun SLU</p> <p>Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft)</p> <p>European Road Assessment Programme (EuroRAP) / European Institute of Road Assessment (EIRA) / Evropski inštitut za ocenjevanje cest</p> <p>Factual Consulting S.L.</p> <p>International Road Assessment Programme (iRAP)</p> <p>National Technical University of Athens / Ethnicon Metsovion Polytechnion (NTUA) – Road Safety Observatory</p> <p>National Technical University of Athens / Ethnicon Metsovion Polytechnion (NTUA) – Traffic Engineering Laboratory</p> <p>OSeven Single Member Private Company / OSeven Telematics</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>Technical University of Munich / Technische Universität München (TUM) – Chair of Transportation Systems Engineering</p> <p>The Floop Ltd</p> <p>Universitat Politècnica de Valencia (UPV)</p>		
Duration (months)	46		
Start date	01.10.2022	End date	31.07.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>Focus: Road Safety - eScooters</p> <p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <p>4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p> <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <p>1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity</p> <p>3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p>		
Keywords	Vulnerable road users, road safety assessment, active mobility, e-scooters, traffic simulation, assessment tools, demand modelling, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) techniques		
Case Studies	Pilot cities: Athens, Valencia, West Midlands		

According to Eurostat, almost 19 000 persons were killed in road accidents in the EU in 2020. To help the EU halve road deaths and injuries by 2030, the PHOEBE project aims to create a framework for the assessment of road safety impacts when planning strategic changes in urban environments and policies. Planning for safer urban environments is especially important in the current constantly changing scenario, with new forms of transport and micro-mobility emerging. The EU-funded PHOEBE project wants to deliver an interdisciplinary solution to integrate traffic simulation, road safety assessment, human behaviour, mode shift and induced demand modelling as well as new and emerging mobility and telematics data into a harmonised, prospective assessment framework for road safety.

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101076963>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

eBRT2030

Project Full Title	European Bus Rapid Transit of 2030: electrified, automated, connected
Website	https://ebrt2030.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101095882 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/ebrt2030/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/european-bus-rapid-transit-2030-electrified-automated-connected
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D5-01
Project Coordinator	International Association of Public Transport / Union Internationale des Transports Publics (UITP) Flavio Grazian, Flavio.grazian@uitp.org
Project Partners	<p>55 partners</p> <p>ALSTOM Transport SA Arriva Personenvervoer Nederland B.V. ASSTRA – Associazione Trasporti Athens Urban Transport Organisation / Organismos Astikon Sygkoinonion Athinon AE (OASA S.A.) AVL List GmbH Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) Connexxion Openbaar Vervoer N.V. Consorti Centre de Recerca Matemàtica (CRM) Ebusco B.V. Elektroline AS Enel X Italia s.r.l. Enel X s.r.l. ETRA Investigacion y Desarrollo SA European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation – Intelligent Transport Systems & Services Europe (ERTICO – ITS Europe) Factual Consulting S.L. FIT Consulting s.r.l. Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V. Fundación TECNALIA Research & Innovation Heliox B.V. Heuliez Bus IDIADA Automotive Technology S.A. İETT İşletmeleri Genel Müdürlüğü (İstanbul Elektrik, Tramvay ve Tünel) Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) / Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institutouto Systematon Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston International Association of Public Transport / Union Internationale des Transports Publics (UITP) Irizar e-mobility S.L. IVECO France / IVECO BUS Lund University National Technical University of Athens / Ethnicon Metsovion Polytechnion (NTUA) – Rural & Surveying Engineering</p>

	<p>Nemi Mobiliy Solutions S.L. Operadora Distrital de Transporte SAS – La Rolita POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Prague Public Transit Company / Dopravní podnik hlavního města Prahy AS (CPP) RINA Consulting S.p.A. Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH Scania CV A.B. Škoda Electric AS Société d'économie mixte des transports en commun de l'agglomération nantaise Stadtwerke München GmbH Start Romagna S.p.A. Stichting Cenex Nederland Systra France Systra SA TEMSA Škoda Sabancı Ulaşım Araçları Anonim Sirketi Transport for Athens / Odikes Sygkoinonies Anonymi Etaireia Transports de Barcelona SA / Transports Metropolitans de Barcelona (TMB) Trivektor Traffic AB trolley:motion – Verein zur Förderung moderner Trolleybussysteme Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) – Barcelona Innovative Transportation (BIT) Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) – Barcelona School of Informatics (inLab FIB) University of Bologna / Università di Bologna University of Pardubice / Univerzita Pardubice (UPCE) – Faculty of Transport Engineering Urban Electric Mobility Initiative (UEMI) gGmbH Volvo Buses / Volvo Bussar Aktiebolag Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electromobility research centre (MOBI) VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Lt / Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY</p>		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.01.2023	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>Focus: ZE Buses KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p>		
Keywords	<p>Public transport, sustainable urban mobility, Bus Rapid Transit (BRT), innovative solutions, economically viable integrated and synchronised eBRT solutions, automation and connectivity functionalities, zero emission sustainable transport, needs of citizens, passenger experience, mobility access of underserved areas, charging solutions, IoT monitoring platform, business models</p>		
Case Studies	Barcelona, Amsterdam, Athens, Prague, Rimini, Eindhoven Region, Bogota		
<p>It is estimated that a third of the 200 000 buses in European public transport will be zero emission vehicles by 2030. In this context, the EU-funded EBRT2030 project will develop technology-focused key innovation solutions for European bus rapid transport (BRT). It will run seven demonstrations of BRT system innovative solutions in real operation. The project will also define a new European concept of BRT for the</p>			

year 2030, benefitting from the evaluation, multiplication and replication of the real-operation test of innovations. The cities involved in the project will have BRT lines in operation or launched within 2023.

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101095882>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

GREEN-LOG

Project Full Title	Cooperative and Interconnected Green delivery solutions towards an era of optimized zero emission last-mile Logistics
Website	https://greenlog-project.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/green-log https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069892 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/green-log/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/cooperative-and-interconnected-green-delivery-solutions-towards-era-optimized-zero-emission
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01
Project Coordinator	Netcompany-Intrasoft SA Amalia Ntemou, amalia.ntemou@netcompany.com info@greenlog-project.eu
Project Partners	<p>30 partners</p> <p>Aimsun SLU</p> <p>Athens University of Economics and Business – Research Center</p> <p>Autoritat del Transport Metropolità (ATM)</p> <p>City of Athens IT Company / Dimos Athinaion Epicheirisi Michanografisis (DAEM)</p> <p>City of Ghent / Stad Gent</p> <p>City of Helsingborg / Helsingborgs Kommun</p> <p>City of Leuven / Stad Leuven</p> <p>City of Mechelen / Stad Mechelen</p> <p>e-Novia S.p.A.</p> <p>Factual Consulting S.L.</p> <p>Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya (FGC)</p> <p>Flanders Institute for Logistics / Vlaams Instituut voor de Logistiek vzw (VIL)</p> <p>Frontier Innovations EE</p> <p>Frontier Kentro Kainotomias Amke</p> <p>Fundacio Eurecat</p> <p>Halmstad University / Högskolan i Halmstad – School of Information Technology</p> <p>Mastisha Worlds Ltd</p> <p>MOBY X SOFTWARE Ltd</p> <p>Mosaic Factor S.L.</p> <p>Municipality of Arad / Municipiul Arad</p> <p>Netcompany-Intrasoft SA</p> <p>Oxfordshire County Council</p> <p>Pedal & Pour Ltd T/A Pedal & Post</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>solucions Ultima Milla S.L.</p> <p>Tachymetafores Elta Anonymos Etaireia</p> <p>University of Antwerp / Universiteit Antwerpen – Department of Transport and Regional Economics (TPR)</p> <p>University of the Aegean / Panepistimio Aigaiou – Transportation and Decision-Making Laboratory</p>

	University of Wolverhampton – Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) lab Valga Municipality / Valga Vald		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.01.2023	End date	30.06.2026
Key Area(s)	KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition		
Keywords	Logistics as a Service (LaaS) platforms, automated delivery concepts, autonomous vehicles, delivery droids, cargo-bikes, multimodal delivery integrating public transportation, city logistics dataspace, sustainable last mile logistics, stakeholder Urban Living Labs, social innovation, scenario building, financial viability		
Case Studies	Living Labs: Athens, Barcelona, Flanders, Oxfordshire, Ispra Follower cities: Arad, Helsingborg, Valga		
<p>Online shopping is convenient and quick. Deliveries are just a click away – for consumers. However, delivering an ever-increasing number of parcels is no easy task. The challenges around urban last mile are particularly pronounced. In this light, the EU-funded GREEN-LOG project will push the gas on economically, environmentally and socially sustainable city logistics. It will develop city platforms and automated delivery concepts to nurture social innovation. On the operational level, GREEN-LOG will use autonomous vehicles and delivery droids as well as innovations based on cargo bikes. Moreover, it will promote the development of harmonised regulatory and policy frameworks and cooperative business models. The approach will be tested in five EU areas (Athens, Barcelona, Flanders, Oxfordshire and Ispra) with more cities to follow.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069892, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

SPINE

Project Full Title	Smart Public transport Initiatives for climate-Neutral cities in Europe
Website	https://www.spine-project.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/spine https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101096664 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/smart-public-transport-initiatives-climate-neutral-cities-europe
Call	HORIZON-MISS-2021-CIT-02
Project Coordinator	Inlecom Innovation Astiki Mi Kerdoskopiki Etaireia Makis Kouloumbis, Sissi Koronaiou, info@spine-project.eu
Project Partners	<p>40 partners</p> <p>Aimsun SLU Autobuses Urbanos de Valladolid SA Barreiro City Council / Municipio do Barreiro cambiaMO Sociedad cooperative Madrilenia CINESI S.L. City Council of Las palmas de Grancanaria / Ayuntamiento de Las Palmas de Grancanaria City Council of Valladolid / Ayuntamiento de Valladolid City of Antwerp / Stad Antwerpen City of Gdynia / Gdynia-Miasto na prawach powiatu City of Sibenik / Grad Šibenik City of Zilina / Mesto Žilina Cityway SAS Civinet Cy El Secretariat Astiki Mi Kerdoskopiki Etaireia EURNEX e.V. European Integrated Project Guaguas Municipales Sociedad Anonima Halmstad University / Högskolan i Halmstad – School of Information Technology Heraklion Municipality Ibi Group Ellas Symbvouloi Epixeiriseon Monoproswnpi Anonymi Etaireia Inlecom Innovation Astiki Mi Kerdoskopiki Etaireia Innovation Engineering s.r.l. Instant System IST-ID Associação do Instituto Superior Técnico para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento Konnecta Systems Ike / Konnecta Sytems Ltd MOBY X SOFTWARE Ltd Municipality of Bologna / Comune di Bologna ODRAZ-Održivi razvoj zajednice PNO Innovation S.L. Przedsiębiorstwo Komunikacji Autobusowej Spolka Z Ograniczona Odpowiedzialnoscia SIA ATOM Tech Sociedad Municipal de Aparcamientos de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria SA SRM Reti e Mobilità s.r.l.</p>

	<p>The City of Tallinn / Tallinna Linn / Tallinn linnavalitsus Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) – Centre d'Innovació i Tecnologia (CIT) de la UPC University of Antwerp / Universiteit Antwerpen – Department of Transport and Regional Economics (TPR) University of Gdansk / Uniwersytet Gdański University of the Aegean / Panepistimio Aigaiou – Transportation and Decision-Making Laboratory University of Zilina / Žilinská Univerzita v Žiline – Department of International Research Projects (ERAdiate+) Urban buses Heraklion / Astiko Ktel Irakleiou Metaforiki Touristiki Anonymos Etaireia Yunex GmbH</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2023	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>		
Keywords	<p>efficient sustainable inclusive public transport systems, New mobility services (NMS), shared mobility, active mobility, micromobility, equity-centered design thinking, digital twinning, open data, data-driven impact assessment models, co-design of inclusive mobility solutions</p>		
Case Studies	<p>Lead City Living Labs: Antwerp, Bologna, Tallin, Las Palmas</p> <p>Twinning City Living Labs: Barreiro, Valladolid, Zilina, Sibenik, Hrakleion, Gdynia, Rouen</p>		
<p>A unique multidisciplinary team from 16 countries is coming together to revolutionise the public transport industry under the EU-funded SPINE project. The primary aim is to accelerate progress towards climate neutrality by reinforcing public transport systems through smart integration with new mobility services, sharing schemes, active transport modes and micromobility. Four Lead City Living Labs – Antwerp, Bologna, Tallinn, Las Palmas – will establish a network of collaboration and foster transferability of the most promising solutions to seven twinning cities: Barreiro, Valladolid, Žilina, Šibenik, Herakleion, Gdynia and Rouen. A series of co-creation activities will take place where multiple stakeholders will be actively engaged in the development and demonstration of efficient, replicable and socially acceptable innovative mobility solutions.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101096664, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

UPPER

Project Full Title	Unleashing the potential of Public Transport in Europe		
Website	https://www.upperprojecteu.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/upper https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101095904 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/upper/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/unleashing-potential-public-transport-europe		
Call	HORIZON-MISS-2021-CIT-02		
Project Coordinator	International Association of Public Transport / Union Internationale des Transports Publics (UITP) Mircea Steriu, mircea.steriu@uitp.org		
Project Partners	41 partners		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2023	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Support sustainable lifestyles <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		
Keywords	safe efficient reliable inclusive and affordable public transport system, sustainable and innovative mobility, push and pull measures, user satisfaction, mindset and culture, urban mobility planning, mobility services ecosystem, road network management, SUMP, users' involvement, behavioural change, democratic governance, Mobility as a Right (MaaR)		
Case Studies	<p>Living Labs: Valencia, Rome, Ile de France, Oslo, Mannheim</p> <p>Twinning cities: Lisbon, Leuven, Hannover, Budapest, Thessaloniki</p>		
<p>Public transport can contribute to sustainable and innovative urban mobility, in line with the Green Deal goals. The EU-funded UPPER project places public transport at the centre of the mobility ecosystem. The project will implement a combination of 84 push-and-pull measures, supported by the UPPER Toolkit and seven IT tools, acting on the five innovation axes that condition user choices: mindset and culture, urban mobility planning, mobility services ecosystem, road network management and democratic governance. The UPPER approach will involve communication, operations, infrastructure and urban fabric. The aim is to achieve an efficient, safe, inclusive and affordable public transport system in line with the concept of Mobility as a Right (MaaR).</p>			

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101095904>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

STREnGth_M

Project Full Title	Stimulating road Transport Research in Europe and around the Globe for sustainable Mobility		
Website	https://www.ertrac.org/support-actions/strength_m/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101096253 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/strength_m/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/stimulating-road-transport-research-europe-and-around-globe-sustainable-mobility		
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D5-01		
Project Coordinator	AVL List GmbH Verena Wagenhofer, verena.wagenhofer@avl.com		
Project Partners	<p>24 partners</p> <p>Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe (ALICE)</p> <p>Aristotle University of Thessaloniki / Panepistimio Thessalias / Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis (AUTH) – Laboratory of Applied Thermodynamics (LAT)</p> <p>AVL List GmbH</p> <p>Bayerische Motoren Werke Aktiengesellschaft (BMW)</p> <p>Centro Ricerche Fiat S.C.p.A.</p> <p>ELES, d. o. o., operater kombiniranega prenosnega in distribucijskega elektroenergetskega omrežja</p> <p>European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation – Intelligent Transport Systems & Services Europe (ERTICO – ITS Europe)</p> <p>FEHRL Forum of European National Highway Research Laboratories / Forum des laboratoires européens de recherche routière AISBL</p> <p>FIER B.V.</p> <p>Gruber Logistics S.p.A.</p> <p>International Association of Public Transport / Union Internationale des Transports Publics (UITP)</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>Ricardo GmbH</p> <p>Robert Bosch GmbH</p> <p>Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH</p> <p>RWTH Aachen University / Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen / RWTH Aachen Campus GmbH – Mechanical Engineering</p> <p>Stiftelsen Chalmers Industriteknik</p> <p>The Institute for Transportation and Development Policy (ITDP)</p> <p>United Nations Human Settlements Programme</p> <p>Urban Electric Mobility Initiative (UEMI) gGmbH</p> <p>Valeo Management Services</p> <p>VDI/VDE Innovation + Technik GmbH</p> <p>Volkswagen AG</p> <p>Volvo Technology AB</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.02.2023	End date	31.01.2026

Key Area(s)	<p>Focus: Road Transport research/ international cooperation</p> <p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p>
Keywords	<p>Future research needs in road transport, research agendas and roadmaps, support and coordination, links between programmes, international cooperation task forces</p>
Case Studies	
<p>Transport represents nearly 25 % of Europe’s greenhouse gas emissions. It is also the main source of air pollution in cities. More secure and sustainable mobility is a necessity, not only in Europe but also worldwide. Along this path, the EU-funded STREngth_M project will accelerate global cooperation in research on road transport to create sustainable mobility. Specifically, the project will outline urgent needs and capacities in innovation. It will link European, African, Asian and Latin American markets related to electric vehicles within existing regional and national efforts, programmes or structures while overcoming barriers in international cooperation. The founding of a Multiplier Group will boost the dissemination of results and engage stakeholders.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101096253, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

CIVITAS MUSE

Project Full Title	Mobility for Urban Sustainability and the Environment CIVITAS 2030 Coordination and Support Action: Sustainable and Smart Mobility for All		
Website	https://civitas.eu/coordination/muse https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103716		
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D2-01		
Project Coordinator	ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH / ICLEI Europasekretariat GmbH		
Project Partners	9 partners DTV Consultants B.V. EIT KIC Urban Mobility S.L. Eurocities ASBL ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH / ICLEI Europasekretariat GmbH Inova+ Innovation Services SA Mobiel 21 vzw Stichting Breda University of Applied Sciences – Academy for Built Environment & Logistics Stichting Breda University of Applied Sciences – Academy for Tourism TRT Trasporti e Territorio s.r.l.		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.05.2023	End date	30.04.2027
Key Area(s)	Focus: Coordination and Support Action for the CIVITAS Initiative KA1 Smart Urban Mobility KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition		
Keywords	Coordination and Support Action, project performance, urban mobility community		
Case Studies			
<p>As the current Coordination and Support Action for the CIVITAS Initiative, MUSE primarily engages in support activities to boost the impact of CIVITAS Community activities on sustainable urban mobility policy.</p> <p>Its main objectives are to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as a destination for knowledge developed by the CIVITAS Community over the past twenty years • Expand and strengthen relationships between cities and stakeholders at all levels • Support the enrichment of the wider urban mobility community by providing learning opportunities <p>Through these goals, the CIVITAS Initiative strives to support the mobility and transport goals of the European Commission, and in turn those in the European Green Deal.</p> <p>(https://civitas.eu/coordination/muse, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

DISCO

Project Full Title	Data-driven, Integrated, Syncromodal, Collaborative and Optimised urban freight meta model for a new generation of urban logistics and planning with data sharing at European Living Labs
Website	https://discoprojecteu.com/ https://knowledgeplatform.etp-logistics.eu/course/view.php?id=304 https://civitas.eu/projects/disco https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103954 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/disco/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/data-driven-integrated-syncromodal-collaborative-and-optimised-urban-freight-meta-model-new
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-02
Project Coordinator	FIT Consulting s.r.l. Paola Cossu, cossu@fitconsulting.it
Project Partners	<p>47 partners</p> <p>A to B Finland OY (A2B)</p> <p>ACS Tachidromikes Ipiresies Monoprosopi Anonymi Emporiki Etaireia / ACS Postal Services SMSA</p> <p>AKKA Industry Consulting GmbH</p> <p>Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe (ALICE)</p> <p>Asociación Logística Innovadora de Aragón</p> <p>Barcelona Municipality / Ajuntament de Barcelona</p> <p>Be-Mobile</p> <p>Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT)</p> <p>City Council of Zaragoza / Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza</p> <p>City of Aarhus / Aarhus Kommune</p> <p>City of Ghent / Stad Gent</p> <p>CITYlogin Iberica S.L.</p> <p>Copenhagen Municipality / Københavns Kommune</p> <p>District Prague 6 / Mestská část Praha</p> <p>Erasmus Centre for Urban, Port and Transport Economics B.V. (UPT)</p> <p>European Parking Association e.V. (EPA)</p> <p>FIT Consulting s.r.l.</p> <p>Flanders Institute for Logistics / Vlaams Instituut voor de Logistiek vzw (VIL)</p> <p>FM Logistic Ibérica S.L.</p> <p>Forum Virium Helsinki OY</p> <p>Fundación de la Comunidad Valenciana para la Investigación, Promoción y Estudios Comerciales de Valenciaport</p> <p>Fundación de la Comunidad Valenciana para la Promoción Estratégica, el Desarrollo y la Innovación Urbana</p> <p>Fundación Zaragoza Ciudad del Conocimiento (FZC)</p> <p>Fundación Zaragoza Logistics Center</p> <p>Inlecom Innovation Astiki Mi Kerdoskopiki Etaireia</p>

	<p>Institut de recherche technologique SystemX (IRT SystemX) Institute for Transport and Logistics Foundation / Fondazione Istituto sui trasporti e la logistica (ITL) International Data Spaces e.V. Interuniversity Microelectronics Centre / Interuniversitair Micro-electronica Centrum (IMEC) Kühne Logistics University gGmbH Lindholmen Science Park AB Municipality of Padua / Comune di Padova Municipality of Piacenza / Comune di Piacenza Municipality of Thessaloniki / Dimos Thessalonikis Next s.r.l. Opleidingscentrum voor Hout en Bouw vzw (OHB) PNO Innovation S.L. POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Region Hovestaden Regional Management Nordhessen GmbH Rolan OY Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH Stichting Breda University of Applied Sciences – Academy for Built Environment & Logistics T-Box Delivery & Solutions S.L. Thessaloniki International Fair / Diethnis Ekthesi Thessalonikis AE Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) – Centre d'Innovació i Tecnologia (CIT) de la UPC Venice International University (VIU) – TeDIS</p>		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.05.2023	End date	31.10.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity</p> <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 1. Support striving neighbourhood economies 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p>		
Keywords	<p>Urban logistics and smart planning frameworks, decarbonised and digital cities, Physical Internet (PI)-led approach, SULPs, data-driven innovative measures, Meta Model Suite, Urban Freight Data Space, microhubs, low-emission last mile delivery, real time data collection methods, multimodal bays, digital twins, consolidation centres, knowledge hub</p>		
Case Studies	<p>Starring Living Labs: Thessaloniki, Copenhagen, Ghent, Helsinki</p> <p>Twinning Living Labs: Padua, Barcelona, Valencia, Zaragoza</p> <p>Follower cities: Prague, Piacenza, Aarhus, North Hesse</p>		
<p>The daily transport of goods in and around urban areas is essential to support the needs of domestic and international commerce as well as local businesses and consumers. However, it contributes to the disruption of citizens' life quality by increasing traffic congestion, noise, road hazards, air pollution and land use conflicts. As urban freight distribution continues to grow, it is vital to mitigate its side effects. To address this, the EU-funded DISCO project aims to develop and demonstrate a centralised European metamodel that integrates urban freight logistics and optimised city land use. The open data-sharing space</p>			

will provide city planners with tools that can help them optimally manage, monitor and dynamically predict city freight flows.

(<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103954>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

REALLOCATE

Project Full Title	Rethinking the dEsign of streets And pubLic spaces to Leverage the mOdal shift to Climate-friendly Active Transport Everywhere
Website	https://reallocatemobility.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/reallocate https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103924
Call	HORIZON-MISS-2022-CIT-01
Project Coordinator	University College Dublin (UCD), National University of Ireland, Dublin – Spatial Dynamics Lab coordinator@reallocatemobility.eu
Project Partners	38 partners Barcelona City Council / Ajuntament de Barcelona – Institut Municipal de Persones amb Discapacitat Barcelona Municipality / Ajuntament de Barcelona Barcelona Supercomputing Center / Centro Nacional de Supercomputación BKK Centre for Budapest Transport / Budapesti Közlekedési Központ Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság Capital City of Warsaw / Miasto Stołeczne Warszawa Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) CEREMA Centre d'études et d'expertise sur les risques, l'environnement, la mobilité et l'aménagement / Centre for Studies on Risks, the Environment, Mobility and Urban Planning City of Gothenburg / Goteborgs Kommun / Göteborgs Stad City of Heidelberg / Stadt Heidelberg City of Lyon / Commune de Lyon / Ville de Lyon City of Tampere / Tampereen Kaupunki City of Utrecht / Gemeente Utrecht City of Zagreb / Grad Zagreb DEKRA Assurance Services GmbH DEKRA Automobil GmbH Demos Research Institute OY Eurocities ASBL European Cyclists Federation ASBL European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation – Intelligent Transport Systems & Services Europe (ERTICO – ITS Europe) Factual Consulting S.L. Fondazione per l'innovazione urbana Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V. Fundacja na Rzecz Wspólnot Lokalnych Na Miejscu Halmstad University / Höskolan i Halmstad ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH / ICLEI Europasekretariat GmbH International Federation of Pedestrians (IFP) – Research Métropole de Lyon Municipality of Bologna / Comune di Bologna Municipality of Budapest / Budapest Főváros Önkormányzata Nemi Mobiliy Solutions S.L.

	NUDGD AB Ove Arup & Partners Ireland Ltd Sindikat Biciklista Udruga Stichting Sport Utrecht University College Dublin (UCD), National University of Ireland, Dublin – Spatial Dynamics Lab University of Zagreb – Faculty of Transport and Traffic Sciences / Sveučilište u Zagrebu – Fakultet prometnih znanosti Veilig Verkeer Nederland (VVN) VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Lt / Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.05.2023	End date	30.04.2027
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	inclusive green safe urban spaces, open proactive data, integrated and innovative sustainable urban mobility solutions, twinning, zero-emission and citizen-centred mobility interventions, safety, affordability, urban design, behavioural nudging, technological and data-driven solutions, collaborative learning, Mission Cities 2030		
Case Studies	Twinned Mission Cities: Gothenburg-Tampere, Heidelberg-Utrecht, Lyon-Warsaw, Budapest-Zagreb, Barcelona-Bologna		
<p>To achieve climate neutrality, European cities urgently need to halve transport emissions by 2030 and by a staggering 90 % by 2050. However, existing mobility infrastructure, services and governance for short-distance travel hinder progress, negatively impacting active modes' safety and security. With this in mind, the EU-funded REALLOCATE project aims to transform European cities into climate-neutral, safe and inclusive urban centres. By integrating cutting-edge sustainable mobility strategies and reallocating street space, the project empowers Mission Cities like Gothenburg-Tampere and Heidelberg-Utrecht. Through pilot programmes in unsafe areas, the project showcases urban space management and reallocation tactics for active modes, ultimately fostering knowledge exchange and collaborative learning among city staff.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103924, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

SYNCHROMODE

Project Full Title	Advanced traffic management solutions for synchronized and resilient multimodal transport services		
Website	https://synchromode.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101104171 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/synchromode/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/advanced-traffic-management-solutions-synchronized-and-resilient-multimodal-transport		
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-02		
Project Coordinator	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) Evangelos Mitsakis, emit@certh.gr Melina Zarouka, mzarouka@polisnetwork.eu info@synchromode.eu		
Project Partners	15 partners		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.05.2023	End date	30.04.2026
Key Area(s)	Focus: Data based multimodal transport KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition		
Keywords	Data driven ICT toolbox, transport network management, data exchange and integration system, cooperative dashboard for real-time monitoring, resilient multimodal transport network support tool, predictive and network optimization capabilities, balancing transport supply and demand		
Case Studies	Case studies: Thessaloniki, Netherlands, Madrid		
<p>The EU-funded SYNCHROMODE project will address major challenges faced by European transport systems, including traffic congestion, road safety, energy consumption, and emissions. The project aims to transform traffic management by incorporating a multimodal network-wide perspective. To that end, it will equip traffic managers with the SYNCHROMODE Toolbox, providing predictive and optimisation capabilities to balance network supply and demand and manage the impacts of events. Furthermore, it will execute research activities beyond the current state of the art in transport modelling, traffic prediction, optimisation of multimodal traffic operations, enhanced data quality, use of new multimodal traffic data sources, and new KPIs for improved monitoring and assessment. Project results will be tested and validated in three real-world case studies: Thessaloniki (Greece), the Netherlands, and Madrid (Spain).</p>			

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101104171>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

UNCHAIN

Project Full Title	Urban logistics and planning: Anticipating urban freight generation and demand including digitalisation of urban freight		
Website	https://unchainproject.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/unchain https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103812 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/unchain/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/urban-logistics-and-planning-anticipating-urban-freight-generation-and-demand-including		
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-02		
Project Coordinator	ETRA Investigacion y Desarrollo SA Elena García Jiménez, elenagarcia.etraid@grupoetra.com		
Project Partners	<p>18 partners</p> <p>Berlin – Senate Department for Mobility, Transport, Climate Protection and the Environment / Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt</p> <p>City Council of Madrid / Ayuntamiento de Madrid</p> <p>City of Florence / Comune di Firenze</p> <p>City of Mechelen / Stad Mechelen</p> <p>City of Prague / Hlavní Město Praha</p> <p>DHL Express Spain S.L.</p> <p>EIT KIC Urban Mobility S.L.</p> <p>Empresa Municipal de Transportes de Madrid (EMT Madrid)</p> <p>ETRA Investigacion y Desarrollo SA</p> <p>Funchal Town Hall / Câmara Municipal do Funchal</p> <p>Instituto de Biomecánica de Valencia (IBV)</p> <p>Municipia S.p.A.</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>Riga City Council / Rīgas pilsētas pašvaldība</p> <p>SPES Consulting s.r.l.</p> <p>United Parcel Service Italia s.r.l.</p> <p>University of Lancaster</p> <p>VMZ Berlin Betreibergesellschaft mbH</p>		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.05.2023	End date	31.10.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics</p> <p>3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p> <p>3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>		

Keywords	Sustainable urban logistics, smart cities, sustainable resilient and safe cities, innovative data-driven city services, last-mile delivery, Urban Freight Distribution (UFD), congestion, safety, efficient space allocation, public-private data exchange and interoperability, SULPs, UVARs, Urban Consolidation Centres (UCCs)
Case Studies	Living Labs: Florence, Berlin, Madrid
<p>Nowadays, almost everything we need can be ordered online and delivered to our doorsteps. However, last-mile delivery is far from supporting a sustainable society. The EU-funded UNCHAIN project aims to contribute to more sustainable urban logistics and help the transition towards climate-neutral and smart cities. To achieve this, it will boost the cooperation between public authorities and logistics stakeholders by implementing a standardised and reliable data exchange ecosystem and an innovative set of urban logistics services. With the UNCHAIN project, public authorities and transport operators will enjoy mutual benefits via cooperation schemes for sustainable urban freight transport policies and operations.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103812, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

Acumen

Project Full Title	Ai-aided deCision tool for seamless mUltiModal nEtwork and traffic management		
Website	https://acumen-project.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103808 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/acumen/		
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-02		
Project Coordinator	Aalto University / Aalto-korkeakoulusäätiö sr – Department of Built Environment Claudio Roncoli		
Project Partners	<p>20 partners</p> <p>Aalto University / Aalto-korkeakoulusäätiö sr – Department of Built Environment</p> <p>Aimsun SLU</p> <p>City of Athens IT Company / Dimos Athinaion Epicheirisi Michanografisis (DAEM)</p> <p>Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – AI for Mobility Lab (AIM Lab)</p> <p>Forum Virium Helsinki OY</p> <p>HERE Deutschland GmbH & Co KG</p> <p>HERE Europe B.V.</p> <p>HERE Global B.V.</p> <p>Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST)</p> <p>LuxMobility S.A.R.L.</p> <p>MobilLysis Srl</p> <p>National Technical University of Athens / Ethnicon Metsovion Polytechnion (NTUA) – Traffic Engineering Laboratory</p> <p>Nomoko AG</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>S.L.A. SA / Sales-Lentz Autocars SA</p> <p>SLG SA</p> <p>Stichting Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions (AMS)</p> <p>Université Gustave Eiffel</p> <p>University of Luxemburg / Université du Luxembourg – MobiLab Transport Research Group</p> <p>University of Naples Federico II / Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.06.2023	End date	31.05.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>Focus: Data based multimodal transport</p> <p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <p>1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options</p> <p>4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p> <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <p>3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies</p>		
Keywords	Ai-aided decision-support tool, seamless sustainable and safe mobility, multimodal transport services, customer needs, data framework, real-time information sharing,		

	effective decision-making, traffic patterns, proactive management strategies, Digital Twins (DT), Hybrid Intelligence (HI) paradigm
Case Studies	Pilots: Athens, Helsinki, Amsterdam, Luxembourg
<p>In today's increasingly congested urban landscapes, efficient transportation has become a pressing challenge. Traffic gridlock, safety concerns, and environmental issues all demand innovative solutions. In this context, the ACUMEN project proposes a cutting-edge, privacy-preserving, data-driven digital paradigm aimed at streamlining network management. Its goal? To enable seamless door-to-door journeys, enhance network-level safety and resilience, and contribute significantly to the transport objectives outlined in the Green Deal. At the heart of ACUMEN lies the concept of a modular, multi-layered digital twin. This high-fidelity representation of complex real-world systems creates a digitised version of sustainable, connected urban mobility. Complemented by plug-in modules or digital tools, ACUMEN harnesses the power of AI to support mobility management and decision-making.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103808, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

AMIGOS

Project Full Title	Active Mobility Innovations for Green and safe city sOLutionS		
Website	https://amigos-project.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/amigos https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101104268		
Call	HORIZON-MISS-2022-CIT-01-01		
Project Coordinator	Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg / Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg Martin Krekeler, amigos@sk.hamburg.de		
Project Partners	<p>28 partners</p> <p>AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH Ankara Elektrik, Havagazi Ve Otobusisletme Muessesesi Ayalon Highways Company Ltd cambiaMO Sociedad cooperative Madrilena City of Lappeenranta / Lappeenrannan Kaupunki Empresa Municipal de la Innovación y Transporte Urbano de Las Rozas de Madrid SA Epigram AS ESTACA European Integrated Project Euroquality SAS Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg / Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg Gallery I.P Telephony Ltd Gozo Regional Development Authority Institute for Road Safety Research / Stichting Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek Verkeersveiligheid (SWOV) Institute of Transport Economics / Transportøkonomisk Institutt (TOI) Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality Jūrmala City Municipality / Jūrmalas valstspilsētas administrācija Lappeenrannan-Lahden Teknillinen Yliopisto (LUT) / LUT University Laval Agglomération Magistrate of the City of Frankfurt am Main / Stadt Frankfurt am Main Der Magistrat Metropolitan City of Bologna / Città metropolitana di Bologna Mozgássérültek Budapesti Egyesülete Municipality of Gabrovo Reykjavik City / Reykjavikurborg State capital Wiesbaden / Landeshauptstadt Wiesbaden Technion – Israel Institute of Technology Tree Technology SA</p>		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.06.2023	End date	31.05.2027
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options		

	<p>2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space</p> <p>4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p> <p>2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society</p>
Keywords	Co-creation, inclusive safe resilient and sustainable innovative urban mobility solutions, public health, active mobility, affordability, quality of space, Living labs, Safety Improvement Areas, digital tools, Mobility Observation Box, big data platform, digital twinning, vulnerable users
Case Studies	<p>Living Labs: Istanbul, Hamburg, Las Rozas, Lappeenranta, Gabrovo</p> <p>Safety Improvement Areas: Istanbul, Ankara, Hamburg, Bologna, Reykjavik, Las Rozas, Nazareth, Lappeenranta, Gabrovo, Jurmala</p> <p>Twin Cities: Malta, Umm al-Fahm, Wiesbaden, Frankfurt, Laval</p>
<p>In the pursuit of carbon neutrality, cities face the pressing challenge of adopting innovative energy models for urban mobility. Success hinges on sustainable solutions that are inclusive, affordable, safe and tailored to community needs. With this in mind, the EU-funded AMIGOS project will use cutting-edge digital tools to identify and tackle mobility issues in 5 cities (living labs) and 10 urban areas. These digital tools, including the Mobility Observation Box and a data collection app, enable the creation of digital twins for visualising mobility scenarios. This technology empowers urban stakeholders to identify challenges and co-develop solutions, promoting reduced traffic, increased public and active mobility, improved safety and the harmonious coexistence of different mobility modes.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101104268, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

ELABORATOR

Project Full Title	The European living lab on designing sustainable urban mobility towards climate neutral cities
Website	https://www.elaborator-project.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/elaborator https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103772 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/elaborator/
Call	HORIZON-MISS-2022-CIT-01
Project Coordinator	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) / Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institutouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston Angelos Amiditis, a.amditis@iccs.gr
Project Partners	<p>38 partners</p> <p>Agenzia Mobilità Ambiente e Territorio s.r.l. (AMAT) Analyse & Tal FMBA Anaptyxiaki Etaireia Dimou Trikkaion Anaptyxiaki Anonymi Etaireia OTA / E-Trikala AE AV Living Lab, inovativne tehnologije d.o.o City Council of Zaragoza / Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza City of Krusevac / Grad Kruševac City of Milan / Comune di Milano City of Split / Grad Split Colas Copenhagen Municipality / Københavns Kommune Czech Technical University in Prague (CTU) / České vysoké učení technické v Praze European Road Assessment Programme (EuroRAP) / European Institute of Road Assessment (EIRA) / Evropski inštitut za ocenjevanje cest Forum Virium Helsinki OY Fundación Circe Centro de Investigación de Recursos y Consumos Energéticos IFP Energies nouvelles Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia / Institut d'Arquitectura Avancada de Catalunya (IAAC) Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) / Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institutouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston International Road Assessment Programme (iRAP) Internet Institute, Communications Solutions and Consulting Ltd Joc Rental S.L. Københavns Universitet / University of Copenhagen – Department of Geosciences and Natural Resource Management (IGN) Linköping University / Linköpings Universitet Lund Municipality / Lunds Kommun Multicriteri-Mcrit AIE Municipality of Ioannina Municipality Velenje / Mestna občina Velenje platomo GmbH POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Sensitive AB</p>

	Socit d'conomie mixte Issy Media (SEM Issy Media) Statutory City of Liberec / Statutrn msto Liberec Stefano Boeri Architetti s.r.l. THINGS s.r.l. University of Bristol University of Zagreb – Faculty of Transport and Traffic Sciences / Sveuilište u Zagrebu – Fakultet prometnih znanosti Urban Radar Urbana Astiki Mi Kerdoskopiki Etaireia VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Lt / Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.06.2023	End date	30.11.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Living Lab, climate neutral-cities, safe inclusive accessible and sustainable urban mobility, smart mobility planning, urban public space design, smart enforcement tools, space redesign, dynamic allocation, shared mobility, active mobility, co-creation, vulnerable user-groups, twinning approach, guidelines, capacity building, SUMPs		
Case Studies	Lighthouse cities: Milan, Copenhagen, Helsinki, Issy-les-Moulineaux, Zaragoza, Trikala Follower cities: Lund, Liberec, Velejne, Ioannina, Split, Krusevac		
<p>New research and observations, along with the increasing demand for sustainable green solutions, have led to new possibilities in urban planning. However, the pursuit of inclusive, sustainable, and safe cities has encountered numerous challenges. The EU-funded ELABORATOR project is committed to developing and implementing a distinctive, comprehensive intervention approach that encompasses the design, planning, presentation and deployment of innovative solutions. These solutions aim to address the need for green and active transportation options, as well as improved smart enforcement tools, space redesign and dynamic allocation. Initially, the project will showcase its approach in six lighthouse cities and six follower cities, from which it will gather critical data to inform novel policies.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103772, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

GEMINI

Project Full Title	Greening European Mobility through cascading innovation INItiatives
Website	https://www.geminiproject.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/gemini https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103801
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-02
Project Coordinator	Urban Electric Mobility Initiative (UEMI) gGmbH Oliver Lah, oliver.lah@wupperinst.org
Project Partners	<p>43 partners</p> <p>5T s.r.l.</p> <p>A1 Slovenija Telekomunikacijske Storitve DD</p> <p>Aimsun SLU</p> <p>Allianz Arena München GmbH</p> <p>Arriva Danmark A/S</p> <p>Arriva Italia s.r.l.</p> <p>Associação Porto Digital / Porto Digital Association</p> <p>Atobe – Moblity Technology SA</p> <p>Bluegreen Strategy s.r.l.</p> <p>Caruso GmbH</p> <p>City of Amsterdam / Gemeente Amsterdam</p> <p>City of Helsingborg / Helsingborgs Kommun</p> <p>Clem'</p> <p>District Prague 6 / Mestská Praha</p> <p>European Passengers' Federation IVZW (EPF)</p> <p>FIER B.V.</p> <p>Forum Virium Helsinki OY</p> <p>Giro Car Share d.o.o</p> <p>GoodMoovs B.V.</p> <p>Inlecom Innovation Astiki Mi Kerdoskopiki Etaireia</p> <p>Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón</p> <p>Konnecta Systems Ike / Konnecta Sytems Ltd</p> <p>Metropolia University of Applied Sciences / Metropolia Amaattikorkeakoulu</p> <p>Pluservice s.r.l.</p> <p>Region Hovestaden</p> <p>Rudersdal Kommune</p> <p>SIA ATOM Tech</p> <p>Smart Innovation Norway AS</p> <p>Stichting Cenex Nederland</p> <p>Stichting Townmaking</p> <p>Technical University of Denmark / Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU)</p> <p>TIER Mobility Denmark APS</p> <p>Toyota Danmarks AS</p> <p>Transport & Mobility Leuven (TML) NV</p>

	TTS Italia Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) – Centro de Investigación del Transporte (TRANSyT) University of the Aegean / Panepistimio Aigaiou Urban Electric Mobility Initiative (UEMI) gGmbH Via Verde Portugal – Gestão de Sistemas Electrónicos de Cobrança SA Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH VMZ Berlin Betreibergesellschaft mbH Volkswagen AG Yunex GmbH		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.06.2023	End date	30.11.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	New Mobility Services (NMS) business ventures, sustainable business models, shared mobility, community engagement, Open Innovation Ecosystem, connected automated vehicles, public transport, MaaS, MaaS, public-private partnerships, mobility hubs, open mobility dataspace, co-creation, financial viability		
Case Studies	Mobility Living Labs: Amsterdam, Copenhagen, Helsinki, Ljubljana, Munich, Paris, Porto, Turin		
<p>As urbanisation surges, so does our reliance on cars, leading to congestion, pollution, and climate concerns. Shared mobility services, active transport modes and micromobility are a big part of the solution. With this in mind, the EU-funded GEMINI project aims to transform urban mobility. It will foster shared services, active transport, and micro-mobility integrated with public transit, ushering in a sustainable era of accessible, climate-neutral transportation solutions. Overall, the project will develop sustainable business models and digital platforms to support diverse mobility services. It will also involve stakeholders to formulate policy recommendations. For instance, its Mobility Living Labs and Twinning Cities serve as testbeds, reshaping urban mobility patterns and reducing reliance on cars.</p> <p>(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103801, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

SUM

Project Full Title	Seamless Shared Urban Mobility
Website	https://sum-project.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/sum https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103646 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/sum/
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-02
Project Coordinator	Institut national de recherche en informatique et en automatique (Inria) sum-coordinator@inria.fr
Project Partners	<p>30 partners</p> <p>Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB – Industrial and Material Science City of Munich / Landeshauptstadt München Coimbra Municipality / Câmara Municipal de Coimbra CONCESIONES UNIFICADAS S.L. (CUNISA) Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – Sustainable Urban Multimodal mobility (SUM) Lab European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation – Intelligent Transport Systems & Services Europe (ERTICO – ITS Europe) Fredrikstad Kommune Free Now Hellas Monoprosopi AE Hydrolift Smart City Ferries AS (Hyke) Institut national de recherche en informatique et en automatique (Inria) Institut VEDECOM Jagiellonian University / Uniwersytet Jagiellonski – Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science Krakow Municipality / Gmina Miejska Krakow – Miasto Na Prawach Powiatu LPT Larnaca Public Transportservices and Operations Ltd MOBY X SOFTWARE Ltd Municipality of Jerusalem Municipality of Penteli / Dimos Pentelis National Technical University of Athens / Ethnicon Metsovion Polytechnion (NTUA) – Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science Nextbike Cy Ltd POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Rotterdamse Elektrische Tram NV (RET) Serviços Municipalizados de Transportes Urbanos de Coimbra (SMTUC) Siemens Mobility B.V. SIGMA 6 Ltd SIXT GmbH & Co. Autovermietung KG Technical University of Munich / Technische Universität München (TUM) – Chair of Traffic Engineering and Control Tel Aviv University – Analytics for Urban Transportation and Operations Laboratory (AUTOLAB) Transports publics genevois (TPG) University of Twente / Universiteit Twente (UT) – Transport Engineering and Management (TEM) research group</p>

	ZF CV Systems Global GmbH		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.06.2023	End date	31.05.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred urban spaces and planning KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition		
Keywords	New and shared mobility systems (NSM), public transport, interconnectivity, innovation, environmental sustainability, safety, resilience, replicability, affordability, reliability, financial sustainability, acceptance, mobility management and pricing, policy tools, operational competitiveness, open data platform, passenger demand prediction, SUMPs, redesign of infrastructure, inclusion, accessibility		
Case Studies	Living Labs: Athens, Jerusalem, Geneva, Munich, Coimbra, Larnaca, Fredrikstad, Krakow, Rotterdam		
<p>European urban mobility systems require innovative interventions to enhance their sustainability. The EU-funded SUM project has set an ambitious goal: the integration of innovative shared mobility systems with public transport in over 15 European cities by 2026, with plans to expand to 30 cities by 2030. This is centred around key principles such as intermodality, interconnectivity, sustainability, safety, and resilience. The project's outcomes aim to deliver cost-effective and reliable solutions that align with the needs of various stakeholders, including end-users, private enterprises, and urban authorities. To achieve these objectives, the project will establish five pillars designed to encourage families who rely on cars to transition to sustainable transportation options. These pillars include practical solutions like prediction tools, scheduling assistance, and real-time management.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101103646, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

GIANTS

Project Full Title	Green Intelligent Affordable New Transport Solutions		
Website	https://giants-project.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101138220 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/giants/		
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D5-01		
Project Coordinator	Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH giants@v2c2.at		
Project Partners	<p>23 partners</p> <p>Clean Air Initiative for Asian Cities (CAI-ASIA) Center Inc Association Non-stock Corporation Clean Motion AB CLEPA, European Association of Automative Suppliers / Association européenne des fournisseurs automobiles Czech Technical University in Prague (CTU) / České vysoké učení technické v Praze – Centre of Vehicles for Sustainable Mobility Foundation for Innovation and Research – Malta (FIR.mt) HiWiTronics, Verein zur prinzipiellen Untersuchung von Hi-fidelity wireless Elektronik-Lösungen i2m Unternehmensentwicklung GmbH IESTA, Institute for advanced energy systems & transport applications / Institut für innovative Energie- & Stoffaustauschsysteme INND Bateries BV (Cleantron) Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (KULeuven) – Mecha(tro)nic System Dynamics (LMSD) POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Renault SAS Solbian Energie Alternative s.r.l. Squad Mobility BV TOJO Motors Corp Toyota Motor Europe NV TUX mobility B.V. Valeo Embrayages SAS Valeo équipements électriques moteur SAS Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electromobility research centre (MOBI) WE!Hub Victoria Limited (WeTu) Wuppertal Institut für Klima, Umwelt, Energie gGmbH</p>		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	30.06.2027
Key Area(s)	<p>Focus: Modular, scalable zero-emission L-type vehicle platform</p> <p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <p>1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options</p> <p>4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p>		

	<p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>1. Support thriving neighbourhood economies</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>
Keywords	Zero-emission L-type vehicle platform, refurbishment of used vehicles, global collaboration, mission-centric urban cargo- and passenger transport, affordable and accessible mobility solutions, local manufacturing, scalable electric mobility
Case Studies	Living Labs: Brugge, Stockholm, Kisumu, Delhi, Manila
<p>The demand for affordable and accessible mobility solutions is important. However, traditional approaches to transportation fail to address the diverse needs of both emerging and advanced markets, leaving many without options. Additionally, concerns over environmental sustainability continue to mount, urging a shift towards greener alternatives. In this context, the EU-funded GIANTS project aims to transform electric mobility. Specifically, the project offers a customisable platform catering to diverse user needs. Featuring modular components, innovative charging solutions, and solar panels, it promises scalable electric vehicles suited for urban traffic. The project prioritises user demands, ensuring practicality in both emerging and advanced markets. By promoting modularity and interoperability, GIANTS paves the way for a sustainable future in transportation.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101138220, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

JULIA

Project Full Title	Joint developments for Urban resilience connecting users to public transport through spAce technology		
Website	https://juliaproject.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101129891 https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/julia/		
Call	HORIZON-EUSPA-2022-SPACE		
Project Coordinator	Factual Consulting S.L.		
Project Partners	<p>14 partners</p> <p>Arriva Slovenija / ARRIVA, družba za prevoz potnikov d.o.o.</p> <p>Athens Urban Transport Organisation / Organismos Astikon Sygkoinonion Athinon AE (OASA S.A.)</p> <p>Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT)</p> <p>EarthPulse S.L.</p> <p>European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation – Intelligent Transport Systems & Services Europe (ERTICO – ITS Europe)</p> <p>Factual Consulting S.L.</p> <p>Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya (FGC)</p> <p>Hellenic Train – Anonymi Sidirodromiki Etaireia</p> <p>INIT Innovative Informatikanwendungen in Transport-, Verkehrs- und Leitsystemen GmbH</p> <p>Keita Mobility Factory S.L. / Lane Patrol</p> <p>Nemi Mobiliy Solutions S.L.</p> <p>Osborne Clarke Belgium</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>Rokubun S.L.</p>		
Duration (months)	30		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	30.06.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport 		
Keywords	Smarter public transport system, space technology, efficiency and reliability, safety, attractive public transport experience, cycling lanes, air quality		
Case Studies			
<p>Cities face multi-faceted public transport challenges, from meeting citizens' mobility needs to growing environmental concerns, traffic congestion and pollution. Key decision-makers grapple with the complexities of optimising systems while attracting more users towards public transport. Existing technologies often lack integration and fail to harness the full potential of EU space services. In this context, the EU-funded JULIA project will enhance public transport networks' reliability, safety and sustainability. By leveraging Galileo services, including OSNMA and HAS, and Copernicus Earth Observation data for air quality estimation, the project will demonstrate the value to key decision-makers, unlocking impacts globally. (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101129891, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

JUST STREETS

Project Full Title	Mobility justice for all: framing safer, healthier and happier streets
Website	https://www.just-streets.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/just-streets https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101104240
Call	HORIZON-MISS-2022-CIT-01
Project Coordinator	Fondazione LINKS – Leading Innovation & knowledge for society Giulia Melis, Giulia.melis@linksfoundation.com Francesca Blanc, Francesca.blanc@linksfoundation.com
Project Partners	<p>32 partners</p> <p>Braga City Council / Municipio de Braga</p> <p>Centro Studi PIM – Centro Studi per la Programmazione Intercomunale dell'area Metropolitana.</p> <p>City Council of Zaragoza / Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza</p> <p>City of Amsterdam / Gemeente Amsterdam</p> <p>City of Kozani / Dimos Kozanis</p> <p>Climate Alliance / Klima-Bündnis / Alianza del Clima e.V.</p> <p>Cugir City / Oraş Cugir</p> <p>European Cyclists Federation ASBL</p> <p>Fondazione LINKS – Leading Innovation & knowledge for society</p> <p>Fundación Circe Centro de Investigación de Recursos y Consumos Energéticos</p> <p>Haifa Municipality</p> <p>International Federation of Pedestrians (IFP) – Research</p> <p>IT University of Copenhagen / IT-Universitetet i København (ITU) – NETwoRks, Data, and Society (NERDS) research group</p> <p>Local Public Transport Agency of the Metropolitan City of Milan, Monza and Brianza, Lodi and Pavia / Agenzia per il Trasporto Pubblico Locale del bacino della Città Metropolitana di Milano, Monza e Brianza, Lodi e Pavia (Agenzia TPL)</p> <p>London Borough of Southwark</p> <p>Metropolitan City of Milan / Città metropolitana di Milano</p> <p>Municipality of Vratsa</p> <p>Politecnico di Torino (POLITO) – Department of Environment, Land and Infrastructure Engineering (DIATI)</p> <p>Politecnico di Torino (POLITO) – Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning (DIST)</p> <p>Riga City Council / Rīgas pilsētas pašvaldība</p> <p>RINA Consulting S.p.A.</p> <p>Sociealfare impresa sociale s.r.l. – Centro per l'Innovazione Sociale</p> <p>Technical University of Cluj-Napoca / Universitatea Tehnică din Cluj-Napoca (UTCN)</p> <p>Technion – Israel Institute of Technology</p> <p>The University of Westminster LBG</p> <p>TREDIT S.A., Transeuropean Consultants for Transport, Development and Information Technology S.A. / Dievropaiki Etairia Symboulon Metaforon Anaptixis Kai Pliroforikis AE</p> <p>UFGC GmbH / Urban Future</p> <p>Universiteit van Amsterdam (UvA)</p> <p>University of Porto / Universidade do Porto – Faculdade de Engenharia</p>

	Vilnius Municipality / Vilniaus miesto savivaldybės administracija Western Norway University of Applied Sciences / Høgskulen på Vestlandet (HVL) – Spatial Planning and Urban Studies research group Westminster City Council YUGOIZTOCHNOEVROPEYSKA TEHNOLOGICHNA KOMPANIA OOD		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	30.06.2027
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space KA2 People-centred urban spaces and planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Spatial justice, public space for all, car-centered mobility narratives, promotion of active mobility, vulnerable mobility users, reshape infrastructure and behaviour, inclusivity, sustainability		
Case Studies	8 pilot cities, 4 follower cities: Kozani, Vratsa, Riga, Amsterdam, Vilnius, Haifa, Braga, Westminster, Milan, London Borough of Southwark, Cugir, Zaragoza		
<p>JUST STREETS supports 8 pilot cities and 4 follower cities in transforming cities’ car-centered mobility narratives that take for granted that streets are for motorized traffic only. The project addresses the pressing need to reshape our streets both from an infrastructural and behavioural dimensions, sharing the generated “how-to-do-it” knowledge with hundreds of cities for rapid replication across Europe. In close collaboration with citizens, policy makers, experts, and interest groups the project will not only develop a new vision of spatial justice where streets become public space for all, but equally important find ways to rapidly implement changes.</p> <p>The focus extends to marginalized groups, including migrants, LGBTQI+ communities and individuals with disabilities, ensuring that their voices are not only heard but actively incorporated into the planning and development process.</p> <p>https://civitas.eu/projects/just-streets, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

metaCCAZE

Project Full Title	Flexibly adapted MetaInnovations, use cases, collaborative business and governance models to accelerate deployment of smart and shared Zero Emission mobility for passengers and freight
Website	https://www.metacaze-project.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/metacaze https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101139678
Call	HORIZON-MISS-2023-CIT-01
Project Coordinator	European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation – Intelligent Transport Systems & Services Europe (ERTICO – ITS Europe) Tamara Djukic, t.djukic@mail.ertico.com
Project Partners	<p>44 partners</p> <p>Agenzia Mobilità Ambiente e Territorio s.r.l. (AMAT) Argaleo B.V. Athens Anaplassis S.A. / Anaplassi dimosion choron anonyimi etaireia Athens Urban Transport Organisation / Organismos Astikon Sygkoinonion Athinon AE (OASA S.A.) B4B Logistics UG BABLE GmbH Budapest University of Technology and Economics / Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem (BME) – Department of Transport Technology and Economics City of Amsterdam / Gemeente Amsterdam City of Munich / Landeshauptstadt München City of Tampere / Tampereen Kaupunki Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – Department of Transport and Planning EMEL Ltd, Limassol Public Bus Transport Company / Etaireia metaforas epibatou lemesou European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation – Intelligent Transport Systems & Services Europe (ERTICO – ITS Europe) Factual Consulting S.L. Floware SAS HC Linear Műszaki Fejlesztő Kft. Institut VEDECOM Krakow Municipality / Gmina Miejska Krakow – Miasto Na Prawach Powiatu Limassol Municipality / Dimos Lemesos Local Council of Yvelines / Département des Yvelines Local Public Transport Agency of the Metropolitan City of Milan, Monza and Brianza, Lodi and Pavia / Agenzia per il Trasporto Pubblico Locale del bacino della Città Metropolitana di Milano, Monza e Brianza, Lodi e Pavia (Agenzia TPL) MaaSLab Malta Public Transport Services (Operations) Ltd Ministry for Transport, Infrastructure and Public Works (Malta) MobiLysis Sàrl MVK Miskolc City Transportation Ltd. / MVK Miskolc Városi Közlekedési Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság</p>

	<p>National Technical University of Athens / Ethnicon Metsovion Polytechnion (NTUA) – Traffic Engineering Laboratory</p> <p>Next s.r.l.</p> <p>Nextbike Cy Ltd</p> <p>Oxygen for Democracy / Oxygono</p> <p>Remoted OY</p> <p>Schenker AG</p> <p>Smart City System Parking Solutions GmbH</p> <p>stadtraum GmbH, Association for urban planning, urban design and traffic technology / Gesellschaft für Raumplanung, Städtebau & Verkehrstechnik mbH</p> <p>Steinbeis Innovation gGmbH / Steinbeis Europa Zentrum</p> <p>Stichting Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions (AMS)</p> <p>Stichting Townmaking</p> <p>Tampere University / Tampereen Korkeakoulusäätiö Sr – Transport Research Centre Verne</p> <p>Technical University of Munich / Technische Universität München (TUM) – Chair of Traffic Engineering and Control</p> <p>Technolution B.V.</p> <p>TRT Trasporti e Territorio s.r.l.</p> <p>University of Malta / Università ta' Malta (UM) – Institute for Climate Change & Sustainable Development (ICCSA)</p> <p>University of Naples Federico II / Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II</p> <p>Zoev City B.V.</p>		
Duration (months)	52		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2027
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 		
Keywords	Zero-emission mobility solutions, electric automated and connected technologies and infrastructure, business innovation, governance models, zero-emission shared mobility for passengers and goods, social acceptance, co-creation		
Case Studies	<p>Trailblazer cities: Amsterdam, Munich, Limassol, Tampere</p> <p>Follower Cities: Athens, Kraków, Gozo, Milan, Miskolc, Poissy (Paris)</p>		
<p>The metaCCAZE project aims to revolutionise mobility in European cities, serving both passengers and freight, with innovative electric, automated, and connected solutions designed to make transportation smarter, net zero, and more efficient for all.</p> <p>In the vibrant streets of four trailblazer cities – Amsterdam, Munich, Limassol, and Tampere – metaCCAZE tests and demonstrates technologies that support shared zero-emission mobility solutions for people and</p>			

goods, contributing to climate neutrality. Successful technologies and activities will be shared with and implemented in six Follower Cities – Athens, Kraków, Gozo, Milan, Miskolc, and Poissy (Paris).

To ensure the technologies meet the needs of citizens and urban mobility stakeholders, a series of co-creation activities will be organised locally in the cities.

(<https://civitas.eu/projects/metacaze>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

MOBILITIES FOR EU

Project Full Title	New MOBility solutions for climate neutrality in EU cities		
Website	https://mobilities-for.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/mobilities-for-eu https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101139666		
Call	HORIZON-MISS-2023-CIT-01		
Project Coordinator	Fundación CARTIF Julia Vicente Gómez, julvic@cartif.es		
Project Partners	<p>29 partners</p> <p>AEDIVE, Asociación Empresarial para el Desarrollo e Impulso de la Movilidad Eléctrica / Asociación de Empresas para el Desarrollo e Impulso del Vehículo Eléctrico</p> <p>Cabinet of the Prime Minister Sarajevo Canton</p> <p>CARNET Future Mobility Research Hub / Fundació Centre d'Innovació i Tecnologia de la UPC</p> <p>City Council of Madrid / Ayuntamiento de Madrid</p> <p>City of Dresden / Landeshauptstadt Dresden</p> <p>City of Espoo / Espoon Kaupunki</p> <p>City of Gdansk / Gdańsk / Gmina Miasta Gdanska</p> <p>City of Trenčin / Mesto Trenčín</p> <p>Empresa Municipal de Transportes de Madrid (EMT Madrid)</p> <p>Ferrovial Construcción S.A.</p> <p>Ferrovial Corporacion S.A.</p> <p>Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V.</p> <p>Fundación CARTIF</p> <p>International Road Federation (IRF)</p> <p>Mercados Centrales de Abastecimientos de Madrid S.A. (Mercamadrid)</p> <p>Municipality of Ioannina</p> <p>Orange Espagne S.A.</p> <p>Plexigrid S.L.</p> <p>PreZero Gestion De Residuos S.A.</p> <p>Proyectos Unificados S.A.</p> <p>Sächsische Energieagentur – SAENA GmbH</p> <p>SAP SE</p> <p>Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava / Slovenská technická univerzita v Bratislave (STU) – Spectra Centre of Excellence of the EU</p> <p>Steinbeis Innovation GmbH / Steinbeis Europa Zentrum</p> <p>Technische Universität Dresden (TU Dresden) – Institute of Communication Technology</p> <p>T-Systems ITC Iberia S.A.</p> <p>Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) – R&D+i center for Energy Efficiency, Virtual Reality, Optical Engineering and Biometry (CeDIInt)</p> <p>Volkswagen AG</p> <p>We Right-Click</p>		
Duration (months)	60		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2028

Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders
Keywords	<p>Innovative urban mobility solutions, electrification, automation, connectivity, climate neutrality, Urban Transport Labs, stakeholder involvement, co-design, community needs, user-centred solutions for passenger mobility and freight transport</p>
Case Studies	<p>Lead Cities: Madrid, Dresden</p> <p>Replication Cities: Ioannina, Trenčín, Espoo, Gdańsk, Sarajevo</p>
<p>MOBILITIES for EU showcases innovative urban mobility solutions, leveraging electrification, automation, and connectivity to transform urban transportation. Seven European cities, aligned with climate neutrality goals by 2030 as part of the 112 Mission Cities, form the project's core.</p> <p>Urban Transport Labs (UT-Labs) in these cities engage local stakeholders throughout project phases, ensuring solutions meet community needs. Madrid and Dresden lead with 27 pilot actions, spanning from technologies such as autonomous e-buses to decentralized data ecosystems.</p> <p>Each solution undergoes rigorous evaluation, guiding future scalability. Replication Cities—Ioannina, Trenčín, Espoo, Gdańsk, and Sarajevo—will adapt and replicate successful solutions from the Lead Cities, fostering sustainable mobility across Europe.</p> <p>https://civitas.eu/projects/mobilities-for-eu, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

CodeZERO

Project Full Title	CO-DESIGN OF E-COMMERCE LAST-MILE DELIVERY AND RETURN OPTIONS WITH ZERO EMISSIONS		
Website	https://www.codezero-project.eu/ https://civitas.eu/projects/codezero https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101146909		
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D6-01		
Project Coordinator	TRT Trasporti e Territorio s.r.l. Claudia De Stasio, destasio@trt.it		
Project Partners	<p>15 partners</p> <p>Agenzia Mobilità Ambiente e Territorio s.r.l. (AMAT)</p> <p>Bpost</p> <p>City of Antwerp / Stad Antwerpen</p> <p>City of Oslo / Oslo Kommune</p> <p>City of Utrecht / Gemeente Utrecht</p> <p>Eurocities ASBL</p> <p>IKEA AS</p> <p>IKEA Italia Retail s.r.l.</p> <p>Institute of Transport Economics / Transportøkonomisk Institutt (TOI)</p> <p>Jumbo Supermarkten B.V.</p> <p>Magma s.r.l. Impresa Sociale – So.De. Social Delivery</p> <p>Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research / Nederlandse Organisatie voor toegepast-natuurwetenschappelijk onderzoek (TNO)</p> <p>Torfs L</p> <p>TRT Trasporti e Territorio s.r.l.</p> <p>Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Mobilise</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.06.2024	End date	31.05.2027
Key Area(s)	<p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 4. Support sustainable lifestyles</p> <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>		
Keywords	Delivery logistics, sustainable e-commerce ecosystem, consumer behaviour, zero-emission last-mile delivery and return solutions, co-design, communication guidelines, toolset for local authorities		
Case Studies	Pilot sites: Antwerp, Milan, Oslo, Utrecht		

CodeZERO is a transformative three-year initiative to create sustainable, zero-emission last-mile delivery and return solutions for e-commerce. Our mission is to make these solutions attractive and viable for retailers, logistics service providers and consumers.

The convenience of online shopping has created high expectations among consumers for fast, free, and flexible delivery options.

However, this poses a significant challenge for retailers and logistics providers striving to meet these demands while minimising environmental impact. The disconnection between consumer expectations and the realities of delivery logistics needs to be addressed to create a more sustainable e-commerce ecosystem. CodeZERO is innovating, testing and sharing solutions to influence consumer behaviour to choose more sustainable delivery options in four pilot sites: Antwerp, Milan, Oslo, and Utrecht.

(<https://www.codezero-project.eu/about-us/>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

GreenTurn

Project Full Title	Enabling stakeholder-centric zero emission e-commerce delivery and return practices through transparent and collaborative supply chains		
Website	https://civitas.eu/projects/greenturn https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101147942		
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D6-01		
Project Coordinator	Łukasiewicz Research Network / Sieć Badawcza Łukasiewicz – Poznań Institute of Technology / Poznański Instytut Technologiczny Bartosz Kożuch, bartosz.kozuch@pit.lukasiewicz.gov.pl		
Project Partners	14 partners Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe (ALICE) Bax Innovation Consulting S.L. / Bax & Company Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB City Council of Zaragoza / Ayuntamiento de Zaragoza ECONSULT Betriebsberatungsges.m.b.H Fundación Zaragoza Ciudad del Conocimiento (FZC) InPost spółka z ograniczoną odpowiedzialnością Logika Apothikefseis Emporevmaton Monoprosopi Etaireia Periorismenis Eythinis LogPOINT Logistics Services GmbH Łukasiewicz Research Network / Sieć Badawcza Łukasiewicz – Poznań Institute of Technology / Poznański Instytut Technologiczny Poznan City Hall / Miasto Poznań University of Antwerp / Universiteit Antwerpen – Department of Transport and Regional Economics (TPR) University of Groningen / Rijksuniversiteit Groningen University of the Aegean / Panepistimio Aigaiou		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.08.2024	End date	31.07.2027
Key Area(s)	KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Zero-emission logistics solutions, e-commerce footprints, delivery and return options, design thinking approach, social sustainability aspects, physical and digital accessibility, work conditions, Stakeholder Advisory Board, behavioural interventions		
Case Studies	Vienna, Lyon, Athens, Zaragoza, Poznan		

GreenTurn uses design thinking approaches to develop solutions which bridge between behavioural interventions (including incentives, nudges and gamification) and delivery and return options (such as time windows, in-store pick-ups and returnable packaging, among others).

To test solutions, GreenTurn implements 5 complementary pilots involving logistic service providers, marketplace providers and retailers as partners or stakeholders.

Besides, the GreenTurn pilots will touch upon social sustainability aspects too, for both customers (e.g. physical and digital accessibility), and e-commerce logistics employees (e.g. work conditions, market reintegration, etc.) Together with its public authorities, GreenTurn will translate results into policies that can secure uptake and long-term impact.

(<https://civitas.eu/projects/greenturn>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

Interreg

Website	https://interreg.eu/ https://keep.eu/
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Interreg initiated in 1990 with an emphasis on cross-border cooperation. It is part of the EU Cohesion Policy and receives funding from the European Regional Development Fund. Currently, Interreg is in its sixth period “Interreg VI”, that will run from 2021 to 2027, and is dedicated to the cohesion policy priorities “Smart growth”, “Green transition”, “Social inclusion”, “Territorial development” and “Efficient and sustainable infrastructure”. Interreg VI involves a budget of €10 billion and around 100 Interreg programmes, categorised into four “Strands of Cooperation” spanning from cross-border cooperation to cooperation with non-European countries (INTERACT Office Viborg, n.d.).

The 12 collected projects are from the previous (2014-2020) and current periods (2021-2027). Ignoring the different periods, four projects belong to the programme Interreg North Sea and another four projects to Interreg Europe.

2014 – 2020

REFORM

Project Full Title	Integrated REgional Action Plan For Innovative, Sustainable and LOw CaRbon Mobility		
Website	https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/reform/ https://keep.eu/projects/18887/Integrated-REgional-Action--EN/ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/reform/		
Call	2014 - 2020 Interreg Europe		
Project Coordinator	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT) Maria Morfoulaki		
Project Partners	7 partners Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT) Institute for Transport and Logistics Foundation / Fondazione Istituto sui trasporti e la logistica (ITL) POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Region Parkstad Limburg Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia on behalf of the Region of Central Macedonia Regione Emilia Romagna Transport for Greater Manchester (TFGM)		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	01.01.2017	End date	31.12.2020
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	SUMPs, learning exchanges, SUMP development process and adoption rate, regional operation programs, low-carbon mobility, stakeholder involvement		
Case Studies	Cities in the regions: Central Macedonia, Emilia-Romagna, Parkstad Limburg, Greater Manchester		
<p>REFORM supports the implementation and deployment of Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMPs) as an instrument for shifting mobility towards low-carbon patterns. In the framework of the project, through regional and interregional learning exchanges, REFORM triggers the SUMP development process and amplifies the SUMP adoption rate by local cities in four European regions: Central Macedonia (Greece), Emilia-Romagna (Italy), Parkstad Limburg (the Netherlands) & Greater Manchester (United-Kingdom).</p> <p>The partners develop guidance materials and organise a series of dedicated events to help local municipalities in the preparation of their SUMP, to ease the transition towards low-carbon alternatives for mobility on their territory.</p> <p>(https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/reform/, retrieved 26 September 2024)</p>			

eHUBS

Project Full Title	Smart Shared Green Mobility Hubs		
Website	https://vb.nweurope.eu/projects/project-search/ehubs-smart-shared-green-mobility-hubs/ https://elopage.com/s/eHubs/ehubs-digital-blueprint https://keep.eu/projects/21149/ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/ehubs/		
Call	2014 – 2020 INTERREG VB North West Europe		
Project Coordinator	City of Amsterdam / Gemeente Amsterdam Debbie Dekkers, d.dekkers@amsterdam.nl		
Project Partners	<p>20 partners</p> <p>Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences – Psychology for Sustainable Cities</p> <p>Autodelen.net – Carshare Belgium</p> <p>Autorité Organisatrice du Transport (AOT), Service Public de Wallonie Mobilité et Infrastructures</p> <p>Bayern Innovativ, Bayerische Gesellschaft für Innovation und Wissenstransfer mbH</p> <p>cargoroo</p> <p>City of Amsterdam / Gemeente Amsterdam</p> <p>City of Arnhem</p> <p>City of Dreux</p> <p>City of Kempten (Allgäu)</p> <p>City of Leuven / Stad Leuven</p> <p>Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) – Department of Transport and Planning</p> <p>Electricity Supply Board (ESB)</p> <p>Mpact vzw / Mpact asbl</p> <p>Municipality of Nijmegen</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>The Highlands and Islands Transport Partnership (HITRANS)</p> <p>Transport for Greater Manchester (TFGM)</p> <p>University of Antwerp / Universiteit Antwerpen – Department of Transport and Regional Economics (TPR)</p> <p>University of Newcastle upon Tyne – Future Mobility Group</p> <p>URBEE, E-Bike Network Amsterdam B.V.</p>		
Duration (months)	58		
Start date	10.01.2019	End date	30.10.2023
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <p>1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options</p> <p>4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p> <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <p>4. Support sustainable lifestyles</p>		

	KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments
Keywords	Shared electric mobility services, e-Mobility hubs, best practices, mobility transition, emission reduction
Case Studies	Manchester, Arnhem-Nijmegen, Leuven, Amsterdam
<p>The eHUBS project will develop on-street locations that bring together e-bikes, e-cargo bikes, e-scooters and/or e-cars, offering users a wide range of options to experiment and use in various situations.</p> <p>E-mobility solutions are growing in both popularity and range, with people now able to access e-bikes, cargo bikes, scooters and cars for purchase or hire. However, more action is needed to make these modes more commonly used in cities and achieve a further shift away from petrol and diesel cars.</p> <p>eHUBS aims to give a high-quality and diverse offer of shared electric mobility services to dissuade citizens from owning private cars, resulting in cleaner, more liveable and pleasant cities. Six partner cities and regions from five different countries - including Manchester, Arnhem-Nijmegen, Leuven and Amsterdam - will realise and promote eHUBS and pave the way for others to do the same. Consortium partners include POLIS, Newcastle University, TU Delft, Cargoroo and others.</p> <p>The eHUBS implementation approach will differ according to the size and needs of the respective cities. In doing so, it will develop knowledge, best practices and a blueprint that would lead to replication of the experiences in other cities and regions, as well as a consistent reduction of air pollution, congestion and carbon emissions in the cities and a growing market for commercial shared e-mobility providers aligned with local policy goals.</p> <p>(https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/ehubs/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

e-smartec

Project Full Title	enhanced sustainable mobility with marketing techniques		
Website	https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/e-smartec/ https://keep.eu/projects/21509/enhanced-sustainable-mobili-EN/ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/e-smartec/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/enhanced-sustainable-mobility-marketing-techniques		
Call	2014 - 2020 Interreg Europe		
Project Coordinator	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT) Maria Morfoulaki		
Project Partners	9 partners Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT) Coventry University Enterprises Ltd (CUE Ltd) – CUE Business Solutions Hessen Trade & Invest GmbH / Fachzentrum Nachhaltige Urbane Mobilität des Landes Hessen (HTAI/FZ-NUM) Municipality of Venlo / Gemeente Venlo POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia on behalf of the Region of Central Macedonia Roma Servizi per la Mobilità s.r.l. / Roma Mobilità Università degli Studi Link Campus University University of Zilina / Žilinská Univerzita v Žiline		
Duration (months)	30		
Start date	01.08.2019	End date	31.01.2023
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Sustainable urban mobility planning, targeted marketing techniques, bottom-up and top-down decision making, low carbon economy, public acceptance, competitive and resource efficient transport system, crowdsourcing, social media, behaviour influence, good practices		

Case Studies	Test-bed areas: Bratislava self-governing region, City of Venlo, Lazio region, Region of Central Macedonia, State of Hessen, West Midlands
<p>Many European urban areas face a series of environmental challenges linked to mobility congestion and air pollution. Based on experience, sustainable urban mobility planning cannot be achieved without the commitment of key stakeholders and travellers and given this need, e-smartec proposes accompanying each step of mobility planning with the deployment of targeted marketing techniques for linking bottom-up and top-down decision making.</p> <p>The e-smartec project is designed to strengthen the urban dimension of regional and local mobility policymaking, contributing to the implementation of the EU Transport White Paper, Urban Agenda and EU 2020 with a view to transit to a low carbon economy.</p> <p>e-smartec aims at developing Action Plans to start and implement effective mobility interventions, as the basis for a competitive, resource-efficient and low carbon oriented European transport system.</p> <p>The 9 e-smartec partners, from 7 EU countries representing the 6 e-smartec test-bed areas, join their forces in an ultimate goal to provide tailored guidelines on citizens and stakeholders' engagement marketing techniques for innovative decision-making and traditional procedures.</p> <p>https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/e-smartec/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

PAV

Project Full Title	Planning for Autonomous Vehicles		
Website	https://northsearegion.eu/pav/ https://keep.eu/projects/23464/Planning-for-Autonomous-Veh-EN/ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/pav/		
Call	2014 - 2020 Interreg VB North Sea		
Project Coordinator	The Highlands and Islands Transport Partnership (HITRANS) Ranald Robertson, ranald.robertson@hitrans.org.uk		
Project Partners	12 partners Almere City CLEAN Clean Tech Delta Ghent University / Universiteit Gent – Social and Economic Geography (SEG) Research group Halmstad University / Högskolan i Halmstad – Centre for Research on Embedded Systems (CERES) Municipality of Varberg POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Region Hannover Robert Gordon University (RGU) – Digital Cities and Society Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH The Highlands and Islands Transport Partnership (HITRANS) The Oslo School of Architecture and Design / Arkitektur- og designhøgskolen i Oslo (AHO)		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	02.09.2019	End date	01.03.2023
Key Area(s)	KA1 Sustainable urban mobility 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred urban spaces and planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA4 Urban governance for mobility transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Autonomous Vehicles (AVs), societal and environmental impacts, sustainable transport and spatial planning strategies, electric shared AVs		
Case Studies	Pilots: Hannover Region, Almere, Varberg		
<p>Autonomous vehicles (AVs) have the potential to radically transform the spaces we travel through and to. While many European cities have already started experimenting with autonomous mobility, much of the current discussion revolves around the technology itself and its potential social and environmental impact. But if AVs aren't properly integrated into a city's spatial planning, chances are high that it won't be able to deliver on its promised potential.</p> <p>PAV is an Interreg NSR-funded project that will help cities develop sustainable spatial planning strategies that include AVs. Beyond working directly with the partner cities, PAV can help other local authorities</p>			

integrate autonomous mobility by making the necessary knowledge and methodology freely and easily accessible.

(<https://northsearegion.eu/pav/>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

Dynaxibility4CE

Project Full Title	Capacities for dynamic and flexible planning for low-carbon mobility trends and policies in Central Europe		
Website	https://programme2014-20.interreg-central.eu/Content.Node/Dynaxibility4CE.html https://keep.eu/projects/24819/Capacities-for-dynamic-and--EN/ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/dynaxibility4ce/		
Call	2014 - 2020 Interreg VB Central Europe		
Project Coordinator	Leipziger Verkehrsbetriebe (LVB) GmbH		
Project Partners	<p>13 partners</p> <p>Agenzia regionale per la prevenzione, l'ambiente e l'energia dell'Emilia-Romagna</p> <p>AustriaTech – Gesellschaft des Bundes für technologiepolitische Maßnahmen GmbH</p> <p>BKK Centre for Budapest Transport / Budapesti Közlekedési Központ Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság</p> <p>City of Graz / Stadt Graz</p> <p>City of Koprivnica / Grad Koprivnica</p> <p>City of Parma / Comune di Parma</p> <p>Leipziger Verkehrsbetriebe (LVB) GmbH</p> <p>Mobilissimus Korlátolt felelősségű társaság</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>Redmint Impresa Sociale s.c.r.l.</p> <p>Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH</p> <p>Verband Region Stuttgart</p> <p>Zarząd Transportu Publicznego w Krakowie (ZTP)</p>		
Duration (months)	27		
Start date	01.03.2020	End date	31.05.2022
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Sustainable urban mobility</p> <p>4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p> <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <p>1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity</p> <p>3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies</p> <p>KA4 Urban governance for mobility transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p> <p>3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>		
Keywords	Low-carbon and low-pollution mobility, public transport, new mobility trends, planning capacities, Mobility as a Service (MaaS), sharing, connected and automated driving (CAD), SUMP projects, Functional Urban Areas (FUAs), environmental and socio-economic impact, Urban Vehicle Access Regulations (UVARs), Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM)		
Case Studies	Budapest, Graz, Koprivnica, Krakow, Leipzig, Parma, Stuttgart		
The Interreg Central Europe-funded project 'Dynaxibility4CE' aimed to improve low-carbon mobility and air quality across the region of Central Europe by increasing the ability of public transport authorities to			

deal with new mobility trends. The latter includes ‘Mobility as a Service’ (MaaS), Urban Vehicle Access Regulations (UVARs), as well as the topic of Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM). The capacity-building was achieved by developing strategies and tools for public (transport) authorities that strengthen the planning capacities of cities throughout the region of Central Europe. Thus, the project enables these authorities to become key actors in creating low-carbon and low-pollution mobility systems in seven cities in the Interreg Central Europe area and their respective Functional Urban Areas (FUAs).

(<https://keep.eu/projects/24819/Capacities-for-dynamic-and--EN/>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

MOBI-MIX

Project Full Title	Improved implementation of shared mobility and MaaS to increase up-take of low-carbon transport in cities		
Website	https://www.interreg2seas.eu/en/MOBI-MIX https://sharedmobilityguide.futuremobility.expert/mobility-guide/cover https://keep.eu/projects/24092/Improved-implementation-of--EN/ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/mobi-mix/		
Call	Programme 2014 - 2020 Interreg V-A Les Deux Mers / Two seas / Twee Zeeën		
Project Coordinator	Municipality of Rotterdam / Gemeente Rotterdam Arjan Oranje, aj.oranje@rotterdam.nl		
Project Partners	10 partners Cambridge Cleantech City of Antwerp / Stad Antwerpen City of Mechelen / Stad Mechelen CoMoUK – Collaborative Mobility UK Ghent University / Universiteit Gent – Social and Economic Geography (SEG) Research group Municipality of Rotterdam / Gemeente Rotterdam Norfolk County Council POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Technopôle Transalley / Association du Technopôle Valenciennois Université Gustave Eiffel – LVMT Laboratoire Ville Mobilité Transport		
Duration (months)	31		
Start date	02.03.2020	End date	30.09.2022
Key Area(s)	KA1 Sustainable urban mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban governance for mobility transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Shared mobility, MaaS, low-carbon transport, mobility hubs, effective implementation, CO2 reduction, decision-making framework, urban mobility plans, public-private collaboration models		
Case Studies	Rotterdam, Antwerp, Mechelen, Norfolk County, Valenciennes		
<p>The MOBI-MIX project partners worked together with the aim of decarbonising road transport (cars in particular).</p> <p>Within the project, they sought to facilitate the private sector to implement Shared Mobility solutions (e.g. e-bikes, e-scooters, shared mopeds, docked bikes, shared cars) and MaaS solutions (the integration of various forms of transport services into a single mobility service accessible on demand) in a more effective approach.</p>			

The aim was to reduce 365.000 kg of CO₂-emissions by avoiding /replacing 2.6M fossil-fuelled car-kilometres in the urban environments of 5 cities in the 2 Seas area over the course of the project.

To foster long-term uptake, MOBI-MIX wanted to embed lessons learned and best practices in the urban mobility plans of the cities, serving 1.5M inhabitants and leading to a significant CO₂ reduction beyond project lifetime. Additionally, they sought to create a comprehensive decision-making framework for urban mobility planners of cities across Europe to facilitate the implementation of MaaS and Shared mobility more effectively.

(<https://www.interreg2seas.eu/en/MOBI-MIX>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

ShareDiMobiHub

Project Full Title	Shared & Digital Mobility Hubs		
Website	https://www.interregnorthsea.eu/sharedimobihub https://keep.eu/projects/27565/Shared-and-Digital-Mobility--EN/ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/sharedimobihub/		
Call	2021 - 2027 Interreg VI-B North Sea		
Project Coordinator	Province of Utrecht / Provincie Utrecht Arjen Rodenburg, arjen.rodenburg@smartmobilityandtransport.nl		
Project Partners	<p>17 partners</p> <p>Autodelen.net – Carshare Belgium</p> <p>City of Amsterdam / Gemeente Amsterdam</p> <p>City of Leuven / Stad Leuven</p> <p>Hamburg University of Applied Sciences (HAW Hamburg) – Sustainable Development and Climate Change Management Research and Transfer Centre (FTZ NK)</p> <p>Mpact vzw / Mpact asbl</p> <p>Municipality of Rotterdam / Gemeente Rotterdam</p> <p>Municipality of Tonsberg / Tønsberg kommune</p> <p>Norwegian Public Roads Administration / Statens vegvesen</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>Porsgrunn Municipality</p> <p>Province of Utrecht / Provincie Utrecht</p> <p>Skien municipality</p> <p>The Capital Region of Denmark</p> <p>University of Antwerp / Universiteit Antwerpen – Department of Transport and Regional Economics (TPR)</p> <p>University of Applied Sciences Utrecht / Hogeschool Utrecht (HU) – Centre of Expertise Smart Sustainable Cities</p> <p>Vervoerregio Amsterdam – Transport Authority for the Amsterdam Region</p> <p>Vestfold and Telemark County / Grenland VTFK</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	20.09.2022	End date	30.09.2025
Key Area(s)	<p>Focus: Shared mobility hubs</p> <p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		
Keywords	Sustainable and accessible urban mobility, uptake of shared mobility hubs, integration into Mobility as a Service (MaaS) and public transport, mobility needs,		

	business case, nudging, sustainable scale deployment, digitalization plans, cooperation
Case Studies	Pilots: Capital Region of Denmark, City of Amsterdam, Vervoerregio Transport Authority for the Amsterdam Region, Province of Utrecht, City of Rotterdam, City of Leuven, Grenland district and Skien and Porsgrunn communes, Tonsberg Municipality and Vestfold County
<p>Making urban mobility more sustainable and accessible is crucial for both health and quality of life of citizens. Reducing private car use in cities and changing people’s travel behaviour are key actions for a transition to a net-zero carbon economy.</p> <p>ShareDiMobiHub aims to improve urban multi-modal accessibility by increasing the introduction and uptake of shared mobility hubs. As well as integrating them into the Mobility as a Service (MaaS) ecosystem and public transport networks, resulting in a modal shift and behavioural change towards shared mobility hubs.</p> <p>Shared mobility hubs may vary in size, type of location, and type of offer. They can be small and located in residential areas, with just one or two parking spots, or bigger well-positioned proximity to stations and major public transport interchanges. In the end, their location, size, and shared vehicle option should be determined according to the mobility needs of cities, end-users, and the business case of electric and shared mobility providers.</p> <p>https://www.interregnorthsea.eu/sharedimobihub, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

SMALL

Project Full Title	Shared Multimodal Mobility For ALL		
Website	https://sharedmobilityforall.eu/ https://www.interregnorthsea.eu/small https://keep.eu/projects/27579/Shared-Multimodal-Mobility-F-EN/ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/small/		
Call	2021 - 2027 Interreg VI-B North Sea		
Project Coordinator	Mpact vzw Esen Köse, esen.kose@mpact.be		
Project Partners	<p>12 partners</p> <p>Brest Métropole</p> <p>City of Amsterdam / Gemeente Amsterdam</p> <p>City of Saint-Quentin / Ville de Saint-Quentin</p> <p>De Fietsambassade Gent vzw</p> <p>Ghent University / Universiteit Gent – Department of Geography</p> <p>Mpact vzw / Mpact asbl</p> <p>Municipality of Varberg</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH</p> <p>The Capital Region of Denmark</p> <p>Vervoerregio Amsterdam – Transport Authority for the Amsterdam Region</p> <p>VU University Amsterdam / Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam – Athena Institute</p>		
Duration (months)	48		
Start date	02.10.2022	End date	02.10.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		
Keywords	Inclusive shared mobility solution, specific mobility needs, accessible shared mobility, People with Reduced Mobility (PRMs), policy database, co-creation of new shared mobility services, MaaS, best practice examples, community platform, user engagement, volunteering schemes, digital solutions		
Case Studies	Pilots: Capital Region of Denmark, City of Saint Quentin, City of Varberg, City of Amsterdam, Brest Metropole, Gent		
Think of a person using a shared bike or scooter. What do you see? It is quite likely you are thinking of a young, fully mobile person zipping down an urban street. There's a reason for this - the vast majority of			

shared mobility users fit this narrow description. Currently, shared mobility is poorly designed for groups with reduced mobility, including: Children and families; The elderly; The physically impaired.

But this does not have to be the case. Shared mobility solutions can improve mobility for all users - but first, we need to design for accessibility.

This is the mission behind our project, Shared multimodal Mobility for ALL (SMALL). Led by Belgian NGO Mpact, this Interreg North Sea Programme project will spend the next four years on:

- Including people with reduced mobility in the design of shared solutions, to make sure they meet their needs
- Deploying and testing inclusive shared mobility solutions, including new vehicles, apps, and volunteering initiative
- Writing guidelines for public authorities on supporting inclusive shared mobility

(<https://www.interregnorthsea.eu/small/about-us>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

SMAPE

Project Full Title	Shared Mobility Action Programmes Exchange		
Website	https://www.interregeurope.eu/smape https://keep.eu/projects/28176/Shared-Mobility-Action-Progr-EN/ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/smape/		
Call	2021 – 2027 Interreg VI-C Interreg Europe		
Project Coordinator	Free Hanseatic City of Bremen / Freie Hansestadt Bremen Rebecca Karbaumer		
Project Partners	10 partners Autodelen.net – Carshare Belgium Bucharest – Ilfov Regional Development Agency / Agentia pentru Dezvoltare Regionala Bucuresti Ilfov (BI RDA) City Council of Bergen / Bergen Kommune Free Hanseatic City of Bremen / Freie Hansestadt Bremen POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Province of Mantua Regional Development Agency of Ljubljana Urban Region / Regionalna razvojna agencija Ljubljanske urbane regije (RRA LUR) Regional Development Fund of North Aegean (PTABA) University of West Attica / Panepistimio Dytikis Attikis (UNIWA) Walloon Organizing Authority for Public and Shared transport		
Duration (months)	51		
Start date	01.03.2023	End date	31.05.2027
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Modal shift, transport poverty, improved shared mobility policies, integration with public transport, Mobility as a Service, dashboards, public private partnerships, SUMPs		
Case Studies			
<p>The Shared Mobility Action Programmes Exchange (SMAPE) project aims to improve shared mobility policies. More specifically, the project will focus on aspects like shared mobility integration with public transport and Mobility as a Service, usage of data (dashboards) for monitoring and policy adjustments and data sharing, influence attitude and behaviour, optimising the mix of mobility modes, regulations, frameworks for public private partnerships and policy recommendations and contributions to Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP).</p>			

The SMAPE consortium consists of partners from Belgium, Germany, Norway, Greece, Italy, Slovenia and Romania and together they will improve 7 policy instruments that have a focus on shared mobility. Two of these instruments concern ERDF-programmes.

What will this project change: Shared mobility has been booming the past 3 years. Shared Mobility solutions can be seen as one of the solutions to create more liveable and greener cities. Many cities, transport operators and shared mobility providers implemented pilots to test these solutions. However, most of the pilots were detached from the general mobility system. Based on best practices, SMAPE will apply an integral approach to improve or draft shared mobility policies.

(<https://keep.eu/projects/28176/Shared-Mobility-Action-Progr-EN/>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

UrbFRail

Project Full Title	Revitalisation of Inner-Urban Freight Rail Hubs		
Website	https://interreg-baltic.eu/project/urbfrail/ https://keep.eu/projects/29186/Revitalisation-of-Inner-Urb-EN/		
Call	2021 - 2027 Interreg VI-B Baltic Sea Region		
Project Coordinator	Berlin – Senate Department for Mobility, Transport, Climate Protection and the Environment / Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt Steve Danesch, steve.danesch@senumvk.berlin.de		
Project Partners	7 partners Berlin – Senate Department for Mobility, Transport, Climate Protection and the Environment / Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad KTH Royal Institute of Technology / Kungliga Tekniska högskolan Lindholmen Science Park AB Metropolis GZM / Upper Silesian-Zaglebie Metropolis / Górnośląsko-Zagłębiowska Metropolia Swedish Transport Administration / Trafikverket Warsaw University of Technology (WUT) – Faculty of Transport		
Duration (months)	24		
Start date	21.04.2023	End date	30.04.2025
Key Area(s)	KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA3 Smart urban logistics, production and service sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	revitalisation of freight rail hubs, sustainable last-mile transport, infrastructure, spatial and transport planning, screening and development tool, Urban Rail Freight Learning Platform		
Case Studies	Stockholm, Warsaw Metropolitan Region, Berlin		
<p>During the past 30 years, inner-urban freight rail transport dramatically lost importance due to de-industrialization following the collapse of socialist countries and commercialisation of rail transport, leaving inner-urban freight rail infrastructure largely unexploited. With the growing need to reduce carbon emissions in transport, these areas are getting into focus again, to shift goods from road to rail and to make last mile transport more sustainable.</p> <p>The development of inner-urban freight rail hubs is a complex issue, as a number of requirements have to be met, e.g. related to infrastructure, spatial planning, economic feasibility as well as financing and governance. Political decisions that may involve substantial public investments, require to be well prepared development concept and process. With inner-urban freight rail transport having been out of the focus for the last 30 years, planners are lacking expertise and guidance is needed.</p>			

This challenge is addressed by UrbFRail by developing a set of tool that will enable spatial and transport planners to select suitable areas for freight rail hubs and to foster their revitalisation: the urban freight rail screening and the urban freight rail development tool. Both tools will be designed to get applied to similar cases with the possibility to adopt them. Via a Urban Rail Freight Learning Platform, planners will be able to access the tool and to use it in their daily work.

(<https://keep.eu/projects/29186/Revitalisation-of-Inner-Urb-EN/>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

MoLo Hubs

Project Full Title	People-Centric Mobility & Logistics Hubs		
Website	https://www.interregnorthsea.eu/molo-hubs https://keep.eu/projects/28288/People-Centric-Mobility-Logi-EN/ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/molo-hubs/		
Call	2021 - 2027 Interreg VI-B North Sea		
Project Coordinator	Logistik-Initiative Hamburg Management GmbH Thomas Brauner, tb@hamburg-logistik.net		
Project Partners	<p>13 partners</p> <p>Aalborg Municipality / Aalborg Kommune Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences City of Amsterdam / Gemeente Amsterdam City of Borås / Borås Stad City of Mechelen / Stad Mechelen Hamburg Institute for Innovation, Climate Protection and Circular Economy GmbH (HiCCCE) Homerunner / CoolRunner Huset Venture Nordjylland Logistik-Initiative Hamburg Management GmbH POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Stadtreinigung Hamburg AöR Transition ApS University of Antwerp / Universiteit Antwerpen – Department of Transport and Regional Economics (TPR)</p>		
Duration (months)	42		
Start date	01.07.2023	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space 4. Support sustainable lifestyles <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		
Keywords	Mobility and logistics hubs, urban mobility and logistics, user centric logistics services, attractiveness of mobility hubs, digital technologies, shared mobility, supply & return flows, integration of new logistics services into mobility hubs,		

	innovative urban value chains, shift to green and active modes of transport, people-centricity, smart spatial planning, social aspects, optimised accessibility and use of public space
Case Studies	Pilots: Hamburg, Amsterdam, Mechelen, Aalborg, Boras
<p>MoLo Hubs goes beyond existing mobility hub projects. It aims to reduce urban traffic by initiating and prototypically implementing new and convenient logistics service offers at urban mobility hubs. Five pilots will make an important contribution to reduce urban traffic, increase the attractiveness and functionality of urban mobility hubs and also give an insight into how user-centred logistics services can be designed.</p> <p>(https://www.interregnorthsea.eu/molo-hubs, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

REFOCUS

Project Full Title	Regional and Local Mobility Planning Focusing on Inclusive Decision Support Tools		
Website	https://www.interregeurope.eu/refocus https://www.imet.gr/index.php/en/projects-en-2/indicative-sector-b-projects-en/1160-refocus-project-en https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/refocus/		
Call	2021 – 2027 Interreg VI-C Interreg Europe		
Project Coordinator	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT) Dr. Maria Morfoulaki, marmor@certh.gr Maria Chatziathanasiou, mariacha@certh.gr		
Project Partners	11 partners Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT) City of Lviv City of Sint-Niklaas / Stad Sint-Niklaas City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad Institute for Transport and Logistics Foundation / Fondazione Istituto sui trasporti e la logistica (ITL) Łukasiewicz Research Network / Sieć Badawcza Łukasiewicz – Poznań Institute of Technology / Poznański Instytut Technologiczny Municipal Enterprise “Susisiekimo pasalaugos” (Vilnius) Municipality of Bologna / Comune di Bologna POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Poznan City Hall / Miasto Poznań Region of Central Macedonia		
Duration (months)	51		
Start date	01.04.2024	End date	30.06.2028
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	SUMPs, Decision Support Tool (DST) approaches, regional and local capacities, inclusive and data-driven decision-making, monitoring, data management, zero-carbon mobility, implementation, stakeholder engagement		
Case Studies	Local stakeholder consultations: Poznan, Sint-Niklaas, Stockholm, Emilia-Romagna, Vilnius, Lviv, Region of Central Macedonia		
REFOCUS brings together 10 partners from 6 EU countries and 1 EU candidate country to exchange their experiences in new (innovative) Decision Support Tool (DST) approaches that can be applied when decision-making for a zero-carbon sustainable mobility planning.			

The overall objective will be to increase regional and local capacities in inclusive decision-making for zero-carbon mobility to ensure the move towards the next generation of SUMP. Thereby, accelerating the implementation of the SUMP measures and innovations (following common technical specifications, when required, prioritising interventions, ensuring regional integration and continuity of measures and more efficient use of resources); ensuring effective monitoring measures in different local/ regional contents and different data management cultures and increasing competences in data-driven decision making for the constant planning and re-planning that SUMP require.

The proposed DST will ensure a coordinated and inclusive decision-making process that integrates local plans within regional strategies and will maximise chances of reaching the target of zero-carbon mobility for the whole region.

(<https://www.interregeurope.eu/refocus>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

EIT Urban Mobility

Website	https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/
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The European Institute for Innovation and Technology (EIT) was initiated in 2008 as an independent body. Since Horizon 2020 it is incorporated in the FPs, In Horizon Europe it is part of the third pillar “Innovative Europe” and links Pillar 2 and 3 (European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation et al., 2023).

The innovation network consists of several Knowledge and Innovation Communities, each dedicated to develop and market solutions addressing one specific global challenge (European Institute of Innovation & Technology, n.d.). One of these challenges regards sustainable urban mobility. The EIT Urban Mobility initiatives was launched in 2019, and its partnership encompasses more than 250 organisations. EIT Urban Mobility supports its community by connecting stakeholders, assisting with other funding opportunities, providing education programmes, accelerating deployment and commercialisation of innovations, and investing in startups (EIT Urban Mobility, n.d.).

POLIS was involved in two projects in EIT Urban Mobility’s Innovation programme. To get a more accurate impression of the initiative, more projects were added to the collection by filtering the collection of projects on the website for the programmes “Innovation” and also “Citizen Engagement”.

Innovation

Website	https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/our-activities/?_sft_project_category=innovation
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FlexCurb

Project Full Title	Implementation of dynamic curbside management solutions to improve sustainable city logistics operations		
Website	https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/flexcurb/ https://marketplace.eiturbanmobility.eu/products/flexcurb-planning-by-urban-radar https://marketplace.eiturbanmobility.eu/products/flexcurb-driver-by-urban-radar https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/flexcurb/		
Call	Innovation		
Project Coordinator	CTAG, Automotive Technology Centre of Galicia / Centre Technologique de l'Automobile de Galice David Fernandez, david.fernandez3160@ctag.com		
Project Partners	<p>8 partners</p> <p>CARNET Future Mobility Research Hub / Fundació Centre d'Innovació i Tecnologia de la UPC</p> <p>City of Leuven / Stad Leuven</p> <p>CTAG, Automotive Technology Centre of Galicia / Centre Technologique de l'Automobile de Galice</p> <p>Eurométropole de Strasbourg</p> <p>Funchal Town Hall / Câmara Municipal do Funchal</p> <p>Ghent University / Universiteit Gent – Department of Industrial Systems Engineering and Product Design</p> <p>POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale</p> <p>Toulouse Métropole</p> <p>Urban Radar</p>		
Duration (months)	12		
Start date	01.01.2022	End date	31.12.2022
Key Area(s)	<p>Focus: digitally managed curbside system</p> <p>KA2 People-centred urban spaces and planning</p> <p>KA3 Smart urban logistics, production and service sites</p> <p>2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <p>1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments</p> <p>3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>		
Keywords	Sustainable city logistics, curbside management, application programme interfaces (APIs), curb regulations, mobile app, city platform, digital tools, use of public space, safe streets, efficient last-mile logistics		
Case Studies	Pilot phase: Leuven, Funchal, Strasbourg, Toulouse		
FlexCurb is a set of application programme interfaces (APIs) that allow creation of a digital inventory of a city's curb regulations, so they can visualise and analyse the patterns of curb allocation and use, as well as to adapt and communicate curb regulations.			

The FlexCurb package is composed of two products targeting two types of end users. The first is a city platform for digitalisation and management of curb regulations. The second is a mobile app so commercial drivers can access up-to-date information about curb conditions and available spaces.

FlexCurb is a package of digital tools that help cities and companies use and manage curb space in a flexible way. It provides a solution to digitally control and balance the use of public space, enabling the transition towards flexible use and management of the curb. Therefore, the curb space can be shared and optimised to serve the needs of different users.

(<https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/flexcurb/>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

ISA-FIT

Project Full Title	Boost Safety and cut Costs with Intelligent Speed Assistance		
Website	https://isa-fit.eu/ https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/intelligent-speed-assistance-isa-retrofit-solutions-for-cities-and-regions/ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/isa-fit/		
Call	Innovation		
Project Coordinator	Technum – Tractebel Engineering nv Sven Vlassenroot, sven.vlassenroot@tractebel.engie.com		
Project Partners	8 partners CTAG, Automotive Technology Centre of Galicia / Centre Technologique de l'Automobile de Galice Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) – Eindhoven AI Systems Institute (EASI) Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) – Future Everyday Municipality of Helmond / Gemeente Helmond POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Technum – Tractebel Engineering nv TN-ITS V-tron B.V.		
Duration (months)	12		
Start date	01.05.2022	End date	31.12.2022
Key Area(s)	Focus: Intelligent Speed Assistance system KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 4. Integrate new technologies in transport		
Keywords	Safety and efficiency of vehicles, Intelligent Speed Assistance (ISA), user-friendly system, fine and accident prevention, reduction in emissions, ready-to-market product, maximum speed limit		
Case Studies	<p>Speeding is the major cause of traffic accidents. As of this year, new vehicles have to be equipped with Intelligent Speed Assistance (ISA) systems that make sure that a vehicle does not exceed the legal speed limit. From 2024, this regulation will extend to all new vehicles imported into the EU region.</p> <p>As vehicles have an average life cycle between 6 and 11.5 years, it will take time to see real impact. The ISA-FIT project aims to provide a retrofit ISA solution for urban environments to speed up implementation and will test a retrofit ISA system in the City of Helmond in the Netherlands in 15 ISA-vehicles. Data will be collected from scenarios testing the quality of the service, driver acceptance, and behavioural outcomes.</p> <p>A European strategy will also be developed to scale-up ISA implementation focusing on cooperation with speed limit databases, deployment standards, and procurement strategies. At the end of the project, a ready-to-market ISA retrofit product will be launched.</p> <p>(https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/intelligent-speed-assistance-isa-retrofit-solutions-for-cities-and-regions/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>		

LivingLAPT

Project Full Title	Future Apt Living Lab for Autonomous Public Transport		
Website	http://livinglapt.eu/ https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/livinglapt-2/		
Call	Innovation		
Project Coordinator	University College London (UCL) – Department of Civil, Environment & Geomatic Engineering Professor Bani Anvari, b.anvari@ucl.ac.uk		
Project Partners	17 partners Applied Autonomy AS / AB Aurriigo AuVe Tech OÜ B.V.V Trade Fairs Brno / BVV Veletrhy Brno BringAuto s.r.o. City of Hasselt / Stad Hasselt City of Prague / Hlavní Město Praha Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) Ghent University / Universiteit Gent – Department of Industrial Systems Engineering and Product Design Ghent University / Universiteit Gent – Department of Telecommunications and information processing Kongsberg Municipality / Kongsberg Kommune Milton Keys City Council Municipality of Helmond / Gemeente Helmond Municipality of Ricany / Městský úřad Říčany PowerHUB z.ú. The Future Mobility Network B.V. University College London (UCL) – Department of Civil, Environment & Geomatic Engineering		
Duration (months)	12		
Start date	01.01.2023	End date	31.12.2023
Key Area(s)	Focus: driverless shuttle and logistics service KA1 Sustainable urban mobility 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA3 Smart urban logistics, production and service sites 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery KA4 Urban governance for mobility transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Driverless shuttle and logistics services, safety framework, user acceptance, collaboration, eco-efficient and safe urban transport, remote operators		
Case Studies	Milton Keys		

Cities face numerous mobility challenges: reducing emissions, improving the safety and mobility of cyclists and pedestrians, and increasing quality of life for citizens. Driverless shuttles or pods can be a game changer for cities as they address many of these challenges. However, current solutions lack a transferrable regulatory and safety framework among European cities. Low public trust and acceptance in combination with high investments in the new technology (such as insurance and a safety driver) are not sustainable for cities and are a massive barrier.

LivingLAPT will deliver sustainable driverless shuttle and logistics services among various European cities by phasing out the need for safety drivers in shuttles and moving towards remote operators who oversee numerous services simultaneously. This will be achieved through a robust transnational safety framework as well as promoting user acceptance and trust in close collaboration with citizens, cities, operators, academia, industry, and policy makers.

(<https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/livinglapt-2/>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

AI4LIFE

Project Full Title			
Website	https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/ai4life/		
Call	Innovation		
Project Coordinator	Kentyou Levent Gürgen, levent@kentyou.com		
Project Partners	4 partners City of Jena ISBAK – Istanbul IT and Smart City Technologies Inc. Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality Kentyou		
Duration (months)	12		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2024
Key Area(s)	Focus: integrated AI-based smart intersection management system KA1 Sustainable urban mobility 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies		
Keywords	AI-based smart intersection management system, improvement of traffic flow and safety, internet of things (IoT), visualisation and decision-making support tool, commercialisation strategy, user experience, sustainable mobility, data-driven decision making		
Case Studies	Istanbul, Jena		
<p>Intersections play a very important environmental, economic and social role in urban environments but are also key bottlenecks and prone to fatal accidents. Thus, the project AI4LIFE aims to build an integrated AI-based smart intersection management system that will reduce congestion, (thus reducing greenhouse gas emissions and time wasted in traffic), reduce accidents, and increase the quality of life of citizens.</p> <p>The project will integrate solutions from two complementary enterprises: ISBAK and Kentyou. ISBAK, the municipal company of Istanbul, will bring the internet of things (IoT) infrastructure and an innovative adaptive signalised intersection management system to AI4LIFE. And Kentyou, an innovative award-winning startup, will bring its interoperable AI-driven data platform and a tool for visualisation and decision-making support.</p> <p>The integrated solution will be validated in two complementary pilot cities: Istanbul, Turkey and Jena, Germany. The project will also build a commercialisation strategy to scale the solution in Europe and beyond.</p> <p>(https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/ai4life/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

EVOSS

Project Full Title			
Website	https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/evoss/		
Call	Innovation		
Project Coordinator	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) Josep Maria Salanova Grau, jose@certh.gr		
Project Partners	6 partners BaTTeRi CARNET Future Mobility Research Hub / Fundació Centre d'Innovació I Tecnologia de la UPC Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) CityZone Major Development Agency Thessaloniki (MDAT S.A.) OTO Parking S.A.		
Duration (months)	12		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2024
Key Area(s)	Focus: Robotic charging device KA1 Sustainable urban mobility 4. Integrate new technologies in transport		
Keywords	Innovative robotic charging device, flexible electric vehicle charging, reduction of infrastructure costs, charging infrastructure, use of space		
Case Studies	Real-life testing: Tel Aviv, Thessaloniki		
<p>The EVOSS project introduces an innovative robotic charging device equipped with a high-capacity battery and one rapid charging plug. The robotic device can provide flexible electric vehicle charging inside parking areas, by moving to the precise location of the parked electric vehicle. In this way, the possibility to significantly reduce infrastructure costs is being provided. Moreover, challenges related to the availability, efficiency, accessibility of charging infrastructure and use of space in urban environments are being addressed. The robotic device has several unique features, it stores electricity on board, so it reduces the stress on the electric grid during peak hours (the robotic device can be charged at night); it improves utilisation of the current infrastructure to reduce CAPEX needed from fleet operators and real estate owners and it brings rapid charging to places that usually install slow charging, enabling EV users to get a full charge in short-term.</p> <p>The robotic device, ideated by the startup, Batteri, will be further improved within the framework of the EVOSS project. EVOSS will also provide the chance for extensive, real-life testing in two different contexts and cities; Tel Aviv, Israel and Thessaloniki, Greece. The testing phase will include both technical evaluation and stakeholders' feedback.</p> <p>(https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/evoss/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

GreenMob

Project Full Title	Multimodal journey planner for sustainable travel		
Website	https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/greenmob/ https://carnetbarcelona.com/project/greenmob/		
Call	Innovation		
Project Coordinator	CARNET Future Mobility Research Hub / Fundació Centre d'Innovació I Tecnologia de la UPC Paloma Nieri, paloma.nieri@carnetbarcelona.com		
Project Partners	8 partners CARNET Future Mobility Research Hub / Fundació Centre d'Innovació I Tecnologia de la UPC Cesena City Council City of Debrecen / Debrecen Megyei Jogú Város Önkormányzata DKV Debreceni Közlekedési Részvénytársaság Instant System Start Romagna S.p.A. Viladecans City Council WeCity		
Duration (months)	12		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2024
Key Area(s)	Focus: Multimodal journey planner KA1 Sustainable urban mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 4. Support sustainable lifestyles		
Keywords	Promotion of sustainable transport options, journey planner, CO2 monitoring tool, awareness, accessibility, integration of public and commercial mobility services		
Case Studies	Tests: Cesena, Viladecans, Debrecen		
<p>The GreenMob project aims to address urban mobility challenges by promoting sustainable transport options and reducing carbon dioxide (CO2) emissions produced by motorised trips. GreenMob proposes a journey planner that integrates various modes of transport providing comprehensive information on routes, schedules, fares, and updates in real-time, as well as the innovative integration of a CO2 monitoring tool that automatically recognises the mode of transport used and calculates emissions, allowing consumers to make informed decisions. By offering a user-friendly interface that calculates and shows CO2 emissions associated with city trips, the project intends to increase awareness and support ecologically responsible transportation options for city travel. Tests will be conducted in the cities of Cesena, Italy; Viladecans, Spain; and Debrecen, Hungary to determine the feasibility and effectiveness of the solution.</p> <p>(https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/greenmob/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

IMPULSE

Project Full Title	Integrated e-bus power management for optimised transport operations		
Website	https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/impulse/		
Call	Innovation		
Project Coordinator	CARNET Future Mobility Research Hub / Fundació Centre d'Innovació I Tecnologia de la UPC Matteo Stoico, matteo.stoico@carnetbarcelona.com		
Project Partners	4 partners CARNET Future Mobility Research Hub / Fundació Centre d'Innovació I Tecnologia de la UPC City of Kadikoy / Kadıköy Companhia Carris de Ferro de Lisboa EM SA realCity ITS Kft.		
Duration (months)	12		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2024
Key Area(s)	Focus: Software for real-time data on battery power for buses KA1 Sustainable urban mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban governance for mobility transition		
Keywords	e-buses, charging, e-bus fleet management, real-time data		
Case Studies	Pilot cases: Lisbon, Kadıköy		
<p>Public road transportation is transitioning to electric vehicles, marking a significant step towards a sustainable future. However, for public transport operators ensuring stable and reliable service using e-buses is still a challenge. The limited life of batteries, long charging times, non-standardised charging infrastructures which can lead to hardware incompatibilities, and a poor coverage of charging stations make it complex to manage charging operations.</p> <p>To address these issues, IMPULSE aims to optimise the management of e-bus fleets through a software platform capable of processing real-time data on batteries' status, vehicles and charging stations used, planned routes and characteristics of the transport network. This will allow public transport operators to optimise the day-to-day charging and usage of e-bus fleets, considering factors such as the bus service plan for the next day, energy prices and renewable energy production. The platform implementations will reduce transport service interruptions due to insufficient battery life, decrease operational costs for public transport operators, and thus foster the electrification of the bus fleets.</p> <p>To assess its effectiveness, two pilot cases with different characteristics of size and type of transport service offered will be carried out in the cities of Lisbon, Portugal and Kadıköy, Turkey throughout 2024.</p> <p>(https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/impulse/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

UMF

Project Full Title	Public transit analytics for a new mobility flows platform		
Website	https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/umf/		
Call	Innovation		
Project Coordinator	THEOREMUS Ltd Hristo Popov, hpopov@theoremus.com		
Project Partners	4 partners DKV Debreceni Közlekedési Részvénytársaság Municipality of Ajka Sofia Urban Mobility Centre EAD / Tsentar za Gradska Mobilnost EAD (SUMC) THEOREMUS Ltd		
Duration (months)	12		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2024
Key Area(s)	Focus: Big data analytics solution for visual insight into travel patterns KA1 Sustainable urban mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban governance for mobility transition		
Keywords	Urban Mobility Flows (UMF) platform, journey patterns, service optimisation, sustainability, market share of public transport, active travel habits, modal share, big data analytics solution		
Case Studies			
<p>The Urban Mobility Flows (UMF) platform is designed to unlock an important capability for transport agencies, city councils and transport operators. It delivers visual insights into journey patterns across multiple public and private modes of urban transport on a single dashboard. The aim of this analysis is to reveal discrepancies between infrastructure, service design, business models and actual travel habits, and to help determine goals for service optimisation. By improving transport offerings in ways that drive adoption of new habits that are aligned with sustainability goals, cities will be able to further extend the relative market share of public transport, reduce private car journeys and improve active travel habits for its citizens.</p> <p>(https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/umf/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

Citizen Engagement

Website	https://engage.eiturbanmobility.eu/?locale=ca https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/our-activities/?_sft_project_category=citizen-engagement
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CES4Kids

Project Full Title	Children and youth empowerment through DECIDIUM digital platform		
Website	https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/ces4kids/ https://engage.eiturbanmobility.eu/processes/CES4Kids-english		
Call	Citizen Engagement		
Project Coordinator	Barcelona City Council / Ajuntament di Barcelona Angel Lopez Rodriguez, angel.lopez@bcnregional.com Barcelona Regional, Agència Metropolitana de Desenvolupament Urbanístic i d'Infraestructures, S.A. Xavier Guarderas Torres, xavier.guarderas@bcnregional.com		
Project Partners	13 partners Barcelona Municipality / Ajuntament de Barcelona Barcelona Regional, Agència Metropolitana de Desenvolupament Urbanístic i d'Infraestructures, S.A. CARNET Future Mobility Research Hub / Fundació Centre d'Innovació I Tecnologia de la UPC edenway European Passengers' Federation IVZW (EPF) IASA Institute for Advanced Studies and Awareness Major Development Agency Thessaloniki (MDAT S.A.) Municipality of Cascais Municipality of Fundão / Município do Fundao PowerHUB z.ú. Técnico Lisboa – Instituto Superior Técnico – Universidade de Lisboa Universidade de Lisboa – Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento do Território Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Mobilise		
Duration (months)	6		
Start date	13.05.2021	End date	
Key Area(s)	Focus: Guidelines and tools for engagement KA1 Sustainable urban mobility KA2 People-centred urban spaces and planning KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	children and youth empowerment, co-creation of mobility planning, mobility habits and needs, educational content, sustainable mobility, awareness-raising, citizen engagement digital platform, social acceptance, schools, clean safe accessible and connected mobility		
Case Studies	Pilot projects (at least two schools in each country): Portugal, Greece, Czech Republic, Spain		
Children and youth empowerment through the DecidiUm digital platform (CES4Kids) aims to provide a direct participation experience for children and youth in the co-creation of mobility planning. Likewise, it			

will allow cities, academia, and industry actors to gain valuable data and knowledge about their mobility habits to design more suitable solutions for them.

Through the Citizen Engagement digital platform, the project will include the creation of classroom-ready educational content, hands-on learning activities, and awareness-raising events, as well as the elaboration, debate, and prioritization of proposals for improving public space and mobility services. Workshops will also act as testbeds for innovative mobility solutions aimed at enhancing daily travel to schools and hastening social acceptance of the change.

(<https://engage.eiturbanmobility.eu/processes/CES4Kids-english>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

DVECE

Project Full Title	Dynamic visualizations to enhance citizens engagement		
Website	https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/dynamic-visualizations-to-enhance-citizens-engagement/		
Call	Citizen Engagement		
Project Coordinator	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT) Josep Maria Salanova Grau, jose@certh.gr Maria Konstantinidou, mariakon@certh.gr		
Project Partners	3 partners Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT) Forum Virium Helsinki OY Stichting Breda University of Applied Sciences		
Duration (months)	12		
Start date	01.01.2022	End date	
Key Area(s)	Focus: Digital Twins for effective and inclusive citizens engagement KA1 Sustainable urban mobility KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	digital twins, inclusive citizen engagement practices, 3D visualisation models, new mobility scenarios, hybrid participation		
Case Studies	Tests in living labs: Kalasatama and Jätkäsaari, Breda, Thessaloniki		
<p>The objectives of DVECE are to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use innovative Digital Twin models to engage citizens who are typically under-represented in participatory processes, so they can envisage new mobility scenarios in an immersive environment • experiment with dynamic visualisation tools to display and validate citizens’ input within the Digital Twins, contributing to a more effective and accurate methodology that incorporates citizen feedback into policy plans <p>Two distinct approaches toward the use of DigiTwins in citizen engagement will be tested within three living lab environments. A first approach uses advanced DigiTwin models and interfaces to help citizens visualize the impact of their feedback on mobility plans. This approach will be tested in the Smart City Living Lab in the Kalasatama and Jätkäsaari Smart Mobility Lab (Finland). A second approach, to be trialled in the Urban Living Lab Breda in the Netherlands, and the Thessaloniki Smart Mobility Living Lab in Greece, focuses on collecting offline input and incorporating this qualitative data into DigiTwin models to test a hybrid digital-offline participation process that accommodates people with lower digital literacy levels.</p> <p>(https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/dynamic-visualizations-to-enhance-citizens-engagement/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

Inclusify

Project Full Title	Women empowerment for inclusive mobility		
Website	https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/women-empowerment-for-inclusive-mobility/ https://ambvosaltres.wesolve.app/account/login https://engage.eiturbanmobility.eu/processes/inclusify?locale=en https://walk21.com/work/projects/inclusify/		
Call	Citizen Engagement		
Project Coordinator	Area Metropolitana de Barcelona (AMB) Mariona Conill de Azpiazu, mconill@amb.cat		
Project Partners	5 partners AMB Informació i Serveis SA Area Metropolitana de Barcelona (AMB) Institut d'Estudis Regionals i Metropolitans de Barcelona iermB / Metropolis Institute Walk21 WeSolve / Social Tech Projects ApS		
Duration (months)	12		
Start date	01.01.2022	End date	
Key Area(s)	Focus: digital tool to improve women's safety in sustainable mobility KA1 Sustainable urban mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space KA4 Urban governance for mobility transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	public transport, accessibility and safety for women, active mobility, co-creation, digital solution, mobility app		
Case Studies	Barcelona		
<p>Although women use public transport more widely and frequently than men, accessibility and safety concerns may deter them from using it. These issues may also influence the uptake of cycling, walking or other forms of active mobility for women.</p> <p>The Inclusify project will develop, test and implement a methodology and digital solution so women in the metropolitan area can share their mobility experiences and co-create with the Public Administration AMB to find solutions regarding specific mobility aspects around safety, accessibility and inclusivity.</p> <p>The digital solution will be embedded within the AMB mobility app to promote its use. The methodology and tool will be scalable and replicable across Europe and internationally.</p> <p>(https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/women-empowerment-for-inclusive-mobility/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

UMCASE

Project Full Title	Citizens' Inclusive and Accessible Urban Mobility Solutions		
Website	https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/citizens-inclusive-and-accessible-urban-mobility-solutions/ https://engage.eiturbanmobility.eu/processes/umcase		
Call	Citizen Engagement		
Project Coordinator	Technum – Tractebel Engineering nv Sven Vlassenroot, sven.vlassenroot@tractebel.engie.com		
Project Partners	6 partners Achmea Holding N.V. Capgemini SE Centro de Estudios Ambientales (CEA) Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) Fundación TECNALIA Research & Innovation Technum – Tractebel Engineering nv		
Duration (months)	12		
Start date	01.01.2022	End date	
Key Area(s)	Focus: interactive method to identify PT user needs KA1 Sustainable urban mobility KA4 Urban governance for mobility transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	participatory approach, online portal, vulnerable users of public transport, older citizens, inclusive new digital mobility services, parking space		
Case Studies	Pilots: Vitoria, Eindhoven		
<p>The purpose of UMCASE is to provide cities with an interactive method to identify user needs and develop tailored public transport systems and digital solutions for the most vulnerable users.</p> <p>The Citizens' Inclusive and Accessible Urban Mobility Solutions project, or UMCASE, is creating an online portal to engage the most vulnerable users of public transport, understand their specific challenges, and learn how to tailor interventions to meet their needs.</p> <p>Using a participatory approach, UMCASE is being piloted in Vitoria, Spain, and Eindhoven, the Netherlands, and connects local residents, transport providers, business actors and policy-makers to develop and evaluate potential solutions. The City of Vitoria seeks to bridge the gap between older citizens and use of digital mobility services, while the City of Eindhoven wants citizens to collaborate and design solutions to reduce private parking spaces as part of the redevelopment of a local district. The UMCASE methodology and implementation guide will be available for cities, citizens, service providers and other stakeholders to support the design of more inclusive mobility services.</p> <p>(https://engage.eiturbanmobility.eu/processes/umcase, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

WSCE

Project Full Title	WeSolve the Citizen Engagement		
Website	https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/wsce/ https://marketplace.eiturbanmobility.eu/products/wesolve-bridging-the-gap-engaging-people		
Call	Citizen Engagement		
Project Coordinator	Trivector Traffic AB Caroline Ljungberg Toulson, Caroline.ljungberg-toulson@trivector.se Caroline Mattsson, Caroline.mattsson@trivector.se		
Project Partners	5 partners City of Jelgava Logrono City Hall / Ayuntamiento de Logroño Trivector Traffic AB VEFRESH WeSolve / Social Tech Projects ApS		
Duration (months)	12		
Start date	01.01.2022	End date	
Key Area(s)	Focus: Platform for dialogue between city and citizens KA1 Sustainable urban mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 2. Focus on people-centred public space 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA4 Urban governance for mobility transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	digital engagement platform, co-creation of solutions, environmentally sustainable mobility, active participation of citizens, gamification, long-term engagement, collaborative decision-making, acceptance, urban design changes		
Case Studies	Logroño, Jelgava		
<p>WeSolve is a digital engagement platform that connects residents in Logroño, Spain, and Jelgava, Latvia, with their local governments to co-create at least five solutions that address a specific mobility challenge, as well as promote environmentally sustainable mobility. A key goal of the project is to stimulate more dialogue between governments and citizens and encourage active participation of citizens to create solutions to issues that directly affect them. Cities will use the WeSolve platform to test gamification and reward features that nurture long-term engagement with participants. Care is taken to include a diverse range of communities and users. The platform's functionality and approach to co-creating solutions will undergo an iterative process and be documented in a final implementation guide.</p> <p>(https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/wsce/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

Bicycle Heroes

Project Full Title	Bicycle Heroes: European Youth Voices for Active Mobility		
Website	https://bycs.org/our-work/bicycle-heroes/ https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/bicycle-heroes-european-youth-voices-for-active-mobility/ https://engage.eiturbanmobility.eu/processes/bicycleheroes		
Call	Citizen Engagement		
Project Coordinator	BYCS Alex Baum, alex@bycs.org Daniel Eppstein, daniel@bycs.org		
Project Partners	6 partners APSI Associação para a Promoção da Segurança Infantil BYCS cooperativa bicicultura.org Dublin City Council Roma Servizi per la Mobilità s.r.l. / Roma Mobilità Trinity College Dublin (TCD)		
Duration (months)	12		
Start date	02.01.2022	End date	
Key Area(s)	Focus: scalable programme for ideation, design and implementation of active mobility KA1 Sustainable urban mobility 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Children, need for and benefits of cycling, needs of vulnerable groups, safety, active mobility solutions, public design competition, implementation		
Case Studies	Dublin, Lisbon, Rome		
<p>Bicycle Heroes involves children in the ideation, design, and implementation of active mobility solutions to increase uptake of active mobility and make cities safer, healthier, and more sustainable for all. Children have a unique perspective on how to solve challenges within our cities. Their needs, when met, make cities safe for other vulnerable groups such as the elderly or disabled and they are effective spokespeople for change given their influence over their families.</p> <p>Despite their unique perspective, children are often overlooked in urban mobility and design planning. To address this oversight, the Bicycle Heroes project works with children in Dublin, Ireland; Lisbon, Portugal, and Rome, Italy, to identify the barriers to, and benefits of, cycling as a form of active mobility. After developing solutions as part of a public design competition, the children will then implement a selected idea in partnership with key stakeholders.</p>			

This participatory model brings together children and cities to promote cycling and other modes of active mobility, and will be piloted as part of the project and available to replicate in other cities.

(<https://engage.eiturbanmobility.eu/processes/bicycleheroes>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

Driving Urban Transitions (DUT) Partnership

Website	https://dutpartnership.eu/ https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069506 https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/driving-urban-transitions
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The **DUT Partnership** is an intergovernmental R&I programme, which is co-funded by 28 countries and the European Commission under Horizon Europe. Launched in 2022, it is based on JPI Urban Europe’s efforts and is structured in three thematic pathways. The 15-minute City (15mC) Pathway is dedicated to urban mobility transitions (DUT Partnership, 2024). For the orientation of its 15mC Pathway, the DUT Partnership also developed the four Key Areas of Action, which were integrated into this project compilation.

The initiative’s first call funded 23 15mC projects, which started in the end of 2023 or the beginning of 2024. All of these projects are included in the following section.

DUT Call 2022

Website	https://dutpartnership.eu/funding-opportunities/dut_call_2022/funded-projects/15mc-projects/ https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf
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emc2

Project Full Title	The Evolutive Meshed Compact City: A Pragmatic Transition Pathway to the 15-minute City for European Metropolitan Peripheries		
Website	https://emc2-dut.org/ Poster		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.3 (Re)imagine Urban Public Spaces and Streets for Vibrant, Sustainable Neighbourhoods		
Project Coordinator	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) – Study of Structures and Processes of Adaptation and Change in Space (UMR ESPACE) Giovanni Fusco, giovanni.fusco@univ-cotedazur.fr		
Project Partners	<p>8 partners</p> <p>Agence d’urbanisme Azurenne</p> <p>Agence de dveloppement et d’urbanisme de Lille Mtropole</p> <p>Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) – Study of Structures and Processes of Adaptation and Change in Space (UMR ESPACE)</p> <p>Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB – Spatial Morphology Group (SMoG)</p> <p>City of Gothenburg / Goteborgs Kommun / Gteborgs Stad</p> <p>City of Viareggio / Comune di Viareggio</p> <p>Technische Universitt Wien (TU Wien) – Research Unit of Urban Design</p> <p>Universit di Pisa – Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell’Energia, dei Sistemi, del Territorio e delle Costruzioni (DESTEC)</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.10.2023	End date	30.09.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 		
Keywords	Multi-Modal Mobility Networks, Synergies and Conflicts, Transition, Spatial Organisation, peripheral locations, living spaces, geospatial and network modelling, observational usage analyses, comparative morpho-functional analyses, ecological and transportation networks		
Case Studies	Six european cities		
<p>The project tackles key structural difficulties for 15mC transition in suburbs by proposing a new urban model satisfying basic morphological and functional requirements. The Evolutive Meshed Compact City (emc2) model foresees selective densification along existing main roads and prioritization of pedestrian usage to transform them into interconnected, vibrant and service-rich high-streets, connected to wider</p>			

mobility options. The project will specify the emc2 model, assess its potential in suburban areas of six European cities through multi-scale geospatial modelling and morphogenetic analysis, address the contribution of ecological and transportation networks, and analyse small test-areas with high emc2 potential to produce transferable models and guidelines.

(<https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf>, retrieved 17 October 2024)

ERGODIC

Project Full Title	Combined Passenger and Goods Transportation in Suburb Traffic		
Website	https://research.chalmers.se/en/project/11274 POSTER		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.2 Foster Sustainable Options for Personal Mobility and Logistics in Urban Outskirts (and Beyond)		
Project Coordinator	Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB – Architecture and Civil Engineering Jiaming Wu, jiaming.wu@chalmers.se		
Project Partners	10 partners British and Irish Trading Alliance (BITA) Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB – Architecture and Civil Engineering Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB – Electrical Engineering City of Linz Einride AB ESG Consultants Ltd Getplus SRL Johannes Kepler Universität Linz – Department Intelligent Transport Systems The University of Liverpool – Centre for Supply Chain Research (CSCR) WSP Sverige AB		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.10.2023	End date	30.09.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Integrated Passenger and Goods Transport, flexible public transport, Sustainability, Accessibility, Multimodal Transport, Suburban, modular vehicles, business model, demand matching, safety, active micromobility, user acceptance, social impacts		
Case Studies	Pilot project in Linz		
Conventional public transport does not currently meet the demand for commuting and goods delivery in suburban areas. A new system of flexible public transport using modular vehicles could reduce the use of			

private cars in suburban areas. Modular vehicles could flexibly change capacity by adjusting the number of interconnected and separate cabins carrying either passengers, goods or micro-vehicles. The ERGODIC project will explore business model development and demand matching of passengers and goods, as well as routing and safety challenges, to develop a multimodal transport service. As a result, the project will deliver a proof of concept with field demonstration.

(<https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf>, retrieved 16 October 2024)

SUMODO

Project Full Title	Sustainable Urban MObility Development in Outskirts		
Website	http://www.sumodo-project.com/ POSTER https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QNkkzV3tbDE		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.2 Foster Sustainable Options for Personal Mobility and Logistics in Urban Outskirts (and Beyond)		
Project Coordinator	SAITEC SA Luis Rodriguez Repiso, luisrodriguez@saitec.es		
Project Partners	7 partners Budapest University of Technology and Economics / Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem (BME) City of Szeged / Szeged Megyei Jogú Város Önkormányzatának City of Veszprém / Veszprém Megyei Jogú Város Önkormányzatának Municipality of Katowice / Katowice – Miasto na prawach powiatu SAITEC SA Silesian University of Technology / Politechnika Śląska (SUT) – Department of Transport Systems, Traffic Engineering and Logistics University of Economics in Katowice / Uniwersytet Ekonomiczny W Katowicach (UEK) – Centre for Economics of Climate Change		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.10.2023	End date	30.09.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Urban Planning Facilitation, Transport Preferences, Accessibility, Activity Based Multimodal Travel Planner, outskirts, citizen’s acceptance, simulation platform, physical and policy based interventions, 15min composite index, multi-objective optimisation algorithms		
Case Studies	Katowice, Veszprém, Szeged		
<p>Urban planners can encourage active transport modes by designing new green areas, pedestrian and cycling infrastructure. Yet, reducing the surface once reserved for private vehicles requires careful consideration of transport preferences to secure citizen’s acceptance of change in their neighbourhood. The SUMODO project will provide a simulation platform with tools to explore aspects such as the frequency and transport mode preferences of citizens and how to compute the accessibility to services.</p>			

Using SUMODO's simulations, urban planners will be able to optimise physical (e.g. pedestrianisation) and policy based (e.g. slow zones) interventions to foster the deployment of 15-min cities with minimum economic and social cost.

(<https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf>,
retrieved 17 October 2024)

Car-goNE-City

Project Full Title	Cargo Bikes and Neighbourhood Engagement in the 15-Minute City: Resident-Based Participatory Approaches to Implementing Effective Shared Bike Mobility for Increasing Accessibility and Reducing Car Use		
Website	https://research.chalmers.se/en/project/11371 Poster		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.2 Foster Sustainable Options for Personal Mobility and Logistics in Urban Outskirts (and Beyond)		
Project Coordinator	Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB – Space, Earth and Environment Devon McAslan, devon.mcaslan@chalmers.se		
Project Partners	16 partners BKK Centre for Budapest Transport / Budapesti Közlekedési Központ Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság Budapest University of Technology and Economics / Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem (BME) Chalmers University of Technology / Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola AB – Space, Earth and Environment City of Constance / Stadt Konstanz City of Gothenburg / Goteborgs Kommun / Göteborgs Stad Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V. Kraftstaden Fastigheter AB Lastenrad-Initiative Für Die Region Karlsruhe E. V. Metrunner AB Möndalsbostäder AB Oslo Metropolitan University (OSLOMET) Storbyuniversitetet Takomat GmbH Tink GmbH Trollhättan Municipality / Trollhättans kommun Västtrafik AB Whee! AS		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.11.2023	End date	31.10.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		

Keywords	Cargo Bike Mobility, Shared Mobility, Active Transport, time-based accessibility, reduce car use, participatory design, digital participation and gamification, residential neighbourhoods, new mobility solutions, decision-making tools, user perspectives, business models
Case Studies	Pilot projects in suburban contexts
<p>Car-goNE-City investigates the extent to which shared cargo bike mobility can increase accessibility by active transport to essential urban functions in 15mC, lower transportation costs, and reduce private car use. Cities involved include Gothenburg, Mölndal, Trollhättan (Sweden), Oslo (Norway), Karlsruhe and Konstanz (Germany), and Budapest (Hungary). This project will generate transition pathways for small, medium and large European cities for active and car-reduced urban mobility and provide policy recommendations on the effective uses of shared cargo bike mobility to achieve sustainable mobility objectives.</p> <p>(https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf, retrieved 16 October 2024)</p>	

CITWIN

Project Full Title	A Generic Digital Twin Framework to Foster Sustainable Mobility in the 15mC		
Website	https://www.citwin.uliege.be/ Poster		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.2 Foster Sustainable Options for Personal Mobility and Logistics in Urban Outskirts (and Beyond)		
Project Coordinator	Université de Liège (ULIEGE) Mario Cools, mario.cools@uliege.be Richa Maheshwari, richa.maheshwari@uliege.be		
Project Partners	8 partners Aarhus University / Aarhus Universitet – Distributed Computational Intelligence City of Aarhus / Aarhus Kommune Eskilstuna Municipality / Eskilstuna kommun European Cyclists Federation ASBL KTH Royal Institute of Technology / Kungliga Tekniska högskolan triply GmbH Université de Liège (ULIEGE) University of Salzburg / Paris-Lodron-Universität Salzburg (PLUS)		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.11.2023	End date	31.10.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Digital Twin, Digitalisation, Mobility Systems, Human-Centric, active transport infrastructure, stakeholder engagement		
Case Studies	Trban living labs: Aarhus, Eskilstuna		
<p>To implement the 15-minute city concept in urban areas, we need to rethink and reorganise our mobility systems. Digitalisation is a key factor in this process, with digital twins being one of the promising technologies to be utilised. In the CITWIN project, we aim to explore this potential by developing a generic digital twin framework that allows us to model potential changes to active transport infrastructure in urban areas, explore and simulate the impact of such changes, and evaluate their contribution towards the realisation of a 15-minute city. To make the framework applicable within the 15-minute city context, we will explicitly model and evaluate human-centric dimensions inside the digital twin. Two urban living labs will be established in the cities of Aarhus and Eskilstuna and serve as a testbed for the developments</p>			

within the project. By engaging with stakeholders and incorporating their input, the CITWIN project aims to create a digital twin framework that is both effective and responsive to the needs of those it serves.

(<https://www.citwin.uliege.be/index.html>, retrieved 16 October 2024)

JiM

Project Full Title	Social and Environmental Justice in 15 Minutes – Toolkit Development for Transition to Urban Sustainable Neighbourhoods		
Website	https://mau.se/en/research/projects/social-and-environmental-justice-in-15-minutes---jim/ Poster		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.1 Strengthen the Mix of Urban Functions and Services		
Project Coordinator	Malmö University / Malmö Universitet – Department of Urban Studies Christina Lindkvist, christina.lindkvist@mau.se Helena Bohman, helena.bohman@mau.se		
Project Partners	16 partners Agence D’urbanisme de la Region Grenobloise Bodrum Municipality City of Gothenburg / Goteborgs Kommun / Göteborgs Stad City of Koszalin / Gmina Miasto Koszalin City of Malmö / Malmö Stad Cracow University of Technology / Politechnika Krakowska – Chair of Transportation Systems Gazi Üniversitesi Lund University – Planetary Health research group Malmö University / Malmö Universitet – Department of Urban Studies Molde University College / Høgskolen i Molde – Transport Research Group (TRG) Region Skåne Sciences Po Grenoble / Institut d’études Politiques de Grenoble Swedish National Road and Transport Research Institute / Statens väg- och transportforskningsinstitut (VTI) Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) – Department of Geography University of Gdansk / Uniwersytet Gdański Västtrafik AB		
Duration (months)	38		
Start date	01.11.2023	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Environmental and social justice, sustainable transport accessibility, informed planning and decision-making policy instruments, placement of services, health outcome of accessibility to green spaces		

Case Studies	
<p>To foster a sustainable urban mobility planning, social and environmental justice must be incorporated together with the understanding on how institutions decide where to localize services and amenities. The JiM project analyses the perceived and actual movements of inhabitants, environmental data and decision-making processes where to localize amenities and services for a fair 15mC planning with experiences from six countries. The project aims to develop tools, guidelines and policy instruments to incorporate different understandings and outcomes of social and environmental justice in planning for the 15mC in various planning contexts.</p> <p>(https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf, retrieved 16 October 2024)</p>	

ENACT 15mC

Project Full Title	Envisioning Neighbourhoods and Co-Creating Thriving Communities in the 15mC		
Website	https://enact15mc.org/ https://prosjektbanken.forskingsradet.no/en/project/FORISS/349676 Poster		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.3 (Re)imagine Urban Public Spaces and Streets for Vibrant, Sustainable Neighbourhoods		
Project Coordinator	Norwegian University of Science and Technology / Norges teknisk-naturvitenskapelige universitet (NTNU) – Department of Architecture and Planning Yu Wang, wang.yu@ntnu.no		
Project Partners	<p>21 partners</p> <p>City Hall of Valencia / Ayuntamiento de València City of Gdansk / Gdańsk / Gmina Miasta Gdanska Confederación Empresarial de la Comunitat Valenciana (CEV) Escuelas de Artesanos Frost Eiendom AS Gdansk University of Technology / Politechnika Gdańska – Faculty of Architecture Kommunal Landspensjonskasse Gjensidig Forsikringselskap (KLP) Make Real Ltd. Nadbałtyckie Centrum Kultury Norwegian University of Science and Technology / Norges teknisk-naturvitenskapelige universitet (NTNU)) – Department of Architecture and Planning OBOS Prosjekt AS Oxford Brookes University (OBU) – School of the Built Environment Oxford City Council Oxford University – Global Centre on Healthcare and Urbanisation (GCHU) Oxfordshire County Council Stocznia Cesarska Development Sp. z o.o. Town and Country Planning Association Trondheim Municipality / Trondheim Kommune Universitat Politècnica de Valencia (UPV) – Architecture, Heritage and Management for Sustainable Development Research Centre Universitat Politècnica de Valencia (UPV) – Research Institute for Materials Technology VU.CITY Modelling Ltd.</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	2023	End date	2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport		

	<p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders
Keywords	Augmented and Virtual Reality, Visualisation, 15mC Concept, People Centred, Planning Instruments, co-creation, walkable and attractive urban areas
Case Studies	Urban living labs: Trondheim, Gdansk, Valencia, Oxford
<p>How can existing urban areas be transformed to make them more walkable and attractive for people to spend time in? The ENACT 15mC consortium will test different approaches to operationalise the 15mC concept. New Urban Living Labs will be set up in Trondheim (NO), Gdansk (PO), Valencia (SP) and Oxford (UK) to explore and create change together with interested groups such as property owners. Augmented and Virtual Reality technologies (AR/VR) will facilitate iterative design processes, addressing critiques and making visualization tools accessible to the public. One of the project outcomes is transferring knowledge and results to other contexts.</p> <p>https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf, retrieved 17 October 2024)</p>	

15minESTATES

Project Full Title	Co-creating Spatial Strategies for Just and Sustainable Mobility in Large-Scale Housing Estates		
Website	http://www.ioer.de/en/projects/15minestates https://www.rtu.lv/en/university/rtu-projects/open?project_number=4850 Poster		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.3 (Re)imagine Urban Public Spaces and Streets for Vibrant, Sustainable Neighbourhoods		
Project Coordinator	Riga Technical University / Rīgas Tehniskā universitāte – Institute of Architecture and Design Sandra Treija, sandra.treija@rtu.lv		
Project Partners	<p>18 partners</p> <p>Budapest Főváros Xx. Kerület Pesterzsébet Önkormányzat Budapest University of Technology and Economics / Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem (BME) City of Halle / Stadt Halle (Saale) – GB Stadtentwicklung und Umwelt Cohousing Budapest Association Csillagászati és Földtudományi Kutatóközpont Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) Kulturbühne Neustadt e.V. Leibniz-institut für Ökologische Raumentwicklung e.V. Municipality of Delft / Gemeente Delft Riga City Council / Rīgas pilsētas pašvaldība Riga Technical University / Rīgas Tehniskā universitāte – Institute of Architecture and Design Sofia Development Association Sofia Municipality Szamitastechnikai ES Automatizalasi Kutatointezet Union of Bulgarian Spatial Planners University of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy / Universitet po Arhitektura Stroitelstvo i Geodezija (UACG) Ziepniekkalna Apkaimes Biedrība</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 		

Keywords	Spatial Strategies and Interventions, Sustainable Mobility, Large Housing Estates (LHEs), co-creation, public spaces, proximity-based planning, mobility needs and behaviour, neighbourhood-specific and general design principles
Case Studies	Mladost 4 LHE Sofia, Pesterzsébeti LHE Budapest, Halle, Delft-West LHE Delft, Ziepniekkalns LHE Riga
<p>Across Europe, residential areas such as Large-Scale Housing Estates (LHEs) need to be transformed for facilitating sustainable mobility. The 15minESTATES project adapts and reframes the 15-minute City concept for the specific context of LHEs. The project team will build a comprehensive knowledge base of the public spaces, existing amenities and transport infrastructure of five LHEs in Bulgaria, Hungary, Germany, the Netherlands and Latvia. Exploring and comparing the mobility needs perceptions and behaviours of different user groups the project will identify specific sustainable mobility challenges in these residential areas. The results of the case studies will be used to propose design principles and approaches for transforming public spaces in LHEs thus enabling transferability of results to other countries.</p> <p>https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf, retrieved 17 October 2024)</p>	

AccessCity4All

Project Full Title	Adapting the 15-Minute City Concept to Support Active Mobility in Neighbourhoods with Different Levels of Accessibility		
Website	https://www.oeaw.ac.at/en/isr/sustainable-urban-region/accesscity4all-adapting-the-15-minute-city-concept-to-support-active-mobility-in-neighbourhoods-with-different-levels-of-accessibility Poster		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.2 Foster Sustainable Options for Personal Mobility and Logistics in Urban Outskirts (and Beyond)		
Project Coordinator	Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften Alois Humer, alois.humer@oeaw.ac.at		
Project Partners	11 partners Austrian Academy of Sciences / Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften (ÖAW) – Urban and Regional Research Çankaya Belediyes City of Munster / Stadt Munster City of Vienna / Stadt Wien Gazi Üniversitesi ILS Research gGmbH Kecioren Municipality Lisbon City Council / Câmara Municipal de Lisboa Provincie Groningen Universidade de Lisboa – Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento do Território University of Groningen / Rijksuniversiteit Groningen – Urban and Regional Studies Institute		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Active Mobility, perceived and actualised accessibility, 15-minute neighbourhoods, walk-along-interviews, GIS surveys, people-centered and place-specific concept of the15mC, innovative urban planning procedures and instruments, various urban settings, individual accessibility needs		
Case Studies	5 Urban Living Labs		
Residents in urban areas may interpret their accessibility to basic services in their neighbourhoods differently. The 15-minute-city concept, which calculates the potential access to specific places within 15 minutes, can be complemented by results from the AccessCity4All project. The project pays special			

attention to people with different needs and abilities. This project assesses and acknowledges residents' perceived and actualised accessibility in ten neighbourhoods located in Portugal, the Netherlands, Germany, Austria, and Türkiye. Using various methods such as walk-along interviews or PPGIS surveys, the project will provide innovative urban planning procedures for an adaptive 15-minute city in both central neighbourhoods and urban outskirts.

(<https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf>, retrieved 16 October 2024)

COMMON_ACCESS

Project Full Title	COMMONing ACCESSibility in Urban Outskirts and Beyond		
Website	https://www.commonaccessproject.com/ https://www.mos.ed.tum.de/sv/forschung-und-beratung/projekte/dut-projects/common-access/		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.2 Foster Sustainable Options for Personal Mobility and Logistics in Urban Outskirts (and Beyond)		
Project Coordinator	The University of Westminster LBG Enrica Papa, E.Papa@westminster.ac.uk		
Project Partners	17 partners City of Amsterdam / Gemeente Amsterdam CoMoUK – Collaborative Mobility UK Derek Halden Consultancy Ltd. Esri UK & Ireland Ghent University / Universiteit Gent Goudappel Coffeng BV Living Streets (The Pedestrians' Association) London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE) – LSE Cities MVV Munich Public Transport Association / Münchner Verkehrs- und Tarifverbund GmbH Oxfordshire County Council Politecnico di Milano (POLIMI) – Department of Architecture and Urban Studies Provincia di Bergamo Provincia di Pavia Provincie Oost-Vlaanderen Technical University of Munich / Technische Universität München (TUM) – Chair of Urban Structure and Transport Planning The University of Westminster LBG Universiteit van Amsterdam (UvA) – Centre for Urban Studies (CUS)		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 3. Provide sustainable solutions for longer trips KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		

Keywords	Peri-urban, Suburban, Commoning Accessibility (CA), Local Planning, community shared practices, physical and digital accessibility services, social dimension, role of communities, community shared vehicles
Case Studies	Testbeds in outskirts neighbourhoods of Munich, Oxfordshire County Council, Province of Bergamo, Province of Pavia, Province of East Flanders, Amsterdam
<p>The implementation of the 15minC principles faces two main barriers: transforming city outskirts and addressing social aspects related to accessibility and mobility. To overcome these barriers, the COMMON_ACCESS project aims to study and operationalize the concept of ‘Commoning accessibility’ in the urban periphery, recognizing accessibility as a common good. The project will work closely with local planning authorities, businesses, and communities in six metropolitan areas to investigate ‘commoning accessibility experiments’. These experiments could include community shared (e-)bikes, (e-) cargo bikes, (e-) cars and (e-)vans, alone or in combination with community managed digital platforms, and social, cultural and care amenities and services. The project aims to generate insights into the key transport, land use and governance barriers and enablers for upscaling successful ‘commoning accessibility’ experiments.</p> <p>(https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf, retrieved 16 October 2024)</p>	

CONFLICTEDSTREETS

Project Full Title	Navigating Conflicts Over Streets and Urban Space in the Transition to the 15mC		
Website	Poster		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.3 (Re)imagine Urban Public Spaces and Streets for Vibrant, Sustainable Neighbourhoods		
Project Coordinator	Lund University Fredrik Pettersson-Löfstedt, fredrik.pettersson-lofstedt@tft.lth.se		
Project Partners	<p>13 partners</p> <p>Agentia Metropolitana pentru Dezvoltare Durabilă Braşov Asociația Bodrum Municipality City of Bielefeld / Stadt Bielefeld City of Polkowice / Gmina Polkowice Cracow University of Technology / Politechnika Krakowska Gazi Üniversitesi Lund University Molde University College / Høgskolen i Molde Municipality of Ljutomer / Občina Ljutomer Municipality Velenje / Mestna občina Velenje Swedish National Road and Transport Research Institute / Statens väg- och transportforskningsinstitut (VTI) Universiteit van Amsterdam (UvA) Vision5 OG</p>		
Duration (months)	28 (36)		
Start date	01.10.2023 (vinnova.se) 01.01.2024 (nwo.nl)	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 		
Keywords	Streetscape transformation, Conflicted Streets, Transition, Mobility, Urban transformation, public participation, redesign pilots, use of space, planning practices		
Case Studies	Bielefeld, Brasov, Bodrum		
<p>A key issue in the planning of the 15mC is the use of space. As different stakeholder groups may represent different interests and perspectives, there is a need to address potential conflicts. The CONFLICTEDSTREETS project aims to build knowledge about planning practices and processes while acknowledging the political and contested nature of urban transformations. It focuses on conflicts between “spaces of flows” (enabling local and regional mobility, but also including spaces currently used for parked vehicles) and “spaces of place” (emphasising urban qualities that make people want to live in</p>			

such places) in plans for the 15mC. As a result, the project will have an impact on the understanding of the causes of conflict and its management.

(<https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf>,
retrieved 17 October 2024)

DREAMS

Project Full Title	Driving Equitable and Accessible 15 Minute Neighbourhood Transformations
Website	https://www.dreams15mc.eu/ Poster
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.2 Foster Sustainable Options for Personal Mobility and Logistics in Urban Outskirts (and Beyond)
Project Coordinator	University of Twente / Universiteit Twente (UT) – Transport Engineering and Management (TEM) research group Karst Geurs, k.t.geurs@utwente.nl
Project Partners	28 partners BKK Centre for Budapest Transport / Budapesti Közlekedési Központ Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság Budapest Főváros XVII. kerület Rákosmente Önkormányzata Budapest University of Technology and Economics / Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem (BME) City of Utrecht / Gemeente Utrecht Conseil département de l'Essonne EIT Urban Mobility Innovation Hub Fietzersbond KTI Hungarian Institute for Transport Sciences Non-Profit Ltd / Magyar Közlekedéstudományi és Logisztikai Intézet Nonprofit Korlátolt Felelősségű Társaság l'Institut d'aménagement et d'urbanisme de la région d'Île-de-France / L'Institut Paris Region MO.Point Mobilitätsservices GmbH Mobyome KG Morgenjungs GmbH Mpact vzw / Mpact asbl MVV Munich Public Transport Association / Münchner Verkehrs- und Tarifverbund GmbH Optimobil Brussel N.V. Région Île-de-France Service public régional de Bruxelles – Brussels Mobility / Bruxelles Mobilité (Administration de l'Équipement et des Déplacements) Sixt Share & Mobility Platform stadtland DI Sibylla Zech GmbH Technical University of Munich / Technische Universität München (TUM) – Chair of Urban Structure and Transport Planning Technische Universität Wien (TU Wien) – Research Unit of Transportation System Planning TIER Mobility Netherlands B.V. Université Gustave Eiffel – LVMT Laboratoire Ville Mobilité Transport University of Applied Sciences Utrecht / Hogeschool Utrecht (HU) University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna / Universität für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU) – Institute for Transport Studies University of Twente / Universiteit Twente (UT) – Transport Engineering and Management (TEM) research group Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Business technology and Operations Wirtschaftsagentur Wien.Ein Fonds Der Stadt Wien

Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	User-centric Shared Mobility Services, Governance Frameworks, Business Models, Accessibility, Sustainability, Mobility Hubs, Activity Hubs, On-demand Services, inclusive 15mC neighbourhoods, urban outskirts, decision support tool, co-creation		
Case Studies	Living labs: Budapest, Brussels, Munich, Paris, Utrecht, Vienna		
<p>In the DREAMS project we are exploring, through co-created and user-centric mobility services, mobility and flexible activity hubs, how we can actively contribute to creating accessible, sustainable, and inclusive 15mC neighbourhoods in the urban outskirts of European cities and regions. We will conduct extensive research in six living labs across Europe, specifically in Budapest, Brussels, Munich, Paris, Utrecht, and Vienna.</p> <p>Our primary objective is to provide a comprehensive and comparative analysis of 15mC lifestyles in various low- to mid-density suburban and urban outskirts within the five regions. Additionally, we are committed to developing and testing new business models and governance frameworks for innovative shared mobility services and flexible activity hubs in low/medium-density areas.</p> <p>Furthermore, we will develop and apply a decision support tool to facilitate the co-creation and impact assessment of mobility services, mobility hubs, and flexible activity hubs within the DREAMS living labs. We will rigorously examine the mobility, accessibility, and broader societal impacts of these services to ensure their effectiveness.</p> <p>Ultimately, our goal is to generate policy recommendations that actively pave the way for sustainable and inclusive urban mobility in 15mC neighbourhoods in urban outskirts. We aim to achieve this by leveraging co-created and user-centric mobility services, mobility and flexible activity hubs, and implementing new governance-business models.</p> <p>(https://www.dreams15mc.eu/, retrieved 16 October 2024)</p>			

ENHANCE

Project Full Title	Enhancing Sustainable Travel in Small Cities and Outer Metropolitan Areas		
Website	https://research.vu.nl/en/projects/enhancing-sustainable-travel-in-small-cities-and-outer-metropolit ; Poster		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.1 Strengthen the Mix of Urban Functions and Services		
Project Coordinator	VU University Amsterdam / Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam – Department of Spatial Economics Eric Koomen, e.koomen@vu.nl Tanhua Jin, t.jin@vu.nl		
Project Partners	10 partners BaTTeRi Birkbeck, University of London City of Alkmaar / Gemeente Alkmaar Municipality of Oeiras / Município de Oeiras Prospective Labs Ltd. Transport for London Universidade Nova de Lisboa University College London (UCL) Vereniging Deltametropool VU University Amsterdam / Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam – Department of Spatial Economics		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 1. Support striving neighbourhood economies KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Sustainable Travel, 15mC in outer metropolitan areas and small cities, scenario modelling, behaviour adaptation, city development, multi-modal accessibility, accessibility indicators, transport inequality, land-use planning		
Case Studies	Alkmaar, Bath, Oeiras		
The sustainability challenges in the outskirts of metropolitan areas and towns often surpass those in inner-city districts, characterised by greater car dependence, struggling local retail centres, disintegrated housing, and weaker active travel infrastructure. The ENHANCE project aims to identify these barriers and			

improve local planning decision-making using 15mC principles. The extent to which daily travel needs can be met through local trips will be investigated by analysing actual travel behaviours. It will also identify barriers and measure progress towards achieving the 15-minute city goals. Through modelling future scenarios, the project could enhance accessibility via transport infrastructure, behaviour adaptation, or city redevelopment.

(<https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf>, retrieved 16 October 2024)

Fair Mobility

Project Full Title	Fair Mobility and Access to Public Life		
Website	https://fair-mobility.eu/		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.2 Foster Sustainable Options for Personal Mobility and Logistics in Urban Outskirts (and Beyond)		
Project Coordinator	Landshut University of Applied Sciences / Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften Landshut (HAW Landshut) – Technology Center of Energy (TZE) Prof. Dr. Raimund Brotsack, raimund.brotsack@th-deg.de Robert Hahn, robert.hahn@haw-landshut.de Juan David Kintero Thokora, Juan-David.Kintero-Thokora@haw-landshut.de		
Project Partners	8 partners Creil Municipality / Ville de Creil Ebensee Municipality / Marktgemeinde Ebensee am Traunsee Frauenforum Salzkammergut Genre et Ville Landshut University of Applied Sciences / Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften Landshut (HAW Landshut) – Technology Center of Energy (TZE) Université Gustave Eiffel – LVMT Laboratoire Ville Mobilité Transport URBASOFIA SRL Wonderland, Platform for European Architecture		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society		
Keywords	Fair Mobility, Accessibility, Gender Minorities, Women, Physical Spaces, gender inclusive approach, safety and pleasure, equity, public living areas, co-construction of urban and mobility planning, suburban and rural municipalities		
Case Studies	Creil, Ebensee		
<p>We need to rethink the physical spaces in our cities to facilitate the mobility of people such as the elderly, people with disabilities, and other groups. The Fair Mobility project aims to transform mobility and accessibility frameworks in a sustainable and inclusive way, focusing on women and gender minorities. The project will develop and test inclusive mobility tools to improve the safety, accessibility and equity of mobility in Creil, France, and Ebensee, Austria. One of the outcomes will be enabling women and gender minorities to lead mobility pattern changes through participatory design. The project results will be disseminated to stakeholders and thematic events will be organised to raise awareness of the issue.</p>			

<https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf>,
retrieved 16 October 2024)

FORTHCOMING

Project Full Title	FOsteRing The City Of proximity through Maas INteGration		
Website	https://sites.google.com/view/forthcomingsite/home-page POSTER		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.2 Foster Sustainable Options for Personal Mobility and Logistics in Urban Outskirts (and Beyond)		
Project Coordinator	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) – Centro de Investigación del Transporte (TRANSyT) Prof. Andres Monzon, andres.monzon@upm.es		
Project Partners	19 partners ALSA Grupo SLU AppCorner Kft. Câmara Municipal de Vila Franca de Xira Centro de Nanotecnologia e Materiais Técnicos, Funcionais e Inteligentes (CeNTI) Città Metropolitana Di Torino City Council of Madrid / Ayuntamiento de Madrid Comune di Settimo Torinese DKV Debreceni Közlekedési Részvénytársaság Empresa Municipal de la Innovación y Transporte Urbano de Las Rozas de Madrid SA Eurocities ASBL HafenCity Universität Hamburg (HCU) – CityScienceLab Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi IST-ID Associação do Instituto Superior Técnico para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento Me Real Estate – Mota-Engil Real Estate Portugal S.A Parabol Yazılım Elektronik Danışmanlık Eğitim San ve Tic Ltd Sti Politecnico di Torino (POLITO) – Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning (DIST) Számítástechnikai ES Automatizálási Kutatóintézet Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) – Centro de Investigación del Transporte (TRANSyT)		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	MaaS, LaaS, Data-driven, User-Centric 15mC Models, Urban Outskirts, KPIs		

Case Studies	Urban living labs: Madrid, Turin, Lisbon, Istanbul, Hamburg, Debrecen
<p>Funded by the Driving Urban Transitions (DUT) Partnership, the FORTHCOMING project (FOsteRing THE City Of proximity through Maas INteGration) will develop and test data-driven and user-centric 15-minute city models for suburban contexts, learning from central city best practices.</p> <p>Outskirts' specific issues in relation to the 4 pillars (density, proximity, diversity, and digitalisation) of the 15-minute city model mean that the uptake of the 15-minute city in low and mid-density zones requires adjustments and potentially different implementation procedures.</p> <p>Objective of the project is fostering the successful transfer of central city strategies to the suburbs, boosting the transition to climate-neutral, liveable, and inclusive cities.</p> <p>The project key features are adoption of ICT MaaS & LaaS tools that provide solutions to site-specific problems, supporting the development of the 15-minute city model in peripheries.</p> <p>Main outputs of the project are A 'Portfolio of Successful 15minC Strategies in Urban Areas', as well as a '15minC Implementation Guidebook for Suburban Areas'.</p> <p>https://sites.google.com/view/forthcomingsite/about, retrieved 16 October 2024)</p>	

FRESH

Project Full Title	The Freight-Shopping Nexus in Urban Outskirts and Beyond		
Website	https://fresh.raumplanung.tu-dortmund.de/ https://www.ivt.ethz.ch/en/tmp/projects/fresh.html POSTER		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.2 Foster Sustainable Options for Personal Mobility and Logistics in Urban Outskirts (and Beyond)		
Project Coordinator	Technical University of Dortmund / Technische Universität Dortmund (TUDO) – Department of Mobility and Transport Prof. Dr. Eva Heinen, eva.heinen@ivt.baug.ethz.ch		
Project Partners	8 partners City of Dortmund / Stadt Dortmund Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich (ETH Zurich) – Institute for Transport Planning and Systems Métropole du Grand Paris Norwegian University of Science and Technology / Norges teknisk-naturvitenskapelige universitet (NTNU) POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Technical University of Dortmund / Technische Universität Dortmund (TUDO) – Department of Mobility and Transport Trondheim Municipality / Trondheim Kommune Université Gustave Eiffel – LVMT Laboratoire Ville Mobilité Transport		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 1. Support striving neighbourhood economies 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Sustainable Urban Logistics, Shopping Travel, Urban Outskirts, Consumer Behaviour, Car Dependency, urban planning, travel demand, integrated personal and freight transport planning, shopping patterns, urban and suburban settings		
Case Studies			
Around a sixth of all private trips are made for shopping, and despite the availability of closer facilities, these trips are often made by car and to distant locations. In addition, online shopping has led to a sharp increase in home deliveries. As shopping opportunities within 15 minutes may be limited in suburban			

areas, there is a need to better understand urban logistics and individual shopping behaviour. The FRESH project aims to investigate the contribution of new and innovative solutions and other opportunities on integrated personal and freight transport planning in urban and suburban settings to develop sustainable urban logistics concepts in relation to shopping in a 15-min city, with a focus on reducing motorized transport.

(<https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf>, retrieved 16 October 2024)

InclusiveCity

Project Full Title	Critical Placemaking for Inclusive Cities		
Website	https://placemaking-europe.eu/project/inclusive-city/ Poster		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.3 (Re)imagine Urban Public Spaces and Streets for Vibrant, Sustainable Neighbourhoods		
Project Coordinator	Superwien urbanism ZT GmbH Roland Krebs, krebs@superwien.com Theresa Koenig, koenig@superwien.com		
Project Partners	<p>18 partners</p> <p>A.S.D. Bastogi Budapest University of Technology and Economics / Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem (BME) City of Oslo / Oslo Kommune – Bykuben Eutropian GmbH Kortárs Építészeti Központ Alapítvány (KÉK) Nabolagshager AS Natural State Nonna Roma ODV Norwegian University of Science and Technology / Norges teknisk-naturvitenskapelige universitet (NTNU) Nuove Ri-Generazioni Lazio Rév8 Jozsefvaros Rehabilitation and Urban Development Co SINTEF AS / SINTEF Technology and Society Stichting Breda University of Applied Sciences – Academy for Built Environment & Logistics Stichting Breda University of Applied Sciences – Academy for Hotel & Facility Stichting Breda University of Applied Sciences – Academy for Leisure & Events Stichting Placemaking Europe Superwien urbanism ZT GmbH University of Applied Arts Vienna / Universität für Angewandte Kunst Wien</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	<p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		
Keywords	Placemaking, Marginalized Citizens, Sustainability, multi-generational and gender-inclusive use of public spaces, natural assets, SDGs, stakeholder involvement, toolbox		

Case Studies	Urban living labs: Vienna, Rome, Budapest, Rotterdam, Oslo
<p>Public spaces in cities can be redesigned with social, economic and environmental considerations in mind. In practice, these aspects relate to age, gender, providing access to natural areas and protecting vulnerable groups from issues such as gentrification. The InclusiveCity project will develop a set of tools, methods and strategies through five urban living labs in Budapest, Oslo Rome, Rotterdam and Vienna. These pilot projects in five cities will support better use of public spaces and involve local stakeholders, communities and specific target groups in their improvement, with the aim of addressing different Sustainable Development Goals.</p> <p>(https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf, retrieved 17 October 2024)</p>	

InPUT

Project Full Title	Engaging Places and Communities for Inclusive Peri-Urban Transitions		
Website	https://www.cecs.uminho.pt/en/projetos/input-engaging-places-and-communities-for-inclusive-peri-urban-transitions/ Poster		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.1 Strengthen the Mix of Urban Functions and Services		
Project Coordinator	Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) Rodrigo Cardoso, r.o.v.cardoso@tudelft.nl Birgit Hausleitner, b.hausleitner@tudelft.nl Caroline Newton, c.e.l.newton-1@tudelft.nl		
Project Partners	11 partners Braga City Council / Municipio de Braga Delft University of Technology / Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft) Hannah Arendt Institute Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management / Ministerie van Infrastructuur en Waterstaat Ministry of the Interior and Kingdom Relations / Ministerie van Binnenlandse Zaken en Koninkrijksrelaties Team Vlaams Bouwmeester Technische Universität Wien (TU Wien) – Research Unit of Sociology University of Antwerp – Centre for Urban History University of Minho / Universidade do Minho – Centro de Estudos de Comunicação e Sociedade University of Porto / Universidade do Porto – Faculdade de Letras Verein Niederösterreich-Wien, Gemeinsame Entwicklungsräume		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Engagement, Peri-Urban Transition, Communities, strategic transformations, spatial morphologies and networks, governance capacities, stakeholder collaboration, locally appropriate spatial visions, 15-minute city ideas		
Case Studies	peri-urban areas in Austria, Belgium, Netherlands, Portugal		
The success of the 15-minute city is closely tied to its implementation in the hyperconnected cities best suited to adopt it. However, achieving a sustainable urban transition requires addressing other forms of			

European urbanisation, particularly the extensive peri-urban areas where many people live and work. In these areas, spatial morphologies and networks are not always ready to receive 15-minute city models, and there may be misalignment between governments and communities regarding their principles. Nonetheless, interventions to improve quality of life, proximity, and accessibility are urgently needed.

InPUT advances these efforts by analysing different types of peri-urban areas and designing specific configurations for the 15 minutes that suit these diverse contexts. Thus, the project goes beyond considering only spatial aspects (TOD, functions, networks) by also examining social aspects, namely governance capacities, which influence investments and priorities, and inhabitants' aspirations, which determine which elements constitute 'their' 15-minute city and the attractiveness of transformations. Based on a selection of peri-urban areas in four countries, InPUT establishes, through collaboration with local stakeholders, a typological catalogue of functional arrangements, mobility networks, governance dynamics and community experiences. This knowledge is then used to co-conceive locally appropriate spatial visions and strategic transformations that enable 15-minute environments. A third work package evaluates the performance and potential of these emerging visions along the key routes of the 15-minute city. InPUT clarifies how the 15-minute city ideas can be extended and supported across Europe, promoting fairer and more cohesive territories.

(<https://www.cecs.uminho.pt/en/projetos/input-engaging-places-and-communities-for-inclusive-peri-urban-transitions/>, retrieved 16 October 2024)

LISTEN

Project Full Title	Collective Listening to Communities and Spaces as a Core Capability in Planning Towards 15-minute Suburban Cities		
Website	https://www.cipra.org/en/cipra/international/projects/current/listen?set_language=en Poster		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.3 (Re)imagine Urban Public Spaces and Streets for Vibrant, Sustainable Neighbourhoods		
Project Coordinator	Hasselt University – Researchgroup ArcK Oswald Devisch, oswald.devisch@uhasselt.be		
Project Partners	6 CIPRA International Lab GmbH City of Genk Hasselt University – Researchgroup ArcK Malmö University / Malmö Universitet – School of Arts and Communication NGBG Rosinak & Partner Ziviltechniker GmbH		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Sustainable Mobility, Listen, 15mC, participatory planning procedures, super-diverse suburbs, semi-public spaces		
Case Studies	3 listening experiments: 15-minute radio, 15-minute atlas, 15-minute walk Workshops in Belgium, Sweden, Austria		
<p>Listen addresses the challenge of polarised debates on concepts like the 15-minute City by advocating for slowing down participatory planning processes and fostering collective listening. In this context, listening implies a collective process involving groups such as local authorities, citizens, interest groups, designers and entrepreneurs in which to discover our interdependencies and imagine common projects. The project will develop frameworks, tools, protocols. In the process, it will explore collective listening forms (e.g. podcast/community radio, live projects community walks) and re-imagine semi-public spaces and participatory planning procedures to support collective listening.</p> <p>(https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf, retrieved 17 October 2024)</p>			

MBD15

Project Full Title	Mobility Benefit Districts: Travel and Liveability Impacts, Acceptability, and Governance of New Tools for Accelerating Transitions in the 15-minute City		
Website	Poster https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mP6mUolEJKc		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.3 (Re)imagine Urban Public Spaces and Streets for Vibrant, Sustainable Neighbourhoods		
Project Coordinator	KTH Royal Institute of Technology / Kungliga Tekniska högskolan Fredrik Johansson, frjo6@kth.se		
Project Partners	10 partners City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad Gävle Municipality / Gävle kommun Goethe University Frankfurt / Johann Wolfgang Goethe-Universität Frankfurt Am Main – Working Group Mobility Research KTH Royal Institute of Technology / Kungliga Tekniska högskolan PlanSinn Büro für Planung und Kommunikation GmbH Science City Darmstadt / Wissenschaftsstadt Darmstadt Sundbyberg Municipality / Sundbybergs kommun Technische Universität Wien (TU Wien) TUB Trafikutredningsbyrå AB UIV Urban Innovation Vienna GmbH		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Travel and Liveability impacts, Governance, Transition, Mobility Benefit Districts, Parking Charges, reuse of parking spaces, acceptability, alternatives to private cars		
Case Studies	Stockholm, Darmstadt-Lincoln, Vienna		
<p>Parking dominates the streets of our cities, reducing the space available for other services and uses that residents might want. The Mobility Benefit Districts (MBD) project can help turn residents’ aspirations into reality by investing parking revenue in local mobility services. The project aims to increase the acceptability of parking charges, while providing residents with alternatives to the private car, and ultimately reusing parking spaces. As a result, the project will provide new insights into the acceptability of MBD among different resident groups with an experimental living lab design in different contexts.</p> <p>(https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf, retrieved 17 October 2024)</p>			

MULTIGINATION

Project Full Title	Multiplicative Imagination of Citizens and Stakeholders towards the 15-minutes City		
Website	https://www.hes-so.ch/en/recherche-innovation/research-projects/detail-projet-recherche/multigation https://projects.tuni.fi/multigation/esittely/ Poster		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.3 (Re)imagine Urban Public Spaces and Streets for Vibrant, Sustainable Neighbourhoods		
Project Coordinator	Haute école spécialisée de Suisse occidentale (HES-SO) – Business, Management and Services faculty Valentino Piana, valentino.piana@hevs.ch		
Project Partners	18 partners Başakşehir Living Lab City of Winterthur / Stadt Winterthur Coventry University – Fab Lab Coventry Drees & Sommer Schweiz AG European Network of Living Labs IVZW (ENoLL) Haute école spécialisée de Suisse occidentale (HES-SO) – Business, Management and Services faculty Lehtovuori Oy Lentola Logistics Oy Municipality of Bergamo / Comune di Bergamo Municipality of Pamplona / Ayuntamiento de Pamplona Open Urbanism Foundation Pirkanmaan Jätehuolto Oy Republic and Canton of Geneva / République et Canton de Genève – Directorate for International Affairs Tampere University of Applied Sciences / Tampereen Ammattikorkeakoulu Oy (TAMK) Verkehrsbetriebe Zürich Visiosoft Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek (VITO NV) Zürcher Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften / Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW)		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	31.12.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 2. Focus on people-centred public space KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		

	<p>2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society</p> <p>3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>
Keywords	Collective Intelligence, Co-Design of Public Spaces, Urban Interventions, Scalable, stakeholder involvement, participatory funding platform, bottom-up process, open-access visualisation tool, marketplace
Case Studies	<p>Başakşehir, Winterthur</p> <p>Followers: Bergamo, Coventry, Pamplona, Geneva</p>
<p>The 15 minutes city needs a multiplication of small urban bottom-up interventions for additional functions and services to sustainably reduce the need of car. The MULTIGATION project provides tools and processes for redesigning urban areas and services while involving stakeholders such as experts, citizens, private companies, researchers, NGOs and city authorities by a Living lab approach. Using this participatory approach and the different tools for visualisation evaluation, financing and implementation provided by this project, cities can decide whether to implement innovative services and explore how to finance them.</p> <p>https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf, retrieved 17 October 2024)</p>	

SuCoLo

Project Full Title	Fostering Sustainable Consumer Behaviour with Inclusive Bicycle Logistics Infrastructure in Urban Outskirts		
Website	https://sucolo.eu/ Poster		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.2 Foster Sustainable Options for Personal Mobility and Logistics in Urban Outskirts (and Beyond)		
Project Coordinator	Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH Michael Thelen, michael.thelen@salzburgresearch.at		
Project Partners	13 partners City of Leipzig / Stadt Leipzig Fulmo Kurierunion GbR Gävle Municipality / Gävle kommun independent L. ONLUS Leipzig University / Universität Leipzig – Chair of Information Management Municipality of Merano / Comune di Merano / Stadtgemeinde Meran Radlogistik Verband Deutschland e.v. Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH Salzburger Verkehrsverbund GmbH Strutture Trasporto Alto Adige SpA / Südtiroler Transportstrukturen AG – Green Mobility Department Sustainability InnoCenter Unione Handels und Dienstleistungsverband Südtirol hds Viabirds Technologies GmbH		
Duration (months)	30		
Start date	01.01.2024	End date	30.06.2026
Key Area(s)	KA1 Smart Urban Mobility KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity 4. Support sustainable lifestyles KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics 3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments		
Keywords	Sustainable consumer behaviour, Inclusive bicycle delivery services, Micro mobility hubs, Living lab, urban outskirts, toolkit, bike sharing platform, cargo bikes, pick-up stations, nudging, inclusive and neighbourhood-centred delivery and collection, simulation model, walk- and bikeability, Sustainable Urban Bicycle Logistics Plans (SUBLP)		
Case Studies	Salzburg, Meran, Leipzig		

As an increasing number of people are shopping online, it is paramount to promote and encourage the use of sustainable goods delivery and local pick-up options on webshops. The SuCoLo project will explore the alignment of needs, opportunities and interactions of relevant (freight) bicycle delivery actors, citizens and digital service providers to develop behaviour change techniques to nudge online consumers to choose net-zero methods of delivery. Using living lab methods and establishing an engaged advisory board, the project will design and test these novel tools and build new local pick-up hubs in Salzburg, Meran and Leipzig. Expected outcomes include tools, such as a behaviour change guidebook, a new simulation model for location planning of bicycle micro hubs and cargo bike-sharing to promote inclusive and neighbourhood-centred delivery/collection in our cities.

(<https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf>, retrieved 16 October 2024)

SPECIFIC

Project Full Title	Specifying Practices Enabled by Cycling in Fifteen-minute Cities		
Website	https://www.15mcityspecific.org/		
Call	DUT Call 2022, 15mC pathway – 2.2 Foster Sustainable Options for Personal Mobility and Logistics in Urban Outskirts (and Beyond)		
Project Coordinator	Oxford University – Transport Studies Unit Tim Schwanen, tim.schwanen@ouce.ox.ac.uk		
Project Partners	<p>15 partners</p> <p>Adam Mickiewicz University Poznań / Uniwersytet im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu (UAM)</p> <p>ATA Associazione traffico e ambiente Svizzera Italiana</p> <p>Bristol City Council</p> <p>City of Bellinzona</p> <p>City of Graz / Stadt Graz</p> <p>City of Maastricht / Gemeente Maastricht</p> <p>Fyrtel Sp. z.o.o</p> <p>Maastricht University – Maastricht Sustainability Institute (MSI)</p> <p>Outspoken Logistics Ltd</p> <p>Oxford University – Transport Studies Unit</p> <p>Poznan City Hall / Miasto Poznań</p> <p>Pro Velo Ticino</p> <p>University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland / Scuola Universitaria Professionale della Svizzera Italiana</p> <p>University of Graz – RCE Graz-Styria</p> <p>Zuid-Limburg Bereikbaar</p>		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	02.01.2024	End date	01.01.2027
Key Area(s)	<p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space 4. Integrate new technologies in transport <p>KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Support sustainable lifestyles <p>KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders 		
Keywords	Low-density Settings, Small and Medium-Sized Cities, 15mC, cycling, commuters, bike couriers, marginalised individuals and communities, equitable and socially just mobility, meta-lab		
Case Studies	Transition experiments: Bellinzona, Bristol, Graz, Maastricht, Poznan		

In the context of promoting sustainable urban mobility, public health, and social inclusion, the 15-minute city (15MC) concept has great potential. However, implementing it in low-density areas can be challenging and may increase social inequalities. To address this issue, a proposed project aims to co-create a tool for tailoring the 15MC concept to low-density settings in small and medium-sized European cities. Transition experiments focused on cycling in five cities – Bellinzona, Bristol, Graz, Maastricht, and Poznan - will be conducted. The project also involves creating a transnational meta-lab to generalize lessons learned from individual cities. The SPECIFIC tool will help practitioners reimagine and repurpose low-density areas into cycling-friendly zones that enable people from diverse backgrounds to fulfil their daily needs.

(<https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf>, retrieved 16 October 2024)

Others

The following five projects are not part of the funding programmes incorporated in this compilation.

SUMI

Project Full Title	Technical support related to sustainable urban mobility indicators (SUMI)		
Website	https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/sumi/ https://www.rupprecht-consult.eu/project/sumi https://www.mobility-academy.eu/enrol/index.php?id=109 https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/sustainable-urban-mobility-indicators		
Call	Service contract for the European Commission's Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport		
Project Coordinator	Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH Siegfried Rupprecht, s.rupprecht@rupprecht-consult.eu		
Project Partners	7 partners Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EKETA) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT) Eurocities ASBL International Association of Public Transport / Union Internationale des Transports Publics (UITP) POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH Transport & Mobility Leuven (TML) NV TRT Trasporti e Territorio s.r.l.		
Duration (months)	33		
Start date	12.2017	End date	08.2020
Key Area(s)	Focus: assess success of mobility measures KA1 Sustainable urban mobility KA4 Urban governance for mobility transition		
Keywords	WBCSD, sustainable urban mobility indicators (SUMI), new mobility practices and policies, benchmarking tool, recommendations		
Case Studies			
<p>The goal? To enable policymakers to assess the success of current mobility measures, as well as to ensure that forthcoming solutions are tailored to respond to the issues most relevant to the cities in question.</p> <p>The sustainable urban mobility indicators (SUMI) provided technical support related to sustainable urban mobility indicators (MOVE/B4/2017-358). The project helped urban areas using the "SMP2.0 Sustainable Mobility Indicators" developed by the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD). The indicators were created for cities to perform a standardised evaluation of their mobility system and measure improvements that result from the implementation of new mobility practices or policies. A common, practical and reliable set of indicators is crucial to assess the sustainability of mobility in European urban areas, providing the scope to track progress towards policy goals and identify the potential for improvement. In addition, SUMI also aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support urban areas to apply the WBCSD mobility indicators • Create a benchmarking add-on to the WBCSD calculator tool • Build experience for the improvement of the WBCSD mobility indicators 			

The main result of the project was recommendations about how the WBCSD indicator set can be improved and about fostering long-term commitment among as many European cities as possible.

(<https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/sumi/>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

APOLLO-EU

Project Full Title	Alliance Platform for Liveable and Low-Carbon Communities in Europe		
Website	https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/apollo-eu-alliance-clean-bus-deployment-initiative/ https://cleanbusplatform.eu/ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/clean-bus-europe-platform		
Call	service contract by the European Commission (support to the Clean Bus Deployment Initiative CBDI)		
Project Coordinator	International Association of Public Transport / Union Internationale des Transports Publics (UITP) Aida Abdulah, aida.abdulah@uitp.org		
Project Partners	5 partners FIT Consulting s.r.l. International Association of Public Transport / Union Internationale des Transports Publics (UITP) POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH Sphera Solutions, Inc.		
Duration (months)			
Start date	2019	End date	2023
Key Area(s)	Focus: clean bus technologies KA1 Sustainable urban mobility 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA4 Urban governance for mobility transition 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Clean Bus Deployment Initiative, Alliance platform, exchange of knowledge and expertise, public transport system, clean vehicles, capacity building, technical assistance		
Case Studies	15 Host Cities, 54 Target Cities, 12 Follower Cities		
<p>APOLLO-EU (Alliance Platform for Liveable and Low-Carbon Communities in Europe) aims to support the Clean Bus Deployment Initiative (CBDI) uptake across the European Member States.</p> <p>The main project objective is the creation of a platform for cities, public transport operators, local authorities, infrastructure providers, OEMs, financing entities as well civil society representatives to boost clean bus deployment across Europe as an alternative to cars. This platform brings together European transport authorities and operators with varying degrees of clean bus deployment know-how to boost and support the exchange of knowledge and expertise. APOLLO-EU project covers all kinds of clean vehicles, battery-electric, fuel cell, CNG, battery trolleys, and plug-in hybrids.</p> <p>APOLLO-EU supports capacity building and ensures that the technical, procedural, and operational know-how on clean bus deployment is effectively and widely transferred beyond the circle of cities that can be considered front-runners in Europe. This is done through the Clean Bus Europe Platform, which offers European cities the opportunity to learn from cities that have already set up clean bus schemes through</p>			

tools such as study visits and webinars. Furthermore, it will provide them with tailored technical assistance in the transition towards clean buses. Lessons learned from previous and current European key research projects like ZeEUS, ASSURED, JIVE, EBSF_2, and ELIPTIC will be systematically assessed and shared to show the wide array of existing solutions related to clean bus technologies.

(<https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/apollo-eu-alliance-clean-bus-deployment-initiative/>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

UVAR Box

Project Full Title	User-friendly Information Tool on Urban and Regional Access Regulations Schemes		
Website	https://uvarbox.eu/ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/uvar-box/		
Call	Preparatory Action — User-friendly Information Tool on Urban and Regional Vehicle Access Regulation Schemes		
Project Coordinator	ARMIS Group Pedro Barradas, Pedro.barradas@armis.pt		
Project Partners	11 partners Albrecht Consult (AC) ARMIS Group AustriaTech – Gesellschaft des Bundes für technologiepoltische Maßnahmen GmbH Harrod Booth Consulting MAP Traffic Management (MAPtm) B.V. MemEx s.r.l. POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale PRISMA solutions EDV-Dienstleistungen GmbH Sadler Consultants Europe GmbH TRT Trasporti e Territorio s.r.l. U-TREX B.V.		
Duration (months)	24		
Start date	01.09.2020	End date	01.09.2022
Key Area(s)	Focus: Digitising UVAR Data for Europe KA1 Sustainable urban mobility KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning 3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders		
Keywords	Urban Vehicle Access Regulations (UVAR), harmonised UVAR information, data collection and digitisation, machine-readable DATEX-II standard, open-source platform, effective use of UVARs, real-time traffic information services, low emission zones, congestion charging, pedestrian zones, parking regulations, stakeholder engagement		
Case Studies	Digitisation of UVARs in Austria, Belgium, The Netherlands, Luxembourg, Italy, Germany		
The EU-funded UVAR Box project aims to foster the digitisation process of UVAR data across several European countries.			

A high number of citizens in urban municipalities across Europe are negatively influenced by air and noise pollution and congestion. Thus, Urban Vehicle Access Regulations (UVARs) are increasingly chosen by cities across Europe to reduce these burdens on citizens.

The project, which started in August 2020 and runs for 24 months, aims to harmonise UVAR information, supporting integrated information on UVAR schemes apps, fleet management tools and navigation devices. This will support both road users to plan journeys across the EU, and local authorities and the Member States to set up digital issuing procedures and comply with European regulations on travel information (ITS Directive and Single Digital Gateway).

The project will establish a structure for UVAR data schemes and develop adequate machine-readable formats in DATEX II. It will support UVAR data collection, maintenance, and accessibility to navigation systems and mobile applications. This will enable the public authorities responsible for UVARs to provide digital, accurate, up-to-date, continuous and interoperable EU-wide real-time traffic information services. It will in turn facilitate access to harmonised information for all road users to plan their trips, through different end-user service providers.

(<https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/uvar-box/>, retrieved 23 September 2024)

Ride2Autonomy

Project Full Title			
Website	https://summalab.nl/r2a/ https://ride2autonomy.eu/ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/ride2autonomy/		
Call	2020 Work Programme for Pilot Projects and Preparatory Actions		
Project Coordinator	Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH Wolfgang Backhaus, w.backhaus@rupprecht-consult.eu		
Project Partners	<p>18 partners</p> <p>Anaptyxiaki Etaireia Dimou Trikkaion Anaptyxiaki Anonymi Etaireia OTA / E-Trikala AE City of Aveiro / Câmara Municipal de Aveiro European Passengers' Federation IVZW (EPF) European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation – Intelligent Transport Systems & Services Europe (ERTICO – ITS Europe) Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) / Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institutouto Systimaton Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston International Association of Public Transport / Union Internationale des Transports Publics (UITP) IT, Instituto de Telecomunicações LuxMobility S.A.R.L. MAP Traffic Management (MAPtm) B.V. Modern Mobility OÜ POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH S.L.A. SA / Sales-Lentz Autocars SA The Future Mobility Network B.V. The Highlands and Islands Transport Partnership (HITRANS) Ubiwhere Università degli studi di Modena e Reggio Emilia (Unimore) VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Lt / Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY</p>		
Duration (months)	20		
Start date	04.2021	End date	30.11.2022
Key Area(s)	<p>Focus: scalable model toolbox to integrate autonomous shuttle solutions</p> <p>KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport</p> <p>KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition 1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments 3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders</p>		
Keywords	Autonomous shuttles, multimodal integration, Scalable Model Toolbox, safety, environmental impact, socio-economic potential, accessible cost-effective and demand-responsive transport, integrated sustainable mobility system, public		

	acceptance, benefits and limits, mobility planning for Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions, business models
Case Studies	Pilot sites: Aveiro, Barcelona, Contern, Esch, Pfaffenthal, Inverness, Reggio Emilia, Tampere, Tartu, Trikala
<p>Running from April 2021 until November 2022, Ride2Autonomy is an EU-funded project demonstrating autonomous shuttles' integration into the transport system in ten EU cities. The variety in approach and context allows the project to analyse the system performance because of safety and environmental impact and its multimodal integration with the transport network. The individual and public response and the socio-economic potential of the services are also looked at. Ride2Autonomy helps develop new mobility concepts for passengers leading to healthier, safer, more accessible, sustainable, cost-effective, and demand-responsive transport.</p> <p>The "Scalable Model" toolbox provides a set of blueprints and recommendations to support any town or city in this undertaking. Ride2Autonomy aims at harmonising research and innovation efforts around automated shuttle solutions. It collects lessons learned from the pilot sites and other sites expressing willingness to exchange knowledge and lessons learned. To establish these key deliverables, Ride2Autonomy involves partners of three major shuttle demonstration projects: SHOW, FABULOS, and ART-Forum, and their demonstration sites.</p> <p>(https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/ride2autonomy/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>	

deployEMDS

Project Full Title	
Website	https://deployemds.eu/ https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/deployemds/
Call	EU Digital Europe Programme
Project Coordinator	Acatech, National Academy of Science and Engineering Lucie Kirstein, info@deployemds.eu
Project Partners	<p>41</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ui!] Urban Software Institute Acatech, National Academy of Science and Engineering Agenzia Mobilità Ambiente e Territorio s.r.l. (AMAT) Autoritat del Transport Metropolità (ATM) Big Data for Smart Society Institute (GATE) BKK Centre for Budapest Transport / Budapesti Közlekedési Központ Zártkörűen Működő Részvénytársaság Cefriel Società consortile a responsabilità limitata Società benefit City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad – Environment and Health Administration City of Stockholm / Stockholms Stad – Transportation Administration City of Tampere / Tampereen Kaupunki EMEL, municipal company for mobility and parking of Lisbon / empresa de mobilidade e estacionamento de lisboa EMTA European Metropolitan Transport Authorities enRoute EONA-X European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation – Intelligent Transport Systems & Services Europe (ERTICO – ITS Europe) Factual Consulting S.L. Fairsfair foundation Fintraffic FIWARE Foundation, e.V. Fraunhofer Institute for Transportation and Infrastructure Systems IVI FRCB B.V. Fundacio Eurecat Fundacio Privada i2Cat, Internet i Innovació Digital a Catalunya Instant System Interuniversity Microelectronics Centre / Interuniversitair Micro-electronica Centrum (IMEC) IONOS Inc. Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (KULeuven) – Research Centre for IT & IP Law (CiTiP) Local Public Transport Agency of the Metropolitan City of Milan, Monza and Brianza, Lodi and Pavia / Agenzia per il Trasporto Pubblico Locale del bacino della Città Metropolitana di Milano, Monza e Brianza, Lodi e Pavia (Agenzia TPL) Mobility Data Space (MDS) / DRM Datenraum Mobilität GmbH Nommon Solutions and Technologies S.L. NTT Data POLIS, Promotion of Operational Links with Integrated Services, Association Internationale

	RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB Sofia Urban Mobility Centre EAD / Tsentar za Gradska Mobilnost EAD (SUMC) Swedish Transport Administration / Trafikverket TML – Transportes Metropolitanos de Lisboa EMT SA TU Braunschweig – Research Centre for Mobility Law ui! The urban institute Magyarorszg Zrt. Vianova SAS Volg Digitaal Vlaanderen op VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Lt / Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY		
Duration (months)	36		
Start date	November 2023	End date	October 2026
Key Area(s)	Focus: Creation of a European mobility data space KA1 Smart Urban Mobility 1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options 4. Integrate new technologies in transport KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition		
Keywords	European mobility data space (EMDS), transport data, decentralised and secure data sharing, efficient multimodal mobility and traffic management, sustainable urban mobility		
Case Studies	16 use cases in nine implementation sites: Barcelona, Budapest, Flanders, le-de-France, Lisbon, Milan, Sofia, Stockholm, Tampere		
<p>The common European mobility data space (EMDS) aims to facilitate data access, pooling and sharing for more efficient, safe, sustainable and resilient transport. It builds on initiatives and applications related to transport data and will be supported by initiatives to boost interoperability, security, and the availability and provision of data and services.</p> <p>Aligned with the European data strategy and the Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy, deployEMDS, a project co-funded under the EU Digital Europe Programme, will support policymaking by enabling data sharing and reuse for efficient multimodal mobility and traffic management, as well as for measuring progress of sustainable urban mobility across Europe.</p> <p>https://deployemds.eu/project/, retrieved 23 September 2024)</p>			

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